

Contents

Obstacles to innovation and policy implications: exploring the case of Romanian firms Mihaela Diaconu	5
Adjusting the 5C pentagon for better health policymaking: observing the leading behavioural risks factors (diet, smoking, and alcohol consumption) Ioana Teodora Bițoiu, Cristina Elena Nicolescu	21
Incentivizing CEOs via pay and forced turnover: Do tenure and managerial ability matter? Nadide Banu Olcay Güner	37
Forecasting the Romanian inflation rate: An Autoregressive Integrated Moving-Average (ARIMA) approach Rareș-Petru Mihalache, Dumitru Alexandru Bodislav	67
The effects of geopolitical risks on tourism revenues of the Middle East and Asian countries İsmet Gocer, Peter Kovacs	77
The potential of macroeconomic forces and ICT in affecting the sectorial growth: ARDL approach in the context of East Asian countries Sadik Aden Dirir	91
Validity of asset pricing models in Istanbul Stock Exchange (ISE) information technology index Akin Arda, Arif Saldanlı, Sümeyra Uzun	115
Dynamic relationship between external debt and unemployment in Sub-Saharan Africa Samuel Erasmus Alnaa, Juabin Matey	137

An analysis of factors influencing empowerment of rural women through Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana – National Rural Livelihood Mission (SGSY) Dr. Ravi Kumar Gupta, Udit Maheshwari, Dr. Debendra Nath Das	153
The impact of Covid-19 payment moratoria on the Romanian banking system Eugen-Marian Vierescu	169
Uncertainty and monetary policy during the Covid-19 pandemic in Tunisia: Evidence from a Bayesian VAR Dorra Turki, Foued Badr Gabsi	177
Research on the evolution of migration in Romania after the fall of the communist regime Ioana Manuela Mindrican, Elena Florentina Matei	189
Black Sea and East Mediterranean approach on sustainable development Elena-Iulia Chita, Silvia Dumitrescu-Popa	205
An economic analysis of trade war and deglobalization in current international relations within the paradigm of globalization Altaf Hussain Padder	215
Financial difficulties and economic recession: Evidence from Canadian seniors Samir Amine, Wilner Predelus	227
Inflation targeting and exchange rate pass-through in India: Lessons from international experience Arshid Hussain Peer, Dr. Mirza Allim Baig	239
The circular economics of constructions Rareş-Mihai Niţu	255
Market mood index and stock market. Evidence from National Stock Exchange Neha Seth, Yogesh Kumar	263
Analysis of the effects of social and fiscal policy on incomes during the COVID-19 pandemic in Romania Eva Militaru, Amalia Cristescu, Silvana Bobârnat	273

Note: The authors are responsible for the content of their articles and for obtaining necessary permissions.

Mircea Dinu

Tel.: (+4) 031.432.96.02

Fax: (+4) 021.210.73.10

E-mail: comenzi@edecon.ro

Data base indexation:

EconLit

<http://www.aeaweb.org>

Research Papers in Economics (RePEc)

<http://www.ideas.repec.org>

<http://econpapers.repec.org>

Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)

<http://www.doaj.org>

EBSCO Publishing

<http://www.ebscohost.com>

**International Consortium for the Advancement
of Academic Publication (ICAAP)**

<http://www.icaap.org>

Cabell's Directories

<http://www.cabells.com>

CNCSIS B+

www.econometeoreticasiaplicata.ro; www.ectap.ro

Reception of texts: economia.ta@edeconomica.com

ISSN 1841-8678 (Print)
ISSN 1844-0029 (Online)

Obstacles to innovation and policy implications: exploring the case of Romanian firms

Mihaela DIACONU

The "Gheorghe Asachi" University of Iasi, Romania
mihaela.diaconu@tuiasi.ro

Abstract. *This paper analyses the weaknesses that characterize innovation in Romanian firms and the main obstacles encountered in innovation. Using CIS7 data referring to innovative firms operating in the manufacturing and services, our results reveals that the main obstacles faced by them are conditioned by the composition of the innovation expenditures and are located essentially within the sphere of lack of knowledge and technological opportunities and also the lack of internal resources for funding and low capacity to attract funding from the financial market. These measures can be the basis for the measures that can be adopted through government policies.*

Keywords: firm, innovation, research and development, government policies, Romania.

JEL Classification: O3.

1. Introduction

Innovation is a source of competitive advantage for firms, allowing them to survive and grow on the national and international markets. The interrelation between the ability of firms, industries and nations to advance technologically and the long-term economic performance has become obvious in the modern society.

This is also of interest to governments that monitor indicators of innovation in order to assess the strengths and weaknesses of innovation systems. It starts from the premise that education and research are the main determinants of innovation capacity and economic growth. In this context, the supply of knowledge is encouraged by supporting education and research activities in the public sector. Education can generate highly qualified staff to be used in various activities, and its absorption capacity in terms of assimilating knowledge and ability of recognizing the usefulness of new information can be used productively. The efficient spending of financial and human resources can result from the interaction of knowledge-generating sectors with knowledge-demand sectors that include innovative firms.

Currently, the literature on the factors affecting the decisions of firms to innovate is well developed, including in this framework the empirical studies using firm-level data as well. The way in which firms manage to use human, financial and informational resources in the innovation activity is being investigated. Despite the increasing number of studies (a survey is conducted by Smith, 2006, pp. 148-177), they have been made especially in European leaders and major innovators countries (Mohnen et al., 2006; Mairesse and Mohnen, 2002, etc.).

Few studies on firm innovativeness and factors affecting innovation, including obstacles to innovation have been made on the case of CEE countries. This paper analyzes the obstacles encountered by the Romanian innovative firms in manufacturing and services. Appropriate measures are identified to be adopted by the government policies to boost innovation by highlighting obstacles with the highest incidence on innovation inputs. Our concern is justified by the fact that Romania has been consistently in the modest innovators group according to the composite indicator of innovativeness (EIS, European Innovation Scoreboard) in the period 2006-2021.

Section 2 reviews the factors affecting the innovation in firms identified in the literature and the main constraints faced by innovative firms. Section 3 characterizes innovation in firms and analyses the obstacles to innovation. In this framework, we start from the premise that the obstacles identified can be used as explanatory variables for innovation inputs, including small share of expenditures in research and development (R&D) in the composition of the total innovation effort as a result of the innovation modes adopted by firms in Romania. In this respect, we consider separate testing models for the innovation inputs in manufacturing and service industries using CIS7 (Community Innovation Survey) data and section 4 concludes and discuss policy implications.

2. Innovation facilitators and barriers

It is well known that innovation process of developing of new products and services involves spending of financing resources. In this respect, projects financing can have several characteristics (Hall, 2009 and 2010; Hall & van Reenen, 2000) and decisions to invest can be conditioned by the market size (Schmookler, 1966), the technological opportunities and appropriability (Jaffe, 1998), that can vary depending on firm's size (Acs and Audretsch, 1991, pp. 39-59; Cohen and Kepler, 1996; Cohen, 2010, pp. 129-213).

The firm's size and its incidence on innovation is the subject of countless investigations in the literature aiming to test differences on enterprises groups. Clear evidences exist regarding the relative advantage of large firms through greater opportunities for funding high-risk R&D projects, obtaining higher yields to the total turnover on which the fixed costs are spread or, due to complementarities between R&D and other activities that are seen to be developed more easily in large companies, and also due to the large capacity to diversify business yields and reducing risk in innovation activity. Counterarguments have also been suggested (especially in Scherer and Ross, 1990) in associating of the large enterprises with diminishing the managerial control or, conversely, with an excessive control that would not be favorable for research caused, inter alia, by lower salaries to individual researchers and diminishing of creative impulses.

Over the time, the research on the relationship between the firm's size and R&D expenditure have been generated lots of models starting from the assumptions summarized above, followed by their testing using R&D intensity as the dependent variable and using a measure of firm's size as regressor. R&D increases proportionally with the firm's size in association with a lower increase in output (Cohen et al., 1987; Lerner, 2006) and the R&D productivity is reduced when the firm's size increases (Acs and Audretsch, 1991, pp. 39-59). Also, although it is suggested that large firms have an advantage by their higher capacity of sharing their fixed costs in achieving yields from R&D, this feature results from their better ability of revenue collection. The relative disadvantage of small firms can be mitigated by licensing of technologies or by rapid growth due to innovation (Cohen, 2010, pp. 129-213).

Regardless of their size, firms must have *financial resources* to innovate. Increasing the share of R&D expenditure in the total funds attaches certain features to R&D projects. As an investment activity, R&D distinguishes from other investments in real assets. First, a significant amount of financial resources are allocated to the staff (scientists and engineers) salaries. Their efforts to increase knowledge and the creation of intangible assets are sources of future profits for firms, but these adjustment expenditures are made gradually (Hall, 2009; Hall, 2010). Second, the R&D investment is expected to generate larger net revenues with higher standard deviation. Uncertainty is higher when the projects are implemented, which implies that the R&D strategy has an options-like character and should not be analyzed in a static framework. Also, since investments are made over time as new information arrives, uncertainty tends to be reduced at the end of the projects. The consequence of this fact is that the decision to invest has to be reassessed throughout the

life of the project. Third, innovation does not imply only a significant amount of financial resources, but also determines the reducing of guarantable assets, alongside increasing the proportion of intangible assets incorporated in the human capital, which determines that debt financing to be less adequate as the R&D increases in the total expenditures. Innovation by adopting new technologies and processes incorporates training costs of personnel, and registers non-recoverable expenditures as well. The uncertain nature of returns to innovation and the intangible character of the assets determine that financing innovation to be more difficult than ordinary investments using financial market mechanisms.

The increase in capital costs due to the risk perceived by capital providers may be a consequence of a reduction in financing innovation from retained earnings. A higher cost of capital than the rate of return (expressed more strongly to R&D) can involve discouraging innovation by reducing expenditures. The financial markets are recognized to be imperfect, resulting low investment expenditures manifested especially in small firms.

The innovation expenditures can be correlated with the *product demand* on the market. A part of the literature has been focused on the effects of market concentration on innovativeness. The various theoretical models adhere either to the Schumpeterian position that firms in concentrated markets have pronounced propensity to innovate or, on the contrary, it is argued (Gilbert and Newbery, 1982) that firms with monopoly power are more innovative and aim to avoid the costs associated with the loss of market power and entry of new companies in the markets space. Initially, the empirical models have investigated simple causal relationships, often between R&D expenditures and the market concentration (expressed as market share) with non-convergent results.

As stated by Cohen (2010), the market concentration (structure) is not itself an independent factor affecting innovation, but it may be a function of other variables, including even innovation. As a result, the correlation observed between the market structure and the R&D intensity may reflect either their co-determination or the impact of innovation on the market structure, that lead to difficulties in interpreting the results. Gilbert (2006) suggests that a low incidence of the market structure on innovation in the empirical studies is due to the industrial effects, which blurs the relationship between the two variables, the lack of control variables of theoretical importance, the limited data used in the econometric approaches or inadequate methods of investigation.

Demand, technological opportunities and appropriability are considered explanatory variables "more fundamental" than the market concentration (Cohen, 2010, pp. 129-213) affecting the firms' decision to innovate. Since the 1960s, numerous studies have been conducted to assess the importance of the demand as determinant of the propensity of firms to innovate. Market pull type assumptions are highlighted for the first time by Schmookler (1966), suggesting that the demand for new products determines the rate and direction in innovation. The theoretical literature shows two main aspects in which the inter-industry differences in demand may affect the propensity of firms to innovate. The first, shown by Schmookler, is the market size. Benefits from product or process innovation are

proportional to the size of the market. Inventiveness will intensify on the largest market when the cost of capital is constant and, also innovation will be stimulated as market is expected to grow rapidly. Second, the price elasticity of demand can affect the marginal return of R&D investments.

The benefits from reducing production costs (process innovation) are even higher as the demand is more elastic. On the other hand, the gains from product quality improvement (through product innovation) will be even higher as the demand is inelastic. Both the current market size (which, in general, has the greatest impact on the introduction of new products) and future (projected) market size influence innovation (Acemoglu and Linn, 2004).

The technology push approach emphasizes the importance of *technological opportunities* as determinants of innovation. The concept of technological opportunity incorporates a variety of phenomena, including the possibility of transforming knowledge into new products or processes, interactions with third parties (other firms, customers, suppliers, research institutions) that perform innovation activities, as well as easiness of knowledge externalities exploitation etc.

Even since the 1970s it has been emphasized the importance of acquiring new knowledge in innovation. In particular, Nelson and Winter (1982) argue that knowledge narrows the research options and allows attention to be focused on the most productive approaches. The consequence is that the research process is more efficient, fewer attempts are needed, fewer errors are recorded, and fewer options are necessary to be evaluated in order to obtain the desired result.

From this perspective, scientific knowledge provides an authentic guide to the processes of technological change. Increasing knowledge acquired in other organizations as collaborating firms on the market or higher education and research institutes can have a positive impact on the propensity of firms to invest in R&D, representing an important dimension of industrial technological opportunities. However, the empirical research in this direction is still one minor, and the results on the incidence of various factors on innovation will be different from one country to another.

For example, hampering factors to innovation such as the lack of financial resources and the technical knowledge are significant for firms in Catalonia (Segarra-Blasco et al., 2007), the lack of funds and reduced market demand are found as barriers to innovation in UK (D'Este et al., 2008) etc. Also, the distance from the technological frontier may involve specific barriers; the more firms are closer to it, as the more so their inability to identify qualified staff and partners becomes the main obstacle. The lack of external financing shapes another significant barrier for firms far from the technological frontier (Hölzl and Janger, 2011).

3. Innovation in Romanian firms and obstacles to innovation

3.1. Innovativeness characteristics in Romanian firms

According to the annual European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS), which provides a comparative assessment of the research and innovation performance of EU Member States, Romania has been constantly in the group of modest innovators, registering a trend that shows no progress in innovation activity reflected in the size of the composite index. Also, EIS sub-indicators show that Romania has significant spreads from the EU average in all areas, particularly related to the small share of innovative firms of the total firms, the extremely modest size of public expenditure allocated to research and development of the GDP, as well as low venture capital financing of innovative companies.

The *innovation facilitators* incorporate elements located outside the firm's decision, which are represented, in essence, by the human capital and public resources allocated to R&D of the GDP, including the participation of venture capital to financing innovation. Training of specialists in educational and research institutions is an important determinant of a nation's potential to innovate and growth in the long run, and this indicator is close to the level of the EU average in Romania.

However, keeping low and reducing public spending for education and research has serious negative consequences for the R&D performance within the innovation system. Although various initiatives have been undertaken to define the strategic research areas and by trying to strengthen the linkages between universities and industrial innovation by implementing science parks located in several university centers to promote local economic development, they remained in a declarative stage in the National Strategy of Research, Development and Innovation 2007-2013 and 2014-2020 by stopping the financing for various programs or by delaying implementation of new projects. In addition, the efficiency of public spending for R&D, the quality and accuracy in the evaluation of financial support applications for projects from public funds according to the National Plan for Research, Development and Innovation (NPRDI), the socio-economic relevance of several public-funded research projects and their relevance to the needs of the Romanian industry are still questioned. Also, the current weaknesses of the NPRDI consist of R&D underfunding from public resources, without a normative framework in assessing the effectiveness of R&D programs, and the poor correlation between R&D and the needs of restructuring and industrial development.

These have impacted negatively the level of financing resources allocated by the venture capital companies to innovative firms. The quasi-absence of business angels segment associated to the unstimulating context of creation and support of innovative firms in the early stages including through public-private partnership cannot, in principle, lead to an increase in the supply of venture capital which, in Romania does not exceed 0.04% of the GDP (check, for instance, the Invest in Europe website where this indicator is calculated annually in the CEE countries). Generally, the venture capital markets have been expanded in the CEE countries and a transition has been made from the traditional sectors to the

manufacturing and knowledge-intensive services. The foreign governmental agencies and not institutional investors are the main financiers of various R&D projects in firms in the CEE, including Romania. Due to their conservative attitudes, the institutional investors still play a minor role on the venture capital market (Diaconu, 2012, 2017).

Increasing the supply of venture capital is a necessary condition but it is not sufficient to raise the number of innovative firms. The world leaders in the field of venture capital have adequate means of stimulating entrepreneurship and the demand for venture capital. Romania needs a culture of risk taking, and exit mechanisms on the secondary financial markets for small enterprises as well. A low level of venture capital funding, such as it is in Romania, reflects a lack of financial resources and innovative firms.

The firm's activity expressed in the EIS composite indicator comprises sub-indicators associated with the R&D and non-R&D investments, cooperation and entrepreneurship, and intermediate innovation output. The unsatisfactory size of financial resources allocated to innovation by firms is mainly the result of the small share of innovative firms, which is much lower than that registered in the EU average, with an upward trend until 2008, subsequently registering a sharp decline (figure 1):

Figure 1. Share of innovative firms of the total firms

Source: Eurostat database (CIS4-CIS11) – innovation core activities.

In the same framework, the innovative firms allocate the lowest level of funds for research, below the EU average. In contrast, non-R&D expenditures have outpaced the EU average, which can be motivated by the need for technological renewal and production organization. This is also a result of a low capacity to innovate through creative effort, low collaboration with other companies and research institutes and an expression of the effects of industrial structure dominated by low-tech groups and significant share of non-innovative SMEs (Diaconu, 2013, pp. 270-349).

As consequence, innovation output indicators remain at levels also well below the EU average. Thus, the contribution of high-tech exports in manufacturing is on average 0.38% of the balance of trade in 2012--2018 (compared to 1.28% of the EU average). Nevertheless, the share of turnover from new to the market and new to the firm products of the total turnover (14.27%) is close to the EU average (14.38%). These indicators are important in assessing the creative effort of firms. However, the "new to the market" indicator is less suitable for international comparisons, as long as the firm's market cannot

be distinguished. Firms can operate on local, national or international markets with various levels of development. Therefore, an indicator built using firm-level data that clarifies the firms' market can be more appropriate in comparing the innovation performance.

Innovation in firms remains affected by weaknesses and significant discrepancies compared to the EU average, such as the lack of internal financing resources, the lack of equity funds from business angels and venture capital firms, the lack of financial support from public resources, weak collaboration with other firms and public research institutions as partners and the fragility of the entrepreneurship. Obviously, the lack of high risk projects funding, low technological opportunities resulting from poor collaboration in business, the lack of information on the markets etc. are obstacles to innovation intensity, which are variable from one firm to another depending on firm's size, sector of activity, and the composition of innovation expenditures.

3.2. Obstacles to innovation in Romanian firms

While it can be admitted that not all firms confront the same barriers to innovation and of the same intensity, we consider that some common features on the main factors hampering innovation can be highlighted. CIS (Commission Innovation Survey) conducted by Eurostat centralizes data every two years, the last were published in 2021 which refers to the period 2016-2018 and provides information on barriers to innovation resulting from interviewing both innovative and the non-innovative firms. CIS questionnaire asks questions about highly important factors hampering innovation activities (FH) resulting groups of innovative and non-innovative responding firms. The variables which we include in our analysis are summarized in the table below:

Table 1. *Important factors hampering innovation*

Variable	Description
FH1	Enterprises that claim the lack of qualified personnel
FH2	Enterprises that claim the lack of information on technology
FH3	Enterprises that claim the lack of information on the markets
FH4	Enterprises that claim the difficulty in finding cooperation partners
FH5	Enterprises that claim the markets dominated by established enterprises
FH6	Enterprises that claim uncertain demand for innovative products
FH7	Enterprises that claim no need to innovate due to prior innovations
FH8	Enterprises that claim no need to innovate due to no demand
FH9	Enterprises that claim the lack of funds within the enterprise or group
FH10	Enterprises that claim the lack of external financing
FH11	Enterprises that claim the innovation costs too high

Source: CIS7 variables selected by the author.

The first step in our analysis is to calculate the partial correlations between the variables, since we expect the existence of complementarities. In this respect, the lack of funds within the enterprise or group (FH9), the lack of finance from sources outside the enterprise (FH10) and the innovation costs too high (FH11) are closely linked. The lack of internal funding determines an increase in cost of capital, and the lack of external financing limits the size of the projects to the level of internal funds. In the same framework, the lack of qualified personnel (FH1), the lack of information on technologies (FH2), the lack of

information on the markets (FH3) or the difficulty in identifying collaboration partners (FH4) can be seen as obstacles related to the lack of technological opportunities. Objectively, the qualified personnel can be considered as facilitator of innovation which allows the access to specialized knowledge, including from collaboration with various partners and the ability to identify potential markets. Also, the market dominated by established enterprises (FH5) and uncertain demand for goods and services (FH6) increase the operational risk of projects impacting the financing method, the projects size and type. Ultimately, the firm's decision to innovate in the current period can be affected by projects undertaken in the previous periods (FH7) or by no demand for innovations (FH8).

According to CIS data, firms with technological innovation introduce new or significant improved products or processes. A preliminary data analysis by types of factors hampering innovation is shown in figure 2, considering the share of firms affected by them by firm's size (small – with a number of employees between 10 and 49; medium – with a number of employees between 50 and 249; large – with more than 250 employees) in manufacturing industries where the innovative firms are more concentrated than in services. We note that the factors associated with the cost of innovation incorporate the main obstacles, followed by those concerning the product market. In the same framework, the small firms appear to be the most affected by all factors hampering innovation, followed by the medium firms. In fact, the total share of small innovative firms (13.46%) is much lower than the large firms (44.42%) according to CIS7 data, and the same characteristics can be found in services where the share of innovative small firms is 10.36%, while large firms summarizes 29.69%.

Figure 2. Share of innovative firms affected by obstacles to innovation of the total innovative firms

Source: Eurostat database (CIS7) – manufacturing industries.

Very often an obstacle is encountered when an activity is undertaken. Figure 2 shows that the main factors affecting innovation in innovative firms are associated with a lack of funding resources.

We find similar proportions between non-innovative firms that claim obstacles, by firm's size. Figure 3 shows that the main factors hampering innovation are found in the sphere of the lack of funding:

Figure 3. Share of non-innovative firms affected by obstacles to innovation of the total non-innovative firms

Source: Eurostat database (CIS7) – manufacturing industries.

However, the variables "obstacles to innovation" are not always very useful for understanding the difference between innovators and non-innovators since responses may either indicate a perception (what they see as a barrier to innovation) or reflect their actual experience (OECD, 2009). Firms with strong innovation activity may encounter obstacles to innovation, while non-innovative firms may have different experiences. The completion of a questionnaire related to obstacles to innovation, based on the two groups of enterprises, innovative and non-innovative, would be more appropriate to be carried out according to the firms' innovative status.

Exploring the data available for other EU Member States on the funding resources as obstacles to innovation encountered by innovative firms, we observe that Romanian firms are among the most financially constrained. Thus, 39.62% of the total innovative firms claim the lack of internal funding (FH9) and this share is exceeded only by the Croatian firms (46.28%), from Bulgaria (40.10%), Spain (39.95%) and Portugal (39.63%). The lack of external financing (FH10) is shown for 26.42% of innovative Romanian firms. This percentage is exceeded by the companies from the above mentioned countries. In addition, firms from Cyprus (29.16%) and Italy (28.43%) claim the lack of external financing. Finally, the share of Romanian firms in which the cost of innovation is considered to be too high (FH11) is 30.43% and it is also one of the highest in the EU (figure 4).

Figure 4. Share of the EU innovative firms affected by financial factors

Source: Eurostat database (CIS7) – all core NACE activities.

In order to identify factors with the highest incidence on innovation inputs we use multiple linear regression models specified by the following general equation:

$$Y_i = \beta_{0i} + \sum_j \beta_j X_{ij} + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where:

Y_i – the dependent variable is represented by the innovation inputs used by innovative firms in i sector;

X_{ij} – the exogenous variables;

β_j parameters that capture the j factor influence on the dependent variable;

ε_i – an independent and identical distributed error term for i .

The CIS7 database includes groups of firms with technological innovation in manufacturing and services. Since we do not have firm-level data, we included all firms from the 27 NACE sectors in the analysis, which enable us to highlight the most important obstacles to innovation.

The dependent variables considered in the model include elements of the total innovation expenditure: in-house and external R&D, acquisition of machinery, equipment, software and external knowledge, $Inno_exp$. Its size on the two main representative components for Romanian firms: expenditure for (in-house and external) research and development, RD_exp , and expenditure for acquisition of machinery, equipment and software, K_exp , in absolute terms (thousands of euros) are included also in separate models.

The independent variables include the share of firms with technological innovation which have experienced barriers to innovation activity of the total product and/or process innovative companies. We conduct the analysis with all variables considered in the models and formulate the following hypothesis: the increase in the share of firms affected by the obstacles to innovation has adverse affect on the innovation inputs ($Inno_exp$, $R\&D_exp$ and K_exp) used by innovative firms.

Table 2 summarizes the correlation matrix between all variables. It can be observed that the factors with significant impact on $Inno_exp$ are FH2 and FH9, which means that the lack of technological opportunities expressed by the lack of information on technologies, and the lack of internal funding represent the main obstacles on the firm's decision to innovate; partial correlations reflecting strong negative impact. The same factors act on K_exp as well, explaining the reduction in the expenditures for acquisition of machinery, equipment and software. The obstacles identified previously appear to be responsible for the variation in RD_exp .

In this case, the perceived significant cost of innovation, FH11, has a negative impact as well. Correlations can be also found between explanatory variables differing by intensity; significant ones result to be between FH1 and FH11, FH7 and FH10, FH5 and FH6, FH4 and FH9, FH10, FH11, and between FH9, FH10 and FH11.

Table 2. Pearson correlations between the variables analyzed

	FH1	FH2	FH3	FH4	FH5	FH6	FH7	FH8	FH9	FH10	FH11	Inno_exp	RD_exp	K_exp
FH1	1													
FH2	0.805** (0.000)	1												
FH3	-0.156 (0.436)	0.031 (0.877)	1											
FH4	0.007 (0.971)	-0.029 (0.885)	0.294 (0.137)	1										
FH5	0.194 (0.332)	0.198 (0.323)	0.235 (0.238)	0.118 (0.557)	1									
FH6	0.160 (0.426)	0.096 (0.634)	0.321 (0.102)	-0.195 (0.331)	0.654** (0.000)	1								
FH7	-0.183 (0.361)	0.028 (0.890)	-0.075 (0.711)	-0.221 (0.267)	-0.022 (0.912)	-0.071 (0.725)	1							
FH8	0.036 (0.859)	0.021 (0.917)	0.221 (0.267)	0.246 (0.215)	-0.014 (0.945)	-0.351 (0.072)	0.278 (0.160)	1						
FH9	0.262 (0.187)	0.198 (0.323)	-0.024 (0.905)	-0.63** (0.000)	0.379 (0.051)	0.718** (0.000)	0.087 (0.664)	-0.235 (0.238)	1					
FH10	0.164 (0.414)	0.202 (0.311)	-0.268 (0.176)	-0.48** (0.010)	0.127 (0.527)	0.252 (0.205)	0.479* (0.011)	-0.253 (0.202)	0.464* (0.015)	1				
FH11	0.516** (0.006)	0.394* (0.042)	-0.256 (0.197)	-0.51** (0.004)	0.130 (0.519)	0.339 (0.084)	0.012 (0.952)	-0.047 (0.815)	0.703** (0.000)	0.494** (0.009)	1			
Inno_exp	-0.296 (0.133)	-0.391* (0.044)	-0.303 (0.125)	0.033 (0.869)	-0.202 (0.312)	-0.367 (0.060)	-0.163 (0.415)	0.072 (0.720)	-0.433* (0.024)	-0.319 (0.104)	-0.230 (0.249)	1		
RD_exp	-0.291 (0.141)	-0.386* (0.047)	-0.333 (0.090)	0.042 (0.836)	-0.193 (0.335)	-0.353 (0.071)	-0.165 (0.412)	0.016 (0.936)	-0.432* (0.024)	-0.293 (0.138)	-0.257 (0.196)	0.994** (0.000)	1	
K_exp	-0.298 (0.132)	-0.392* (0.043)	-0.289 (0.144)	0.030 (0.884)	-0.205 (0.304)	-0.371 (0.056)	-0.162 (0.419)	0.097 (0.631)	-0.431* (0.025)	-0.330 (0.093)	-0.217 (0.277)	0.999** (0.000)	0.998** (0.000)	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

We build several models and select the best regression model able to explain the relationship between the variables. In this respect, we use all the variables considered and remove the weakest independent variable at every step. The parameters of the models are estimated using linear regression. The coefficients resulted, the standard errors, and the values of econometric tests are centralized in table 3. The final results of each econometric model include statistically significant values only.

Table 3. Regression models coefficients

	Model 1 Dependent variable Inno_exp		Model 2 Dependent variable RD_exp		Model 3 Dependent variable K_exp	
	Coefficient	Std. error	Coefficient	Std. error	Coefficient	Std. error
FH4					-41530.404	21062.364
FH2	-17631.775	10685.836	-5347.622	3256.366	-10908.968	7600.033
FH3	-43727.757	20627.869	-14280.720	6286.068		
FH9	-10876.928	7277.777	-3483.566	2217.805	-14972.485	6048.157
FH10	-11831.804	9967.384	-3229.011	3037.427	-8578.104	7021.009
Constant	1269739.547	319051.682	389739.961	97226.738	1288563.199	380908.726
R-squared	0.413		0.421		0.401	
F-statistic	3,874		3,997		3,688	
Durbin-Watson	2.102		2.239		2.089	

Source: author's calculation.

The regression results from the first model indicate that the total innovation expenditure (Inno_exp) is negatively influenced by the increases in the share of firms claiming the lack of information on technologies (FH2) and markets (FH3), the lack of funds within the enterprise or group (FH9) and the absence of external financial resources (FH10). The same factors with similar proportions affect the expenditure for research and development (RD_exp), although their intensity is different. The estimators of the regression equation from the model 3 show that the expenditure for acquisition of machinery, equipment and software, K_exp, is significantly correlated with the share of firms that claim difficulties in identifying cooperation partners (FH4), the lack of information on technologies (FH2) and lack of funding from internal and external resources (FH9 and FH10). The models can explain a large proportion of the variability of the total innovation expenditure ($R^2 = 0.413$), and also on the two components ($R^2 = 0.421$ and $R^2 = 0.401$ for RD_exp and K_exp) and standard econometric tests have also good results (table 3).

Summing up, our analysis identifies that innovation expenditures are influenced by the lack of technological opportunities and knowledge as well as by the lack funding resources, which are the main obstacles responsible for reducing innovation effort in Romanian firms. However, innovation expenditures and output remain severely affected by the low level of expenditure on research performed by firms. Industrial restructuring and increasing of innovation performance involve enhancing measures to be taken by the government policy, especially in supporting research and development in firms.

4. Conclusions and policy implications

The results we obtain on the main obstacles to innovation in Romania are not surprising. In general, the abandonment of projects by firms is low (under 3% according to Eurostat). This leads to the conclusion that the obstacles can reduce the number of innovators and innovation effort in firms. Such indicators are below the EU average and have further implications on the results obtained by firms from innovation. In the same framework, our results are consistent with other indicators of innovation, including the small number of innovative firms and their concentration in a few sectors of the economy (Diaconu, 2013, pp. 270-349). The options for different mechanisms of boosting innovation must take shape in relationship to the variables that characterize the innovation activity and its obstacles.

Our study on the effects of the main obstacles to innovation expressed by innovation inputs suggests that they are interdependent and reinforce each other. We identify that the main obstacles are the lack of technological opportunities and knowledge (lack of technological and market information, lack of cooperation partners) and the lack of funding (within the enterprise or group and from sources outside the enterprise), while the obstacles associated with the market (markets dominated by established enterprises and uncertain demand for innovative goods or services) and other factors (no need to innovate due to prior innovations and due to no demand for innovations) appear to be less important. The two main groups of factors are complementary.

For instance, the influence of active diffusion of knowledge (resulted from collaborative activities with other firms or institutions) and non-interactive diffusion (derived from using acquisition of knowledge) on innovation is well recognized. Transfer of knowledge through collaborative innovation activities and interaction with suppliers and customers can provide the missing inputs and learning processes that the firm cannot easily acquire. Also, collaboration in innovation activities can reduce the costs of innovation, facilitating the identification, adaptation and acquisition of relevant information and risks sharing that maximize the innovation results. This is why various government initiatives promote collaborative relationships between firms and research institutions, or between innovative firms, suppliers and customers, leading to behavioral additionality.

Nevertheless, several explanations regarding the significant share of firms that do not innovate in collaboration include concerns on sharing benefits or information disclosure to the contract partners (Arundel and Borody, 2003, pp. 158-182). The need for collaboration can be related to the technological characteristics of fixed assets used by firms, their growing complexity requiring external expertise activities.

Romanian firms are modestly involved in collaborative activities. The active diffusion through collaboration has positive impact by reducing barriers associated with failure to obtain funding for projects due to the uncertain results or low absorption of knowledge. We consider these barriers more important for small firms, having the highest probability of dealing with these difficulties. Despite the potential benefits of collaboration agreements, small firms are the least involved in collaboration.

The most practiced are cooperation agreements with suppliers and customers, and the least common are agreements with higher education institutions (5.10%) and research institutions (3.01% of the total innovative firms). These results are the consequence of reducing public financial support for innovation through direct and indirect mechanisms, including a low access to the research results funded from public resources. Firms in Romania are characterized by a level of collaboration among the lowest in the EU (Diaconu, 2013, pp. 270-349). That is why it is necessary the collaboration activities of firms with research and higher education institutions to be stimulated by the government policies, as sources of knowledge and technological opportunities, which would increase the innovative capacity. In the same framework, the supply side of financial resources needs a special attention. Stimulating both the demand and the supply sides can mitigate significant vulnerabilities that hinder the economic development based on knowledge: the concentration of economic and creative capacity in a few sectors that cause the dependence on imported technologies and external sources of knowledge in other sectors, as well as insufficient funding from venture capital.

References

- Acemoglu, D. and Linn, J., 2004. Market size in innovation: Theory and evidence from the pharmaceutical industry, *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 119, pp. 1049-1090.
- Acs, Z.J. and Audretsch, D.B., 1991. R&D, Firm Size and Innovative Activity. In: Z.J. Acs and D.B. Audretsch (Eds.), *Innovation and Technological Change*. London: Harvester Wheatsheaf.
- Arundel, A. and Bordoy, C., 2003. Collaboration and innovation outputs. In: Y. Caloghirou, A. Constantelou and N. Vonortas (Eds.), *Knowledge Flows in European Industry: Mechanisms and Policy Implications*. Routledge.
- Cohen, W M., 2010. Fifty years of empirical studies on innovative activity and performance. In: B. Hall and N. Rosenberg (Eds.), *Handbook of Economics of Innovation*, Vol. I. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- Cohen, W.M. and Klepper, S., 1996. A reprise of size and R&D. *Economic Journal*, 106, pp. 925-951.
- Cohen, W.M., Levin R.C. and Mowery, D.C., 1987. Firm size and R&D intensity: A re-examination. *Journal of Industrial Economics*, 35, pp. 543-563.
- D'Este, P., Iammarino, S., Savona, M. and von Tunzelmann, N., 2008. What hampers innovation? Evidence from the UK CIS4. *SPRU Electronic Working Paper Series*, Paper No. 168.
- Diaconu, M., 2017. Private equity markets developments in Central and Eastern Europe. *Theoretical and Applied Economics*, XXIV(1), pp. 131-146.
- Diaconu, M., 2013. The incidence of taxation on technological innovation. In: Păun-Oțiman I., C. Ionescu and E. Dinga (Eds.), *Post-doctoral studies in economics. Post-doctoral dissertations, Studies and research in the fiscal-budgetary field*, vol. III. Bucharest: Romanian Academy Publishing (in Romanian).
- Diaconu, M., 2012. Characteristics and drivers of venture capital investments in Romania. *Theoretical and Applied Economics*, XIX(7), pp. 111-132.
- Gilbert, R., 2006. Looking for Mr. Schumpeter: Where are we in the competition-innovation debate?, In: A. Jaffe and S. Lerner (Eds.), *Innovation Policy and the Economy*, Vol. VI (pp. 159-215). Cambridge MA: MIT Press/NBER.
- Gilbert, R. and Newbery, D., 1982. Preemptive patenting and the persistence of monopoly. *American Economic Review*, pp. 72, 514-526.
- Hall, B., 2010. The Financing of Innovative Firms. *Review of Economics and Institutions*, 1(1), pp. 1-30.
- Hall, B., 2009. The Financing of R&D and Innovation. *NBER Working Paper 15325*, Cambridge MA: NBER.
- Hall, B. and Van Reenen, J., 2000. How effective are Fiscal Incentives for R&D? A Review of the Evidence. *Research Policy*, 29, pp. 449-469.
- Hölzl, W. and Janger, J., 2011. Innovation barriers across firm types and countries. *The DIME Final Conference*, Maastricht.
- Jaffe, A., 1998. The Importance of 'Spillovers' in the Policy Mission of the Advanced Technology Program. *Journal of Technology Transfer*, Summer, pp. 11-19.
- Lerner, J., 2006. The new financial thing: The origins of financial innovations. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 79, pp. 223-255.
- Mairesse, J. and Mohnen, P., 2002. To Be or Not to Be Innovative: An Exercise in Measurement. *STI Review*, 27, pp. 103-128.

-
- Mohnen, P., Mairesse, J. and Dagenais, M., 2006. Innovativity: A comparison across seven European countries. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 15(4-5), pp. 391-413.
- Nelson, R. and Winter, S., 1982. *An Evolutionary Theory of Economic Change*. Harvard: Harvard University Press.
- OECD, 2009. *Innovation in Firms – A Microeconomic Perspective*. Paris: OECD.
- Schmookler, J., 1966. *Invention and Economic Growth*. Harvard: Harvard University Press.
- Scherer, F.M. and Ross, D., 1990. *Industrial Market Structure and Economic Performance*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- Segarra-Blasco, A., García-Quevedo, J. and Teruel-Carrizosa, M., 2007. Barriers to Innovation and Public Policy Implications in Catalonia. *Institut d'Economia de Barcelona*, working paper 6.
- Smith, K., 2006. Measuring Innovation. In: J. Fagerberg, D.C. Mowery and R. Nelson (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Innovation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Adjusting the 5C pentagon for better health policymaking: observing the leading behavioural risks factors (diet, smoking, and alcohol consumption)

Ioana Teodora BIȚOIU

National University of Political Studies and Public Administration, Bucharest, Romania
teodora.bitoiu@snsa.ro

Cristina Elena NICOLESCU

National University of Political Studies and Public Administration, Bucharest, Romania
cnicolescu@snsa.ro

Abstract. *Smoking, alcohol consumption, and dietary risks pertain to the goods that can destabilise the market should their production trigger too many negative externalities and not enough research to counterbalance them. Moreover, all three are among the factors that, connected to ever-present risky behaviours, drive the most death and disability combined (the other two risk factors being the metabolic ones and the environmental/occupational risks). Therefore, they are to be considered as relevant to both the perceived health of the population and analysed in relation to the data on smokers, alcohol consumers, and poor diet impact.*

However, the design of these health policies must be adapted to the pattern of national culture of Romania, increasing the degree of their acceptance by the population. This is particularly true when less-damage alternatives are present in the market. Policymakers should incentivize their use over more-damaging products. In fact, the existence of better alternatives deepens the market failure that a sub-optimal allocation of resources produces when consumers opt for more damaging products over better goods. Clearly, the objective of policymakers ought to be to differentiate based on the risk profile of the products present on the market.

Keywords: health policy, cost, national culture, behavioural risk factors.

JEL Classification: H51, I18, Z13.

Introduction

The health crisis associated with the COVID-19 pandemic was the basis of the unprecedented negative impact generated in socio-economic terms. This impact has been felt until now, and more will weigh on society in the future. The need to improve the health of the population and the recovery of national economies requires strengthening the capacity of the authorities to substantiate, formulate, and operationalize public policies suitable for solving public health problems.

From this perspective, the Cross-Country Analysis of The European Observatory COVID Response Monitor – HSRM (see <https://eurohealthobservatory.who.int/monitors/hstrm/hstrm-countries>) highlights two issues of interest: the ineffectiveness of the 3C trilemma (Cost, Coverage, Choice), and the fracture between strategic and operational planning. These deficiencies were adamantly reflected in the low resilience of the national health systems when facing the pandemic shock.

Considering the 3C trilemma an ideal and a benchmark for the success or failure of a health policy assumed the elimination of other determining factors for better policymaking. Equally, the increase in the well-being of the population after the period of economic-financial crisis (2008-2010) led to the exacerbation of the economic optimum of the Cost – Coverage – Choice model and was reflected, among other things, by the decrease in the share of general public expenditures for health in GDP.

If we refer to the last programming period 2014-2020, Eurostat statistical data shows that during the period 2014-2019, counterintuitively, most EU member states (15 out of 27) reduced the share of general public health expenditure in GDP. However, Romania is not among these states. The EU average 2014-2019 registered a negative value (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The overall rate of change of general government expenditure on health 2014-2019 and 2019-2020, at the level of the EU (%)

Source: Eurostat (gov_10a_exp).

Compared to 2019, in 2020, against the backdrop of the health crisis, all member states increased the value of these expenses (as a share of the national GDP). Romania even reached the EU average, but this was not automatically reflected in an increased resilience of the healthcare system to external shocks such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Thus, at the EU level, in the period 2020-2021, Romania, but also Bulgaria, Croatia, and Poland experienced a decrease in their resilience levels⁽¹⁾.

Regarding the general government expenditure on health, broken down into categories (medical products, appliances and equipment, public health services, hospital services, outpatient services, and R&D Health), as a share of GDP, between 2014 and 2019, 11 EU Member States (Austria, Cyprus, Croatia, Estonia, Germany, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Romania, Slovenia, and Spain) have increased the general government expenditure (as a share of GDP) both on hospital services and on outpatient services.

However, an increase in health expenditure does not automatically imply an increase in the ability to deliver health (which is the fundamental aim of the health system) or in the population's health level. Namely, in 2013 an estimation by the OECD and the European Commission upon health systems' efficiency highlighted that "up to 20% of total health care spending in Europe could be reallocated to better use, such as toward producing more health services." (EU Expert Group on Health Systems Performance Assessment – HSPA, 2019). Such a statement clearly shows the understanding that alternative policymaking is needed. Borrowing for a moment a term dear to monetary theory, "helicopter money" will not solve the problem. A better management of resources, and nudging consumers toward the consumption of better products, would go a long way in improving the resilience of the healthcare system.

This is also the case of Romania, which makes efforts to increase the budgetary allocations of the sector but continues to face an overall inefficient allocation and use of resources in the public health system. Despite extensive actions to modernize the national health system established through dedicated public policy documents (strategies, policies, plans, etc.) over time, the central pillar of this system remains the hospital sector, which is still underfunded. However, "half of the resources of the Single National Health Insurance Fund (FNUASS) are allocated to hospital care, leaving less than half for primary healthcare, specialist outpatients, medicines, other services, and medical technologies". (Romanian Government, National Health Strategy 2022-2030 "Together, for health", p. 16)

In Romania, there is an improvement in certain established indicators for assessing the health status of the population (Figures 2-6). However, life expectancy remains among the lowest in the European Union (the EU27 average being 80.1 years) although it has increased by more than three years since 2004 (from 71.4 years to 75.6 years in 2019). In addition, during the period 2007-2020, healthy life expectancy decreased by 1.5 years in Romania (Figure 4).

The low level and modest rate of increase in life expectancy reflect "unhealthy behaviours, socioeconomic imbalances, as well as deficiencies in the provision of and access to health

services” (Romanian Government, National Health Strategy 2022-2030 “Together, for health”, p. 11). It is the opinion of these authors that Romanian policies should aim to reduce the negative effects of unhealthy behaviours via the change of behavioural consumption patterns – a solution that would free national resources to be destined for primary healthcare.

According to the WHO statistics for Romania regarding the number of deaths in 2019 directly caused by behavioural and environmental risk factors (Our World in Data), the first three categories of risk factors are behavioural (high systolic blood pressure (28.79%), high body-mass index (12.85%), and smoking (11.90%)). These three risk factors amass 53.54% of the total deaths. These are followed by other 3 risk factors, also of behavioural origin, which produce 22.74% of total deaths (diet high in sodium (8.48%), high fasting plasma glucose (8.28%), and alcohol use (5.98%)). Practically, a limited number of non-communicable diseases, especially chronic diseases, have a negative impact on disability and mortality, especially avoidable, and are responsible for over 76% of the total number of deaths recorded in 2019 in Romania. Moreover, according to Eurostat (Figures 8 and 9), in 2019, Romania ranked 3rd in the ranking of EU Member States regarding the standardized death rate for preventable diseases/conditions (almost 296 per 100,000 inhabitants) and first place in the standardized mortality rate for treatable diseases/conditions (over 208 per 100,000 population). Like the other EU Member States, Romania has a standardized death rate for preventable diseases/conditions higher than the standard death rate for treatable diseases/conditions.

The current National Health Strategy 2022-2030 identifies as the main causes of this situation “the destruction of the networks that provided eminently preventive health services as close as possible to the citizen, the political indecision and the lack of an adequate understanding of the political decision-makers regarding the fundamental importance of prevention”, and also the lack of health education. (Romanian Government, National Health Strategy 2022-2030 “Together, for health”, p. 22)

Therefore, ensuring the optimum point of the 3C trilemma is not comprehensive, despite a balance between the economic and the social plan. It is necessary to expand this model through a better adaptation to the national context by including other determining factors such as the *characteristics of the “political-administrative construction” process of public policy*. At the same time, special attention must also be paid to the *cultural context* understood as a catalytic or inhibiting factor of the authorities’ initiatives to achieve public policy objectives. The characteristics of the national culture explain to a good extent the level of awareness among the population about health issues, the trust/reluctance of the population towards the authorities, and their actions, including the degree of compliance with the rule/norm of the citizens. These societal reactions play an important role also when talking about lower-risk products, and alternatives in general. In other words, nudging consumers towards better alternatives and better lifestyles can be easier (or harder) depending on the concept explained just above.

Figure 2. Romania: Healthy life years in absolute value at birth (year)

Source: Eurostat (hlth_hlye).

Figure 3. Life expectancy in absolute value at birth (year)

Source: Eurostat (sdg_03_10).

Figure 4. Healthy life years in absolute value at birth versus Life expectancy in absolute value at birth (year)

Source: Eurostat (hlth_hlye; sdg_03_10).

Figure 5. Healthy life years in absolute value at 65 (year)

Source: Eurostat (hlth_hlye).

Figure 6. Romania: Healthy life years in absolute value at birth x Life expectancy in absolute value at birth x Healthy life years in absolute value at 65 (Year)

Source: Eurostat (hlth_hlye; sdg_03_10).

Figure 7. Standardised death rates for preventable diseases/conditions, persons aged less than 75 years, 2019 (per 100 000 inhabitants)

Source: Eurostat (hlth_cd_apr). Data for France are not available.

Figure 8. Standardised death rates for treatable diseases/conditions, persons aged less than 75 years, 2019 (per 100 000 inhabitants)

Source: Eurostat (hlth_cd_apr). Data for France are not available.

I. The 3C trade-off

Healthcare policymaking, too, cannot escape the 3C trilemma. The decision maker is pushed to pay attention to the objectives and constraints filtered through the 3Cs of decision-making (the trilemma Cost, Coverage, Choice), allowing it to also make different comparisons (Bițoiu and Rădulescu, 2015).

Policymakers must juggle three priorities when offering a public service: coverage, cost, and choice. They almost always have to sacrifice at least one of the three. As austerity bites, this equation is going to lead to very tricky decisions. Health is an area where the trilemma clearly applies (Buttonwood, 2011).

The cost of healthcare, especially in the case of healthcare provided to cover the effects of the consumption of non-merit goods, cannot rely upon the traditional cost factors. It must also take into account the externalities and the competition's failure which contributes to building certain costs. The actions of the public decision-maker must identify and optimally cover the social cost (Zilberman, 1999).

The marketplace needs to be designed in a way that makes consumers – both doctors and patients – more aware of the trade-off between cost and quality of the various healthcare interventions. It needs to do so without leading to a situation in which people receive ever-cheaper products without trading off any of their health (Ubel, 2009, p. 17). In order to do so, policymakers need to deal with a 3C trade-off; cover the negative externalities triggered by the consumption of the non-merit goods; mind the economic approach of subsidiarity specific to the multi-level governance as to reach a balanced solution for all stakeholders – citizens, economic agents, and the government. This last actor makes a map to cover the social costs created by negative externalities. It must be in line with both national decisions as well as European ones (see Dinu and Dumitrică, 2014). Economic development leads to changes in consumers' behaviour, with results that do not always correspond to the principles of sustainable consumption. The risk of irreversibly affecting the ecological balance requires focusing on administrative measures aimed at reducing negative

externalities. Sustainable economic development implies a set of quantitative, structural, and qualitative transformations, in the economy, in scientific research and manufacturing technology, in the functioning mechanisms and organizational structures of the economy, and last but not least, in the administrative mechanisms of the local authorities who must monitor, evaluate and regulate the entire process. Creating a map of public decision-making to deal with this market failure (externalities triggered by the non-sustainable consumption behaviour), using the tools offered by the multi-level governance and the principle of subsidiarity in order to provide a more efficient relationship between the costs and benefits of a sound policy-making. The application of the 3C model inevitably involves constant interaction with all stakeholders, an improved 5C model would imply even more though. Namely, it appears necessary to formulate decisions at an administrative level regarding negative externalities that take into account the possible contributions of all actors through the application of the principles of collaborative governance, in the context of wide-ranging national specific needs, as part of the newly defined dimensions of culture and conception. This is especially true when better alternatives are added to the market's mix. In fact, negative externalities can be lowered thanks to better decision-making of consumers – triggered by sound policy-making – in an obvious example of positive interaction between the different subjects of the 5C model.

II. Mind the culture and conception

The culture of a nation represents a universal concept illustrating the “distinctive manner of their behaviour and the understanding of values, beliefs, regulations, and premises” (Moldoveanu, 2005, p. 166), being an element of Community empowerment⁽²⁾.

From this point of view, culture, the collective programming of thought that distinguishes the members of one society from another, is assumed to be the fourth element in our Cs pentagon model. Minding the culture when dealing with the 3C trilemma is the key to a more careful measurement of cost by better valuing both the health care and the health status of the population (assessed later through the fifth element: the conception of the system).

We argue that Hofstede's sixth dimensions described below (Hofstede, 2011) are to be considered in the health policy-making process, especially for the substantiation of the health cost assessment for non-merit goods.

1. *Power Distance*, related to the different solutions to the basic problem of human inequality (PDI).
2. *Uncertainty Avoidance*, related to the level of stress in a society in the face of an unknown future (UAI).
3. *Individualism* versus *Collectivism*, related to the integration of individuals into primary groups (IND).
4. *Masculinity* versus *Femininity*, related to the division of emotional roles between women and men (MAS).
5. *Long Term* versus *Short Term Orientation*, related to the choice of focus for people's efforts: the future or the present and past (LTO).
6. *Indulgence* versus *Restraint*, related to the gratification versus control of basic human desires related to enjoying life (IVR).

In Hofstede’s 6D model countries are positioned relative to other countries through a score defining each dimension. The dimensions are statistically distinct and do occur in all possible combinations, although some combinations are more frequent than others (Hofstede, 2011, p. 8).

The choice of the 6th dimension (IVR, is based on the result of the correlation between the values of this indicator for the EU28 member states (2014-2019) and the national averages of the weights of government budget allocations in GDP for health from the time interval chosen as a reference (see the Appendix).

Methodologically, the tested hypothesis was that the EU is an integrated macro-system within which, in a programmatic period regulated by European norms and standards, the Member States must align their national policies with the European benchmarks by contextualizing them to the national specific needs. From the programming period 2014-2020 only the interval before the start of the COVID-19 pandemic (the interval 2014-2019) was selected. For this reason, the average of the weights of budgetary allocations in GDP for health was used for the entire period 2014-2019, instead of selecting the values of this budgetary indicator for a single year.

The statistical correlation between the ranking of general government expenditure on health for all 28 EU Member States (the average of this expenditure for the period 2014-2019) and the Hofstede 6-D national culture model shows an important correlation *only* between the budgetary indicator and the sixth dimension of the Hofstede model. Therefore, the strong, positive correlation ($\rho = 0.73$, $p = 1.28087E-05$, $R^2 = 0.53$) and this result is significant (at probability value $p < .01$).

In short, certain characteristics of the pattern of national culture (the dimensions of *Indulgence* versus *Restraint*) explains 53% ($R^2 = 0.53$) of the levels of budget allocations.

III. The pattern of national culture of Romania in accordance with Hofstede’s 6-D model

The figure below provides a synthesis of the scores calculated for Romania on the six dimensions of Hofstede’s 6-D national culture model.

Figure 9. Overview of the deep drivers of the Romanian culture relative to other world cultures

Source: data retrieved from <https://www.hofstede-insights.com/country-comparison/romania/>, January 9, 2023.

When examining these scores, we keep in mind the described characteristics of the national culture:

- PDI – 90 – Romania scores high on this dimension (score of 90) which means that people accept a hierarchical order in which everybody has a place and which needs no further justification. Hierarchy in an organization is seen as reflecting inherent inequalities, centralization is popular, subordinates expect to be told what to do and the ideal boss is a benevolent autocrat.
- NB (Mc Breen et al., 2011, p. 12). The younger agents are more susceptible to following certain rules, and unlikely to provoke the higher-status agent (Mc Breen et al., 2011, p. 12). This could lead to some interesting policy conclusions. For instance, that an invitation from the higher-status agent to the lower-status agent to change the behaviour towards better alternatives (think about moving from smoking to the use of e-cigarettes and HTPs, or from eating high trans-fat-content goods to lighter food) could result in positive effects on the youth.
- UAI – 90 – Romania scores 90 on this dimension and thus has a very high preference for avoiding uncertainty. Countries exhibiting high Uncertainty Avoidance maintain rigid codes of belief and behaviour and are intolerant of unorthodox behaviour and ideas. In these cultures, there is an emotional need for rules (even if the rules never seem to work). Time is money, people have an inner urge to be busy and work hard, precision and punctuality are the norm, innovation may be resisted, and security is an important element in individual motivation.
- IND – 30 – Romania, with a score of 30 is considered a collectivistic society. This is manifest in a close long-term commitment to the member “group”, be that a family, extended family, or extended relationships. Loyalty in a collectivist culture is paramount and overrides most other societal rules and regulations. Society fosters strong relationships where everyone takes responsibility for fellow members of their group. In collectivist societies offence leads to shame and loss of face, employer/employee relationships are perceived in moral terms (like a family link), hiring and promotion decisions take account of the employee’s in-group, and management is the management of groups.
- MAS – 42 – Romania scores 42 on this dimension and is thus considered a relatively Feminine society. In Feminine countries the focus is on “working in order to live”, managers strive for consensus, people value equality, solidarity and quality in their working lives. Conflicts are resolved by compromise and negotiation. Incentives such as free time and flexibility are favoured. The focus is on well-being; status is not shown.
- LTO – 52 – Normative societies which score low on this dimension, for example, prefer to maintain time-honoured traditions and norms while viewing societal change with suspicion. Those with a culture that scores high, on the other hand, take a more pragmatic approach: they encourage thrift and efforts in modern education as a way to prepare for the future.
- IVR – 20 – With a very low score of 20, Romanian culture is one of Restraint. Societies with a low score in this dimension tend towards cynicism and pessimism. Also, in contrast to Indulgent societies, Restrained societies do not put much emphasis on leisure time and control the gratification of their desires. People with this orientation have the perception that their actions are Restrained by social norms and feel that indulging themselves is somewhat wrong.

IV. Implementing Subsidiarity – Embracing National Modern Policy Making – How to Minimize Harm in a Society with Lower State’s investment in Health Care

As seen above the Romanian health system is facing a 3C trilemma, and according to Hofstede’s 6 D model, the Romanian citizens are looking at their policymakers to solve the trilemma and deliver a better healthcare system to patients.

Taking into consideration the principle of subsidiarity – whereby decisions should be taken at the most immediate or local level possible – the policymakers in Romania should consider adopting a policy that minimizes the harm in society resulting from the consumption of non-merit goods. In order to do so, a better classification of non-merit goods should be performed. This should take into consideration both the risk profile of the goods and the potential impact that such goods can have on the health of the consumers. For instance, if a scale from 0 to 100 defining degrees of toxicity is created (where 0 is the lowest possible value of toxicity, and 100 is the highest one) a product standing at 100 should be treated in a much harsher way than another product tested at 15.

Countries such as the UK, Australia, and New Zealand differentiate between non-merit goods based on their risk profile, presenting an example of modern policymaking. To prevent NCDs, the WHO (2016) recommends States impose a Sugar-Sweetened beverages tax and create subsidies on fruit and vegetables.

According to research led by Liu, Veugelers, Liu, and Ohinmaa (2022), fifteen studies were conducted in six countries (the US, Australia, South Africa, the UK, and Mexico). These studies revealed that the enforcement of a sugar tax improved the health-related quality of life of citizens. Savings from avoided health care costs and revenue from the sugar taxes (totaling US\$87 to US\$167,799 million) exceeded intervention costs (US\$5 to US\$2177 million). Each of the 15 studies concluded that the sugar tax constitutes a cost-effective intervention that resulted in relevant cost savings.

Romanian’s fiscal policy towards nicotine consumption shows a clear differentiation between products. Cigarettes are recognized as the most harmful form of nicotine consumption and thus taxed at the highest level, whereas Heated Tobacco Products and E-cigarettes are taxed at a significantly lower level. Given that Romania presents a large number of smokers, and that the country’s smoking incidence continues to rise, it is the opinion of these authors that policymakers should further increase the existing differential, incentivizing consumers towards better products.

V. Conclusions. The scenario of the coming years: building the 5C pentagon for better health policymaking

We aim to also include the conception element in our 5C pentagon, to improve the cost assessment, by helping the decision-maker to better value the health service that the population needs.

Conception must be reflected in the public health policy process (measures, interventions, and actions/inactions) just like utility mirrors prices. The process must correct the non-action approach specific to the laissez-faire state and more and more present in societies with hard-tested economies and, in particular, with a decentralised health management system.

This is also the case in Romania, a state with a national budget bent by a dangerously expanding public debt (around 50 percent of GDP), and hard tried by the deceleration of economic growth⁽³⁾. In addition, the transfer of the management of the sanitary system at the subnational level is affected by the lack of a clear division of competencies on the matter between the central and local administrative levels. This leads, on the one hand, to the dilution of the responsibility of the authorities at both administrative levels and; on the other hand, to the emphasis of the so-called “leaky bucket” economic phenomenon in the budgets of decentralized hospitals which end up taking over medical emergency cases that should fall under the competence of hospitals subordinate to the Ministry of Health (Nicolescu et al., 2016, pp. 75-81). Additionally, the major deficit of the FNUASS is generated by the fact that only a third of the insured pay health contributions to this fund (Romanian Government, National Health Strategy 2022-2030 “Together, for health”, p. 16).

For Romania, an important lesson of the COVID-19 health crisis is precisely the avoidance of premature withdrawal of budgetary support (Romanian Government, Tax and Budgetary Strategy for 2022-2024, p. 8) and the need for adequate coordination by the state of its policies, including through better regulation. A first reaction to “dismantle” public health policies, consists in expanding the tax base for social health insurance contributions by establishing the payment obligation on all incomes obtained by natural persons, regardless of their nature (Romanian Government, National Health Strategy 2022-2030 “Together, for health”, p. 30).

Balancing the FNUASS would allow a financial consolidation of the health programs it supports and the improvement of the prevention component. However, the measure must be corroborated with the adoption of coherent and formalized policies to combat the main behavioural risk factors (smoking, alcohol consumption, and poor diet) directly associated with a large segment (26.36%) of all deaths in Romania. In this sense, the existence of alternatives that produce lower costs to society represents a great opportunity to decrease costs and improve public health outcomes.

To build our argument and calibrate the conception element of our pentagon, we turn to a subjective measure of how people judge their health in general on a scale from “very good” to “very bad”. This particular Eurostat indicator is expressed as the share of the population aged 16 or over perceiving itself to be in “good” or “very good” health. People’s perceived general health has been found to be a good predictor of people’s future healthcare use and mortality, thus indicating the direction of government intervention.

Figure 10. Share of people with good or very good perceived health (percentage) – 16 years or over, 2010-2021

Source: Eurostat (SDG_03_20). The data stem from the EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU SILC).

The aggregates, be them for the EU 27 or EU 28 (as shown in Figure 10) are always below Romania’s trend, showing a strong self-assessed good health of the population.

The current non-existence of such policies and the laxity of public decisions (including their insufficient substantiation) can be explained by the increasing percentage of the Romanian population with very good or good self-perceived health, increasing by over 13% in the year 2021 (28%) compared to 2019 (31.8%) (Eurostat (hlth_silc_10), accessed February 26, 2023), despite the negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The situation remains, however, unchanged among people with a higher level of education.

V.1. The scenario of poor diet – crosschecking data and measures

Figure 11. Body mass index (percentage) – 2014 vs. 2019

		BMI	Underweight	Normal	Obese
GEO	TIME				
European Union - 27 countries (from 2020)	2014	2.9	47.5	14.9	
European Union - 27 countries (from 2020)	2019	2.9	45.8	16.8	
European Union - 28 countries (2013-2020)	2014	2.8	47.0	15.4	
European Union - 28 countries (2013-2020)	2019	:	:	:	
Romania	2014	1.6	44.5	9.1	
Romania	2019	1.0	42.5	10.5	

Source: Eurostat (HLTH_EHIS_BM1E).

V.2. The scenario of smoking habit – crosschecking data and measures

Figure 12. Daily smokers of cigarettes (percentage) – 2014 vs. 2019

		European Union - 27 countries	European Union - 28 countries	Romania
SMOKING	TIME			
Total	2014	19.8	18.4	19.8
Total	2019	18.4	:	18.7
Less than 20 cigarettes per day	2014	12.9	12.5	14.9
Less than 20 cigarettes per day	2019	12.6	:	13.3
20 or more cigarettes per day	2014	6.1	5.0	4.9
20 or more cigarettes per day	2019	5.9	:	5.4

Source: Eurostat (HLTH_EHIS_SK3E).

V.3. The scenario of alcohol abuse – crosschecking data and measures

Figure 13. Frequency of heavy episodic drinking (percentage) – 2014 vs. 2019

GEO	TIME	FREQUENC			
		At least once a week	Every month	Less than once a month	Never or not in the last 1...
European Union - 27 ...	2014	4.9	14.7	19.7	60.8
European Union - 27 ...	2019	3.7	14.8	18.0	63.5
European Union - 28 ...	2014	5.5 (e)	14.4 (e)	20.2 (e)	59.9 (e)
European Union - 28 ...	2019	:	:	:	:
Romania	2014	10.6	24.3	15.0	50.1
Romania	2019	11.1	23.9	21.5	43.5

Source: Eurostat (HLTH_EHIS_AL3E).

In turn, this perception can also be explained through the lens of the characteristics of the national culture presented above, among which we distinguish the high level of conformity of the Romanian society to the *de facto* situations it faces, including negative ones. Acceptance by resignation of the shortcomings of the national health policy, although counterintuitive, can be reflected at the individual level by inducing the citizens to overestimate their own health status.

The context is estimated to be a much more worrying one if we refer to the unquantified effects of goods that are not fiscally highlighted, some of them counterfeited: namely, the black market of cigarettes and alcohol, but also the production of alcohol by Romanian households.

This worrying situation could be improved by modern policymaking, directed to nudge consumers towards better alternatives, alleviating those negative effects that are intrinsic to a market failure. A risk-based regulation (for instance, based on the sugar contained in specific products, or on the toxicity levels of goods such as cigarettes) could improve the resource allocation of the market, producing a concrete improvement in both health and economic terms. The presence of better alternatives in the market urges public authorities to move towards a more courageous kind of policymaking, where different products are treated differently, and where market failures are addressed properly. In doing so, the economic and financial cost of Romanian healthcare will decrease, helping public accounts, increasing efficiency, and bettering public health outcomes.

Notes

- (1) According to the Pandemic Resilience Index, the resilience of the health system has dropped from an average to a below average level. See <https://consumerchoicecenter.org/pandemic-resilience-index-2022/>
- (2) Community empowerment refers to the social action by means of which individuals play an active role in the decisions affecting their communities (international, national, local). Community empowerment stimulates involvement, participation, commitment and increases the community's control in the process of elaborating and executing these decisions.
- (3) See National Strategy and Forecast Commission, <https://cnp.ro/>

References

- Bițoiu, T.I. and Rădulescu, C., 2015. The 3c Decision Cockpit for A Market-Oriented Public Administration, SEA – Practical Application of Science, Romanian Foundation for Business Intelligence, Editorial Department, Issue 8, pp. 127-134, June.
- Mc Breen, J., Di Tosto, G., Dignum, F., Hofstede, G., 2011. *Linking Norms and Cultures*, IEEE Computer Society.
- Dinu, T.I. and Dumitrică, C.D., 2014. Covering the social costs of market failure – the unsub of the value added, *Theoretical and Applied Economics*, Vol. XXI, No. 12(601), pp. 51-62.
- Hofstede, G., 2011. Dimensionalizing Cultures: The Hofstede Model in Context, Online Readings in Psychology and Culture, Unit 2. Retrieved from <<http://scholarworks.gvsu.edu/orpc/vol2/iss1/8>>
- Liu, S., Veugelers, P.J., Liu, C. et al. The Cost Effectiveness of Taxation of Sugary Foods and Beverages: A Systematic Review of Economic Evaluations, *Appl Health Econ Health Policy* 20, pp. 185-198 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40258-021-00685-x>
- Moldoveanu, G., 2005. *Analiză și comportament organizațional*, Economic Publishing House, Bucharest.
- Niculescu, C.E., Bițoiu, I.T., Rădulescu, C.R., 2016. The challenges of the Romanian healthcare system-bigger means state of the art competencies for the more and more complex healthcare services demand. In Țăranu, A. (Ed.), Proceedings of the third Academos Conference 2016. Governing for the future: interdisciplinary perspectives for a sustainable world, Medimond, Bologna, pp. 75-81.
- Ubel, P.A., 2009. *The Price of Life and the Cost of Health Care: Why the Free Market Alone Can't Fix Health Care*, Harvard Business Review Press, Product #: 3944BC-PDF-ENG, Publication date: 20 January 2009.
- Zilberman, D., 1999. *Externalities, Market Failure, and Government Policy*, EEP 101, retrieved on January 19 2023, available at <<http://are.berkeley.edu/courses/EEP101/Detail%20Notes%20PDF/Cha03,%20Externalities.pdf>>
- Buttonwood, 2011. The return of rationing. The difficult decisions needed in an age of austerity, *The Economist*, print edition Finance and Economics, June 23, 2011.
- EU Expert Group on Health Systems Performance Assessment (HSPA), 2019. Tools and methodologies to assess the efficiency of health care services in Europe. An overview of current approaches and opportunities for improvement. Report by the Expert Group on Health System Performance Assessment, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, p. 7.
- European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies. The COVID-19 Health Systems Response Monitor (HSRM): Cross-Country Analysis. <<https://eurohealthobservatory.who.int/monitors/hcrm/hcrm-countries>>
- Our World in Data, <<https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/number-of-deaths-by-risk-factor?tab=table>>
- Romanian Government, National Health Strategy 2022-2030 “Together, for health”. Document pending advice and approval. Retrieved from <https://www.ms.ro/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/SNS_2022-2030.pdf>
- Romanian Government, Tax and Budgetary Strategy for 2022-2024, p. 8.
- The Consumer Choice Center. The Pandemic Resilience Index. Available at <<https://consumerchoicecenter.org/pandemic-resilience-index-2022/>>

Appendix

Table 1. The correlation between public health expenditure pattern (2014-2019) and the 6-D of the Hofstede model of national culture (at the EU level)

The Member States of the European Union (2014-2019)	General government expenditure (as a share of gross domestic product ^{*)} On health (Average 2014-2019)	The 6-D of the Hofstede model of national culture					
		Power Distance	Uncertainty Avoidance	Individualism versus Collectivism	Masculinity versus Femininity	Long Term versus Short Term Orientation	Indulgence versus Restraint
Italy Beveridge	6,90	50	76	70	75	61	30
Spain	6,10	57	51	42	86	48	44
Austria	8,17	11	55	79	70	60	63
Germany	7,23	35	67	66	65	83	40
United Kingdom	7,55	35	89	66	35	51	69
Sweden	6,90	31	71	5	29	53	78
Finland	7,25	33	63	26	59	38	57
Denmark	8,38	18	74	16	23	35	70
Croatia	6,25	73	33	40	80	58	33
Belgium	7,70	65	75	54	94	82	57
Poland	4,73	68	60	64	93	38	29
Lithuania	5,80	42	60	19	65	82	16
Bulgaria	5,15	70	30	40	85	69	16
Slovakia	7,32	100	52	100	51	77	28
Slovenia	6,62	71	27	19	88	49	48
Romania	4,37	90	30	42	90	52	20
Estonia	5,18	40	60	30	60	82	16
Hungary	4,75	46	80	88	82	58	31
Czech R.	7,50	57	58	57	74	70	29
Latvia	3,82	44	70	9	63	69	13
France	8,08	68	71	43	86	63	48
Portugal	6,32	63	27	31	99	28	33
Netherlands	7,73	38	80	14	53	67	68
Cyprus	2,82	60	35	57	100	45	50
Greece	5,10	28	70	68	35	24	65
Ireland	5,25	40	60	50	70	64	56
Luxembourg	5,07	56	59	47	96	47	66
Malta	5,40	50	76	70	75	61	30
Correlation between the general government expenditure (as a share of GDP) on Health (Average 2014-2019) and each of the 6 D Hofstede's model of national culture		rho = -0.32	rho = -0.15	rho = 0.22	rho = 0.14	rho = 0.29	rho = 0,73
		Error; no correlation					

^{*)} Eurostat (gov_10a_exp), retrieved on 22 March 2021.

Incentivizing CEOs via pay and forced turnover: Do tenure and managerial ability matter?

Nadide BANU OLCAY GÜNER
University of Houston-Downtown, USA
olcaygunern@uhd.edu

Abstract. *Direct pay and dismissal for poor performance are important instruments to incentivize CEOs. I empirically analyze how the use of them depends on tenure and managerial ability. For managers promoted from within a firm, ability is proxied by age at the time of promotion. For outside hires, I use constructed measures of reputation based on media citations. Using a sample of firms in S&P 1500, I find that pay and performance sensitivity of dismissal probability increase with tenure. For outsider CEOs, better reputation increases pay, but decreases tenure sensitivity of pay with stronger effects for more current measures. For both insiders and outsiders, ability decreases the dismissal probability.*

Keywords: incentives, CEO pay, CEO dismissal, managerial ability, job tenure.

JEL Classification: J41, J63, L20, M52, M55.

Introduction

How to design the right type of executive compensation plans? This has been a constant challenge for boards and shareholders, and in essence, is a typical agency problem: the executive (the agent) must be motivated to act in the best interests of the shareholders (the principals), who have delegated their authority to the board of directors. The theoretical agency literature has mainly focused on the use of performance-related pay as an incentive device. However, incentives can also be provided by the threat of termination of employment following poor performance. These two instruments interact: a termination threat provides good incentives only if the expected future pay within the firm is significantly higher than the outside option.

Lazear (1981) argues that wages should increase with tenure to provide good incentives. But it is less clear whether the optimal termination threat will also be increasing; i.e., if poor performance is more likely to result in termination for senior than for junior executives. Moreover, Lazear's upward sloping wage schedule requires a long-run commitment as the wage exceeds marginal product over time. However, long-term contracts are not common in CEO labor markets; every year performance is mostly evaluated, and contracts are renewed.

In Olcay (2016), I consider a dynamic agency model with limited commitment to study the optimal contracts with incentive pay and termination threat. The model is designed to study incentive pay, but due its simplifying assumptions, the interpretation of its results applies to total pay as well. The main prediction is that the use of both incentive devices increases with tenure. A termination threat is included in the short-term contract if and only if the agent's expected future surplus from the relationship is sufficiently high compared to the principal's expected future gain. Moreover, at a given point in time, the observed productivity ("ability") of the agent affects the optimal contract in opposite ways. The higher is the agent's ability, the higher should be the wage conditional on good performance, and the smaller should be the risk of termination after poor performance.

The focus of this empirical study is to which extend pay and forced turnover are used as incentive devices for CEOs as well as whether there is a significant relationship of job tenure and managerial ability to these devices. We also consider how ability and tenure interact in the provision of incentives: does managerial ability influence the sensitivities of CEO pay and forced turnover to tenure? Several previous theories also have implications for these relationships: the learning theory of Murphy (1986), the career concerns model of Gibbons and Murphy (1992), and the entrenchment theory of Hermalin and Weisbach (1998).

Murphy's (1986) adverse selection model requires that the optimal contract should be designed to facilitate the shareholder's learning about managerial ability. Pay-performance sensitivity decreases over time as the shareholders learn more about ability by assessing CEO's performance. Yet, as beliefs about ability are updated through time, pay level increases.

Gibbons and Murphy's (1992) model also has adverse selection with unknown managerial ability; however, the presence of a competitive executive market creates career concerns:

the junior executive is motivated to work hard to establish her reputation and reluctant to bear too much risk. Therefore, the optimal pay-performance sensitivity increases over tenure as the board needs to offset the reduction in her career concerns and it becomes less difficult to share the risk. Moreover, learning leads to a decrease in the variance of expected performance and hence a performance that would not have triggered termination earlier may do so later: i.e., the sensitivity of dismissal probability increases (Allgood and Farrell, 2000).

The entrenchment theory of Hermalin and Weisbach (1998) differs dramatically from standard agency theories of optimal contracting; hence, produces quite different predictions. The senior executive is more likely to get entrenched, hence dominate the board becoming harder to be dismissed for performance and setting her own pay, which is higher and less sensitive to performance (Bebchuk and Fried, 2004).

Regarding the impact of managerial ability on incentive provision, career concerns theory makes an intuitive prediction. If the CEO has enough bargaining power, she may negotiate for a raise after strong profits and can capture the whole surplus created by the good news. Moreover, if low profits reveal bad news about ability, the shareholders have to bear the full negative surplus. Formalizing this perspective, Harris and Holmstrom (1982) suggest that shareholders suffer more from bad news than they benefit from good news. The entrenchment theory would again predict a positive ability-pay relationship: higher ability CEOs being more likely to get entrenched and increase their own pay.

Regarding the second incentive tool, the theories imply a weaker relationship with performance for highly talented CEOs. In a career concerns model, the reason is that those CEOs are identified with less performance uncertainty; hence, their performance is less likely to be informative. According to the entrenchment model, they are more powerful and hence more likely to face a passive board of directors; i.e. dismissal probability is both weaker and less sensitive to performance.

Table 1. *Theoretical predictions*

	Learning		Career Concerns		Entrenchment		Olcay (2016)	
	Tenure	Ability	Tenure	Ability	Tenure	Ability	Tenure	Ability
Total CEO Pay	+	n/a	n/a	+	+	+	+	+
Pay-Performance	-	n/a	+	n/a	-	-	+	+
Probability of Forced Turnover	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	-	-	+	-
Probability of Forced Turnover-Perf.	n/a	n/a	+	-	-	-	+	-

Table 1 summarizes the predictions of these theories we discussed so far. The empirical analysis here to investigate these hypotheses is twofold. Section 3 focuses on how CEO pay changes by tenure and managerial ability. Section 4, runs a similar analysis on performance-related turnover. Two empirical proxies for managerial ability are used: media visibility, attempting to capture reputational aspects of the outsider CEO's ability (hand-collected through counting articles in top business journals), and age when the insider CEO is promoted to the position. The idea is that higher media visibility and lower age at the time of promotion are both signals of higher managerial ability. Data on executive compensation, firm performance and control variables, both at the CEO and firm level, is

drawn from the COMPUSTAT database for the firms in S&P 1500 between 1998-2008. Data for forced turnover is hand-collected by reading news items found through Factiva and Google web search.

The results suggest that performance and the two incentive devices are highly correlated; i.e., these tools are indeed used as incentive mechanisms. Also, I find that pay and performance sensitivity of performance related dismissal probability increases with seniority. However, there is no strong evidence that dismissal probability follows a particular time pattern. For outsider CEOs, reputation, as a measure for managerial ability, increases pay but decreases dismissal probability where the impact is strongest as more current measures are used. It also decreases tenure sensitivity of pay only when it is proxied by the most current (i.e., short-term) measure. For insider CEOs, the likelihood of dismissal is also decreasing in managerial ability where ability is proxied by Age-at-promotion.

Early studies on the relationship between executive pay and performance (Coughlan and Schmidt, 1985; Murphy (1986); Jensen and Murphy, 1990; Abowd, 1990; Leonard, 1990) mainly agree that firm performance is largely positively related to pay-performance sensitivity after controlling for risk. Other studies are focused on whether CEOs are rewarded for performance which is measured relative to the market or industry (Antle and Smith, 1986; Gibbons and Murphy, 1992).

An important early finding in growing literature of CEO turnover is that a firm's net of market performance and the probability of turnover are inversely associated (Coughlan and Schmidt (1985) and Warner et al. (1988); yet, managers are rarely fired due to poor performance. Later research provides evidence that turnover rates become more sensitive to performance (e.g., Huson et al., 2001; Kaplan and Minton, 2012); i.e. termination, as an incentive tool, is becoming a more important threat over executives.

A related finding by Weisbach (1988) is that the magnitude of the turnover-performance relation is strongest in companies dominated by independent outside directors. Parrino (1997) shows that the outside replacements are mostly used by companies which perform poorly as compared to their peers. These studies indicate that poor firm performance is the single most important determinant of forced turnover.

Another line of empirical research disregards the implications of optimal contracting and instead explores the entrenchment effect of executive's equity ownership. Murphy and Zimmerman (1993), Denis et al. (1997) and Hadlock and Lumer (1997), Goyal and Park (2002), Dahya, Lonie, and Power (1998) and Nguyen (2011) investigate the impact of corporate governance and found that probability of turnover is negatively related to the ownership stake.

The paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 describes the data sources and variables. Sections 3 and 4 present the empirical tests and results regarding pay and forced turnover, respectively. Section 5 concludes.

1. Data description

To analyze the impact of tenure and managerial ability on pay and the likelihood of forced turnover, I construct a data set of the CEO labor market which contains detailed information on turnovers and empirical proxies for ability. This section explains how the data set is constructed and the collection process of variables.

1.1. Sample selection

The CEO succession data is hand-collected and includes all firms in S&P 500-Large Cap between 1998-2008. ExecuComp provides information on the top five executives of all firms in S&P 1500. I recognize a turnover for each year in which the CEO is identified in ExecuComp changes.

To identify forced departure, I carefully search news items on the Lexis-Nexis Academic Universe and Factiva for each CEO change. Changes accompanied by poor performance are identified as forced turnover. These news items openly state that prior stock price or accounting returns have been declining in the past quarters. Also, for each succession in the sample, I hand collect exact announcement dates which are the earliest dates of the news about incumbent CEO departure and successor CEO appointment. All other news which explicitly mention that CEO has departed the company because she became a CEO at another firm, forced out for different reasons (improper use of corporate funds, violation of Security Exchange Act, etc.), resigned due to conflict with board, left due to health reasons, deceased or retired are not included. This method of identifying turnover is similar to that of Weisbach (1988) and Denis and Denis (1995).

Table 2. CEO turnover

Year	Number of CEO changes	Turnover rate	Resign/retire bad perf.	Resign 1	Resign 2	Resign 3	Retire 1	Retire 2	Merger/Interim	Nothing
1998	43	11.2	11	1	1	2	12	10	3	3
1999	48	11.9	11	1	0	1	14	13	2	6
2000	58	13.8	18	3	2	4	10	13	2	6
2001	40	9.5	7	1	1	1	7	16	4	3
2002	44	10.3	11	3	2	1	7	11	3	6
2003	55	12.5	8	1	2	6	16	13	5	4
2004	63	14.0	9	0	5	7	18	20	0	4
2005	48	10.4	4	2	0	5	9	14	7	7
2006	63	13.3	10	4	6	3	21	13	2	5
2007	58	12.0	11	0	0	10	16	7	2	11
2008	22	5.5	5	1	0	2	5	5	2	2
TOTAL	542	11.4	105	17	19	42	135	135	32	57

Note: Resign/Retire Bad Per. consists of CEO changes after it is explicitly announced that the CEO change is due to bad performance. Resign1 is the cases where in the news it says the CEO suddenly quits and no further explanation is found. Resign2 is CEO changes after scandals (law suits due to affair with subordinates or violated such and such act), arrested or forced out for different reasons (such as conflict with the board or left the company for personal reasons.) Resign3 is cases where CEO left the firm for good reason, health reasons or deceased. Retire1 is instances where CEO has retired and joined the board as executive/non-executive chairman afterwards. Retire2 includes CEO changes with explicit evidence that CEO has really retired or being retired is not related with performance. Merger/interim refers to CEO changes after merger or acquisition, or CEO had appointed on interim basis before. Nothing consists of cases where no news item related with CEO change is found.

Table 3. *Forced CEO turnover*

	Number of CEO changes	Forced 1	% in all changes	Forced 2	Forced 3	% in all changes
1998	43	11	25.6	6	17	39.5
1999	48	11	22.9	9	20	41.7
2000	58	18	31.0	10	28	48.3
2001	40	7	17.5	3	10	25.0
2002	44	11	25.0	10	21	47.7
2003	55	8	14.5	10	18	32.7
2004	63	9	14.3	13	22	34.9
2005	48	4	8.3	8	12	25.0
2006	63	10	15.9	18	28	44.4
2007	58	11	19.0	12	23	39.7
2008	22	5	22.7	8	13	59.1
TOTAL	542	105	19.4	107	212	39.1

Note: FORCED1 consists of the observations in the category, Resign/Retire after Bad Perf. in Table 1. FORCED 2 is CEO changes below age of 60 and related with categories Retire1, Retire2 (excluding instances explicitly unrelated with performance), Resign1, Nothing. FORCED3 is the sum of FORCED1 and FORCED2.

By using news items, I form different categories for reasons of CEO departure. Table 2 includes information about the number of departures for different reasons during 1998-2008. The sample consists of 542 CEO changes out of 4769 firm-year observations during 1998-2008. The total turnover rate is 11.4%.⁽¹⁾ Using this detailed information, I construct the forced turnover data in Table 5. Forced 1 is constructed using the news items in which it is explicitly stated that the CEO is terminated for poor performance. This yields 105 CEO changes. For the rest of classification, I follow Parrino's (1997) method. Such classification is important in a study of forced turnover since CEOs are seldomly fired openly due to poor performance. I classify the remaining changes as potential forced departure if the departing CEO is less than the normal retirement age which is the mean age for CEO departure. In our sample, this is around age 61. In Table 5, Forced 2 includes CEO changes if the reason of departure is announced either as retired (but excluding those announcements which explicitly state that the departure is not related with performance), or if the reason is not specified, or the news item specifies the departure as unexpected or abrupt, and for all these observations the CEO is below the normal retirement age. This yields 107 more observations for forced turnover. Forced 3 is the sum of Forced 1 and Forced 2.

In Table 5, 39% of all CEO changes are performance related. This finding is in line with a total forced turnover rate of 36%, as found by Falato et al. (2015) whose sample covers the firms in S&P 1500 during 1993-2005. However, it is relatively higher than 23.4% as reported by Huson et al. (2001) for a sample of executives listed only in Forbes over the period 1989-1994. Table 5, however, reveals that while the turnover data in our sample does not show a particular time pattern, there is significant time variation in the rate of both forced and overall turnovers.

1.2. Measures for firm performance and firm level controls

I enhance the data set with several measures of firm performance, in addition to various firm level controls which have been identified as important measures in the CEO labor market. All measures discussed below are at calendar year-end and taken from COMPUSTAT. Descriptive statistics for these variables are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. *Descriptive statistics*

	N	Mean	Med.	Std.Dev.	Max	Min
CEO Characteristics and Pay						
Tenure	10276	7.8	5	7.5	42	1
Age	10246	55.1	55	7.3	85	34
Outsider	5915	0.35	0	0.47	1	0
Total CEO Pay (\$thousand)	10659	8	8	1.09	13.3	5.5
Performance Measures and Firm Controls						
Size (log Total Assets, \$mil.)	10019	7.4	7.3	1.5	12.9	1.9
Dividend Yield	10011	1.38	0.6	3.27	169.7	0.1
Return on Assets (ROA)	11024	0.054	0.049	0.079	0.59	-1.66
Return on Equity (ROE)	10933	0.12	0.14	0.36	16.09	-1.97
Net Income over Assets (NIA)	11034	0.05	0.05	0.087	0.98	-2.8
Industry Adjusted ROA	11034	0.037	0.019	0.14	2.07	-4.48
Industry Adjusted ROE	10933	0.1	0.044	0.82	16.8	-18.7
Industry Adjusted NIA	11034	0.03	0.01	0.18	2.08	-5.06
Corporate Governance						
Share Ownership	11804	0.03	0	0.19	1	0
Board Member	11804	0.97	1	0.12	1	0
CEO Ability						
Age-at-promotion	3646	49.08	49	7.4	79	34
Good Press (1 year)	4781	23.6	6	65.6	1227	0
Good Press (3 years)	4781	57.7	17	155.6	3489	0
Good Press (5 years)	4781	81.5	25	221.8	4333	0
Press (1 year)	4781	29.5	8	84.8	1673	0
Press (3 years)	4781	73.7	20	199.4	4040	0
Press (5 years)	4781	104.2	29	286	4987	0

I use three different measures of firm performance: return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE) and ratio of Net Income to the book value of assets (NIA). To filter out industry specific shocks, I create industry average counterparts. In the COMPUSTAT database, each firm has been specified with a four-digit SIC code. To identify the industry, I use the first two digits of the SIC code which is used in calculating firm's industry-adjusted performance. By using the overall sample in COMPUSTAT (over 20,000 firms), I calculate industry averages for the firms in the sample at hand.

The main set of firm controls includes firm size (logarithm of total assets) and firm's dividend yield. While firm size is an important variable on CEO labour markets (Gabaix and Landier, 2008 and Tervio, 2007), dividend yield of the firm is used to control for firm's riskiness.

1.3. CEO pay, tenure and CEO characteristics

To examine the pay-tenure relationship, I use the natural logarithm of the dollar value of CEO's total pay (ExecuComp's TDC1) which includes salary, bonus, long-term incentive plans, restricted stock, and stock appreciation rights.

Previous research suggests that CEO pay is a function of age (e.g. Milbourn, 2003 and Chevalier and Ellison, 1999), hence it is included as a control variable. Data for CEO tenure is created by using data items in Execucomp. Finally, I classify CEOs who had been with their firms for one year or less at the time of their appointments as outsiders. As Table 4 summarizes, the median CEO in our sample has 5 years of tenure, is 55 years old and has been promoted from inside.

1.4. Measures for CEO's power on Corporate Governance

To control for CEO's potential power on corporate governance, I create two dummy variables using data items in ExecuComp: Board Member is equal to 1 if CEO has served as a director during the calendar year, and Share Ownership is equal to 1 if she holds more than 5% of the firm's total shares. Table 4 indicates that 3% of the sample contains firm-year observations with the firm's CEO holding either 5% or more of the total shares. Also 97% of the observations contain CEOs who are a board member.

1.5. Measures for CEO ability

I construct three different empirical proxies for ability. The first empirical proxy, Press, measures the media visibility of a CEO and attempts to capture how her ability is perceived. To create Press variable, I count the number of articles containing the CEO's name and company affiliation that appear in the major US global newspapers and business journals for a given year (see Appendix A). However, since reputation, as implied by Press variable builds in time, I extend this proxy further and create three different proxies out of it: Press (1 year), Press (3 years) and Press (5 years) which refer to the number of articles during the previous year, last three years, and last five years prior to the current year. With this extension, media visibility measures reputation in different time windows; Press (1 year) refers to a relatively more current measure of reputation whereas Press (5 years) is a proxy for less current measure.

Using Lexis-Nexis database and restricting the search to the sources in Appendix A, I conduct text searches using both the CEO's last name and company name. The classification of media visibility variable uses the same methods as previously used by Milbourn (2003), Francis et al. (2008), and Rajgopal et al., (2006): CEOs with higher media visibility are more likely to be of higher ability.

Following Falato et al. (2015), I construct a second empirical proxy, Good Press, by classifying the articles in which CEO's name appear by connotation. This aims to prevent any potential mistake that Press variable might cause since Press does not necessarily imply Good Press. Good Press only includes the number of articles with non-negative tone. To do that, I first create a Bad Press variable, which includes the number of articles only with negative connotation. To find the number of articles which Bad Press will include, I count the number of articles containing words with a negative connotation that appear in the major U.S. and global business newspapers in a calendar year (see Appendix A). Finally Good Press is defined by the difference between Press and Bad Press. Similar to the previous studies, in our sample Good Press is highly correlated with Press (0.97). However, in line with the cross sectional difference as Falato et al. (2015) finds, the correlation is higher at the high end of the distribution of Press (0.81 for above median CEOs), and relatively lower at the low end (0.67 for below median CEOs). According to Table 4, the median CEO receives 8 media mentions, out of which 6 is positive during a year. This number is equal to 20 (17 positive) when media mentions are counted over three years and equal to 29 (25 positive) when counted over five years.

The final empirical proxy in our empirical analysis is Age-at-promotion, which will be used in analyzing the sub-sample of insider CEOs. The idea is that the firm has an opportunity

to observe the performance of an insider executive for a significantly long time before she is promoted to the position. Therefore, the lower the age at the time of promotion, the higher managerial ability as perceived by the board. CEOs of higher ability will spend less time on the corporate ladder and given the potential reluctance of firms to promote younger executives due to well-known hurdles, a lower age at the time of promotion is indeed a signal for higher ability. In this way, I intend to capture observed aspects of managerial ability, which cannot be achieved by our reputation proxy. To create this variable, I use ExecuComp's data items on current age and date when the executive became CEO and also use OneSource for missing data entries in ExecuComp. As Table 4 indicates, the median CEO's age when she is promoted to the position is equal to 49.

Measuring managerial ability has in fact been a great challenge for empirical researchers. Among these, Hayes and Schaefer (1999) proposes an interesting method which utilizes deriving implications for financial market responses to news of unexpected firm-manager separations. But this counts on infrequent events. More recently Demerjian et al. (2012) use Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) which yields a measure for managerial efficiency isolated from firm efficiency. However, the results are highly sensitive to how the relative importance of the variables used for firm's efficiency score is specified and this cannot be statistically tested.

2. Analysis I: Relations of CEO pay with tenure and managerial ability

2.1. CEO pay and tenure

The theoretical background for this section is based on the models as discussed in the Introduction. Before the results, we discuss our empirical strategy which will be used to test the hypothesis on tenure-pay relationships.

2.1.1. Empirical strategy

The econometric model specifications used consider both linear and nonlinear relationships regarding the tenure variable. Additionally, to deal with the potential problem of unobserved heterogeneity, a fixed-effects (FE) model is used to study the relationship between tenure and pay. The baseline regression takes the following form:

$$w_{ijt} = \beta_1 \times Tenure_{ijt} + \beta_2 \times Tenure_{ijt}^2 + \beta_3 \times Tenure_{ijt} \times Performance + \beta_4 \times Tenure_{ijt}^2 \times Performance + \beta_5 \times Performance + \beta_6 \times Controls_{ijt} + \alpha_{ij} + e_{ijt} \quad (1)$$

where w_{ijt} is the log of annual total pay (TDC1) of CEO i , at firm j , in year t . The controls are both at the firm and at the CEO level and discussed in Section 2. Since in our data set, we do not observe CEOs working for more than one firm, in equation (1), α_{ij} is the time invariant and unobserved CEO-firm fixed effect (i.e. the "match effect") whereas e_{ijt} is the idiosyncratic error term. Although the previously discussed theories do not suggest a particular prediction on the sign of β_2 they persistently point out a positive sign for β_1 .

The advantage of the FE model is to eliminate the well-known bias created by the OLS method which discards the unobserved differences across individuals in the study of panel

data. Although it has limitations in investigating the effects of time invariant and observed individual characteristics (e.g. being an outsider CEO), FE model performs more efficiently, especially in the presence of time invariant unobserved heterogeneity which is correlated with other explanatory variables, i.e. alpha in equation (1) (see also, for example, Murphy (1986), Aggarwal and Samwick (1999, 2003); Cichello (2005)). Employing a fixed-effect at the CEO-firm level helps us to interpret the results of the estimation as a measure of the relationship between pay and tenure for a given CEO-firm match.⁽²⁾ Note that by using equation (1), we investigate the determinants of total pay which is in logs. But since the performance variable is in levels, β_5 helps us to calculate total pay-performance elasticities. Therefore, β_3 is estimate of tenure impact on total pay-performance elasticities.⁽³⁾

2.1.2. Results

Using the specification in equation (1) to relate natural logarithm of CEO total pay to CEO tenure variables, I consider alternative measures for firm performance: ROA, ROE and NIA.⁽⁴⁾ These measures are based on accounting returns which are widely used in the study of executive compensation literature due to lower noise they have as compared to stock prices (Banker and Datar, 1989). Year dummies are also included to control potential common factors which affect all individuals in a given year.

Results of the regressions are presented in Table 5. Standard errors are corrected for both heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation, and clustered at the CEO level. In Table 5, the first specification considers ROA as a performance measure whereas the second and third use ROE and ratio of NIA, respectively. Regardless of whether a linear or non-linear specification is used, the results systematically report a positive and statistically significant relationship between the level of CEO pay and tenure.

Table 5. CEO performance, pay and tenure

Variables	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
Tenure	0.028* (2.21)	0.0510*** (3.58)	0.0254* (2.06)	0.0486*** (3.67)	0.0273* (2.09)	0.0477** (3.36)
Tenure ²		-0.000948** (-2.93)		-0.00102*** (-3.38)		-0.000868** (-2.71)
ROA	0.907** (4.06)	0.874*** (4.11)				
ROE			0.0763* (2.05)	0.0424* (2.07)		
NIA					0.082*** (4.32)	0.65*** (4.28)
ROA*Tenure	0.0479 (1.35)	0.0499 (0.62)				
ROA*Tenure ²		-0.000760 (-0.27)				
ROE*Tenure			0.0176 (1.68)	0.0120 (0.53)		
ROE*Tenure ²				0.000180 (0.19)		
NIA*Tenure					0.0557 (1.77)	0.0954 (1.37)
NIA*Tenure ²						-0.00216 (-0.92)
Age	0.0256 (1.88)	0.0248 (1.96)	0.0259* (1.98)	0.0249 (1.90)	0.0268 (1.96)	0.0258 (1.88)

Variables	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
Size	0.261** (4.37)	0.207*** (3.50)	0.323*** (5.52)	0.256*** (4.21)	0.267*** (4.48)	0.211*** (3.54)
Divyield	0.251 (1.11)	-0.00792 (-0.98)	0.343 (1.49)	-0.0102 (-1.12)	0.239 (1.05)	-0.00812 (-1.01)
Share Ownership	-0.0297 (-0.43)	-0.0323 (-0.49)	-0.0319 (-0.46)	-0.0368 (-0.56)	-0.0251 (-0.36)	-0.0296 (-0.45)
Board Member	-0.376 (-0.23)	-0.203 (-0.26)	-0.385 (-0.28)	-0.201 (-0.30)	-0.371 (-0.18)	-0.203 (-0.20)
Number of Obs.	7568	7568	7508	7508	7568	7568
Number of CEOs	1930	1930	1922	1922	1930	1930
R ²	17%	21%	23%	25%	18%	21%

Note: Model 1 uses Return on Assets (ROA), Models 2 and 3 uses Return on Equity (ROE) and the ratio of Net Income to the book value of assets (NIA) respectively. Size is proxied by natural log of Net Sales. Divyield is the firm's dividend yield. Share Ownership is a dummy which takes value 1 if the CEO's ownership of total shares is greater than 5%. Board Member is a dummy variable which is equal to one if the CEO served as a board member during the fiscal year. All specifications include year dummies. In parantheses, we present t-statistics using robust standard errors clustered by CEO. Level of significance are denoted by ***, **, and * for statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

In terms of the control variables, the results also suggest a positive and statistically significant relationship between firm performance indicators and CEO pay. Since pay is in logarithms but all performance measures are in levels, it is possible to interpret the performance-pay elasticities using the fitted value of each performance measure evaluated at its sample median. For example, under non-linearity assumption, the related estimated coefficient implies that 1% increase in ROA (ROE and NIA, respectively), corresponds to 0.06% increase in total pay (0.02% and 0.06%, respectively).⁽⁵⁾ However, note that the coefficients of the interaction variables between tenure and performance are not significant.

The results report that larger firms pay higher levels of pay; larger firms may employ better qualified and better paid managers (Rosen, 1982; Kostiuk, 1990). Since firm size is defined as natural logarithm of sales, the estimated coefficient in Table 5, is directly interpreted as the elasticity of CEO pay to firm size. The results predict that, holding everything else constant, a firm that is 10% larger in size, depending on the econometric model specification, will pay its CEO about 20-25% more.

CEO age has a marginally significant and positive impact on total pay. Calculating the elasticity of pay to age by evaluating the fitted value of age at sample median yields the following prediction: controlling for performance, tenure, firm size, risk and CEO's power in corporate governance, a CEO at the age of 55 will be paid 15% more relative to a CEO at the age of 50. One explanation is that older CEOs are more experienced and hence compensated by a higher level of pay. The other reason could be that older CEOs are likely to be wealthier as compared to their younger peers; therefore they are more expensive to incentivize. Finally, I include controls for the CEO's corporate governance; i.e., Board Member and Share Ownership, both of which are defined in Section 2. However, the results report no significant relationship between these controls and CEO pay.

Figure 1 plots the relationship between log of total pay for a non-linear tenure-pay relationship using the estimates of Models 1, 2 and 3, and is obtained in the following way: for each model, the predicted values for pay are obtained through the estimated coefficients of second specification in Table 5. Consistent with the theoretical predictions, the figure

suggests that tenure increases pay. Although the theory does not provide a particular prediction, observe that the impact of tenure on pay has a decreasing rate: pay is highly sensitive to tenure in first years of appointment, but less sensitive thereafter.

Figure 1. Tenure and CEO Pay

2.2. The impact of ability on CEO pay and tenure-pay relationship

Recall that all theories discussed have a common prediction: higher managerial ability is associated with higher pay regardless of the assumption about the information on ability (i.e.; imperfect (as in learning and career concerns models) or not (as in Olcay, 2016)). To test this, I use the age of an insider CEO as a proxy since the younger the CEO is at the time of promotion, the higher her managerial ability will be as evaluated by the board. For outsider CEOs, however, media visibility will be used to proxy managerial reputation.

Table 6. Proxy: media visibility

	Press		Good Press	
	Top 25%	Bottom 25%	Top 25%	Bottom 25%
Panel A (1 year)				
Median Media Visibility	51	1	40	1
Tenure	5	5	5	5
CEO Pay(log total compensation)	9.84	8.3	9.23	8.4
ROA	0.068	0.052	0.058	0.053
ROE	0.170	0.142	0.161	0.146
NIA	0.058	0.052	0.058	0.053
Panel B (3 years)				
Median Media Visibility	129	3	101	3
Tenure	5	5	5	5
CEO Pay(log total compensation)	9.26	8.35	9.26	8.38
ROA	0.056	0.052	0.056	0.052
ROE	0.159	0.147	0.160	0.147
NIA	0.057	0.054	0.057	0.054
Panel C (5 years)				
Median Media Visibility	177	5	140	4
Tenure	5	5	5	4
CEO Pay(log total compensation)	9.26	8.36	9.25	8.38
ROA	0.058	0.051	0.058	0.051
ROE	0.161	0.144	0.161	0.144
NIA	0.058	0.052	0.058	0.052
Number of Obs.	1195	1195	1195	1195

Table 7. Proxy: Age-at-promotion

	Top 25%	Bottom 25%
Age-at-promotion	45	56
Tenure	9	3
CEO Pay(log total compensation)	8.69	8.71
ROA	0.058	0.04
ROE	0.146	0.142
NIA	0.059	0.047
Number of Obs.	2609	2609

Tables 6 and 7 present the descriptive statistics of our empirical proxies for the top and the bottom quartiles of the sample. In Table 6, median tenure is equal to 5 years. Not surprisingly, median CEO's performance is always higher in the top quartile. In terms of how far ability affects tenure sensitivity of pay, Figure 2 provides a brief idea where the two quartiles are compared in terms of the percentage change in compensation as the median CEO's tenure increases from less than 5 years to more than 5 years. Note that median CEO at the top quartile experiences a higher percentage change in compensation as compared to median CEO at the bottom quartile.

Figure 2. % Change in Median CEO Compensation as tenure Increases (from "less than 5 years" to "more than 5 years") – Top 25% vs. Bottom 25%

2.2.1. Empirical strategy

To explore the impact of managerial reputation over pay and tenure-pay relationship, I again use FE model where equation (1) is modified in the following way:

$$w_{ijt} = \beta_1 \times Tenure_{ijt} + \beta_2 \times Tenure_{ijt}^2 + \beta_3 \times Ability_{it} + \beta_4 \times (Ability_{it} * Tenure_{ijt}) + \beta_5 \times (Ability_{it} \times Tenure_{ijt}) + \beta_6 \times Controls_{ijt} + \alpha_{ij} + e_{ijt} \quad (2)$$

In line with the previously discussed theories, we expect to have estimated $\beta_3 > 0$. Even though our theoretical discussion does not provide a particular prediction, we also test whether ability has an impact on tenure-sensitivity of CEO pay, i.e. whether the estimated $\beta_4 > 0$ is statistically different than zero.

3.2.2. Results

Focusing on the short-term measure of reputation in Table 8, we find that one unit increase in the number of "positive" media mentions increases CEO pay by 1.22% when ROA is used as a performance measure (by 1.19% and 1.18% when ROE and NIA is used,

respectively). However, the impact is much lower when total media mentions is used: in Table 10, one more media mention increases CEO pay by 0.48% when ROA is used as a performance measure.

The median CEO in our sample earns \$6.7k. Therefore our results imply that one more positive media mention implies an increase in CEO pay by \$80,000 (by \$40,000 if total mentions is used). On the other hand, the estimated coefficients of the interaction terms suggest a consistent finding across Tables 5-10 and Tables 11-13: reputation decreases the tenure sensitivity of CEO pay. More specifically, one more media mention, depending on the choice of performance measure, decreases the sensitivity by around 0.05%.

Table 8. CEO performance, pay, tenure and reputation – Good Press (1 year)

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)
Tenure	0.0790* (2.44)	0.0716* (2.30)	0.0791* (2.44)
Tenure ²	-0.00246** (-2.81)	-0.00234** (-2.70)	-0.00245** (-2.80)
ROA	1.972* (2.43)		
ROE		0.321* (2.07)	
NIA			1.801* (2.31)
Good Press (1 year)	0.0119* (2.44)	0.0116* (1.86)	0.0114* (2.25)
Good Press (1 year)*Tenure	-0.00153* (-2.18)	-0.00142* (-2.01)	-0.00149* (-2.08)
Good Press (1 year)*Tenure ²	0.0000397 (1.76)	0.0000366 (1.74)	0.0000385 (1.67)
Good Press (1 year)*ROA	0.00369 (0.13)		
Good Press (1 year)*ROE		0.00664 (0.55)	
Good Press (1 year)*NIA			0.00583 (0.21)
Size	0.280*** (3.77)	0.270*** (3.91)	0.286*** (3.85)
Age	-0.00991 (-0.53)	0.0000745 (0.00)	-0.0103 (-0.56)
Share Own.	0.973* (2.49)	0.970** (2.71)	0.970* (2.49)
Divyield	0.444 (0.82)	0.773 (1.71)	0.449 (0.83)
No. of Obs.	524	513	524
No. of CEOs	125	123	125
R ²	21.0%	19.3%	21.4%

Note: This table reports panel regression of CEO pay levels (log of annual compensation) on various variables where CEO-firm fixed effects is used. Model 1 employs Return on Assets (ROA) as a performance measure. Models 2 and 3 uses Return on Equity (ROE) and the ratio of Net Income to the book value of assets (NIA) respectively. Reputation is proxied by Good Press(1 year), which counts the number of articles where CEO's name appears during 1 year prior to the current fiscal year. Size is proxied by natural log of Net Sales. Divyield is the firm's dividend yield. Share Ownership is a dummy which takes value 1 if the CEO's ownership of total shares is greater than 5%. Board Member is a dummy variable which is equal to one if the CEO served as a board member during the fiscal year. All specifications include year dummies. In parentheses, we present robust standard errors clustered by CEO. Level of significance are denoted by ***, **, and * for statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

The impact of reputation, however, decreases when measured over a longer term. In Table 9, when measured over 3 years, sensitivity of pay to reputation is around 0.08%: as the median CEO receives one more positive media mention, the total pay increases by 0.48% on average (by 0.38% if number of total mentions is used in Table 12). Moreover, the medium-term measure does not play a significant role on tenure elasticity of pay as we consider the results in Tables 5 and 12 and run F-tests for joint significance of this proxy measure and tenure variables.⁽⁶⁾

Similarly, we find that if reputation is measured over 5 years, results are insignificant both for tenure-pay relationship and tenure-elasticity of pay (see Table 9).

Table 9. CEO performance, pay, tenure and reputation – Good Press (3 & 5 years)

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)
Tenure	0.0609 (1.44)	0.0444 (1.12)	0.0611 (1.44)	0.0623 (1.09)	0.0424 (0.8)	0.0616 (1.08)
Tenure ²	-0.00207* (-2.00)	-0.00178 (-1.76)	-0.00207* (-2.00)	-0.00221 (-1.76)	-0.0019 (-1.59)	-0.00218 (-1.74)
ROA	1.874* (-2.17)			1.688 (-1.3)		
ROE		0.261 (-1.79)			1.487* (-2.24)	
NIA			1.724* (-2.09)			1.554 (-1.22)
Good Press (3 year)	0.00462* (-2.13)	0.00402* (-2.15)	0.00439* (-2.04)			
Good Press (3 year)*Tenure	-0.000556* (-2.05)	-0.000488* (-2.01)	-0.000538* (-2.06)			
Good Press (3 year)*Tenure ²	0.0000143 (-1.87)	0.0000127 (-1.8)	0.0000138 (-1.74)			
Good Press (3 year)*ROA	0.00268 (-0.45)					
Good Press (3 year)*ROE		0.0022 -0.87				
Good Press (3 year)*NIA			0.00382 -0.64			
Good Press (5 year)				0.00157 (-0.88)	0.00217 (-1.17)	0.00143 (-0.77)
Good Press (5 year)*Tenure				-0.000224 (-1.13)	-0.00026 (-1.29)	-0.000212 (-1.02)
Good Press (5 year)*Tenure ²				0.00000628 (-1.13)	0.00000749 (-1.38)	0.0000058 (-1)
Good Press (5 year)*ROA				-0.000138 (-0.03)		
Good Press (5 year)*ROE					-0.00193 (-1.02)	
Good Press (5 year)*NIA						0.00117 (-0.24)
Size	0.265** (-2.95)	0.247** (-3.04)	0.271** (-3.02)	0.308** (-2.74)	0.262* (2.43)	0.308** (-2.74)
Age	-0.00716 (-0.30)	0.00685 -0.34	-0.00742 (-0.31)	0.00401 (-0.15)	0.0169 (-0.7)	0.004 (-0.15)
Share Own.	0.930* (-2.38)	0.936** (-2.67)	0.929* (-2.38)	0.947* (-2.59)	0.912* (-2.61)	0.949* (-2.6)
Divyield	0.581 (-0.9)	1.075* (-2.06)	0.597 (-0.92)	0.715 (-0.98)	1.293 (-1.95)	0.715 (-0.97)
No. of Obs.	405	400	405	306	305	306
No. of CEOs	108	106	108	81	80	80
R ²	20.40%	18.90%	20.20%	19.60%	22.10%	19.60%

Note: This table reports panel regression of CEO pay levels (log of annual compensation) on various variables where CEO-firm fixed effects is used. Model 1 employs Return on Assets (ROA) as a performance measure.

Models 2 and 3 uses Return on Equity (ROE) and the ratio of Net Income to the book value of assets (NIA) respectively. Reputation is proxied by Good Press(3 years) (or Good Press (5years), depending on the specification) which counts the number of articles where CEO's name appears during 3 years (5 years) prior to the current fiscal year. Size is proxied by natural log of Net Sales. Divyield is the firm's dividend yield. Share Ownership is a dummy which takes value 1 if the CEO's ownership of total shares is greater than 5%. Board Member is a dummy variable which is equal to one if the CEO served as a board member during the fiscal year. All specifications include year dummies. In parantheses, we present robust standard errors clustered by CEO. Level of significance are denoted by ***, **, and * for statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

Table 10. CEO performance, pay, tenure and reputation – Press (1 year)

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)
Tenure	0.0775* (2.42)	0.0703* (2.28)	0.0774* (2.41)
Tenure ²	-0.00243** (-2.80)	-0.00231** (-2.69)	-0.00241** (-2.79)
ROA	1.988* (2.49)		
ROE		0.327* (2.12)	
NIA			1.837* (2.37)
Press (1 year)	0.00830* (2.34)	0.00742* (2.15)	0.00792* (2.11)
Press (1 year)*Tenure	-0.00111* (-2.12)	-0.00105 (-1.92)	-0.00108* (-1.99)
Press (1 year)*Tenure ²	0.0000292 (1.69)	0.0000275 (1.67)	0.0000284 (1.58)
Press (1 year)*ROA	0.00260 (0.12)		
Press (1 year)*ROE		0.00490 (0.53)	
Press (1 year)*NIA			0.00381 (0.17)
Size	0.286*** (3.84)	0.274*** (3.99)	0.291*** (3.93)
Age	-0.0103 (-0.55)	-0.000128 (-0.01)	-0.0106 (-0.57)
Share Own.	0.985* (2.53)	0.981** (2.75)	0.980* (2.52)
Divyield	0.456 (0.84)	0.785 (1.74)	0.460 (0.84)
Number of Obs.	524	513	524
Number of CEOs	125	123	125
R ²	21%	19%	21%

Note: This table reports panel regression of CEO pay levels (log of annual compensation) on various variables where CEO-firm fixed effects is used. Model 1 employs Return on Assets (ROA) as a performance measure. Models 2 and 3 uses Return on Equity (ROE) and the ratio of Net Income to the book value of assets (NIA) respectively. Reputation is proxied by Press (1 year), which counts the number of articles where CEO's name appears during 1 years prior to the current fiscal year. Size is proxied by natural log of Net Sales. Divyield is the firm's dividend yield. Share Ownership is a dummy which takes value 1 if the CEO's ownership of total shares is greater than 5%. Board Member is a dummy variable which is equal to one if the CEO served as a board member during the fiscal year. All specifications include year dummies. In parentheses, we present robust standard errors clustered by CEO. Level of significance are denoted by ***, **, and * for statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

Table 11. CEO performance, pay, tenure and reputation – Press (3&5 years)

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)
Tenure	0.061 (-1.44)	0.0449 (-1.13)	0.0612 (-1.45)	0.0616 (-1.09)	0.0422 (-0.8)	0.0609 (-1.08)
Tenure ²	-0.00207* (-2.02)	-0.00179 (-1.78)	-0.00207* (-2.01)	-0.0022 (-1.77)	-0.0019 (-1.60)	-0.00217 (-1.75)
ROA	1.913* (-2.19)			1.736 (-1.33)		
ROE		0.272 (-1.84)			1.517* (-2.27)	
NIA			1.775* (-2.12)			1.618 (-1.26)
Press (3 years)	0.00367* (-2.05)	0.00332* (-2.16)	0.00351* (-2.08)			
Press (3 years)*Tenure	-0.000448* (-2.07)	-0.000406* (-2.50)	-0.000436* (-2.32)			
Press (3 years)*Tenure ²	0.0000117 (-1.97)	0.0000106 (-1.91)	0.0000113 (-1.84)			
Press (3 years)*ROA	0.00167 (-0.36)					
Press (3 years)*ROE		0.00146 (-0.73)				
Press (3 years)*NIA			0.00247 (-0.52)			
Press (5 years)				0.00122 (-0.91)	0.0018 (-1.28)	0.00112 (-0.8)
Press (5 years)*Tenure				-0.000178 (-1.18)	-0.000217 (-1.42)	-0.000169 (-1.07)
Press (5 years)*Tenure ²				0.00000512 (-1.2)	0.00000634 (-1.53)	0.00000476 (-1.06)
Press (5 years)*ROA				-0.00058 (-0.16)		
Press (5 years)*ROE					-0.00183 (-1.22)	
Press (5 years)*NIA						0.000328 (-0.08)
Size	0.267** (-2.96)	0.249** (-3.06)	0.272** (-3.03)	0.311** (-2.76)	0.264* (-2.46)	0.311** (-2.76)
Age	-0.00742 (-0.31)	0.0067 (-0.33)	-0.00766 (-0.32)	0.00393 (-0.15)	0.0169 (-0.7)	0.00391 (-0.15)
Share Own.	0.924* (-2.38)	0.926** (-2.67)	0.922* (-2.38)	0.935* (-2.57)	0.898* (-2.59)	0.937* (-2.58)
Divyield	-0.577 (-0.89)	1.074* (-2.05)	0.592 (-0.91)	0.72 (-0.98)	1.302 (-1.96)	0.721 (-0.98)
Number of Obs.	405	400	405	306	305	306
Number of CEOs	108	106	108	81	80	80
R ²	20%	19%	20%	19%	22%	19%

Note: This table reports panel regression of CEO pay levels (log of annual compensation) on various variables where CEO-firm fixed effects is used. Model 1 employs Return on Assets (ROA) as a performance measure. Models 2 and 3 uses Return on Equity (ROE) and the ratio of Net Income to the book value of assets (NIA) respectively. Reputation is proxied by Press (3 or 5 year), which counts the number of articles where CEO's name appears during 3 or 5 years prior to the current fiscal year. All specifications include year dummies. In parentheses, we present robust standard errors clustered by CEO. Level of significance are denoted by ***, **, and * for statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

Table 12. CEO performance, pay, tenure and ability (Age-at-promotion)

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Tenure	-0.0433 (-1.02)	-0.0506 (-1.19)	-0.0430 (-1.01)
Tenure ²	0.000399 (0.26)	0.000555 (0.36)	0.000390 (0.25)
Age-at-promotion	-0.00171 (-0.29)	-0.00348 (-0.61)	-0.00167 (-0.28)
Age-at-promotion*Tenure	0.00143 (1.54)	0.00157 (1.69)	0.00143 (1.53)
Age-at-promotion*Tenure ²	-0.0000202 (-0.49)	-0.0000234 (-0.57)	-0.0000200 (-0.49)
ROA	0.224 (0.85)		
ROE		0.00129*** (6.06)	
NIA			0.305 (1.12)
Size	0.439*** (24.67)	0.443*** (25.21)	0.439*** (24.67)
Share Ownership	-0.464** (-2.63)	-0.450* (-2.53)	-0.465** (-2.63)
Dividend Yield	0.272* (2.37)	0.297** (2.66)	0.277* (2.40)
Number of Obs.	5977	5977	5977
Number of CEOs	1569	1569	1596
R ²	32.6	32.7	32.1

Note: This table reports estimates from panel OLS regression of CEO pay levels (log of annual compensation) on various variables by replicating the analysis of pay as presented in Tables 8-11, but ability is this time proxied by the CEO's age at the time of promotion. In parenthesis, we present robust standard errors clustered by CEO. Level of significance are denoted by ***, **, and * for statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

Our last empirical proxy, Age-at-promotion, is used for insider CEOs but it is a time-invariant variable; therefore OLS is appropriate to evaluate the effect of this fixed CEO characteristic. In Table 12 we find no significant impact of ability on pay or tenure-elasticity of pay. But we will see that Age-at-promotion performs well in the analysis of forced turnover.

3. Analysis II: Relations of CEO forced turnover with tenure and managerial ability

3.1. CEO forced turnover and tenure

Our primary interest in this section is to explore how the likelihood of performance-related turnover changes through a CEO's tenure and test the hypotheses as discussed in the Introduction. In Figure 3, we observe that frequency of forced turnover significantly increases in the first 7 years of tenure. However, after that, it decreases.

Figure 3. Incidence of forced CEO turnover

3.1.1. Empirical strategy

I employ a Cox semi parametric proportional hazard model although previous literature has extensively used logistic models (e.g. Falato et al., 2015 and Subramaniyan et al., 2002). However, given the right-censored nature of forced turnover data, logistic regressions might lead to inconsistent results. One advantage of the Cox model is that it provides the probability of forced turnover at a given point in time conditional on the fact that CEO has survived up to this point. Moreover, it is semi-parametric and makes no assumption about the nature of the survival distribution.

The hazard function represents the probability of employment termination conditional on the duration lasting up to time t and takes the following form:

$$\lambda(t|X(t)) = \lambda_0(t)e^{\beta'X(t)} \quad (3)$$

where the X vector includes CEO and firm controls, CEO age, firm size and performance and several other controls for corporate governance. The baseline hazard rate, $\lambda_0(t)$, is a function of time only and it does not depend on the covariates. To estimate β , Cox model uses a semi-parametric technique: the likelihood function is the sum of the probabilities that a CEO-firm relationship is forced to end at a particular time, given that one such event has occurred at time t .

3.1.2. Results

We start with a baseline specification using limited number of controls to estimate equation (3). The failure event is defined as the incident of forced turnover taking value 1 if there is forced turnover, and zero otherwise. Hazard rate is treated as a dependent variable. Therefore, a positive (negative) coefficient implies a positive (negative) marginal impact on the hazard: the covariate induces a shorter (longer) expected time as the CEO. Furthermore, the impact of a unit increase in a covariate over the hazard rate is simply calculated by $e^{\hat{\beta}}$, where $\hat{\beta}$ is the Cox estimated coefficient of the covariate.

In Table 13, the results are obtained by using NIA as a performance variable (including ROE and ROA produce qualitatively similar results). For each model in Table 13, the first

specification includes performance measures only; second and third specification includes controls, and controls with interaction terms, respectively. The other controls are firm size, CEO age and industry performance. In all specifications, standard errors are clustered at CEO level and they are adjusted taking into account that multiple error terms can be attributed to each CEO.

Table 13. CEO performance and forced turnover

Variable	Model 1			Model 2		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)
Firm Perf.	-0.67*** (-3.71)	-0.845*** (-4.11)	3.169 (0.63)			
Size		0.232** (2.93)	0.268*** (3.47)		0.228** (2.91)	0.272*** (3.37)
Age		-0.034*** (-3.37)	-0.034*** (-3.37)		-0.034*** (-3.38)	-0.036*** (-3.41)
Size*Firm Perf.			-0.812* (-2.30)			
Age*Firm Perf.			0.0088 (0.16)			
Adj. Firm Perf.				-0.69*** (-3.83)	-0.854*** (-4.16)	4.505 (1.02)
Industry Perf.				0.294 (1.10)	0.637* (2.35)	6.556 (1.38)
Size*Adj. Firm Perf.						-0.926 (-1.57)
Age*Adj. Firm Perf.						-0.0002 (-0.23)
Size*Ind. Perf.						-1.103 (-1.78)
Number of Obs.	4269	4226	4226	4269	4226	4226
Number of CEOs.	934	915	915	934	915	915
Log Pseudolikelihood	-1162.4	-1039.2	-1038.1	-1161.7	-1039.1	-1037.7

Note: This table presents the estimates from Cox Proportional Hazard Model where hazard rate is the dependent variable. Failure event is defined as performance related departure. Firm performance is measured by Return on Assets (ROA) in Model 1 and in Model 2 by industry-adjusted ROA and 2-digit SIC industry ROA as a measure of industry performance. Robust-clustered (within industry) standard errors are reported in parenthesis. Level of significance are denoted by ***, **, and * for statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%.

The results suggest that firm performance, whether adjusted or not, has a negative coefficient: as performance increases, the hazard of forced turnover decreases. The sizes of the predicted coefficients also imply that this effect is economically significant. Age and firm size consistently have opposite effects on the hazard ratio. Holding everything else constant, older CEOs are exposed to a lower hazard of forced turnover. However, the hazard increases as the firm size increases. Intuitively, larger firms attract a greater pool of executives; hence, it is much easier to replace a poorly performing CEO. Firm size is also significant when interacts with firm performance: size increases the sensitivity of hazard of forced turnover to firm performance. Finally, industry performance is only marginally significant. To increase robustness, we add several controls capturing CEO's power on corporate governance. In Table 14, observe that the results do not drastically change and note that the hazard rate of forced turnover is inversely related with both measures of this variable. Now, we illustrate the estimated survival probability using the regression results in Table 14.⁽⁷⁾

Table 14. CEO performance and forced turnover – More controls

Variable	Model 1		Model 2	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
Outsider	-0.247* (-2.41)	-0.243* (-2.37)	-0.244* (-2.35)	-0.250* (-2.41)
Firm Performance	-0.254*** (-5.12)	-0.716* (-2.10)		
Size	0.0180* (1.99)	0.0180* (1.99)	0.0175* (2.94)	0.0170
Age	-0.00379** (-3.26)	-0.00382*** (-3.30)	-0.00380** (-3.27)	-0.00377*** (-3.31)
Share Ownership	-13.82*** (-34.05)	-12.43*** (-32.11)	-12.90*** (-32.73)	-13.02*** (-32.91)
Board Member	-0.254*** (-3.40)	-0.260*** (-3.70)	-0.253*** (-3.39)	-0.157 (-1.05)
Board Member*Firm Perf.		0.00474 (1.42)		
Adjusted Firm Performance			-0.258*** (-5.01)	-0.655 (-1.39)
Industry Performance			0.200*** (3.57)	2.437 (0.86)
Board Member*Adj. Firm Perf.				0.396 (0.86)
Board Mbr.*Industry Perf.				-2.639 (0.86)
Number of Obs.	4226	4226	4226	4226
Number of CEOs.	915	915	915	915
Log Pseudolikelihood	-1022	-1021.9	-1021.5	-1020.7

Note: This table presents the estimates from Cox Proportional Hazard Model where hazard rate is the dependent variable. Failure event is defined as the performance related departure. Sample period covers 1998-2008. In Model 1, firm performance is measured by Return on Assets (ROA). Model 2 uses industry-adjusted ROA and 2-digit SIC industry ROA as a measure of industry performance. Size is proxied by natural log of Net Sales. Outsider is a dummy which takes value 1 if the CEO is an external hire, 0 otherwise. Share Ownership is a dummy which takes the value 1 if the CEO's ownership is higher than 5% of the total shares of the firm; and 0 otherwise. Board Member is a dummy if the CEO served as a board director for the fiscal year. Robust clustered (within industry) standard errors are reported in parenthesis. Level of significance are denoted by ***, **, and * for statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

In Figures 4b and 4c we investigate how probability of survival varies across different performance groups. Observe that for the lowest performer CEOs survival probability gets very close to zero over tenure. This contradicts with the entrenchment theory which suggests that senior CEOs are more entrenched and hence would be more likely to be retained after poor performance.

Finally, we focus on how the hazard rate changes over time and whether its performance sensitivity follows a particular time pattern. In Figure 5, hazard rate increases during approximately 17 years of tenure. The performance sensitivity increases over time as the two hazard functions get further apart through tenure. Since Cox proportional hazard estimation limits the analysis of hazard rate in relation to tenure at a qualitative level, I employ logit regression as a robustness check. Table 15 reports the results (the coefficients reported as marginal effects). Observe that the interaction terms are significant and negative: the performance sensitivity of dismissal probability increases over time, supporting the predictions of career concerns model and Olcay (2016).

Figure 4. [a] Tenure and Likelihood of Forced CEO Turnover; [b] Tenure and Likelihood of Forced CEO Turnover (Top 25% vs. Bottom 25% Performance); [c] Tenure and Likelihood of Forced CEO Turnover (At Top 5%, Top 25%, Bottom 25% and Bottom 5% Performance)

Figure 5. Incidence of Forced CEO Turnover – Top 25% vs. Bottom 25%

Table 15. CEO Performance and Forced Turnover – Logit

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Tenure	-0.0006 (0.010)	-0.0007 (0.011)	0.0037 (0.012)	0.0042 (0.012)	0.0050 (.0127)
Adj. Firm Perf.		-0.0285*** (0.004)	-0.0165 * (0.006)	-0.0162** (0.007)	-0.0158** (0.007)
Industry Perf.		0.0255*** (0.004)	0.0236*** (0.006)	0.0250*** (0.004)	0.0253 (0.0047)
Tenure*Adj.Firm Perf			-0.0016 (0.0006)**	-0.0017** (0.0007)	-0.0018** (0.0008)
Age				0.0032 (0.011)	0.0019 (0.011)
Size				0.0759 (0.074)	0.0643 (0.074)
Board Member				0.1350 (0.554)	-0.4982 (0.728)
Outsider				-0.0474 (0.087)	-0.0507 (0.088)
Board Mbr.*Adj.Firm Perf.					0.0766* (0.044)
Board Mbr.*Ind.Perf.					0.1095 (0.078)
Number of CEOs	912	912	912	912	912
Number of Observations	4309	4309	4309	4309	4309
Log pseudolikelihood	-779.8	-720.6	-709.9	-673.6	-671.6

Note: This table presents the estimates from Logit regression. Dependent variable takes value 1 if the CEO is dismissed due to poor performance, 0 otherwise. Sample period covers 1998-2008. Firm performance is measured by Return on Equity (ROA). Size is proxied by natural log of Net Sales. Outsider is a dummy which takes value 1 if the CEO is an external hire, 0 otherwise. Share Ownership is a dummy which takes the value 1 if the CEO's ownership is higher than 5% of the total shares of the firm; and 0 otherwise. Board Member is a dummy if the CEO served as a board director for the fiscal year. Robust clustered (within industry) standard errors are reported in parentheses. Level of significance are denoted by ***, **, and * for statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

3.2. The impact of ability on forced turnover and tenure-forced turnover relationship

The theories discussed consistently predict that a CEO of higher ability will be less likely to be forced out. However, they differ regarding what they assume about the information on ability. Learning and career concerns models assume imperfect information of the board where true ability is unknown but the belief on ability is updated each time, yet Olcay (2016) assumes no such informational problem.

Before the analysis, in Figure 5 we compare the forced turnover rates of the top and bottom quartiles of the sample population. Observe that the top quartile (CEOs with higher media visibility) experiences a higher forced turnover rate as compared to the bottom quartile regardless of the type of empirical proxy employed. However, the top quartile shows significant variation. For example, when we use Good Press (1year), among the first top 5% of the sample population, the forced turnover rate is 30%. But for the second top 5% and the third top 5% of the sample population, the rates are 37% and 39%, respectively.

3.2.1. Empirical strategy and results

To estimate equation (3) while including ability as an additional covariate, I employ two set of regressions: one with the subsample of outsider CEOs (using the press variable as a proxy for reputation) and second with the subsample of insider CEOs (using Age-at-promotion).

The results for the outsider CEOs are in Tables 16 and 17. All standard errors are clustered at the CEO level.⁽⁸⁾ The results suggest a significant impact for media visibility as a proxy for reputational aspects of managerial ability: higher media visibility implies lower estimated hazard of forced turnover. However, coefficients of Press variables in Table 17 are notably lower than their counterparts in Table 16. Not surprisingly, Good Press, which includes only positive reputation, decreases the hazard rate more than Press of whose small fraction accounts for negative reputation. However, there is a common result: the impact of reputation gets weaker as it is measured over longer terms; i.e., the short-term measure has the strongest effect on the likelihood of forced turnover.

Table 16. CEO performance, forced turnover and reputation – Good Press

Variables	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
Adj. Firm Perf.	-0.214* (-2.24)	-0.0809 (-0.45)	-0.224* (-2.41)	-0.0451 (-0.23)	-0.207 (-1.96)	-0.118 (-0.68)
Industry Perf.	-0.487 (-1.43)	-0.439 (-1.12)	-0.489 (-1.45)	-0.418 (-1.01)	-0.193 (-0.88)	-0.184 (-0.67)
Good Press(1y.)	-.0006*** (-3.85)	-0.0002 (-0.57)				
Good Press(1y.)*						
Adj. Firm Perf.		-0.00541 (-1.17)				
Good Press(1y.)*						
Ind. Perf.		-0.00423 (-0.75)				
Good Press(3y.)			-.00019** (-3.64)	-0.00006 (-0.53)		
Good Press(3y.)*						
Adj. Firm Perf.				-0.00147 (-1.32)		
Good Press(3y.)*						
Ind. Perf.				-0.0008 (-0.63)		
Good Press(5y.)					-0.00010* (-2.25)	-0.00007 (-1.08)
Good Press(5y.)*						
Adj. Firm Perf.						-0.00006 (-1.03)
Good Press(5y.)*						
Ind. Perf.						-0.0004 (-0.64)
Age	-0.00394* (-2.28)	-0.0039* (-2.26)	-0.0038* (-2.28)	-0.0038* (-2.16)	-0.0042* (-2.31)	-0.0043* (-2.30)
Firm Size	0.0454 (1.92)	0.0449 (1.76)	0.0444 (1.86)	0.0434 (1.70)	0.0346 (1.56)	0.0339 (1.45)
Share Ownership	-2.550*** (-17.82)	-3.787 (.)	-3.822 (.)	-3.821 (.)	-3.839 (.)	-3.841 (.)
Board Member	-0.46*** (-7.02)	-0.43*** (-7.21)	-0.46*** (-7.16)	-0.44*** (-7.68)	-0.46*** (-8.30)	-0.45*** (-7.74)
Number of Obs.	559	559	490	490	372	372
Pseudo Log.	-101.68	-101.23	-101.91	-101.28	-80.64	-80.39

Note: This table presents the estimates from Cox Proportional Hazard Model where hazard rate is the dependent variable. Failure event is defined as the performance related departure. Sample period covers 1998-2008. Firm performance is measured by Return on Equity (ROA). Size is proxied by natural log of Net Sales. Outsider is a dummy which takes value 1 if the CEO is an external hire, 0 otherwise. Share Ownership is a dummy which takes the value 1 if the CEO's ownership is higher than 5% of the total shares of the firm; and 0 otherwise. Board Member is a dummy if the CEO served as a board director for the fiscal year. Press1, Press 3 and Press 5 count the number of articles in which CEO's names appeared during the last 1 year, 3 years, and 5 years prior to the fiscal year. The number only includes articles with positive or neutral connotations. Robust clustered (at the CEO level) standard errors are reported in parentheses. Level of significance are denoted by ***, **, and * for statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

Table 17. CEO performance, forced turnover and reputation – Press

Variables	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
Adj. Firm Perf.	-0.211* (-2.23)	-0.0926 (-0.55)	-0.223* (-2.41)	-0.0496 (-0.26)	-0.207 (-1.94)	-0.123 (-0.72)
Industry Perf.	-0.488 (-1.44)	-0.457 (-1.17)	-0.489 (-1.45)	-0.421 (-1.02)	-0.195 (-0.88)	-0.187 (-0.69)
Press(1y.)	-0.0005*** (-4.40)	-0.0001 (-0.60)				
Press(1y.)*						
Adj. Firm Perf.		-0.0044 (-1.18)				
Press(1y.)*						
Ind. Perf.		-0.003 (-0.75)				
Press(3y.)			-0.0001*** (-4.24)	-0.00005 (-0.59)		
Press(3y.)*						
Adj. Firm Perf.				-0.0012 (-1.27)		
Press(3y.)*						
Ind. Perf.				-0.0007 (-0.64)		
Press(5y.)					-0.00009* (-2.30)	-0.00006 (-1.24)
Press(5y.)*						
Adj. Firm Perf.						-0.00005 (-0.98)
Press(5y.)*						
Ind. Perf.						-0.00035 (-0.62)
Age	-0.0039* (-2.31)	-0.004* (-2.32)	-0.0038* (-2.29)	-0.0038* (-2.18)	-0.0042* (-2.33)	-0.0043* (-2.32)
Firm Size	0.0460 (1.93)	0.0456 (1.78)	0.0448 (1.86)	0.0440 (1.72)	0.0353 (1.58)	0.0349 (1.49)
Share Own.	-2.502*** (-17.53)	-2.435*** (-17.45)	-3.822 (.)	-3.822 (.)	-3.840 (.)	-3.841 (.)
Board Mbr.	-0.46*** (-7.07)	-0.43*** (-7.09)	-0.47*** (-7.34)	-0.44*** (-7.65)	-0.47*** (-8.41)	-0.46*** (-7.64)
Number of Obs.	559	559	490	490	372	372
Pseudo Log	-101.61	-101.18	-101.85	-101.25	-80.55	-80.27

Note: This table presents the estimates from Cox Proportional Hazard Model where hazard rate is the dependent variable. Failure event is defined as the performance related departure. Sample period covers 1998-2008. Firm performance is measured by Return on Equity (ROA). Size is proxied by natural log of Net Sales. Outsider is a dummy which takes value 1 if the CEO is an external hire, 0 otherwise. Share Ownership is a dummy which takes the value 1 if the CEO's ownership is higher than 5% of the total shares of the firm; and 0 otherwise. Board Member is a dummy if the CEO served as a board director for the fiscal year. Press1, Press 3 and Press 5 count the number of articles in which CEO's names appeared during the last 1 year, 3 years, and 5 years prior to the fiscal year. Robust clustered (at the CEO level) standard errors are reported in parentheses. Level of significance are denoted by ***, **, and * for statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

Finally, we employ Age-at-promotion. Note that higher values signal lower ability. Therefore, the results in Table 18 suggest that there is a significant and inverse relationship between ability and dismissal probability, reinforcing our results with reputation. Note that these results support the predictions of the previously discussed theoretical models. However, we find no significant impact of ability regarding the performance sensitivity of this incentive tool.

Table 18. CEO performance, forced turnover and ability (Age-at-promotion)

Variables	Model 1		Model 2	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
Age-at-promotion	0.0213* (2.19)	0.0314* (1.97)	0.0196* (2.08)	0.0266* (2.12)
Adjusted Firm Perf.			-0.00106* (-2.32)	-0.613 (0.95)
Firm Perf.	-0.199 (-0.93)	0.707 (0.74)		
Industry Perf.			-0.187 (-0.85)	
Age-at-promotion*Adj. Firm Perf.				-0.0178 (-1.35)
Age-at-promotion*Firm Perf.		-0.0198 (-0.92)		
Age-at-promotion*Adj. Firm Perf.				-0.0223 (-0.55)
Size	0.00890 (0.76)	0.00889 (0.75)	0.0102 (0.84)	0.00891 (0.74)
Share Ownership	-14.36 (.)	-9.323*** (-26.96)	-9.770*** (-28.19)	-10.19*** (-28.75)
Board Member	0.438 (.)	-0.296 (-1.40)	-2.699 (.)	0.695 (.)
Number of Obs.	1565	1565	1565	1565
Number of CEOs	364	364	364	364
Log-pseudo likelihood	-182.76	-182.6	-182.64	-182.38

Note: This table presents the estimates from Cox Proportional Hazard Model where hazard rate is the dependent variable. Failure event is defined as the performance related departure. Sample period covers 1998-2008 and internally-hired CEOs. In Model 1, firm performance is measured by Return on Assets (ROA). Model 2 uses industry-adjusted ROA and 2-digit SIC industry ROA as a measure of industry performance. Size is proxied by natural log of Net Sales. Share Ownership is a dummy which takes the value 1 if the CEO's ownership is higher than 5% of the total shares of the firm; and 0 otherwise. Board Member is a dummy if the CEO served as a board director for the fiscal year. Ability is proxied by the age of CEO at the time of promotion. Robust clustered (at the CEO level) standard errors are reported in parentheses. Level of significance are denoted by ***, **, and * for statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

4. Concluding comments

Both total pay and threat of dismissal are common tools to provide incentives for top executives. I study the impact of tenure, managerial ability and their interactions on the use of these incentive tools. I examine the predictions of several theories (namely, Murphy (1986), Gibbons and Murphy (1992), Hermalin and Weisbach (1998) and Olcay (2016)) to test the significance of these variables on both CEO pay and likelihood of forced CEO turnover.

Using a sample of firms in S&P 1500, I find a positive relationship between tenure and total pay, in support of all the theories discussed. However, the results on survival probability over tenure rule out the entrenchment effects as suggested by Hermalin and Weisbach (1998). This result, together with the strong connection of performance with the two devices, could be interpreted in favour of the optimal contracting models (Murphy, 1986; Gibbons and Murphy, 1992, and Olcay, 2016): incentives matter and firms use both instruments more strongly as the CEO is more senior in her tenure.

In order to explore how executive contracts are associated with managerial ability, I use two different proxies. For outsider CEOs, a media visibility measure, aiming to capture

reputational aspects of ability, and for insiders, age at time of promotion are employed. In line with the theoretical predictions, I find that reputation increases pay, yet with stronger impacts for more current measures. Reputation also decreases dismissal probability, but again current measures have stronger impacts. For insiders, ability is found to reinforce the adverse impact on the dismissal probability. These findings support the theoretical literature on optimal contract design. Furthermore, I find evidence for the predictions of Gibbons and Murphy (1992) and Olcay (2016) that the dismissal probability becomes more sensitive to performance over tenure. Finally, to inspire future theoretical work on executive contract design, I examined ability for its potential impact on tenure sensitivity of the two incentive tools and found that only a short-term measure has a significant impact and it decreases the tenure sensitivity of pay.

Acknowledgements

I am thankful to Tomas Sjöström, Carolyn Moehling, Mark Killingsworth and the seminar participants at International Conference on Applied Economics, Istanbul, Türkiye. The financial support from Fritz Thyssen Foundation is gratefully acknowledged.

Notes

- (1) This is consistent with previous studies, 12.2% (Parrino, 1997), 9.3% (Denis et al., 1997).
- (2) In line with fixed effects assumption, all regressions in this section report a correlation between vector of controls and individual fixed-effects.
- (3) One could instead analyze the pay-performance sensitivities which requires to calculate both share and option sensitivity which necessitate calculation of the prices of outstanding options unreported in the annual statements. See Guay (2002) for a recent estimation technique to overcome this issue.
- (4) The use of single performance measure is as common as the use of multiple performance measures. Murphy (1998) documents that even when multiple measures are used, they are additive and can be treated like separate plans, e.g. 80% of the cash compensation is based on NIA and 20% is based on ROA, with a separate schedule relating cash compensation to each performance measure.
- (5) These could be contrasted with other studies which estimate pay-to-performance sensitivities using a change in share holder value as a performance variable. For example, Jensen and Murphy (1990), reports an estimated pay-to-performance sensitivity of 0.325 for a sample of Forbes executives.
- (6) Related p-values for F-test are 0.1719, 0.1897 and 0.1766 in Table 9 for model specifications 1, 2 and 3, respectively.
- (7) This is done using Model 2. Model 1 yields qualitatively similar results
- (8) Since firm performance, either adjusted or not, produces qualitatively similar results, I present only the estimation results with adjusted firm performance.

References

- Abowd, J.M., 1990. Does Performance-based Compensation Affect Corporate Performance?, *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*, 43(3), February, pp. 52S-73S.
- Aggarwal, R. and Samwick, A., 1999. The other side of the tradeoff: The impact of risk on executive compensation, *Journal of Political Economy*, 107, pp. 65-105.
- Aggarwal, R. and Samwick, A., 2003. Performance Incentives within Firms: The Effect of Managerial Responsibility, *Journal of Finance, American Finance Association*, 58(4), pp. 1613-1650, 08.
- Allgood, S. and Farrell, K.A., 2000. The Effect of CEO Tenure on the Relationship between Firm Performance and Turnover, *The Journal of Financial Research*, 23(3), p. 73.
- Antle, R. and Smith, A., 1986. An Empirical Investigation of the Relative Performance Evaluation of Corporate Executives. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 24(1), Spring, pp. 1-39.
- Banker, R., and Datar, S., 1989. Sensitivity, precision, and linear aggregation of signals for performance evaluation, *Journal of Accounting Research*, 27, pp. 21-39.
- Bebchuk, L. and Fried, J.M., 2004. *Pay without Performance: The Unfulfilled Promise of Executive Compensation*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, MA.
- Benjamin, E. and Weisbach, M.S., 1996. Endogenously Chosen Boards of Directors and Their Monitoring of the CEO, *American Economic Review*, 88(1), pp. 96-118.
- Chevalier, K. and Ellison R., 1999. Are Some Mutual Fund Managers Better Than Others? Cross- Sectional Patterns in Behavior and Performance, *Journal of Finance, American Finance Association*, 54(3), pp. 875-899, 06.
- Cichello, M., 2005. The impact of firm size on pay-performance sensitivities, *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 11(4), pp. 609-627.
- Core, J. and Guay, W., 2002. Estimating the Value of Employee Stock Option Portfolios and Their Sensitivities to Price and Volatility, *Journal of Accounting Research*, 40, pp. 613-630.
- Coughlan, A. and Schmidt, R., 1985. Executive compensation, management turnover, and firm performance: An empirical investigation, *Journal of Accounting and Economics* 7 (1-3), pp. 43-66.
- Cox, D.R., 1972. Regression Models and Life-Tables, *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)* 34 (2), pp. 187-220.
- Dahya, J., Lonie, A.A. and Power, D.M., 1998. Power, Ownership structure, firm performance and top executive change: An analysis of UK firms, *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 25 (9 & 10).
- Demerjian, P., Lev, B. and McVay, S., 2012. Quantifying Managerial Ability: A New Measure and Validity Tests, *Management Science*, 58(7).
- Denis, D.J., Denis, D.K. and Sarin, A., 1997. Ownership structure and top executive turnover, *Journal of Financial Economics*, 45, pp. 193-221.
- Falato, T.A., Li, D. and Milbourn, T., 2015. Which Skills Matter in the Market for CEOs? Evidence from Pay for CEO Credentials, *Management Science*, 61(12), pp. 2825-3096.
- Francis, J., Huang, A.H., Rajgopal, S. and Zhang, A.Y., 2008. *CEO reputation and reporting quality*, *Contemporary Accounting Research* 25(1), pp. 109-147.
- Gabaix, X. and Landier, A., 2008. Why has CEO pay increased so much?, *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 123, pp. 49-100.
- Goyal, V.K. and Park, C.W., 2002. Board leadership structure and CEO turnover, *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 8, pp. 49-66.

- Gibbons, R. and Murphy K., 1992. Optimal Incentive Contracts in the Presence of Career Concerns: Theory and Evidence, *Journal of Political Economy*, 100(3), pp. 468-505.
- Hadlock, Ch.J., Lumer, G.B., 1997. Compensation, turnover and top management incentives: Historical evidence, *Journal of Business* 70, pp. 153-187.
- Hayes, R. and Schaefer, S., 1999. How much are differences in managerial ability worth?, *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 27, pp. 125-148.
- Huson, M., Parrino, R. and Starks, L., 2001. *Internal monitoring mechanisms and CEO turnover: A long term perspective*, *Journal of Finance*, 56, pp. 2265-2297.
- Jensen, M. and Murphy, K.J., 1990. Performance pay and top management incentives, *Journal of Political Economy*, 98(2), pp. 225-264.
- Kaplan, S.N. and Minton, B.A., 2012. How has CEO turnover changed?, *International Review of Finance*, 12(1), pp. 57-87.
- Kostiuk, P., 1990. Firm Size and Executive Compensation, *Journal of Human Resources*, 25, pp. 90-105.
- Leonard, J., 1990. Executive pay and firm performance, *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*, 43.
- Milbourn, T., 2003. CEO Reputation and Stock Based Compensation, *Journal of Financial Economics*, 68, pp. 233-262.
- Murphy, K., 1986. Incentives, learning, and compensation: a theoretical and empirical investigation of managerial labor contracts, *Rand Journal of Economics*, 17(1), Spring.
- Murphy, K.J. and Zimmerman, J., 1993. *Financial performance surrounding CEO turnover*, *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 16, pp. 273-315.
- Nguyen, B.D., 2011. Ownership Structure and Board Characteristics as Determinants of CEO Turnover in French-Listed Companies, *Finance*, 32(2), pp. 53-89.
- Olcay, N.B., 2016. Dynamic incentive contracts with termination threats, *Review of Economic Design*, 20(4), pp. 255-288.
- Parrino, R., 1997. CEO turnover and outside succession: A cross-sectional analysis, *Journal of Financial Economics*, 46, pp. 165-197.
- Rajgopal, S., Shevlin, T. and Zamora, V., 2006. CEOs' Outside Employment Opportunities and the Lack of Relative Performance Evaluation in Compensation Contracts, *Journal of Finance*, LXI(4), August, pp. 1813-1844.
- Rosen, S., 1982. Authority, Control, and the Distribution of Earnings, *Bell Journal of Economics*, 13(2), Autumn, pp. 311-323, The RAND Corporation.
- Subramanian, N., Chakraborty, A., Seikh, S., 2002. *Performance Incentives, Performance Pressure and Turnover*, Finance 0210003, University Library of Munich, Germany, revised 24 Oct 2002.
- Tervio, M., 2007. Differences that CEOs Make: An Assignment Model Approach, *American Economic Review*, 98(3), pp. 642-668.
- Warner, J., Watts, R. and Wruck, K., 1988. Stock prices and top management changes, *Journal of Financial Economics*, 20, pp. 461-492.
- Weisbach, M., 1988. Outside directors and CEO turnover, *Journal of Financial Economics*, 20(1-2), pp. 461-560.

Appendix

Publications included in the search to construct the media visibility variables: Businessweek, Dow Jones News Service, Financial Times, Forbes, Fortune, International Herald Tribune, Los Angeles Times, The Economist, The New York Times, The Wall Street Journal, The Wall Street Journal Asia, The Wall Street Journal Europe, The Washington Post, USA Today.

Our Good Press proxy excludes from the total count articles containing the following keywords (taken from Falato, 2015): scandal or investigate* or (cut w/2 jobs) or resign* or (force* w/3 quit) or dismiss* or demote* or demotion or accuse* or criticism* or allegation* or indict* or arrest* or guilty or fraud or litigation or abrasive or excessive pay or overpaid or perquisites or (force* w/3 step down) or under scrutiny or under pressure or law suit or class action or in trouble.

Forecasting the Romanian inflation rate: An Autoregressive Integrated Moving-Average (ARIMA) approach

Rareş-Petru MIHALACHE

National Institute for Economic Research "Costin C. Kirilăescu", Romanian Academy, Romania
rares.mihalache9@gmail.com

Dumitru Alexandru BODISLAV

Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
alex.bodislav@ase.ro

Abstract. *The primary objectives of this paper are to empirically create an univariate Autoregressive Integrated Moving-Average (model) using Box-Jenkins methodology to forecast Romanian inflation and inspect the prediction performance of the estimated model between October 2021 and October 2022. This study uses Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique for estimation purposes. On the foundation of different selection assessment and diagnostic criteria, the best model is selected to predict inflation in Romania in the short-run. We find that ARIMA (7, 1, 1) model is a suitable one under model identification, parameters estimation, diagnostic checking, and inflation prediction. In-sample forecasting is performed and the estimated ARIMA model reasonably tracks the actual inflation in the sample period.*

Keywords: ARIMA, Box-Jenkins, inflation forecasting, time-series modelling, National Bank of Romania (NBR).

JEL Classification: C010, C51, C520, C530, E3.

1. Introduction

Inflation represents one of the most significant macroeconomic variables and the most worried by the economic agents, including the government, because it brings severe influence on the level of the welfare and on the architecture of the production costs. Some of the nations which experienced hyperinflation highlighted that poor inflation would yield to political and social instability (Yolanda, 2017).

Inflation is defined as an important macroeconomic imbalance manifested by a general growth in the price level over an interval of time, resulting in a constant decrease in the purchasing power of money. When there is a general rise in prices, each currency unit purchases fewer services and goods. As a result, inflation displays a decline in the purchasing power of the money (Csorba and Juravle, 2022). There are two main categories of inflation: demand pull inflation and cost push inflation. Demand pull inflation defines inflation where the root cause comes from the demand part. The constant growth in demand is determined by factors such as an increase in money supply, a growth in government purchase, increases in exports, etc. When demand is increased and it cannot be satisfied by a similar increase in supply, the general price level will raise and inflation will happen. On the other hand, cost push inflation, also called supply push inflation, happens due to a rise in the production cost. For instance, an increase of the raw materials price, a growth of wage rate, etc. The general price level of services and goods will increase when there is a rise of production costs within industries (Majumder, 2016).

Monetary authorities have a main task of achieving price stability. They do this by issuing various forms of money, fixing an array of interest rates, generating fiscal revenues, outlining the unit of account, and influencing marginal costs of production through credit regulations, among other policies (Castillo-Martinez and Reis, 2019).

The main goal of the National Bank of Romania (NBR) is to assure and maintain price stability, with monetary policy being employed under inflation targeting regime starting August 2005. In this situation, active communication of the central bank to the public at large represents an important role, and the crucial tool that the monetary authority utilizes to this end is the Inflation Report. Among other aspects, the Report highlights the National Bank of Romania's (NBR) quarterly inflation forecast over an eight-quarter period, comprising the related uncertainties and risks. Also, it provides an examination of recent and future macroeconomic context from a monetary policy decision's perspective.

Unanticipated events such as the Coronavirus pandemic or the war in Ukraine have dire consequences on the economy. Therefore, central banks should keep inflation close to the target, not only to meet its main objective, but also to ensure the optimal function of the economy. Our study aims at forecasting the Romanian inflation rate using the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA). Unlike other analyses which focus on forecasting the Consumer Price Index (CPI) through the ARIMA technique, this study comprises the actual values of the monthly inflation rate from 2018 to 2022. Furthermore, there are a few studies which consider the structural break issue and solve this in their analyses. To correct the structural break issue, we construct a dummy variable and include it in our econometric model.

2. Literature review

Inflation is considered as one of the barometer tools to examine the health of an economy. A rate of inflation which is too high will diminish the level of social welfare. Conversely, a low rate of inflation shows an economy that does not function maximally, with an impact on slowing economic growth, increased poverty, and stagnant job formation. Considering these, inflation represents a macroeconomic problem that central banks should carefully consider.

The main focus of monetary policy has generally been the maintenance of a low and stable inflation rate as defined by traditionally embraced measures, such as the Consumer Price Index (CPI). The fundamental justification for this goal is the extensive consensus, supported by various economic studies, which highlight that inflation is costly insofar since it weakens the real economic activity.

Inflation forecasting represents a key aspect that the central bank of a country should consider when implementing monetary policies. Also, this plays an important role within the Eurozone, since a significant departure from the inflation target of a country might affect the stability of the Eurosystem. Therefore, given the likelihood of continuous differences in inflation levels across euro area currencies and the consequent impact on competitiveness, examining and understanding price developments in individual countries will remain of substantial importance.

There are a number of techniques available for predicting economic time-series. However, this paper focuses on the ARIMA approach. The main findings of other authors using this method are presented below.

Okafor and Shaibu (2013) deploy an univariate Autoregressive Integrated Moving-Average (ARIMA) econometric model for the Nigerian inflation rate and examine the prediction performance of the forecasted model between 1981 and 2010. Based on different selection evaluation and diagnostic criteria, the best model is chosen for the short-run prediction of Nigerian inflation rate. They discover that ARIMA (2, 2, 3) is the optimal model to use for forecasting. They confirm that the predicted inflation equation clearly shows that expected inflation represents a significant determinant of actual inflation within the estimation period.

In order to estimate a time-series model, which encompasses monthly inflation data between January 1997 and August 2013, (Baciu, 2015) applies the Box-Jenkins methodology. The ARIMA (1, 1, 2) model is selected and the inflation rate prediction for September 2013 is made. The results of the study reveal that there is a significant difference between the actual inflation rate and the forecast made on the selected model. An ARIMA (1, 1, 2) model is also used to forecast inflation in Tanzania by using the Box-Jenkins ARRIMA approach and annual inflation data from 1966 to 2017. The results demonstrate that inflation rate in Tanzania is likely to follow an upward trend in the following decade. The study encourages policymakers to apply tight fiscal and monetary policy measures to handle inflation in Tanzania (Thabani, 2019a). A similar approach is followed to forecast inflation in the Philippines. In his analysis, (Thabani, 2019b) uses annual inflation data ranging from 1960 to 2017. He finds that an ARIMA (1, 1, 3) model is stable and acceptable for forecasting inflation level in the Philippines.

In an attempt to forecast the monthly inflation rate in Pakistan, (Salam et al., 2007) deploy different ARIMA models, and the candid one is proposed. Based on different diagnostic, selection and evaluation criteria, they select the best model for the short-term prediction. Also, Jafarian-Namin et al. (2021) focus on modelling and predicting the yearly inflation level in Iran from 1960 to 2019 using ARIMA models. Different models are examined and they find that non-seasonal ARIMA (1,0,0) is the right model to predict the inflation rate for the next years.

3. Theoretical framework, methodology, and data source

3.1. Basics of ARIMA

Autoregressive Integrated Moving-Average (ARIMA) modelling represents a particular subset of univariate modelling, in which a time-series data is defined in terms of previous values of itself (the autoregressive element) and current and lagged values of an error term called "white noise" (the moving-average element).

ARIMA methodology for predicting time-series data is essentially agnostic. Contrary to other methods, it does not consider any fundamental economic model or structural associations. It is considered that past values of the series and previous error terms include information for the objectives of forecasting. The major advantage of ARIMA prediction is that it requires data on the time-series under analysis only. Firstly, this characteristic is advantageous if predicting a significant number of time-series. Secondly, this avoids an issue that appears occasionally with multivariate models, for example, it might be possible that a consistent time-series is only available for a less period than the other series, limiting the period over which the econometric model is estimated. Thirdly, in multivariate modelling, data timeliness might be a problem.

Also, this method includes several disadvantages. For example, some of the classic model identification methods are subjective and the trustworthiness of the selected model might depend on the experience and skill of the researcher (even though this criticism regularly applies to other modelling techniques as well). Another disadvantage refers to the fact that it is not embedded within any elemental theoretical model or structural relationships and therefore, the economic significance of the chosen model is not clear. Additionally, ARIMA models are basically "backward looking" and as such, they are normally poor at forecasting turning points, unless the turning point is a return to long-term equilibrium. However, ARIMA models have demonstrated to be relatively powerful, especially when producing short-run inflation predictions (Kenny et al., 1980).

As highlighted by the authors Okafor and Shaibu (2013), the ARIMA modelling approach connects two different processes into one equation. The first characteristic defines an autoregressive process, while the second characteristic represents a moving-average. ARIMA modelling promotes an association between a particular time-series data and its own lagged values.

A p^{th} – order autoregressive expresses the dependent variable as a function of its past values, as in the following equation:

$$Y_t = \phi_0 + \phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \phi_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where Y_t represents the dependent variable predicted at time t ; $Y_{t-1}, Y_{t-2}, Y_{t-3}, \dots$ are the targets at time lags $t-1, t-2, \dots, t-p$; $\phi_0, \phi_1, \dots, \phi_p$ are the coefficients to be estimated; ε_t defines the error term at time t .

A q^{th} – order moving-average process defines a response variable, Y_t , as a function of the lagged values of the q error terms, as in the following equation:

$$Y_t = \mu + \varepsilon_t + \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \theta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} + \dots + \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} \quad (2)$$

Where Y_t represents the dependent variable predicted at time t ; μ displays the constant mean of the process; $\theta_0, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_q$ are the coefficients to be estimated; ε_t highlights the error term at time t ; $\varepsilon_{t-1}, \varepsilon_{t-2}, \dots, \varepsilon_{t-q}$ are the errors in the past period that are included in the response variable, Y_t .

To construct an ARIMA model, we start with an econometric equation, which contains no exogenous variables ($Y_t = \beta_t + \varepsilon_t$) and add to it both the autoregressive (AR) component and the moving-average (MA) component. Therefore, considering equations (1) and (2), the ARIMA (p, d, q) model takes the following form:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \phi_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t + \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \theta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} + \dots + \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} \quad (3)$$

Where the ϕ s and θ s represent the coefficients of the autoregressive and moving-average processes; d represents the order of integration of the series.

In the ARIMA modelling and forecasting technique, we consider the following steps:

1. The first step involves collecting and assessing graphically the data to be predicted. In this regard, an extensive time series data is asked for univariate time-series forecasting. It is generally recommended that at least 50 observations to be available. Using the Box-Jenkins approach can be problematic if few observations are included. Unfortunately, although a large time-series is available, it is probable that the series incorporates a structural break, which might imply analyzing a subset of the entire dataset, or otherwise using dummy variables. Furthermore, graphically exploring the data is important. Data should be examined in levels, logarithms, and differences. These steps might reveal if there is an important seasonal pattern in the series, or if any structural breaks, outliers or data errors happen. One approach to examine the characteristics of a time-series is to plot its correlogram. However, even if the correlogram offers some indication as to whether series is stationary or not, formal tests for stationarity with known statistical properties are more appropriate.
2. The second step refers to whether series is stationary or if differencing is required. Series under analysis must be stationary before identifying an appropriate ARIMA model. With this respect, Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is performed.
3. Once the data is concluded to be stationary, we seek to discover and estimate the optimal ARIMA model. Having identified the suitable order of differencing required to make the series stationary, the next step is to find the best form of ARIMA to model the stationary data. The traditional Box-Jenkins approach consists of a repetitive process of model identification, model estimation, as well as model evaluation. The Box-Jenkins

approach represents a quasi-formal method with model identification depending on the subjective assessment of correlograms and partial correlograms plots of the data.

4. The next step involves checking if the model is a good one by deploying tests on the parameters and residuals of the model. It examines the statistical properties of the estimated ARIMA model in observing the model adequacy.
5. The last step relates to the usage of the selected model. If the model does not violate the diagnostic tests' requirements, then it can be utilized for forecasting.

3.2. Methodology

The research technique for this study is modelled according to the Box-Jenkins methodology (Box and Jenkins, 1976), which is typically applied to short-term forecasting of time-series events. The ARIMA model deployed in this study is expressed in equation 3 from above, in the defined time-series characteristics identified as (p, d, q) , where p represents the order of the autoregressive (AR) component, d is the number of the differences applied on the series in order to become stationary, and q is the order of the moving-average (MA) component. This paper focuses on analyzing different ARIMA models based on monthly inflation data in Romania and use the most suitable one for prediction.

3.3. Data source

Data used in this analysis was collected from the YCharts database, encompassing a period between September 2018 and October 2022. This means that data contains 50 variables, which meets the requirement of univariate time-series modelling. EViews econometric software is used within the entire analysis.

4. Results and discussions

4.1. Visual examination of the series

The first phase in modelling time-series is to investigate the structure of the data in order to get some preliminary information regarding stationarity of the series. Before applying formal tests, the graphs of the time-series under analysis are plotted. These plots offer initial knowledge about the possible nature of the time series.

Figures show that there might be evidence of the presence of structural break in the series. Also, they highlight that building a model for the logarithmic values is likely to be more appropriate, since the modifications in the logarithmic series show a more stable variance than the modifications in the original series. The logarithm transformation helps stabilizing the variance of the series.

To check if structural breaks exist within the series, we perform the Multiple Breakpoints Tests.

Table 1. *Multiple breakpoints tests*

Break Dates	Sequential	Repartition
1	2021M10	2020M03
2	2020M02	2021M03
3	2021M03	2021M10

Source: Authors' own computations.

Table 1 shows that there are multiple structural breaks in the series. In order to keep the same sample size of 50 observations, we construct a dummy variable, which takes the value of 0 up until 2021M9 and value of 1 from 2021M10 onwards. The dummy variable is statistically significant and after including it in the regression, the null hypothesis of the CUSUMSQ test (H_0 : parameters are stable) is not rejected (the blue line lies within the red lines). Therefore, the problem of structural breaks is eliminated and we can proceed with testing the stationarity of the series.

4.2. Unit root test

Series must be stationary before it can be used to identify and estimate a model. With this respect, the *Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test (ADF)* help us identifying if data is stationary or not. The test results are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2. *Augmented Dickey-Fuller test*

Variable	Trend Specification		Remark
	Level	First Difference	
LINFL	-1.345034	-4.584306***	I(1)

Note: *, **, *** denote statistical significance at 10%, 5%, and 1% levels.

Source: Authors' own computations.

Results presented in Table 2 indicate that the ADF test statistic for the variable of interest is greater than the corresponding 95% critical values. Inflation variable became stationary after its first difference.

4.3. Model identification, estimation, and interpretation

The main objective of this paper is to assess inflation dynamics with ARIMA modelling technique. Since the logarithm of the inflation rate variable becomes stationary after taking the first order difference, the model that we are looking at is defined by ARIMA (p, 1, q). Next, we identify the best model, estimate appropriate parameters, perform diagnostic tests, and ultimately, forecast the inflation series.

The following approach is applied in estimating the univariate ARIMA model. Firstly, inflation rate series is transformed to stabilize the variable. Secondly, tentative models are identified utilizing the autocorrelation function (ACF), together with the partial autocorrelation function (PACF), and estimated through the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method. Thirdly, the most performant model is selected considering the smallest values for the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), the significance of the ARMA components, and the value of adjusted R^2 . Fourthly, the selected model is estimated and diagnostic tests are performed. Ultimately, the estimated model is used to forecast inflation and the prediction performance is examined.

4.3.1. ARIMA model identification

We perform the series correlogram for the first difference, which consists of the ACF and PACF values. We notice the patterns in the ACF and PACF, and identify the values for the parameters p and q for the ARIMA model. The autocorrelation part from the correlogram defines the MA(q) component, while the partial autocorrelation part highlights the AR(p) component. Also, the parsimony characteristic is important, which means that including

more variables in the model will raise the model fit (R^2), but at the cost of decreasing degrees of freedom. From the autocorrelation part, we select MA(1) and MA(7), while from the partial correlation part, AR(1) and AR(7) might be suitable. Therefore, there are four tentative models: ARIMA (1, 1, 1), ARIMA (7, 1, 1), ARIMA (1, 1, 7), and ARIMA (7, 1, 7).

4.3.2. ARIMA model estimation

After identifying the candidate models, it is a good practice to estimate each of them, then compare and select the most appropriate one.

Table 3. *The comparison of the candidate models*

Selection Criteria	Model			
	ARIMA (1, 1, 1)	ARIMA (1, 1, 7)	ARIMA (7, 1, 1)	ARIMA (7, 1, 7)
Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)	-1.333231	-1.370237	-1.397255	-1.242131
Schwarz Criterion (SIC)	-1.178797	-1.215803	-1.242821	-1.087697
Hannan-Quinn Criterion (HQ)	-1.274639	-1.311645	-1.338663	-1.183539
Adjusted R^2	0.183632	0.222027	0.241532	0.121301
Significance of the ARMA components	p[AR(1)]=0.8138; p[MA(1)]=0.1118	p[AR(1)]=0.0495; p[MA(7)]=0.0624	p[AR(7)]=0.0512**; p[MA(1)]=0.0042*	p[AR(7)]=0.9971; p[MA(7)]=0.5822

Note: *, **, *** denote statistical significance at 10%, 5%, 1% levels.

Source: authors' own computations.

The results in Table 3 indicate that ARIMA (7, 1, 1) is the appropriate one, since it has the lowest AIC, SIC, HQ, the ARMA components are significant, and adjusted R^2 is the highest. Therefore, it is reasonable to proceed with this model in our analysis.

4.3.3. Diagnostic tests

It is necessary to analyse the statistical properties of the estimated ARIMA model in observing the model adequacy. The model is tested for specification error, normality of the residuals, serial correlation, and heteroskedasticity. Additional checks will be made in order to see if the estimated AR(I)MA process is (covariance) stationary (if AR roots lie inside the unit circle) and if the estimated AR(I)MA process is invertible (if all MA roots lie inside the unit circle).

Table 4. *ARIMA (7, 1, 1) Diagnostic tests*

Test	F-statistic	P-value
Jarque-Berra test	0.874403	0.645841
Ramsey RESET test	0.104598	0.7479
Breusch-Godfrey LM test	0.097736	0.9071
Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (ARCH) test	1.035766	0.3141

Source: Authors' own computations.

Table 5. *Stationarity of the AR(I)MA process*

AR Root(s)	Modulus
-0.183580 ± 0.804316i	0.825000
-0.743299 ± 0.357954i	0.825000
0.514379 ± 0.645011i	0.825000
0.825000	0.825000
Conclusion: No root lie outside the unit circle	

Source: Authors' own computations.

Table 6. Invertibility of the AR(I)MA process

MA Root(s)	Modulus
-0.440065	0.440065
Conclusion: No root lie outside the unit circle	

Source: Authors' own computations.

Results in Table 4 indicate that the model is well specified based on the Ramsey RESET test and serially uncorrelated on the basis of the Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test. The Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (ARCH) test shows that there is no fluctuation clustering in Romania's inflation monthly data. Also, the Jarque-Berra (JB) test that the residuals are normally distributed.

4.3.4. Forecast evaluation for ARIMA (7, 1, 1) model

Next, we forecast the Romanian inflation rate using the ARIMA (7, 1, 1) model. The period of forecasts is from October 2021 to October 2022.

Figure 1. The forecast of the inflation rate for the period October 2021 – October 2022

In Figure 1, the blue line is the forecast value of inflation. The red lines which are above and below the predicted monthly inflation rate display the forecast with ± 2 of standard errors. Some prediction measurements such as the mean absolute error (MAE), root mean squared error (RMSE), and Theil inequality coefficient are presented. The estimated result for ARIMA in Figure 1 shows that the model is a good one.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we present the ARIMA model and the steps required in order to make forecasts for a particular series. We discover that ARIMA (7, 1, 1) is the best one and hence, we use this model to forecast the monthly inflation rate in Romania. However, for a higher increase in the accuracy of the forecasts, we suggest two aspects to be considered for future research. The first one refers to using models from machine learning/deep learning area. Even if some of them are very complex and difficult to interpret, they ensure high performance of the models. There will be a trade-off between model efficiency and

interpretability. The second suggestion relates to an expansion of the sample size. This is also a pre-requisite for using complex algorithms, since these require hundreds even thousands of observations, depending on the algorithm type. We envisage that machine learning models will replace many traditional algorithms, which are currently used in the central bank area. However, we do not exclude the possibility of a mix use of traditional and machine learning models.

References

- Baciu, I.C., 2015. Stochastic models for forecasting inflation rate. Empirical evidence. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, Vol. 20, pp. 44-52. doi: 10.1016/S2212-5671(15)00045-3
- Box, G. and Jenkins, G.M., 1976. *Time Series Analysis: Forecasting and Control*, s.l.: San Francisco: Holden-Day Inc.
- Castillo-Martinez, L. and Reis, R., 2019. How do central banks control inflation? A guide for the perplexed, s.l.: LSE Manuscript.
- Csorba, L.M. and Juravle, D.J., 2022. Study Regarding the Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Inflation in Romania in the 2019-2020 period. *Revista Economica*, 74(1), pp. 51-64.
- Jafarian-Namin, S., Fatemi-Ghomi, S., Shojaie, M. and Shavvalpour, S., 2021. Annual forecasting of inflation rate in Iran: Autoregressive integrated moving average modeling approach. *Engineering Reports*, 3(4), pp. 1-11. doi: 10.1002/eng2.12344
- Kenny, G., Meyler, A. and Quinn, T., 1998. Forecasting Irish inflation using ARIMA models, s.l.: Central Bank of Ireland (No. 3/RT/98).
- Majumder, S.C., 2016. Inflation and Its Impacts on Economic Growth of Bangladesh. *American Journal of Marketing Research*, 2(1), pp. 17-26.
- Okafor, C. and Shaibu, I., 2013. Application of ARIMA Models to Nigerian Inflation Dynamics. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(3), pp. 138-150.
- Salam, M.A., Salam, S. and Feridun, M., 2007. Modeling and forecasting Pakistan's inflation by using time series ARIMA models, s.l.: Economic Analysis Working Papers (No. 2007, 1).
- Thabani, N., 2019a. Modeling and forecasting inflation in Tanzania using ARIMA models, s.l.: Munich Personal RePEc Archive (MPRA No. 92458).
- Thabani, N., 2019b. Modeling and forecasting inflation in Philippines using ARIMA models, s.l.: Munich Personal RePEc Archive (MPRA No. 92429).
- Yolanda, Y., 2017. Analysis of Factors Affecting Inflation and its Impact on Human Development Index and Poverty in Indonesia. *European Research Studies Journal*, XX(4B), pp. 38-56. doi: 10.35808/ERSJ/873

The effects of geopolitical risks on tourism revenues of the Middle East and Asian countries

Ismet GOCER

University of Szeged, Hungary
gocer.ismet@szte.hu
ismetgocer@gmail.com

Peter KOVACS

University of Szeged, Hungary
kovacs.peter@eco.u-szeged.hu

Abstract. *In this study; the effects of Geopolitical Risks (GPR) on tourism revenue of the Middle East and Asia countries were examined by using panel data analysis under the cross-section dependency for the 1995-2021 period. According to the results, GPR has negative effects on tourism income in China, Hong Kong, India, Malaysia and Korea. Relative prices have a positive effect on tourism income in Indonesia, Malaysia, S. Arabia and Thailand. There are causality relations between GPR to tourism income in China, Hong Kong, Israel, Malaysia, Philippines, Russia, Korea and Thailand. Relative prices affect the tourism income in China, Hong Kong, Israel, Malaysia, Thailand and Turkey.*

Keywords: geopolitical risk index, tourism revenue, panel data analysis under the cross-sectional dependence.

JEL Classification: D81, L82, L85.

1. Introduction

Tourism is an important income source for developing countries. Tourism revenues reduce the current account deficits and economic crisis risks of countries by reducing their debt burden and their dependence on foreign currency. Tourism is the third-largest industry in terms of global export (WTO, 2018).

But geopolitical risks may significantly affect people's choices of tourism destinations. Because vacation is basically an activity for pleasure and entertainment, in cases where life safety and health conditions are not fully met, people can easily change or cancel their vacation plans (Marsiglio, 2016). Additionally, geopolitical risks have a crucial role in investments (Balcilar et al., 2018). Geopolitical risks also affect transportation costs (Webster and Ivanov, 2014). These may closely affect the tourism income, employment and economic growth of the host countries (Altay and Celebioglu, 2015, pp. 22-23; Gozgor and Ongan, 2017, p. 99). Despite all the importance, the research on the impact of geopolitical risks on tourism activities are very scant (Demir et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2020).

Geopolitical risks sharply increased with the 9/11 terror attacks in the US in 2001 and Second Gulf War in Iraq from 2003 to 2011 (Caldara and Iacoviello, 2019, p. 3). The protests of the Arab Spring, which started in Tunisia in December 2010 and spread to all Middle East and North African countries, and civil wars and mass migration events caused by them had significant effects on geopolitical risks (Gocer, 2015, p. 53). The withdrawal of the USA from Afghanistan and the Taliban's takeover of the administration in this country has been the last link that has increased the security concerns and geopolitical risks in this region (Mehra and Wentworth, 2021). At this point, it is of great benefit to frequently analyze the effects of increasing geopolitical risks on the economies of the countries in the region and to develop necessary policy recommendations.

In this study; the effects of the changes in the Geopolitical Risk Index (GPR⁽¹⁾) developed by Federal Reserve Board experts Caldara and Iacoviello (2019) on tourism movements in 12 countries in the Middle East and Asia were examined by using panel data analysis methods operating under cross-section dependence. Our methods also produce individual results. Moreover, the effects of GPRs on tourism demand for these countries could be detailly analyzed. The relative prices and the number of tourists were also added to the study as control variables.

This paper is one of the first studies to explore the effects of GPRs on tourism demand in the developing Middle East and Asian countries. It is expected that the findings of the study may shed light on the tourism policies of countries and the future planning of tourism agencies.

2. Literature review

Since the GPR index has just been created, the literature in this field has only just begun to form. Among them, Balli et al. (2019) focused on the effects of GPRs on tourism demand in 8 emerging countries (Malaysia, Indonesia, Mexico, Philippines, South Korea, South Africa, Turkey and Thailand). They detected that impact of GPR is heterogenous for these countries. While Mexico was heavily affected by the GPR, Indonesia and other countries

were found to be resistant to GPR shocks. According to these results, the impact of GPR is minimal in popular tourism destinations. Demir et al. (2019) analyzed the effects of GPR on inbound tourism in 18 countries from the 1995-2016 period and they found that GPR negatively affects the domestic number of tourists. Also, they determined that, while GDP, nominal exchange rate and population have positive effects on tourist numbers, inflation has a negative effect on it. Tiwari et al. (2019) investigated the effects of GPR and EPU (Economic Policy Uncertainties) on the number of tourists in India for the period of 2003M01-2017M06. They reached that GPR's effects are greater than EPU in the long run on tourism in India. EPU has a negative impact on tourism in the short run.

Akadiri et al. (2020) examined the causal relations between GPR and economic growth to tourism in Turkey for the period of 1985Q1-2017Q4 by using Toda and Yamamoto's (1995) causality test. They detected a unidirectional causality from GPR to tourism and GPR to economic growth. Authors also found that one standard deviation shock of GPR has a remarkable negative effect on tourism income and economic growth, both in the short- and long-term. Demir et al. (2020) analyzed the impact of GPR on Turkey's tourist arrivals for the period of 1990M01-2018M12 by means of the NARDL method. They found that GPR has an asymmetric effect on tourist arrivals in the short run. Thus, while the GPR increases, the number of tourists decreases, yet, when GPR decreases, it doesn't have any effect on tourist numbers.

Polat et al. (2021) searched the impacts of GPR on the tourism index in the stock market (BIST) and tourist arrival in Turkey for 1998M01-2020M10 by using the Hatemi-J causality test. They detected an asymmetrical relationship between the GPR of Turkey and the BIST tourism index. An increase in Turkey's GPR level remarkably decreases the BIST tourism index returns. Also, a reduction of GPR in Turkey causes an increase in tourist numbers. Ghosh (2022) examined the effects of GPR on tourism demand in India for the period from January 2015 to December 2017, by using Bayer and Hanck's (2013) causality method. He determined that there are causal relationships between GPR and policy uncertainty to tourism demand and GPR affects the tourism demand of India in the long term. Hence, the author stated that the tourism agencies and politicians should develop new/creative marketing strategies and reduce the GPR level to boost the confidence of the tourists.

This study will make important contributions to the literature, as there is no panel data analysis on this topic that produced individual results for countries since existing studies are either in the form of a time series for a single country or they produce results for the whole panel.

3. Econometric analysis

3.1. Data set

In this analysis, the following data sets were used for detecting GPRs on tourism revenue in the 12 Middle East and Asian Countries (China, India, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Israel, Philippines, Malaysia, Russian Federation, South Korea, Saudi Arabia, Turkey and Thailand) and the study covers the 1995-2021 period.

GPR Index (GPR): GPR Index was developed by Caldara and Iacoviello (2019). They construct this index by counting the occurrence of words related to geopolitical tensions (“geopolitical risk”, “terrorist attack”, “piracy”, “risk of war”, “geopolitical tension”, “geopolitical concern”, “geopolitical uncertainty” and “threats based on terror”) in 11 main newspapers (The Daily Telegraph, The Boston Globe, Chicago Tribune, Financial Times, The Guardian, The Globe and Mail, Los Angeles Times, The Times, The New York Times, The Washington Post and The Wall Street Journal). This index was created by calculating the counting of a number of articles related to geopolitical risk. The GPR index spikes around the First (1990) and Second (2003) Gulf Wars, the 9/11 2001 terrorist attack, during the 2014 and 2022 Ukraine – Russian Federation crises. This data set was obtained from Policy Uncertainty (2022). In Appendix, figures created by GPR data of countries can be seen.

Tourist Number (TNUM): Number of tourist arrivals. This data was taken from the World Bank database (2022a).

Tourism Income (TINC): Tourism receipts (US Dollars). This data was retrieved from the World Bank database (2022b).

Relative Prices (RPRC): Real effective exchange rate data is used for this purpose. This data set was obtained from Bruegel (2021). This data was prepared by Darvas (2021) and it was used by following Irani et al. (2021).

Logarithmic transformation is applied to all series by following Dogan et al. (2016, p. 77). Summary statistics of the original data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary statistics

	GPR	TINC	TNUM	RPRC
Mean	98.22	15	22	103
Median	92.81	10	12	104
Maximum	205.7	65	163	151
Minimum	44.69	1	1	50
Std. Dev.	25.68	14	31	18
Skewness	0.84	2	3	0.00
Kurtosis	4.19	6	10	3
Prob. of Jarque-Bera	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Observations	312	312	312	312

Note: TINC as billion Dollars and TNUM as million people.

According to Table 1, the data are distributed around their mean. The differences between the maximum and minimum values are small. Therefore, the standard deviations of the data are low. This indicates that the problem of heteroscedasticity problem will not occur at the end of the analysis. The number of observations used in the study is 312, which is adequate. The GPR series achieved its highest value (205.7) in Hong Kong in 2020. The TINC series reached its highest value (65 billion Dollars) in Thailand in 2019. The TNUM series received its greatest value (163 million people) in China, and the RPRC series saw its greatest value (151) in 1998 in Hong Kong.

3.2. Model

By following Stryzhak et al. (2022, p. 92) and Wang et al. (2022, p. 4) the econometric models set in this study were given below:

$$TINC_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GPR_{it} + \beta_2 TNUM_{it} + \beta_3 RPRC_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$TNUM_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 GPR_{it} + \alpha_2 RPRC_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where i ; countries ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 12$), t ; the time dimension of the panel ($t = 1, 2, \dots, 26$). ϵ_{it} ; shows error terms with random walk process. $TINC_{it}$ is tourism income, GPR_{it} is geopolitical risk level, $TNUM_{it}$ is tourist arrival numbers, $RPRC_{it}$ is relative prices in the country i , in the year t .

3.3. Analysis

In this study, panel data analysis methods operating under cross-section dependence were used. We also used methods which can produce individual results.

3.3.1. Cross-section dependence test

Cross-section dependence is an important subject for panel data analyses. When there is a cross-sectional dependence and it is ignored, results may be biased. In order to solve this problem first, the LM test was developed by Breusch and Pagan (1980). This test focuses on Eq. (3):

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_i x_{it} + \epsilon_{it}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, t = 1, \dots, T \quad (3)$$

Where x_{it} refers to deterministic components, N ; cross-section and T is for the time dimension. This cross-sectional dependence test is based on covariance among ϵ_{it} error terms. The null hypothesis is “ $Cov(\epsilon_{it}, \epsilon_{jt}) = 0, i \neq j$ ”. It shows no cross-sectional dependence. In order to test these hypotheses, Breusch and Pagan (1980) obtained the LM test statistic as follows:

$$LM = T \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \hat{\rho}_{ij}^2 \quad (4)$$

Here $\hat{\rho}_{ij}^2$ shows covariance coefficients, which are obtained by estimating Eq. (3) via least-squares method (Destek, 2016, p. 41). Baltagi et al. (2012) also corrected the asymptotic deviations in the LM tests and obtained the LM_{BC} test statistic:

$$LM_{BC} = \left(\frac{1}{N(N-1)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \left((T_i \hat{\rho}_{ij}^2 - 1) - \frac{1}{2(T-1)} \right) \quad (5)$$

In this paper, LM and LM_{BC} cross-sectional dependence tests were used and the obtained results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Cross-sectional dependence tests results

	GPR	TNUM	TINC	RPRC
LM	271.39*** (0.00)	1160*** (0.00)	1325.57*** (0.00)	356.97*** (0.00)
LM _{BC}	17.64*** (0.00)	94.98*** (0.00)	109.39*** (0.00)	25.09*** (0.00)

Note: *** shows stationarity in 1% significance. Prob. values are given in the parentheses.

According to the results in Table 2, the null hypothesis is strongly rejected and it is determined that there is cross-section dependence among the countries. Therefore, analysis methods that take this situation into consideration should be used in the next stages of the study.

3.3.2. Panel unit root test

Stationarity levels of these series were investigated via Hadri and Kurozumi's (2012) panel unit root test (HK). This test takes the cross-sectional dependence among countries into consideration. Furthermore, it solves the autocorrelation problem in series by $AR(p + 1)$ the process of Sul et al. (2005). HK is based on Eq. (6):

$$y_{it} = z_t' \delta_i + f_t \gamma_i + e_{it} \quad (6)$$

Where f_t is the common factors, e_{it} has an $AR(1)$ process and can be written as Eq. (7):

$$e_{it} = \phi_1 e_{it-1} + u_{it} \quad (7)$$

In Sul et al. (2005) method, y_{it} is assuming as it is $AR(p)$ and modified as it is in Eq. (8):

$$y_{it} = z_t' \delta_i + \hat{\phi}_{i1} y_{it-1} + \dots + \hat{\phi}_{ip} y_{it-p} + \hat{\zeta}_{i0} \underline{y}_t + \dots + \hat{\zeta}_{ip} \underline{y}_{t-p} + \hat{u}_{it} \quad (8)$$

Long term variation of the estimated equation is written as in Eq. (9):

$$\hat{\sigma}_{u_i}^2 = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \hat{u}_{it}^2 \quad (9)$$

Variation of Sul et al. (2005) (SPC) is calculated by using Eq. (10):

$$\hat{\sigma}_{u_{iSPC}}^2 = \frac{\hat{\sigma}_{u_i}^2}{(1 - \hat{\phi}_i)^2} \quad (10)$$

Operating this, Z_A^{SPC} test statistics is obtained with Eq. (11):

$$Z_A^{SPC} = \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}_{u_{iSPC}}^2 T^2} \sum_{t=1}^T (S_{it}^w)^2 \quad (11)$$

Variance is computed in Choi's (1993) Lag Augmented (LA) method by using $\tilde{\sigma}_{u_i}^2$:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{u_{iLA}}^2 = \frac{\hat{\sigma}_{u_i}^2}{(1 - \tilde{\phi}_{i1} - \dots - \tilde{\phi}_{ip})^2} \quad (12)$$

Where $\tilde{\sigma}_{u_i}^2 = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \tilde{u}_{it}^2$, it obtained estimation of Eq. (13):

$$y_{it} = z_t' \tilde{\delta}_i + \tilde{\phi}_{i1} y_{it-1} + \dots + \tilde{\phi}_{ip+1} y_{it-p-1} + \tilde{\zeta}_{i0} \underline{y}_t + \dots + \tilde{\zeta}_{ip+1} \underline{y}_{t-p-1} + \tilde{u}_{it} \quad (13)$$

Then, Z_A^{LA} test statistic is obtained via Eq. (14):

$$Z_A^{LA} = \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}_{u_{iLA}}^2 T^2} \sum_{t=1}^T (S_{it}^w)^2 \quad (14)$$

Null hypothesis of this test is; " $\phi_i(1) \neq 0$ for all i , no unit root". and Alternative of this hypothesis is; " $\phi_i(1) = 0$ for some i , has a unit root". In this study, Hadri and Kurozumi's (2012) panel unit root test was used and outcomes are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Panel unit root test results

Variables	Level		First Difference	
	Z_A^{SPC}	Z_A^{LA}	Z_A^{SPC}	Z_A^{LA}
GPR	5.31 (0.00)	5.06 (0.00)	0.07*** (0.47)	0.50*** (0.50)
TNUM	2.40 (0.00)	2.77 (0.00)	0.57*** (0.28)	0.47*** (0.31)
TINC	2.97 (0.00)	2.30 (0.00)	0.008*** (0.49)	0.06*** (0.52)
RPRC	9.63 (0.00)	15.88 (0.00)	-0.35*** (0.63)	-0.40*** (0.65)

Note: *** indicates stationarity in 1% significance. Prob. values are given in the parentheses.

According to the results in Table 3, all series are non-stationary in the level and they are stationary in the first differences. Thus, all series are I(1). Therefore, applying a cointegration test is necessary according to Engle and Granger (1987).

3.3.3. Panel cointegration test

The existence of cointegration among the series was searched by means of the Durbin-Hausman panel cointegration test of Westerlund (2008). This method considers the cross-section dependency among countries. This test is based on Eq. (15):

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_i x_{it} + z_{it} \quad (15)$$

Here $x_{it} = \delta_i x_{it-1} + w_{it}$ and $z_{it} = \lambda_i' F_t + e_{it}$. Then $e_{it} = \phi_i e_{it-1} + v_{it}$. F_t is the common factor and it can be written as Eq. (16):

$$F_{jt} = \rho_j F_{jt-1} + u_{jt} \quad (16)$$

Westerlund (2008) has developed two different test statistics in this method:

$$DH_g = \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{S}_i (\tilde{\phi}_i - \hat{\phi}_i)^2 \sum_{t=2}^T \hat{e}_{it-1}^2 \quad (17)$$

$$DH_p = \hat{S}_i (\tilde{\phi}_i - \hat{\phi}_i)^2 \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{t=2}^T \hat{e}_{it-1}^2 \quad (18)$$

Where DH_g is Durbin-Hausman group statistics for heterogeneous panel and DH_p is panel statistics for the homogeneous panel.

Here $\hat{S}_i = \frac{\hat{\omega}_i^2}{\hat{\sigma}_i^2}$ and $\hat{\omega}_i^2 = \frac{1}{T-1} \sum_{j=-M_i}^{M_i} (1 - \frac{j}{M_i+1}) \sum_{t=j+1}^T \hat{v}_{it} \hat{v}_{it-j}$. \hat{v}_{it} is the OLS residual, M_i is bandwidth and $\hat{\sigma}_i^2$ is variance.

The null hypothesis of Durbin-Hausman test is “ $\phi_i = 1$ for all i , no cointegration” and the alternative hypothesis is “ $\phi_i < 1$ for some i , cointegration”. Results of the Westerlund (2008) Durbin-Hausman panel cointegration test are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Panel cointegration test results

	DH_g	DH_p
Model: $TINC = f(GPR, TNUM, RPRC)$	7.85*** (0.00)	4.95*** (0.00)
Model: $TNUM = f(GPR, RPRC)$	5.31*** (0.00)	6.66** (0.02)

Note: *** and ** indicates the existence of cointegration in the model at 1% and 5%, respectively. Prob. values are given in the parentheses.

These results demonstrate that there are cointegration relationships among series in both models. The results of DH_g and DH_p tests confirmed the existence of a long-run relationship (Malhotra and Kumari, 2016, p. 143) between the tourism sector and geopolitical risks in the selected Middle East and Asian countries. According to these cointegration relations, spurious regression problems will not be encountered in subsequent analyzes (Engle and Granger, 1987).

3.3.4. Panel regression analysis

Panel regression analysis was conducted by the Panel AMG estimator of Eberhardt and Bond (2009). This method takes into consideration cross-sectional dependence. The results obtained by the AMG method are represented in Table 5 and Table 6.

Table 5. Panel regression analysis results (dependent variable: *TINC*)

	GPR	TNUM	RPRC	Constant
China	-0.77*** (0.00)	0.57*** (0.00)	0.27 (0.56)	15.35*** (0.00)
Hong Kong	-0.32** (0.03)	0.58* (0.05)	0.23 (0.49)	13.66*** (0.00)
India	-0.38*** (0.00)	0.25* (0.09)	0.78 (0.13)	15.85*** (0.00)
Indonesia	-0.09 (0.15)	0.98*** (0.00)	0.24* (0.07)	6.51*** (0.00)
Israel	0.36** (0.01)	0.74 (0.57)	0.28 (0.18)	8.08*** (0.00)
Malaysia	-0.15** (0.03)	0.90*** (0.00)	0.85*** (0.00)	4.65*** (0.00)
Philippines	0.004 (0.98)	1.04*** (0.00)	-0.37 (0.32)	7.85* (0.05)
Russia	-0.09 (0.79)	0.46* (0.05)	0.12 (0.77)	14.13*** (0.00)
Saudi Arabia	-0.13 (0.46)	-0.09 (0.61)	0.90*** (0.00)	19.40*** (0.00)
South Korea	-0.16* (0.09)	0.70*** (0.00)	-0.68*** (0.00)	15.65*** (0.00)
Thailand	0.001 (0.97)	0.72*** (0.00)	1.14*** (0.00)	6.12*** (0.00)
Turkey	0.0004 (0.99)	0.58*** (0.00)	0.14 (0.22)	12.94*** (0.00)
Panel	-0.11* (0.06)	0.67*** (0.00)	0.34** (0.04)	11.71*** (0.00)
Number of obs.	312	Prob > chi2		0.00
Wald chi2(3)	67.38	RMSE		0.12

Note: ***, ** and * indicates significance in 1%, 5% and 10%. Prob. values are given in the parentheses.

According to the results in Table 5, geopolitical risks negatively affect the tourism income in China, Hong Kong, India, Malaysia, South Korea and the entire panel. If GPR increases by 1%, the tourism income of China decreases by 0.77%, by 0.32% in Hong Kong, by 0.38% in India, by 0.15% in Malaysia, by 0.16% in S. Korea and by 0.11% in the panel. Though it has a positive effect in Israel. It shows that the tourism demand of Israel is inelastic to GPR. The number of tourists increases the tourism income in China, India, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Philippines, Malaysia, Russian Federation, South Korea, Turkey, Thailand and the entire panel. When tourist arrivals increase by 1%, it improves tourism income by 0.57% in China, 0.58% in Hong Kong, 0.25% in Indonesia, 0.90% in Malaysia, 1.04% in Philippines, 0.46% in Russia, 0.70% in S. Korea, 0.72% in Thailand, 0.58% in Turkey and 0.67% in panel. Hence, these countries attracting more tourists will also increase their tourism revenues. If relative prices increase by 1%, tourism income expands by 0.24% in Indonesia, by 0.85% in Malaysia, by 0.90% in Saudi Arabia and by 1.14% in Thailand. These results indicate that the price elasticity of tourism demand is very low in the given countries. They can improve their tourism revenue by increasing the prices. Raising prices has reduced tourism revenues in South Korea. Thus, South Korea should avoid raising tourism prices.

Table 6. Panel regression analysis results (dependent variable: TNUM)

	GPR	RPRC	Constant
China	-0.19* (0.07)	-2.07*** (0.00)	28.46*** (0.00)
Hong Kong	-0.02 (0.75)	-0.45** (0.01)	18.39*** (0.00)
India	-0.25 (0.21)	1.77*** (0.00)	7.70*** (0.00)
Indonesia	-0.36*** (0.00)	-0.35 (0.10)	18.36*** (0.00)
Israel	-1.29*** (0.00)	0.18 (0.72)	19.10*** (0.00)
Malaysia	0.21 (0.28)	0.14 (0.80)	14.13*** (0.00)
Philippines	-0.23** (0.01)	0.55*** (0.00)	12.79*** (0.00)
Russia	-0.28 (0.39)	-0.32 (0.36)	19.16*** (0.00)
Saudi Arabia	0.46*** (0.00)	-0.39 (0.14)	15.53*** (0.00)
South Korea	0.09 (0.39)	-0.06 (0.74)	14.89*** (0.00)
Thailand	-0.23*** (0.00)	0.36* (0.07)	15.04*** (0.00)
Turkey	-0.29* (0.08)	0.45** (0.02)	15.28*** (0.00)
Panel	-0.19*** (0.00)	0.03 (0.84)	16.14*** (0.00)
Number of obs.	312	Prob > chi2	0.01
Wald chi2(2)	8.12	RMSE	0.14

Note: ***, ** and * indicate significance in 1%, 5% and 10%. Prob. values are given in the parentheses.

According to the results in Table 6, geopolitical risks negatively affect the tourist arrivals in China, Indonesia, Israel, Philippines Thailand, Turkey and the entire panel. If GPR increases by 1%, it decreases tourists' number by 0.19% in China, by 0.36% in Indonesia, by 1.29 in Israel, by 0.23% in the Philippines and Thailand, by 0.29% in Turkey and by 0.19% in the panel. However, GPR has a positive effect in Saudi Arabia at 0.46%. As shown, tourism demand in Saudi Arabia is inelastic due to the holly pilgrimage. An increase in the relative prices diminishes tourists in China and Hong Kong by 2.07% and 0.45%, respectively. It would be advantageous for these countries to not increase their prices of goods and services in order to increase the number of tourists. When relatively prices are increased by 1%, the number of tourists increases by 1.77% in India, 0.55% in the Philippines, 0.36% in Thailand and 0.45% in Turkey. These results indicate that the price elasticity of tourism demand is low in these countries.

3.3.5. Causality test

Existence of causality relations among series was examined by Konya's (2006) SUR test. The cross-section dependence among these countries is taken into consideration in this method. The Konya (2006) method uses this equation system for testing causality relations from X to Y :

$$Y_{1,t} = \varphi_{1,1} + \sum_{j=1}^{p_{y_1}} \alpha_{1,1,j} Y_{1,t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^{p_{x_1}} \gamma_{1,1,j} X_{1,t-j} + \epsilon_{1,1,t} \quad (19)$$

$$Y_{2,t} = \varphi_{1,2} + \sum_{j=1}^{p_{y_1}} \alpha_{1,2,j} Y_{2,t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^{p_{x_1}} \gamma_{1,2,j} X_{2,t-j} + \epsilon_{1,2,t} \quad (20)$$

....

$$Y_{N,t} = \varphi_{1,N} + \sum_{j=1}^{p_{y_1}} \alpha_{1,N,j} Y_{N,t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^{p_{x_1}} \gamma_{1,N,j} X_{N,t-j} + \epsilon_{1,N,t} \quad (21)$$

Where p_{y_1} and p_{x_1} are optimal lag lengths. This method can be used when the series is stationary or cointegrated (Konya, 2006, p. 980)⁽²⁾. The null hypothesis of this test is “ $\gamma_{1,1,j} = 0$, for all j . No causality X to Y ”, and the alternative hypothesis is “ $\gamma_{1,1,j} \neq 0$, for some j . Causality from X to Y in some cross-sections”. Konya’s (2006) test results were presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Causality test results for each country

	GPR → TINC	GPR → TNUM	TNUM → TINC	RPRC → TINC	RPRC → TNUM
China	5.96** (0.01)	2.80* (0.09)	0.14 (0.70)	20.30*** (0.00)	18.16*** (0.00)
Hong Kong	23.76*** (0.00)	20.47*** (0.00)	0.57 (0.99)	18.44*** (0.00)	16.63*** (0.00)
India	0.22 (0.63)	1.39 (0.23)	8.86*** (0.00)	0.87 (0.92)	0.41 (0.51)
Indonesia	0.95 (0.32)	0.83 (0.77)	4.54** (0.03)	1.31 (0.25)	1.55 (0.21)
Israel	5.05** (0.02)	1.21 (0.26)	1.90 (0.16)	4.89** (0.02)	10.10*** (0.00)
Malaysia	11.04*** (0.00)	6.25** (0.01)	28.53*** (0.00)	11.49*** (0.00)	32.32*** (0.00)
Philippines	3.50* (0.06)	5.70** (0.01)	25.91*** (0.00)	0.27 (0.86)	0.47 (0.82)
Russia	23.20*** (0.00)	0.54 (0.45)	0.12 (0.72)	12.83*** (0.00)	0.35 (0.85)
Saudi Arabia	0.24 (0.96)	8.16*** (0.00)	5.73** (0.01)	0.12 (0.71)	2.06 (0.15)
South Korea	6.02** (0.01)	0.70 (0.40)	0.24 (0.61)	0.16 (0.68)	1.30 (0.25)
Thailand	11.79*** (0.00)	3.20* (0.07)	1.14 (0.28)	2.78* (0.09)	4.16** (0.04)
Turkey	1.88 (0.16)	0.18 (0.67)	3.11* (0.07)	5.39** (0.02)	9.62*** (0.00)

Note: ***, ** and * indicates significance in 1%, 5% and 10%. Prob. values are given in the parentheses.

According to the causality test results in Table 7, there are causality relations from GPR to tourism income in China, Hong Kong, Israel, Malaysia, Philippines, Russia, South Korea, Thailand and the entire panel. Likewise, there are causality relations between GPR to tourist numbers in China, Hong Kong, Malaysia, Philippines, Saudi Arabia, Thailand and the entire panel. On the other hand, the number of tourists affects the tourism income in India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Saudi Arabia and Turkey. These countries should focus on increasing their number of tourists. Relative prices affect the tourism income in China, Hong Kong, Israel, Malaysia, Russia, Thailand, Turkey and the entire panel. Moreover, prices affect the number of tourists in China, Hong Kong, Israel, Malaysia, Thailand, and Turkey. If these countries can accurately manage tourism prices, they can then increase their number of tourists and tourism income.

4. Conclusions

In this study; the effects of GPR on tourism movements towards Turkey, South Korea, Russian Federation, India, Saudi Arabia, China, Indonesia, Thailand, Philippines, Israel, Malaysia and Hong Kong were examined by using panel data analysis under the cross-section dependence for the period of 1995-2021. Our methods further produce individual results. Additionally, relative prices and tourist numbers were added as control variables to the analysis.

The cross-sectional dependence was tested via LM and LM_{BC} tests and it was decided that there is cross-section dependency among the Middle East and Asian countries. Stationarity levels of series were investigated by means of Hadri and Kurozumi's (2012) method and it was seen that all series are $I(1)$. Cointegration relations of series are investigated via Westerlund's (2008) method and it was determined that series are cointegrated.

Panel regression analyses were conducted by using the AMG technique of Eberhardt and Bond (2009). According to panel results, GPR has a negative effect on tourism income in China, Hong Kong, India, South Korea, Malaysia and the entire panel. These countries should try to decrease the geopolitical risks on their territory in order to increase their tourism revenue. The most significant impact was found in China. GPR has a positive effect in Israel. The result shows that the tourism demand of Israel is inelastic to GPR. Likewise, GPR has a negative effect on tourist arrivals in China, Indonesia, Israel, Philippines, Thailand, Turkey and the overall panel. These countries should focus on decreasing their GPR level in order to increase their numbers of tourists. It is seen that Israel is the most vulnerable country in this domain. Quite the opposite, GPR has a positive effect in Saudi Arabia, which means that the tourism demand in Saudi Arabia is inelastic due to the holy pilgrimage. Price increases have a positive effect on tourism revenue in Indonesia, Malaysia, Saudi Arabia and Thailand. These results indicate that the tourism demands of these countries are inelastic. These countries can improve their tourism income by raising the prices. Thailand is the most advantageous country in this respect. While rising prices reduced tourist numbers in China and Hong Kong, the number has increased in India, the Philippines, Thailand and Turkey. These results imply the price elasticity of tourism demand is low in China and Hong Kong. Thus, China and Hong Kong should degrade their tourism prices.

According to the Konya (2006) test results, there are causality relations between GPR to tourism income in China, Hong Kong, Israel, Malaysia, Philippines, Russia, S. Korea and Thailand. Likewise, there are causality relations between GPR to tourist numbers in China, Hong Kong, Malaysia, the Philippines, Saudi Arabia and Thailand. On the other hand, tourist numbers affect the tourism revenue in India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Saudi Arabia and Turkey. These countries should focus on increasing the number of tourists in order to make increase their revenue from the tourism sector. Relative prices affect the tourism income and the number of tourists in China, Hong Kong, Israel, Malaysia, Russia, Thailand and Turkey. If these countries can accurately control tourism prices, they can then increase their income.

According to the findings acquired from the analyses, the tourism industry should explain the sources of geopolitical risks, decrease tourism prices and the major stakeholders should establish platforms and develop international cooperation in their countries to reduce travellers' fears. This study emphasizes the mentioned countries to reduce GPRs. Otherwise, these risks may be damaging to the tourism sector.

Notes

- (1) This index measures geopolitical risk levels, which are related to wars, terror attacks, and problems between countries that affect the peaceful course of life (Caldara and Iacoviello, 2019, p. 5).
- (2) This situation is represented in the Konya (2006: 980) study as follows: It is assumed that Y_t and X_t are stationary or cointegrated therefore, depending on the time-series properties of the data, they might denote the level, the first difference or somewhat higher difference of X and Y .

References

- Akadiri, S.S., Eluwole, K.K., Akadiri, A.C. and Avci, T., 2020. Does Causality Between Geopolitical Risk, Tourism and Economic Growth Matter? Evidence from Turkey. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 43, pp. 273-277.
- Altay, H. and Celebioglu, F., 2015. The Impacts of Political Terrorism on Gross Domestic Product in Eurasia: A Spatial Data Analysis. *Eurasian Journal of Business and Economics*, 8(15), pp. 21-37. DOI: 10.17015/ejbe.2015.015.02.
- Balcilar, M., Bonato, M., Demirer, R. and Gupta, R., 2018. Geopolitical Risks and Stock Market Dynamics of the BRICS. *Economic Systems*, 42(2), pp. 295-306.
- Balli, F., Uddin, G.S. and Shahzad, S.J.H., 2019. Geopolitical Risk and Tourism Demand in Emerging Economies. *Tourism Economics*, 25(6), pp. 997-1005.
- Baltagi, B.H., Feng, Q. and Kao, C., 2012. A Lagrange Multiplier Test for Cross-Sectional Dependence in a Fixed Effects Panel Data Model. *Journal of Econometrics*, 170(1), pp. 164-177.
- Breusch, T.S. and Pagan, A.R., 1980. The Lagrange Multiplier Test and Its Applications to Model Specification in Econometrics. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 47(1), pp. 239-253.
- Bruegel, (2021). *Real Effective Exchange Rates for 178 Countries: A New Database*. Available at <<https://www.bruegel.org/publications/datasets/real-effective-exchange-rates-for-178-countries-a-new-database/>>
- Caldara, D. and Iacoviello, M., 2019. *Measuring Geopolitical Risk*. Available at <https://www.matteoiacoviello.com/gpr_files/GPR_PAPER.pdf>
- Choi, I., 1993. Asymptotic Normality of the Least-Squares Estimates for Higher Order Autoregressive Integrated Processes with Some Applications. *Econometric Theory*, 9(2), pp. 263-282.
- Darvas, Z., 2021. Timely Measurement of Real Effective Exchange Rates. Working Paper 2021/15, Bruegel, 23 December 2021.
- Demir, E., Gozgor, G. and Paramati, S.R., 2019. Do Geopolitical Risks Matter for Inbound Tourism? *Eurasian Business Review*, 9(2), pp. 183-191.
- Demir, E., Simonyan, S., Chen, M.H. and Marco Lau, C.K., 2020. Asymmetric Effects of Geopolitical Risks on Turkey's Tourist Arrivals. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 45, pp. 23-26.
- Destek, M.A., 2016. The Nexus between Military Spending and Economic Growth in Newly Industrialized Countries: Panel Evidence from Cross-Sectional Dependency. *Eurasian Journal of Business and Economics*, 9(17), pp. 37-50.
- Dogan, B., Albeni, M., Baydar, V. and Akcayir, O., 2016. A Research on the Performance and Characteristics of the Firms in Turkish Manufacturing Industry. *Eurasian Journal of Business and Economics*, 9(17), pp. 67-86.
- Eberhardt, M. and Bond, S., 2009. Cross-section Dependence in Nonstationary Panel Models: A Novel Estimator. *MPRA Paper*, No. 17870.
- Engle, R.F. and Granger, C.W.J., 1987. Cointegration and Error Correction: Representation, Estimation and Testing, *Econometrica*, 55, pp. 251-276.
- Ghosh, S., 2022. Geopolitical Risk, Economic Growth, Economic Uncertainty and International Inbound Tourism: An Indian Illustration. *Review of Economics and Political Science*, 7(1), pp. 2-21.
- Gocer, I., 2015. The Reasons of Arab Spring, Its International Dimension and Impacts on Turkey's Foreign Trade and Tourism Incomes. *Kafkas University Economics and Administrative Sciences Faculty, The Journal of KAU IIBF*, 6(10), pp. 51-68.
- Gozgor, G. and Ongan, S., 2017. Economic Policy Uncertainty and Tourism Demand: Empirical Evidence from the USA. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 19(1), pp. 99-106.

- Hadri, K. and Kurozumi, E., 2012. A Simple Panel Stationarity Test in the Presence of Serial Correlation and a Common Factor. *Economics Letters*, 115, pp. 31-34.
- Irani, F., Athari, S.A. and Hadood, A.A.A., 2021. The Impacts of Country Risk, Global Economic Policy Uncertainty, and Macroeconomic Factors on the Turkish Tourism Industry. *International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration*, 22(4), pp. 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15256480.2021.1935393>
- Konya, L., 2006. Exports and Growth: Granger Causality Analysis on OECD Countries. *Economic Modelling*, 23(6), pp. 978-992.
- Lee, C.C., Olasehinde-Williams, G. and Akadiri, S.S., 2020. Geopolitical Risk and Tourism: Evidence from Dynamic Heterogeneous Panel Models. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 23(2), pp. 26-38.
- Malhotra, N. and Kumari, D., 2016. Export Performance and Economic Growth in East Asian Economies – Application of Cointegration and Vector Error Correction Model. *Eurasian Journal of Business and Economics*, 9(18), pp. 135-152.
- Marsiglio, S., 2016. Uncertainty, Crowding Aversion and Tourism Aversion in Tourism Destinations. *Tourism Economics*, 22, pp. 111-123.
- Mehra, T. and Wentworth, M., 2021. *The Rise of the Taliban in Afghanistan: Regional Responses and Security Threats*. Available at <<https://icct.nl/publication/the-rise-of-the-taliban-in-afghanistan-regional-responses-and-security-threats/>>
- Pesaran, M.H., 2006. Estimation and Inference in Large Heterogeneous Panels with a Multifactor Error Structure. *Econometrica*, 74(4), pp. 967-1012.
- Pesaran, M.H., 2007. A Simple Panel Unit Root Test in the Presence of Cross Section Dependence. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 22, pp. 365-312.
- Polat, M., Alpturk, Y. and Gursoy, S., 2021. Impact of geopolitical risk on BIST tourism index and tourist arrivals in Turkey. *Journal of Tourism Theory and Research*, 7(2), pp. 77-84.
- Policy Uncertainty (2022). *Geopolitical Risk Index*. Available at <<https://www.policy-uncertainty.com/gpr.html>>
- Stryzhak, O., Sayar, R. and Ari, Y.O., 2022. Geopolitical Risks, GDP and Tourism: An ARDL-ECM Cointegration Study on Ukraine. *CES Working Papers*, XIV(1), pp. 85-113.
- Sul, D., Phillips, P.C.B. and Choi, C.Y., 2005. Prewhitening Bias in HAC Estimation. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 67, pp. 517-546.
- Tiwari, A.K., Das, D. and Dutta, A., 2019. Geopolitical Risk, Economic Policy Uncertainty and Tourist Arrivals: Evidence from a Developing Country. *Tourism Management*, 75, pp. 323-327.
- Wang, H., Khan, Y.A., Mouldi, A., Khier, B.S.A. and Guo, W., 2022. The Impact of Geopolitical and Pandemic Risks on Tourist Inflows: Evidence sia-Pacific Region. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 10(850729), pp. 1-9. doi: 10.3389/fenvs.2022.850729.
- Webster, C. and Ivanov, S.H., 2014. Geopolitical Drivers of Future Tourist Flows. *Journal of Tourism Futures*, 1(1), pp. 59-69.
- Westerlund, J., 2008. Panel Cointegration Tests of the Fisher Effect. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 23(2), pp. 193-223.
- World Bank, 2022a. *International Tourism, Number of Arrivals*. Available at <<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/ST.INT.ARVL?view=chart>>
- World Bank, 2022b. *International Tourism, Receipts (Current US\$)*. Available at <<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/ST.INT.RCPT.CD?view=chart>>
- WTO, 2018. *UNWTO Tourism Highlights*. World Tourism Organization, UNWTO, Madrid.

Appendix. GPR indexes of countries

The potential of macroeconomic forces and ICT in affecting the sectorial growth: ARDL approach in the context of East Asian countries

Sadik Aden DIRIR

University of Djibouti, Djibouti
Sadikaden1999@gmail.com

Abstract. *The current study examines the potential of macroeconomic forces and information and communications technology in affecting sectorial growth. Hereby, the paper employs annual time series data varying from 2000 to 2021 with the regard to East Asia and the Pacific as a focus region. Within this framework, the study considers three different sectors namely manufacturing, services, and agriculture as proxies for sectoral growth. To proceed with the examination Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model and Granger causality test are performed to capture the long-run and short-run dynamic relationship among the variables. As well as to determine the direction of these relationships. In accordance with the findings, the paper uncovered that both in the long and short run fixed telephone subscription, gross capital formation, government expenditure, population growth, and both importation and exportation are decreasing the growth of the manufacturing, agricultural, and service sectors. On the other hand, the general expenditure of the government and the rate of agricultural exportation raise the value produced by the agricultural sector in the long term. The recent findings can be used as evidence particularly for emerging nations and policymakers, on the necessity of utilizing certain macroeconomic elements and technology to support their nation's sectoral growth.*

Keywords: sectoral growth, ICT, macroeconomic factors, manufacturing sector, service sector, agricultural sector.

JEL Classification: F62, O11, O13, O32.

1. Introduction

The Asian powerhouse did not rise overnight. The "Asian Miracle", a phase of rapid economic growth marked by a "moving geese" form of growth, followed rapid expansion in Japan set the stage for this in the mid-1970s, and then the "Four Tigers" Hong Kong, Korea, Singapore, and Taiwan took off. Malaysia and Thailand followed these nations to take advantage of the high development route in the mid-1980s. China began to pick up pace in the late 1970s, particularly after entering the World Trade Organization at the beginning of 1990, it began to enjoy double-digit development, becoming a major economic power in Asia.

Notwithstanding the crisis's exceptional effects, the continent's economy demonstrated its ability and resiliency by quickly regaining the profitable export-led restoration path. This was especially true for several Asian economies. The Lehman Shock and the ensuing world financial crisis serve as a more contemporary example of this resiliency. The Asian economy maintained a reasonably high overall development after the recession.

Emerging Asia responded well throughout the 2008-2009 global recession. With the aid of bold and extensive financial policy and macroeconomic policy measures, it became the earliest area to recover from turbulence. Household consumption has remained strong, particularly in the bigger nations in the area, and the market trend strongly implies that economies have reached a bottom and are starting to rebuild. Within the first quarter of 2010, some Asian nations even got triple growth in their domestic product (GDP). Numerous elements contributed to this. Several scientific findings were capable of summarizing the factors behind Asia's economic development, which had been labeled a "marvel" in the nineties. They emphasize the significance of investment, intellectual resources, and demographic, structural, and political factors. (Lucas, 1993). For instance, Steven et al. (2001) conclude that East Asia's quick development was caused by its significant capacity for keeping pace, advantageous location and institutional traits, population surplus, and fiscal policies and growth-friendly tactics. The empirical research demonstrates that the continent's prolonged development was greatly influenced by economic policies, especially those that emphasized openness. (Lee and Hong, 2010, pp. 1-2).

Following the Second World War, significant Asian markets such as Japan, the Republic of Korea, and the People's Republic of China (PRC) underwent dramatic economic changes, experienced rapid capital accumulation growth, and witnessed considerable workforce shift patterns away from the farming industry and toward the manufacturing industry. Over this time, the manufacturing industry has emerged as a major driver of development. Substantial accumulation and expenditure levels, as well as export-focused regulations, have aided in this fast industrialization. Nevertheless, in recent years, the rapidly industrializing East Asian nations' rate of productivity growth has dropped dramatically. As the difference between their respective capita incomes and those of the US closed throughout the period, Japan's and other Asian economies formerly experienced high growth and started to slow down. The main drivers of the development slowdown have been identified as a variety of variables, notably reduced employment growth, lower capital rates, diminishing prices of return on capital, and slow technological innovation (Lee and McKibbin, 2018, p. 247).

The economic frameworks of different nations are incredibly varied. Regardless of whether the formation is driven by the exploitation of mineral materials, exports, farming practices that are targeted toward rural areas, commercial mass manufacturing, particularly in Asian nations, or the rise of services like communications and entertainment, etc. (Pham and Riedel, 2019, pp. 214-216).

By using ICT and beneficial market mechanisms, many nations maintain their sectorial growth. In order to visualize the cause and effect from the implied framework of development standpoint, the neoclassical theory of economic expansion and its amplified edition, the intrinsic component new tech transformation model, and the constructivist viewpoint to economic growth, the significance of innovation as a device of economic development has sparked numerous crucial and sensitive studies. Contrary to other sorts of technology, ICT's ability to contribute to growth and progress in nations, particularly in poor nations is reliant on a number of variables, including externalities and spillover, institutionalized regulations that favor discoveries, and social resources. ICT may therefore be considered an overall technology that has an impact on several economic sectors and progressively alters how technology approaches development from a variety of angles. Firstly, ICT is a tool for integrating technology to different economic sectors, which has externalities or spillover effects on performance levels or GDP contributions. Second, ICT has aided in the remodeling of industrial operations, the development of systems, and the enhancement of information interchange both nationally and internationally. Thirdly, ICT has made it easier for those who are less fortunate to sustain their way of life. Fourthly, the development of e-government, e-finance, and e-commerce have contributed to the transformation of the way services are provided (Oyebanji et al., 2022, pp. 237-238).

The examination concerning economic forces, ICT influence, and economic growth have not existed without disparities. For instance, authors mainly focus on a limited sector or specific country. Notably, Asongu and Nwachukwu (2019) concentrated only on the impact of ICT, on the financial sector development. Garcia et al. (2016) examined only the link between ICT and the service sector without considering the influence of external factors. And Su et al. (2019) only attributed an exclusive focus on the influence of economic forces on labor participation. What is more, previous studies never investigated various sectors in the same paper. Authors have the tendency to separate sectorial analysis, for example, there is a scarcity of research comparing the service with the manufacturing sector or agriculture with the service sector, and so on. Accordingly, this paper examines the potential of economic forces and information and communications technology in affecting the sectorial growth of the East Asia region. Consequently, in order to investigate this case, the paper selected three different sectors namely, manufacturing, service, and agricultural sectors as proxies for sectorial growth. What is more, the ARDL approach and Granger causality test are used to observe the long-run and short-run estimates as well the direction of the relationships.

The format of this article is described in the following. The available literature is reviewed in the second part. The third section provides information on the sources and usage of the data as well as the econometric model. The fourth section interprets the empirical findings. The paper is concluded in the fifth section.

2. Literature review

The academic has accorded the factors that influence economic expansion a lot of emphasis. Within the last several years, development and research (R&D) and technology-based information and communication (ICT) have become more significant engines of economic development, according to a variety of conceptual and empirical frameworks. ICT's significant contribution to increased economic output, corporate profit growth, and the creation of high-value employment has led certain nations to step up their R&D spending and introduce new ICT systems. These expenditures have given rise to innovative ICT advancements that have accelerated economic expansion globally (Nair et al., 2020, pp. 1-2)

Since ICT and R&D have a favorable multiplier effect on economic growth, nations and business sectors all over the world have increased their R&D expenditures in the globalized era (Freire-Seren, 2001, pp. 20-21). According to current data by the European Commission and Organization for Economics and Development (OECD), the largest 2000 Technology transfer investors are driving advancements in the ICT sector, where over 75% of them have ICT copyrights and some other 60% have ICT concepts (Daiko et al., 2017). These expenditures and inventions have helped countries all around the world's economies flourish.

ICT is a term used to describe the convergence and interaction of operating systems, telecommunications, technology, networks, and information providers that have an impact on people, businesses, and the market in general. The increased use of ICT has resulted in lower communication prices, which has eventually aided in the dissemination of information and data. ICT is a crucial driver of economic progress, particularly in modern nations, and the present embodiment of the technology transformation (Farhadi et al., 2012, pp. 1-2). The use of the web and mobile devices over the past couple of decades has sped up the spread of ICT technologies. ICT development has connected economies throughout the world. Via international supply chains and metropolitan areas, it is gradually integrating its systemic framework and technical infrastructure into complex, bidirectional interconnections that span from the individual's micro-level establishment to the worldwide platform. As a result of the success and emergence of ICT-enabled connectivity groups in these countries, markets in the twenty-first century have become interlinked with urban centers (Majeed and Ayub, 2018, p. 444).

The majority of authors believe that ICT advancement is crucial for bettering living circumstances, fostering innovation, and fostering entrepreneurship and economic progress. ICT can contribute to local inclusion and trade efficiency. Additionally, it makes knowledge and data exchange, global awareness, and financial activity easier. ICT also improves worker productivity and competencies, which have a positive indirect impact on economic development, as well as commerce and banking improvement. ICT also has an impact on other significant economic sectors, like e-business, e-trading, and e-banking. By optimizing information availability, minimizing possible business segregation, and lowering high admission prices, e-commerce is cutting travel management, market discovery, and communication expenses as well as addressing many exporters' and manufacturers' limits (Xing, 2018, pp. 566-567).

2.1. An overview of the sectoral growth

The manufacturing sector has several positive effects that are essential for economic change and perform a pivotal function in the contemporary economy. In terms of growth in proportion to GDP intake, the manufacturing industry is notably significant in the urbanization process. Because of the sector's potential role as a driver of development, urbanization, industrialization, and technological changes, as well as a provider of skilled employment and a source of beneficial spillover and positive externalities, the manufacturing sector is of particular relevance in this research.

The manufacturing industry in East Asia has developed over the period and now encompasses a broad variety of economic operations, including the refining of petroleum, the production of cement, fresh vegetables, beverages, and nicotine, the manufacture of textiles, clothing, and shoes, the manufacture of papermaking products, the production of chemicals and pharmaceuticals, the production of non-metallic goods, the production of polycarbonate and plastic products, the production of electric power and internet-based products, the production of basic metals like iron and steel (Kehinde et al., 2019, pp. 53-54).

Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), specifically, are serving a significant role in boosting the economic growth of Asian nations as they have become more prominent in the international economy Dey et al. (2022, pp. 2-3). According to Penélope and Thirlwall (2013), manufacturing possesses the traits that enable growth for two principal reasons. First, overall constant and dynamic returns are increasing for manufacturing, but returns for land-based industries and small services are dropping. Second, when the manufacturing industry expands job opportunities increase in comparison to other industries.

Okon and Osesie (2017, pp. 11-13), examined the impact of the manufacturing sector on Nigeria's economic development during 1981 to 2015 using the ordinary least square (OLS) approach. The paper employed the preceding factors as the dependent and independent variables in its analysis of manufacturing output, government spending, investment rate, and money supply: gross domestic product, manufacturing output, government expenditure, investment rate, and money supply. According to the report, the main factors influencing economic development in Nigeria are an investment, technology, and the industrial sector's production. The findings also indicated that neither the workforce nor the caliber of organizations had any bearing on economic growth.

Rioba (2014, pp. 34-35) looked at how crucial the manufacturing sector is to Kenya's economic development. Time-series data from 1971 to 2013 were used in the study. The analyses' dependent variables were the growth rates of manufacturing employment, non-manufacturing output, and manufacturing output. Using the standard least squares approach, the data were examined. The study found a correlation between manufacturing output and economic development in Kenya, but it was not strong enough to support further expansion.

Another research emphasizes the position and significance of the Romanian industry, particularly the manufacturing sector, as well as its effects on labor and long-term growth. The study's findings indicate that Romania has been in a loss of manufacturing jobs process

for more than 20 years. Manufacturing was able to continue to be the foundation of the Romanian sector and the overall economy after 2000 as the severity of the loss of manufacturing jobs diminished. Romanian manufacturing has significant challenges due to its poor worker efficiency and low level of high- and medium-tech industrial operations (Herman, 2016, p. 982).

The expansion of service sectors and the significant shift in employment from manufacturing to the service sector are two additional significant aspects of East Asia's prosperity. The well-known empirical observation that has been modeled demonstrates that there is a favorable correlation between the percentage of services in GDP (Eichengreen and Gupta, 2013).

Another empirical investigation with a concentration on the Indian service industry shows that the sector accounts for more than 55 percent of India's Gross domestic product. In many respects, the growth of services as the most vibrant sector of the Indian economy exceedingly even the conventional sectors have been referred to as a revolution. The Indian service sector serves a growing number of overseas (outsourcing) customers in addition to serving the sizable Indian market. This has accelerated even further as a result of rising globalization and improved technology-enabled enhanced communication. Along with serving a significant local market, Indian service companies also deliver a variety of services to numerous overseas companies at lower prices (Idris and Naqshbandi, 2018, p. 169).

Numerous research has objectively looked at how FDI affects the growth of the service sector, and their findings have also varied. Agya and Wunuji (2014, p. 59) discovered a two-way causal relationship between the expansion of the service sector and FDI influx. They discovered that FDI supports the growth of the services sector by giving both monetary and technical aid, but as this sector expands, it also increases the influx of FDI from overseas. They contend that FDI investment into the service sector will raise service performance. Parallel to how it will be able to draw more FDI from overseas as it grows more profitable.

Additionally, a number of studies have shown the beneficial impact of trade openness on the expansion of the service sector. Singh and Kaur (2014, pp. 401-405) contend that trade openness has a particularly good impact on the expansion of the service sector. They claim that as trade becomes more open, the proportion of services in global commerce will rise. El Khoury and Savvides (2006, pp. 5-7) discovered that when trade is more open and the trading nation has a greater rate of per capita earnings, the percentage of services in trade volume will raise. However, when the trading nation has a lower rate of per capita income, the proportion of commodities in trade volume will significantly raise at the expense of the share of services in total trade.

Hamidov et al. (2016) examined the effects of agricultural land usage in five Central Asian nations between 2008 and 2013 by analyzing 362 papers. Owing to its position, Central Asia is crucial both geopolitically and strategically. China, the Middle East, and Europe

are connected commercially via the nations of Central Asia. Because it contributes between 20 and 50% of the working force and accounts for 10 to 45% of the national GDP, agriculture is one of the key economic sectors in Central Asian nations.

The agriculture industry is another crucial one for any country. For instance, this sector is crucial to the expansion of the economies of most MENA nations, yet these nations are located in the driest and most water-scarce region of the globe, and many of them, particularly those in the Mediterranean region, are heavily reliant on agriculture. As a result, the influence of the least developed industry on the region's economies varies greatly, for instance, from roughly 3.2 percent in Saudi Arabia to 13.4 percent in Egypt. Increased automation and substantial irrigation have allowed for the vast cultivation of high-value cash commodities, such as fruits, vegetables, grains, and glucose (Abdelmadjid, 2019, p. 3).

Bakari and Mabrouki (2018, p.10), looked into the connection between agricultural commerce and economic development in four North African nations between 1982 and 2016. Frameworks with fixed and random effects were employed. The research showed that Economic output, capital accumulation, and agricultural exports all positively affect economic growth, with the exception of agricultural imports, which had an insignificant sign. They claimed that in order to offset the number of imports, the agricultural sector needs to be developed and expenditures committed.

Using the ARDL model Fayçal and Ali (2016, p. 112) looked at the link between economic development in Algeria between 1970 and 2014 and government assistance for the agriculture sector. Additionally, they came to the conclusion that overall agricultural assistance, irrespective of how it relates to output and suppliers, has a beneficial long-term impact on agricultural efficiency development and economic growth.

In a study conducted by Dirir (2022, p. 23), he performed panel data from 2002 to 2022 on eight nations to estimate the number of agricultural exports. The research found that all other factors had a notable and substantial impact on agricultural exports throughout the models, with the exception of agricultural irrigated land and yearly freshwater withdrawals in agriculture.

Faridi (2012, p. 143) used a VECM model and evaluated the long-term relationship between Pakistan's GDP, agricultural exports, and non-agricultural exports from 1972 to 2008. He discovered that the capital value, employment levels, and non-agricultural exports all significantly and positively impact economic growth, suggesting that an increase of only one unit in any of these factors might increase GDP's velocity.

3. Data, model, and methodology

3.1. Data source and description

The current study examines the potential of macroeconomic forces and information and communications technology in affecting sectorial growth. Hereby, the paper employs annual time series data varying from 2000 to 2021 with the regard to East Asia and the Pacific as a focus region. The selection of this region is because of the dramatic evolution after the Second World War and the 1997 crisis. This evolution is called the East Asian economic miracle, which was achieved due to low levels of government spending and taxes, exceptionally high asset accumulation by Keynesian criteria, consistent overabundance in government revenues, and a minimal welfare state. More importantly, the prominent technological development of the region contributed to sustaining economic growth.

Based on this fact, the study considered three different sectors namely manufacturing, services, and agriculture to assess sectoral growth. As a result, we consider indicators such as Manufacturing value-added, Services value-added, and Agriculture value-added as proxies for the three sectors. What is more, the study is considering factors such as fixed telephone subscriptions, and Mobile cellular subscriptions as proxies for ICT measurement. Further, various macroeconomic forces notably, Gross fixed capital formation, General government final consumption expenditure, Population growth, and the trade of each sector are selected. Within this scope, to carry on with the examination Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model and Granger causality test are performed to capture the long-run and short-run dynamic relationship among the variables. As well as to determine the direction of these relationships.

All the information was extracted from the World Bank Indicators.

Table 1. Description of variables

Variable	Abbreviation	Description	Measurement	Proxy
Dependent	MA	Manufacturing growth	Manufacturing, value added (% of GDP)	Sectorial growth
	VA	Service growth	Services, value added (% of GDP)	
	AV	Agricultural growth	Agriculture, value added (% of GDP)	
Independent	FT	Fixed telephone subscriptions	Fixed telephone subscriptions per 100 people	Information and communications technology
	MC	Mobile cellular subscriptions	Mobile cellular subscriptions per 100 people	
Independent	MI	Manufacturing import	Manufactures imports (% of merchandise imports)	Macroeconomic Forces
	MX	Manufacturing export	Manufactures exports (% of merchandise exports)	
	SI	Service import	Service import in us\$	
	SE	Service export	Service export in us\$	
	AE	Agricultural export	Agricultural (% of merchandise exports)	
	AI	Agricultural import	Agricultural (% of merchandise imports)	
	GF	Capital formation	Gross fixed capital formation (% of GDP)	
	GV	Total Expenditure	General government expenditure (% of GDP)	
	PG	Population growth	Population growth (annual %)	

3.2. Econometric model

The study applies the ARDL method for an empirical investigation of cointegration developed by (Pesaran and Shin, 1999). The ARDL approach has the benefit of not requiring the same degree of integration for each variable, which is a benefit. It is not particularly important if a factor has order zero, order one, or a variable order of integration. ARDL is preferable to traditional cointegration methods because of this property. Since the traditional cointegration techniques become unstable because the test's ability to detect cointegration is reduced when there is a mixed order of integration (Laurenceson and Chai, 2003). Accordingly, the empirical models for this study are divided into three categories: the manufacturing sector model, the service sector model, and the agricultural sector model.

$$MA = \int (FT, GF, GV, PG, MI, MX, MC) \quad (1)$$

$$VA = \int (FT, GF, GV, PG, SI, SE, MC) \quad (2)$$

$$AV = \int (FT, GF, GV, PG, AE, AI, MC) \quad (3)$$

We observe MA, VA, and AV which expresses the three different sectorial models employed in the study and FT, GF, GV, PG, MI, MX, SI, SE, AE, AI, and MC which denote the regressors. Once the above equations are log-linearized, the below equation is generated:

$$MA_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FT_t + \beta_2 GF_t + \beta_3 GV_t + \beta_4 PG_t + \beta_5 MI_t + \beta_6 AMX_t + \beta_7 MC_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

$$VA_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FT_t + \beta_2 GF_t + \beta_3 GV_t + \beta_4 PG_t + \beta_5 SI_t + \beta_6 SE_t + \beta_7 MC_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (5)$$

$$AV_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FT_t + \beta_2 GF_t + \beta_3 GV_t + \beta_4 PG_t + \beta_5 AE_t + \beta_6 AI_t + \beta_7 MC_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (6)$$

In these equations, β_0 is the constant, and ε_t is regarded as the equation's error term. The parameters of β_1 through β_7 are the coefficients that are utilized to calculate the different sectorial growth. Additionally, it is possible to compute both the short-run and long-run coefficients simultaneously. The preceding models were developed in order to establish ARDL bounds:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta MA_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_1 \Delta MA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_2 \Delta FT_{t-i} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_3 \Delta GF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_4 \Delta GV_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_5 \Delta PG_{t-i} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_6 \Delta MI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_7 \Delta MX_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_8 \Delta MC_{t-i} + \lambda_1 MA_{t-1} + \lambda_2 FT_{t-1} + \lambda_3 GF_{t-1} + \lambda_4 GV_{t-1} \\ & + \lambda_5 PG_{t-1} + \lambda_6 MI_{t-1} + \lambda_7 MX_{t-1} + \lambda_8 MC_{t-1} \varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta VA_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_1 \Delta VA_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_2 \Delta FT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_3 \Delta GF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_4 \Delta GV_{t-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_5 \Delta PG_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_6 \Delta SI_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_7 \Delta SE_{t-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_8 \Delta MC_{t-1} + \lambda_1 MA_{t-1} + \lambda_2 FT_{t-1} + \lambda_3 GF_{t-1} + \lambda_4 GV_{t-1} \\ & + \lambda_5 PG_{t-1} + \lambda_6 SI_{t-1} + \lambda_7 SE_{t-1} + \lambda_8 MC_{t-1} \varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta AV_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_1 \Delta AV_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_2 \Delta FT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_3 \Delta GF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_4 \Delta GV_{t-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_5 \Delta PG_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_6 \Delta AE_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_7 \Delta AI_{t-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=t}^p \alpha_8 \Delta MC_{t-1} + \lambda_1 MA_{t-1} + \lambda_2 FT_{t-1} + \lambda_3 GF_{t-1} + \lambda_4 GV_{t-1} \\ & + \lambda_5 PG_{t-1} + \lambda_6 AE_{t-1} + \lambda_7 AI_{t-1} + \lambda_8 MC_{t-1} \varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The α parameters in the equation denote the short-term relationship.

On the other hand, the λ symbol represents long-term relationships. Consequently, this approach tests the null hypothesis of no cointegration ($\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \lambda_4 = \lambda_5 = \lambda_6 = \lambda_7 = \lambda_8 = 0$) or the alternative hypothesis of cointegration ($\lambda_1 \neq \lambda_2 \neq \lambda_3 \neq \lambda_4 \neq \lambda_5 \neq \lambda_6 \neq \lambda_7 \neq \lambda_8 \neq 0$) based on the F-test. Additionally, this F-test was developed based on the relevance of the lower and upper bound values, which were primarily expressed by (Pesaran et al., 2001).

As a result, this method aids in providing pertinent information regarding whether the elements are cointegrated. Thus, if over a long period of time, the variables are cointegrated, an error correction model is used to estimate each variable's coefficient. The formulas are shown below.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta MA_t = & \gamma_0 + \sum_{i=t}^p \delta_i \Delta MA_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta FT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta GF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta GV_{t-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta PG_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta MI_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta MX_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta MC_{t-1} \\ & + \mu ECT_{t-1} + v_t \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta VA_t = \gamma_0 + \sum_{i=t}^p \delta_i \Delta VA_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta FT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta GF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta GV_{t-1} \\ + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta PG_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta SI_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta SE_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta MC_{t-1} \\ + \mu ECT_{t-1} + v_t \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta AG_t = \gamma_0 + \sum_{i=t}^p \delta_i \Delta AG_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta FT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta GF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta GV_{t-1} \\ + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta PG_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta AE_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta AI_{t-1} + \sum_{i=t}^p \phi_i \Delta MC_{t-1} \\ + \mu ECT_{t-1} + v_t \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

According to the overall models above, the parameters μ , reflect the speed of adjustment, and ECT stands for the error correction term.

3.3. Granger causality test

Additionally, it was intended to record how the different variables related to one another causally. The Granger causality test, recommended by (Granger, 1969), was performed to ascertain whether there is a causal link between the variables. Below a more comprehensive explanation of the model is provided:

$$X_t = \sum_{l=1}^p (a_{11,1} X_{t-1} + a_{12,1} Y_{t-1}) + \mu_t \quad (13)$$

$$Y_t = \sum_{l=1}^p (a_{21,1} X_{t-1} + a_{22,1} Y_{t-1}) + \epsilon_t \quad (14)$$

As presented in equation (13) and (14) is the model order, $a_{ij,1}$ ($i, j = 1, 2$) are the coefficients of the model, and μ_t and ϵ_t denotes the residuals. Ordinary least squares can be used to estimate the coefficients, and F tests can identify the Causality relationship between X and Y.

3.4. Unit root test

To ensure the stability and reliability of the data the study performed stationarity tests that consist of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (ADF) and the Phillips-Perron test (PP). Starting with the augmented Dickey-Fuller test, it assumes that u is a white noise error term. However, if u is autocorrelated we would need a drift version of the test which allows for higher-order lags. Accordingly, the test is augmented using p lags of the original series (Dickey and Fuller, 1979). Furthermore, the Phillips-Perron test corrects for any serial correlation and heteroskedasticity in the errors by some direct modification to the test statistics (Phillips and Perron, 1988). Below the equations for both tests are presented.

$$\Delta y_t = \psi y_{t-1} + \mu + \alpha t + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta \Delta y_{t-i} + u_t \quad (15)$$

$$\Delta y_t = \psi y_{t-1} + \mu^* + \delta t + u_t, \quad u_t \sim I(0), ARMA(p, q) \quad (16)$$

As per equation (15) p is used to augment the past autoregressive lags of the difference term. While μ and αt denotes the time trend parameter and also the intercept. In equation (16) ψy consist of the initial term of the data while the term u_t implies the stationarity at level $I(0)$. Additionally, μ^* expresses the intercept while δt denotes the time trend.

4. Findings analysis

The figure below provides an overview of the different sectoral growth in East Asian countries. Based on Figure 1, the manufacturing sector has continued to grow over the years reaching a peak of 24.8% in 2021 in comparison to other sectors. Next, the service sector appears to be decreased over the years from 60% to 55%. Interestingly, even with the rise of technological development and the prominent industrialization of East Asia, the agriculture sector has never stopped expanding during the last 21 years which illustrates the efforts of East Asian countries of promoting the agricultural sector.

Figure 1. An overview of East Asian sectorial growth

Source: Author's analysis.

The descriptive statistics enabled researchers to undertake an extensive analysis of the variables that affected the dependent variables in addition to guiding their trend analysis over the course of the period. Table 2 displays the descriptive statistics for the variables. Starting with the manufacturing sector the percentage of growth in that sector ranges from 22.99 to 24.75, with an average of 23.92. Next, the service sector reveals a minimum of 56.23% to a maximum of 60.66% and an average of 58.05%. Further, the agricultural sector exhibits a minimum growth of 4.44% and reaches a maximum growth of 6.08% over the years. All the variables have a positive kurtosis and low level of standard deviation which implies the absence of volatility among the variables. More importantly, all the variables are negatively skewed except VA, GV, MI, AE, and AI.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics

	MA	VA	AV	FT	GF	GV	PG
Median	23.92	58.05	5.47	8.61	31.90	16.2	0.73
Maximum	24.75	60.66	6.08	8.71	35.12	17.5	0.94
Minimum	22.99	56.23	4.44	8.45	27.47	15.3	0.26
Std. Dev.	0.48	1.42	0.54	0.08	2.77	0.50	0.14
Skewness	-0.01	0.31	-0.31	-0.2	-0.17	0.39	-1.40
Kurtosis	1.91	1.87	1.65	1.61	1.41	3.50	5.40
Jarque-Bera	1.07	1.52	2.03	1.91	2.41	0.79	12.49
	MI	MX	SI	SE	AE	AI	MC
Median	66.5	81.5	11.96	11.93	1.20	2.26	9.24
Maximum	75.5	84.1	12.17	12.11	1.61	3.24	9.48
Minimum	59.1	75.4	11.5	11.51	0.88	1.71	8.37
Std. Dev.	4.97	3.16	0.21	0.20	0.167	0.39	0.34
Skewness	0.20	-0.3	-0.47	-0.54	0.22	0.66	-0.75
Kurtosis	2.15	1.51	1.80	1.80	3.26	3.08	2.33
Jarque-Bera	0.81	2.46	2.126	2.38	0.25	1.61	2.47
Observation	22	22	22	22	22	22	22

Source: Author's analysis.

Another crucial method for getting assumptions between variables before they are approached is the correlation matrix.

In Table 3 the results for the manufacturing sector demonstrates a moderate positive correlation between FT, GF, SI, SE, AE, and MC with the manufacturing sector. Whereas, we observe a negative correlation between GV, PG, MI, and AI with the manufacturing sector. Similarly, we perceive a positive relationship between FT, GF, GV, SI, SE, and MC with the agricultural sector. This suggests, both the manufacturing and agricultural sector are correlated with the same ICT indicators and macroeconomic forces. However, the service sector display unidentical outcome. For instance, we detect a negative correlation between FT, GF, GV, SI, SE, AE, and MC with the service sector. Based on this result we comprehend that the service sector is negatively correlated with the factors that have a positive relationship with the manufacturing and agricultural sectors.

Table 3. Matrix of correlation

Variables	MA	VA	AV	FT	GF	GV	PG
MA	1	-0.63	0.48	0.38	0.31	-0.22	-0.19
VA	-0.63	1	-0.82	-0.38	-0.68	-0.15	0.17
AV	0.48	-0.82	1	0.02	0.88	0.59	-0.50
FT	0.38	-0.38	0.02	1	-0.24	-0.52	0.21
GF	0.31	-0.68	0.88	-0.24	1	0.72	-0.65
GV	-0.22	-0.15	0.59	-0.52	0.72	1	-0.62

Variables	MA	VA	AV	FT	GF	GV	PG
PG	-0.19	0.17	-0.50	0.21	-0.65	-0.62	1
MI	-0.64	0.91	-0.79	-0.37	-0.70	-0.23	0.32
MX	-0.51	0.79	-0.61	-0.58	-0.33	0.01	-0.14
SI	0.42	-0.75	0.88	-0.06	0.96	0.58	-0.64
SE	0.45	-0.78	0.89	-0.04	0.95	0.57	-0.64
AE	0.13	-0.04	-0.29	0.34	-0.50	-0.51	0.72
AI	-0.33	0.56	-0.75	-0.09	-0.80	-0.54	0.83
MC	0.40	-0.74	0.89	0.02	0.93	0.62	-0.69
Variables	MI	MX	SI	SE	AE	AI	MC
MA	-0.64	-0.51	0.42	0.45	0.13	-0.33	0.40
VA	0.91	0.79	-0.75	-0.78	-0.04	0.56	-0.74
AV	-0.79	-0.61	0.88	0.89	-0.29	-0.75	0.89
FT	-0.37	-0.58	-0.06	-0.04	0.34	-0.09	0.02
GF	-0.70	-0.33	0.96	0.95	-0.50	-0.80	0.93
GV	-0.23	0.01	0.58	0.57	-0.51	-0.54	0.62
PG	0.32	-0.14	-0.64	-0.64	0.72	0.83	-0.69
MI	1	0.74	-0.76	-0.79	-0.01	0.63	-0.75
MX	0.74	1	-0.39	-0.42	-0.34	0.24	-0.42
SI	-0.76	-0.39	1	0.99	-0.47	-0.85	0.98
SE	-0.79	-0.42	0.99	1	-0.44	-0.85	0.97
AE	-0.01	-0.34	-0.47	-0.44	1	0.71	-0.50
AI	0.63	0.24	-0.85	-0.85	0.71	1	-0.90
MC	-0.75	-0.42	0.98	0.97	-0.50	-0.90	1

Source: Author's analysis.

In order to ascertain whether the random walk assumption is present in the long-term fluctuated period information, the ADF and Phillip Perron test unit root tests are used.

Consequently, in accordance with Table 4, the outcome for both tests reveals that all the variables are stationary at first difference except for MA, and MC which displayed stationarity both at the level and first difference. Hence, we can proceed with the cointegration approach since the panel unit root test results indicate that certain variables are stationary at a level while others are stationary after the first difference and the variables did not reach the second difference.

Table 4. Unit root test

Variables	Panel A: Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (ADF) test				
	At level	Note	At first difference	Note	Decision
MA	-2.781*	Stationary	-4.748***	Stationary	I(0)I(1)
VA	-1.693	Not stationary	-2.772*	Stationary	I(1)
AV	-1.378	Not stationary	-3.632**	Stationary	I(1)
FT	-2.006	Not stationary	-3.217**	Stationary	I(1)
GF	-1.004	Not stationary	-4.350***	Stationary	I(1)
GV	-0.983	Not stationary	-3.527**	Stationary	I(1)
PG	1.234	Not stationary	-2.843*	Stationary	I(1)
SI	-2.020	Not stationary	-3.236**	Stationary	I(1)
SE	-1.846	Not stationary	-3.247**	Stationary	I(1)
MI	-1.803	Not stationary	-3.086**	Stationary	I(1)
MX	-1.201	Not stationary	-2.728*	Stationary	I(1)
AI	-1.880	Not stationary	-3.358**	Stationary	I(1)
AE	-1.501	Not stationary	-4.050***	Stationary	I(1)
MC	-2.547	Not stationary	-4.223***	Stationary	I(1)

Variables	Panel B: Phillips-Perron test (ADF) test				
	At level	Note	At first difference	Note	Decision
MA	-2.524	Not stationary	-3.367**	Stationary	I (1)
VA	-1.318	Not stationary	-3.417**	Stationary	I (1)
AV	-1.516	Not stationary	-3.625**	Stationary	I (1)
FT	-1.779	Not stationary	-4.032***	Stationary	I (1)
GF	-0.394	Not stationary	-3.381**	Stationary	I (1)
GV	-1.604	Not stationary	-4.763***	Stationary	I (1)
PG	-1.036	Not stationary	-3.181**	Stationary	I (1)
SI	-1.767	Not stationary	-4.367***	Stationary	I (1)
SE	-1.658	Not stationary	-5.133***	Stationary	I (1)
MI	-1.600	Not stationary	-3.863***	Stationary	I (1)
MX	-1.428	Not stationary	-5.008***	Stationary	I (1)
AI	-1.879	Not stationary	-3.134**	Stationary	I (1)
AE	-1.455	Not stationary	-4.742***	Stationary	I (1)
MC	-10.621***	Stationary	-2.576	Not stationary	I (0) I (1)

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively

Source: Author's analysis.

In order to create an effective analysis, the Autoregressive distributed lag test method will assist us to assess the short- and long-run elasticities between variables. With that in mind, the ARDL bounds prediction of Table 5 demonstrates that all the models contain factors that are serially correlated and exhibit long-run relationships. Accounting for causality and partial equilibrium correlations seen between variables, the F-statistics are noteworthy for all the models at the 1% level with 9.42, 4.61, and 4.22 values that are underneath the I (1) upper limit. As a result, we will proceed with the error correction and long-run estimation.

Table 5. ARDL bounds testing estimates

Significance	I (0) Bound	I (1) Bound
10%	1.92	2.89
5%	2.17	3.21
2.5%	2.43	3.51
1%	2.73	3.9
Model 1. Manufacturing sector		
Test Statistic	Value	K
F-Statistic	9.4245	7
Model 2. Service sector		
Test Statistic	Value	K
F-Statistic	4.6109	7
Model 3. Agricultural sector		
Test Statistic	Value	K
F-Statistic	4.2216	7

Source: Author's analysis.

Table 6 expresses both the long-run and short-run cointegration for the manufacturing sector. Additionally, the model shows that the error correction term (called Adjustment) is statistically significant and negative (-1.41). This statement demonstrates the rate at which equilibrium is restored following a shock to the long-run causal relation. Based on the short-run results, we observe that FT, GF, GV, PG, MI, and MX are negatively affecting the growth of the manufacturing sector. This implies that fixed telephone subscription, gross capital formation, government expenditure, population growth, and both importation and exportation are decreasing the growth of the manufacturing sector. Simultaneously, the long-run result displays an identical outcome to the short-run estimation. For instance, we

perceive the level of fixed telephone subscription, gross capital formation, government expenditure and the percentage of trade are reducing the manufacturing sector by 9.6%, 0.3%, 1.1%, -0.12%, and -0.13% respectively.

Table 6. Model 1 manufacturing sector

Sector: Manufacturing value added				
Selected Model: ARDL (1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1)				
Short-run cointegrating Form				
Variables	Coefficients	St. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
$\Delta MA(-1)$	-1.418180***	0.380420	-3.727930	0.0058
ΔFT	-13.74944**	4.098137	-3.355047	0.0100
ΔGF	-0.233315	0.199166	-1.171459	0.2751
$\Delta GF(-1)$	-0.548084*	0.256178	-2.139463	0.0648
ΔGV	-1.581604***	0.351740	-4.496519	0.0020
ΔPG	-3.080948**	1.166113	-2.642066	0.0296
ΔMI	-0.077112	0.042415	-1.818041	0.1066
$\Delta MI(-1)$	-0.175074**	0.056355	-3.106625	0.0145
ΔMX	-0.097163	0.056570	-1.717567	0.1242
$\Delta MX(-1)$	-0.191729***	0.050965	-3.761929	0.0055
ΔMC	-9.950752	5.961275	-1.669232	0.1336
$\Delta MC(-1)$	0.994432	1.852337	0.536853	0.6060
$ECT(-1)$	-1.418180***	0.108884	-13.02466	0.0000
Long-run coefficients				
Variables	Coefficients	St. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
FT	-9.695132***	2.515552	-3.854077	0.0048
GF	-0.386470**	0.150610	-2.566037	0.0333
GV	-1.115235***	0.206040	-5.412719	0.0006
PG	-2.172466	1.267692	-1.713718	0.1249
MI	-0.123450**	0.039900	-3.093946	0.0148
MX	-0.135193**	0.048121	-2.809443	0.0229
MC	0.701203	1.158882	0.605068	0.5619
Constant	152.4187***	34.47137	4.421603	0.0022

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

Source: Author's analysis.

The outcome of the service sector growth is illustrated in Table 7. In correspondence with the results, we detect that both in the long run and short run factors such as population growth and service importation have an influence on the service sector. This suggests the level of East Asia population growth decreases the service growth by 3.45%, whereas the importation rate of service increases the service sector by 13%. The rest of the variables exhibit no evidence of cointegration.

Table 7. Model 2 service sector

Sector: Service value added				
Selected Model: ARDL (2, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0)				
Short-run cointegrating Form				
Variables	Coefficients	St. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
$\Delta VA(-1)$	0.304392	0.328472	0.926690	0.3849
$\Delta VA(-2)$	-1.409062***	0.302132	-4.663735	0.0023
ΔFT	30.30267	12.44349	2.435223	0.0451
$\Delta FT(-1)$	-4.974293	4.354659	-1.142292	0.2909
ΔGF	-0.402639	0.234624	-1.716105	0.1299
ΔGV	0.243764	0.669664	0.364009	0.7266
ΔPG	-4.863056*	2.498893	-1.946084	0.0927
ΔSI	7.857509	11.74006	0.669290	0.5248
$\Delta SI(-1)$	18.93500	10.83533	1.747524	0.1240

Sector: Service value added				
Selected Model: ARDL (2, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0)				
Short-run cointegrating Form				
Variables	Coefficients	St. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
Δ SE	-7.052522	6.267885	-1.125184	0.2976
Δ SE(-1)	-14.36116	7.920713	-1.813114	0.1127
Δ MC	-3.927921	6.931242	-0.566698	0.5886
ECT(-1)	-1.409062***	0.149424	-9.429979	0.0000
Long-run coefficients				
Variables	Coefficients	St. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
FT	-3.530217	3.382056	-1.043808	0.3313
GF	-0.285750	0.151112	-1.890978	0.1005
GV	0.172997	0.468396	0.369340	0.7228
PG	-3.451272**	1.371209	-2.516956	0.0400
SI	13.43802*	6.419832	2.093204	0.0746
SE	-10.19200*	5.195188	-1.961815	0.0906
MC	-2.787614	4.725039	-0.589966	0.5738
Constant	83.58436	65.61847	1.273793	0.2434

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

Source: Author's analysis.

Table 8 presents both the long-run and short-run estimates for the agricultural sector growth. Within this scope, the table shows that in the short-run FT, PG, AE, and AI have an impact on the growth of the agricultural sector. Nevertheless, this impact differs across factors for instance the level of fixed telephone subscription, and agricultural importation reduce the agricultural sector growth by 4.32% and 3.20%. Whilst, the population growth, and the rate of agricultural exportation in East Asian countries increase the agricultural sector growth by 2.9% and 3.3%. What is more in the long-run result we discern that government expenditure and the rate of agricultural exportation increase the value generated by the agricultural sector.

Table 8. Model 3 Agricultural sector

Sector: Agricultural value added				
Selected Model: ARDL (1, 1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0)				
Short-run cointegrating Form				
Variables	Coefficients	St. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
AV(-1)	-0.898563***	0.218988	-4.103254	0.0046
Δ FT	-9.936182**	3.940336	-2.521658	0.0397
Δ FT(-1)	-4.323338*	2.163945	-1.997896	0.0859
Δ GF	-0.142361	0.105821	-1.345293	0.2205
Δ GV	0.121890	0.141464	0.861632	0.4174
Δ GV(-1)	0.343888	0.205189	1.675955	0.1377
Δ PG	0.349543	1.907456	0.183251	0.8598
Δ PG(-1)	2.940861*	1.321090	2.226088	0.0613
Δ AE	0.735459	0.855641	0.859541	0.4185
Δ AE(-1)	3.323559**	1.052920	3.156516	0.0160
Δ AI	-0.663077	0.844908	-0.784792	0.4583
Δ AI(-1)	-3.202281**	1.194758	-2.680276	0.0315
Δ MC	-0.370388	1.048810	-0.353150	0.7344
ECT(-1)	-0.898563***	0.103192	-8.70772	0.0001
Long-run coefficients				
Variables	Coefficients	St. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
FT	-4.811390	2.583191	-1.862576	0.1048
GF	-0.158432	0.117109	-1.352858	0.2182
GV	0.382709*	0.199222	1.921021	0.0962
PG	3.272848*	1.404486	2.330282	0.0526

Sector: Agricultural value added				
Selected Model: ARDL (1, 1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0)				
AE	3.698748**	1.361880	2.715913	0.0299
AI	-3.563779	1.491127	-2.389990	0.0482
MC	-0.412200	1.194823	-0.344988	0.7402
Constant	51.05213	30.31491	1.684060	0.1360

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

Source: Author's analysis.

The Granger causality test uncovers a sequence of associations among factors, resulting in long-term economic remedies. The Granger causality estimates in Table 9 reveal various associations among the factors. For instance, starting with the manufacturing growth model there are unidirectional causal relationships between fixed telephone subscriptions and manufacturing sector growth. Also, between population growth and manufacturing sector growth.

Next, there is relationship between the manufacturing importation and exportation and manufacturing sector growth. This suggests that fixed telephone subscriptions, population growth, and manufacturing importation and exportation have prominent associations with the manufacturing sector growth.

Similarly, in Table 10 we perceive various unidirectional causal relationships in terms of the service sector. In particular between Fixed telephone subscriptions and service sector growth. Between population growth and service sector growth. And between service exportation and service sector growth. These outcomes imply that the service sector and manufacturing sector possess a causal relationship with the same factors.

Finally, in Table 11 which portrays the agricultural sector, the result showcases a unidirectional causal relationship with gross capital formation, agricultural importation, and Mobile cellular subscriptions. The rest of the variables demonstrated no evidence of causality with examined sectors.

Table 9. The Granger causality estimates for the manufacturing sector

Model 1. Manufacturing sector		
Hypothesis	Prob.	Decision
FT Granger cause MA	0.0030**	Unidirectional
MA Granger cause FT	0.8682	
GF Granger cause MA	0.4179	No causality
MA Granger cause GF	0.6053	
GV Granger cause MA	0.2795	No causality
MA Granger cause GV	0.1955	
PG Granger cause MA	0.0925*	Unidirectional
MA Granger cause PG	0.3991	
MI Granger cause MA	0.0581*	Unidirectional
MA Granger causes MI	0.5681	
MX Granger cause MA	0.0185**	Unidirectional
MA Granger cause MX	0.1728	
MC Granger cause MA	0.3311	No causality
MA Granger cause MC	0.1548	

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

Source: Author's analysis.

Table 10. *The Granger causality estimates for the service sector*

Model 2. Service sector		
Hypothesis	Prob.	Decision
FT Granger cause VA	0.0115**	Unidirectional
VA Granger cause FT	0.2210	
GF Granger cause VA	0.1308	No causality
VA Granger cause GF	0.3494	
GV Granger cause VA	0.5974	No causality
VA Granger cause GV	0.2417	
PG Granger cause VA	0.0528*	Unidirectional
VA Granger cause PG	0.7283	
SI Granger cause VA	0.6663	No causality
VA Granger causes SI	0.1497	
SE Granger cause VA	0.6767	Unidirectional
VA Granger cause SE	0.0567*	
MC Granger cause MA	0.8814	No causality
MA Granger cause MC	0.2884	

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

Source: Author's analysis.

Table 11. *The Granger causality estimates for the agricultural sector*

Model 3. Agricultural sector		
Hypothesis	Prob.	Decision
FT Granger cause AV	0.298	No causality
AV Granger cause FT	0.262	
GF Granger cause AV	0.085*	Unidirectional
AV Granger cause GF	0.413	
GV Granger cause AV	0.967	No causality
AV Granger cause GV	0.240	
PG Granger cause AV	0.208	No causality
AV Granger cause PG	0.998	
AE Granger cause AV	0.707	No causality
AV Granger causes AE	0.202	
AI Granger cause AV	0.253	Unidirectional
AV Granger cause AI	0.001**	
MC Granger cause AV	0.042**	Unidirectional
AV Granger cause MC	0.983	

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

Source: Author's analysis.

The final problem we discuss has to do with how well our ARDL models fit. A number of stability and diagnostic tests were run for this purpose. Heteroscedasticity, conditional heteroscedasticity, Ramsey's RESET test, and normality are all examined using diagnostic tests.

Therefore, in accordance with Table 12, the provided models have no evidence of heteroskedasticity based on the Breusch-Godfrey and Harvey tests. Also, the Ramsey RESET test's results demonstrate that the proposed model is free of misspecification errors. While the Jarque-Bera for normality confirms all the models are normally distributed. Hereby, the ARDL bounds test yield objective and reliable estimates. Additionally, the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ plot demonstrates that all the models are stable because the graph is contained inside the 5% level of significance limits. See Figure 2.

Table 12. *The diagnostic test*

Sectorial Models	Specification	Ramsey RESET Test	Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Godfrey	Heteroskedasticity Test: Harvey	Jarque-Bera (normality)
Manufacturing sector	F-statistic	0.3537	0.7283	1.442	0.3638
	Prob.	0.7340	0.7007	0.3078	0.8336
Service sector	F-statistic	2.9611	0.6644	2.0660	3.2434
	Prob.	0.1418	0.7454	0.1712	0.1975
Agricultural sector	F-statistic	0.6213	2.0225	0.9683	2.0259
	Prob.	0.5572	0.1775	0.5456	0.3631
Decision		No omitted variables	No evidence of Heteroskedasticity	No evidence of Heteroskedasticity	All the models are normally distributed

Source: Author’s analysis.

Figure 2. *CUSUM and CUSUMQ for sectorial growth*

Source: Author’s analysis.

5. Conclusion

Asia, the biggest and most populated of the hemispheres, has had the fastest rate of global wealth growth since 1960. In reality, this increase has not happened across the region at the same rate. The eastern half of Asia, which includes China, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, China, and Thailand, outperformed the western region overall during this time period, though there were also regional differences in performance. The Philippines had the worst performance, growing at a rate of around 2 percent annually in per capita terms, almost in line with the standard of non-Asian nations. Better performance was seen in China, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, and Thailand, which had growth rates of 3-5 percent.

Due to advanced manufacturing output and affordable intermediate input manufacturing, East Asian expansion has been notably significant in terms of its dominance of global markets. This increase in performance has been supported by rapidly growing real salaries, significant and increasing expenditures in human resources, and a more equitable dispersion of income. Measures of healthcare, education, and other socioeconomic metrics have surged as unemployment has significantly declined in East Asian nations. In reality, per capita income in several of these nations has increased so quickly that they are no longer considered emerging.

Within this scope, the current paper examined the influence of selected macroeconomic factors and ICT on the sectorial growth of the East Asian and Pacific region from the period 2000 to 2021. To proceed with the study, we considered three different sectors namely manufacturing, services, and agriculture as proxies for sectoral growth. What is more, the paper performed the ARDL approach and Granger causality test to capture the long-run and short-run dynamic relationship among the variables. As well as to determine the direction of these relationships.

Based on the findings we discovered numerous outcomes across the three different sectors. Starting with the manufacturing sector, both the short-run and long-run results revealed that fixed telephone subscription, gross capital formation, government expenditure, population growth, and both importation and exportation are decreasing the growth of the manufacturing sector. Next, the service sector model displayed that the level of East Asia's population decreases the service growth, whereas the importation rate of service increases the service sector in both the short and long-run estimates. Moreover, model three, which evaluates the region's agricultural growth, showed that the extent of fixed telephone subscriptions and agricultural imports restrain the sector's expansion. On the other hand, the expansion of the East Asian population and the rate of agricultural exporting contribute to the expansion of the agricultural industry. Furthermore, we discover that government spending and the rate of agricultural exporting raise the value produced by the agricultural sector in the long term. Finally, the Granger causality test demonstrated that fixed telephone subscriptions, population growth, and manufacturing importation and exportation have prominent associations with the manufacturing sector growth. Simultaneously, the service sector and manufacturing sector possess a causal relationship with the same factors.

Finally, the agricultural sector showcased a unidirectional causal relationship with gross capital formation, agricultural importation, and Mobile cellular subscriptions. The rest of the variables demonstrated no evidence of causality with examined sectors.

The current findings can provide evidence, especially to developing countries and policymakers about the fact of capitalizing on particular macroeconomic factors and technologies to assist the sectoral growth of their country. Additionally, since Asia is a diverse and vibrant continent in terms of economy and resources, the paper offers an overview of three different sectors in East Asia.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

References

- Abdelmadjid, S.H., 2019. The Impact of Agricultural Sector on Economic Growth in MENA Countries: A Panel Econometric Approach. *Knowledge of Aggregates Magazine*, 5(2), pp. 142-157.
- Agya, A.A., and Wunuji, E.A., 2014. Effect of foreign direct investment on China economic growth: a Granger Causality approach. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, 2(4), pp. 56-63.
- Asongu, S.A. and Nwachukwu, J.C., 2019. ICT, financial sector development and financial access. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 10(2), pp. 465-490.
- Bakari, S. and Mabrouki, M., 2018. The Impact of Agricultural Trade on Economic Growth in North Africa: Econometric Analysis by Static Gravity Model. *University Library of Munich, Germany*, (No. 85116).
- Daiko, T., Dernis, H., Dosso, M., Gkotsis, P., Squicciarini, M., Tuebke, A. and Vezzani, A., 2017. *World top R&D investors: Industrial property strategies in the digital economy* (No. JRC107015). Joint Research Centre (Seville site).
- Dey, P.K., Malesios, C., Chowdhury, S., Saha, K., Budhwar, P. and De, D., 2022. Adoption of circular economy practices in small and medium-sized enterprises: Evidence from Europe. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 248, 108496.
- Dickey, D.A. and Fuller, W.A., 1979. Distribution of the estimators for autoregressive time series with a unit root. *Journal of the American statistical association*, 74(366a), pp. 427-431 <<https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1979.1048253>>
- Dirir, S.A., 2022. Study on the Factors that Stimulate Agricultural Exportation in the Largest Producing Countries of Agricultural Commodities. *Journal of Applied Agricultural Economics and Policy Analysis*, 5(1), pp. 19-24.
- Eichengreen, B. and Gupta, P., 2013. The two waves of service-sector growth. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 65(1), pp. 96-123.
- Farhadi, M., Ismail, R. and Fooladi, M., 2012. Information and communication technology use and economic growth. *PloS one*, 7(11), e48903.

- Faridi, M.Z., 2012. Contribution of agricultural exports to economic growth in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences (PJCSS)*, 6(1), pp. 133-146.
- Fayçal, M. and Ali, H.M., 2016. Economic growth and government subventions for the agriculture sector in Algeria: An ARDL model. *Arab Economic and Business Journal*, 11(2), pp. 105-114.
- Freire-Seren, M.J., 2001. R&D expenditure in an endogenous growth model. *Journal of Economics*, 74(1), pp. 39-62.
- Garcia Manjon, J.V., Mompo, R. and Redoli, J., 2016. Accelerating innovation in small and medium-sized enterprises in the ICT services sector. *SAGE Open*, 6(3), 2158244016670198.
- Granger, C.W., 1969. Investigating causal relations by econometric models and cross-spectral methods. *Econometrica: journal of the Econometric Society*, pp. 424-438 <<https://doi.org/10.2307/1912791>>
- Hamidov, A., Helming, K. and Balla, D., 2016. Impact of agricultural land use in Central Asia: a review. *Agronomy for sustainable development*, 36(1), pp. 1-23.
- Herman, E., 2016. The importance of the manufacturing sector in the Romanian economy. *Procedia Technology*, 22, pp. 976-983.
- Idris, F. and Naqshbandi, M.M., 2018. Exploring competitive priorities in the service sector: evidence from India. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*.
- Kehinde, E.J., Abiodun, S.O. and Dauda, O.Y., 2019. Capital inflows, manufacturing exports and economic growth in Nigeria: A threshold regression analysis. *Journal of Economics and International Finance*, 11(5), pp. 52-59.
- El Khoury, A.C. and Savvides, A., 2006. Openness in services trade and economic growth. *Economics Letters*, 92(2), pp. 277-283.
- Laurenceson, J. and Chai, J.C., 2003. *Financial reform and economic development in China*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Lee, J.W. and Hong, K., 2010. Economic growth in Asia: determinants and prospects. *Asian Development Bank Economics Working Paper Series* (220).
- Lee, J.W. and McKibbin, W.J., 2018. Service sector productivity and economic growth in Asia. *Economic modeling*, 74, pp. 247-263.
- Lucas Jr, R.E., 1993. Making a miracle. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, pp. 251-272.
- Majeed, M.T. and Ayub, T., 2018. Information and communication technology (ICT) and economic growth nexus: A comparative global analysis. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences (PJCSS)*, 12(2), pp. 443-476.
- Nair, M., Pradhan, R.P. and Arvin, M.B., 2020. Endogenous dynamics between R&D, ICT, and economic growth: Empirical evidence from the OECD countries. *Technology in Society*, 62, 101315.
- Okon, E.O. and Osesie, S.W., 2017. Hazards of the manufacturing sector and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences, Humanities, and Education*, 1(1), pp. 1-16.
- Oyebanji, I.J., Olanipekun, D.B. and Kleynhans, E.P., 2022. The Potential of Information and Communication Technologies to Generate International Trade in Africa. *Managing Global Transitions*, 20(3).
- Penélope, P. and Thirlwall, A.P., 2013. A new interpretation of Kaldor's first growth law for open developing economies. *University of Kent KDPE School of Economics Discussion Papers*, 1312.

- Pesaran, M.H. and Shin, Y., 1999. An Autoregressive Distributed Lag Modeling Approach to Cointegration Analysis, In: Strom, S., Holly, A., Diamond, P. (Eds.), Centennial Volume of Rangar Frisch, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Pesaran, M.H., Shin, Y. and Smith, R.J., 2001. Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of applied econometrics*, 16(3), pp. 289-326.
- Pham, T.H. and Riedel, J., 2019. Impacts of the sectoral composition of growth on poverty reduction in Vietnam. *Journal of Economics and Development*.
- Phillips, P.C. and Perron, P., 1988. Testing for a unit root in time series regression. *Biometrika*, 75(2), pp. 335-346. <<https://doi.org/10.1093/biomet/75.2.335>>
- Rioba, M.E., 2011. *Manufacturing industry and economic growth in Kenya: a Kaldorian approach for (1971-2013)* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
- Singh, M. and Kaur, K., 2014. India's services sector and its determinants: An empirical investigation. *Journal of Economics and Development Studies*, 2(2), pp. 385-406.
- Su, C.W., Li, Z.Z., Tao, R. and Lobont, O.R., 2019. Can economic development boost the active female labor force? *Quality & Quantity*, 53(2), pp. 1021-1036.
- Steven, R., Jeffrey, S. and Jong-Wha, L., 2001. The determinants and prospects of economic growth in Asia. *International Economic Journal*, 15(3), pp. 1-29.
- Xing, Z., 2018. The impacts of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) and e-commerce on bilateral trade flows. *International Economics and Economic Policy*, 15(3), pp. 565-586.

Validity of asset pricing models in Istanbul Stock Exchange (ISE) information technology index*

Akin ARDA

Istanbul University, Turkey
akinarda@windowslive.com

Arif SALDANLI

Istanbul University, Turkey
saldanli@istanbul.edu.tr

Sümeyra UZUN

Istanbul University, Turkey
sumeyrauzun@istanbul.edu.tr

Abstract. *Statistical models have been created to understand capital assets' return and risk. In the empirical studies in which these developed models were tested, it was concluded that the models were valid in some periods and some samples, but not in others. In this study, it is aimed to test whether the developed asset pricing models are valid for the stocks in the Borsa Istanbul (Istanbul Stock Exchange – ISE) Information Technology Index. Model tests were carried out with panel data analysis. The data set consists of the monthly returns of 13 companies traded in the ISE Information Technology Index for the period 2013/January-2019/December. Model tests were performed on both portfolio and stock basis.*

As a result of the tests, it was concluded that CAPM is valid in firm-based studies in the ISE Information Technology Index, and both CAPM and C4F are valid in portfolio-based studies.

Keywords: Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM), Fama French Pricing Models, ISE Technology Index, panel data.

JEL Classification: G12, C33.

* This study is derived from the master's thesis named "Alternative models of expected stock return and risk Istanbul Stock Exchange(ISE) application", prepared by Akin Arda.

Introduction

There are various definitions of the terms investment and investor. However, the capital market definition of these words is important because the subject of the research is the stocks/portfolios in ISE. In capital markets, investors are defined as real or legal persons who have savings and invest their savings in capital market instruments. The motivation of the investors is to generate income through their investments (SPL, 2019).

Although it is claimed that risk-free or relatively risk-free earnings can be made through various investment tools, there are risk factors in every transaction. The risk can be defined as the situation of deviating from the targeted results while operating. As a result of deviation from the results, additional benefit or loss may be obtained and can be interpreted as an opportunity or a danger, depending on the direction of the deviation from the results with the effect of risk (ISO, 2018). Although the term risk generally brings negative connotations to people, it can be considered as uncertainty because it contains not only loss but also gains. The perspective on risk varies from person to person. Actions to be taken by legal entities and people vary according to their risk perspectives. People can be grouped as risk seekers, risk-neutral, and risk-averse (Basoglu et al., 2001).

Like people do, companies identify risks in their operations and try to reduce those risks. Risk management is also related to efforts to reduce these risks. Identifying risks, taking measures for them, controlling the measures taken afterward, and making updates, if necessary, are the basic steps of risk management that can be applied to individuals or institutions. Thanks to this cycle, the effects of the risks encountered are reduced. In many studies, the relationship between risk and return has been tried to be explained scientifically. As a result of the related studies, asset pricing models were designed. In this study, we used some of the most referenced related models, which follow each other and include similar factors. The Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM), Fama-French 3-Factor Asset Pricing Model (FF3F), Carhart 4-Factor Asset Pricing Model (C4F), Fama-French 5-Factor (FF5F), and the 6 Factor Model (6F), created by adding the momentum factor from the C4F to the FF5F, are tested by using the stocks'/portfolios' values in ISE Information Technology Index and tried to determine which model is more explanatory for the relevant stocks/portfolios.

1. Conceptual – theoretical framework

1.1. Risk and risk management

The term risk is a concept that has existed for all kinds of financial mechanisms. However, risk has been defined in different ways. In 1921, Frank Knight mentioned the concepts of measurable uncertainty and unmeasurable uncertainty in his work. The concept of measurable uncertainty is a reflection of antecedent and statistical probabilities, and unmeasurable uncertainty is expressed as the uncertainty of subjective probabilities. In 1952, Harry Markowitz, in his study titled "Portfolio Selection", stated that the expected return is desired by the investor, but the variance of the expected return is undesirable for

the investor. Harry Markowitz expressed risk as to the standard deviation of expected returns. With this expression, the expected return variance is accepted as a numerical measure of risk (Holton, 2004).

Risk types can be classified according to their sources, results, and many more different ways. In this paper, classification is related to risk reduction. Some of the risks can be reduced by asset diversification. If the risks decrease as a result of asset diversification, the relevant risks are called unsystematic risks. If asset diversification does not affect the risk reduction, the related risks are called systematic risks. Systematic risks occur due to macroeconomic factors. Total risk consists of systematic risk and unsystematic risk (Reilly and Brown, 2002).

The system that determines the risk to be reached to achieve the company target which maximizes the company value and tries to achieve the target is called risk management. On the other hand, enterprise risk management is the systematic process that is created to define the potential issues that may have an impact on firms, manage the risks according to the risk appetite of the companies and give reasonable assurance to achieve the goals of the companies. The risk management process consists of defining, analyzing, prioritizing risks, identifying solutions, monitoring the process, and communication steps (TÜSİAD, 2008).

1.2. Portfolio theory, portfolio selection and capital assets pricing models

Portfolio theory is discussed under two main headings as traditional portfolio theory and modern portfolio theory. The most important distinction between traditional and modern portfolio theory is the consideration of the relationship between financial assets. In the traditional portfolio theory, the relationship between the financial assets in the portfolio is not taken into account. It has been concluded that the risk can be reduced by increasing the number of financial assets in the portfolio, diversifying their maturities, and incorporating financial assets from different sectors into the portfolio. In the modern portfolio theory, it is stated that the main aim of the investors is profit maximization, and for this, the concepts of expected return and risk are important. In addition, the low covariance of the assets included in the portfolio indicates correct diversification.

In portfolio selection, the investor can first choose how many risky and risk-free assets to invest, as well as the selection of risky assets according to the effective limit in the Mean-Variance Model (MVM). MVM states that portfolios with the highest average return but the lowest variance will be selected when creating the portfolio, and the line formed by the portfolios that show the highest return at a certain risk level is called the effective limit. In addition, while determining the optimal portfolio, the utility function of the investor outside the effective limit is also taken into account. Indifference curves are formed depending on the utility function. Investors want to reach the highest indifference curve. The optimal portfolio is formed at the point where the efficient frontier and the indifference curve of investors are tangent (SPL, 2020).

When the literature on asset pricing models is reviewed, it is seen that many models have been developed to use them in the return and risk estimations of financial assets. In this study, the CAPM, FF3F, C4F, FF5F, and the 6F model were used.

The model in the studies of Sharpe (1964), Lintner (1965), and Black (1972) are stated in the studies of Fama and French as the CAPM. In CAPM, the relationship between the expected return of the financial asset and the degree of risk is shown (Ceylan and Korkmaz, 1998). CAPM took the capital market line a step forward by allowing it to assess the link between risk and expected return for individual risky assets. In CAPM, the risk is specified as the systematic component of total risk rather than total risk. Also, the systematic risk of a financial asset or portfolio is indicated by the beta (β) coefficient, which indicates the sensitivity of the asset's return to changes in the return of the hypothetical market portfolio, in CAPM. Regardless of the individual asset or portfolio, since the return consists of the return of the risk-free asset and the expected risk premium, a risk-expected return relationship can also be established for individual assets other than portfolios.

Although the CAPM model has many assumptions, many criticisms have been brought to these assumptions. These criticisms are related to issues such as unlimited borrowing and lending at risk-free interest rates, the adequacy of beta being a risk measure, whether the market portfolio represents the market, and the linear relationship between risk and return. As a result of these criticisms, the FF3F model has emerged. Since CAPM is criticized for trying to predict the expected returns of financial assets on a single factor, in the study conducted by Fama and French in 1992, factors such as the size of the firms, leverage ratio, price/earnings ratio, cash cycle, book value, past sales growth, and long and short-term historical returns were added to the model (Yolsal, 2005).

Fama and French stated that factors such as firm size, price/earnings ratio, and book value/market value are effective factors in explaining stock returns. In the "3-Factor Asset Pricing Model" developed by Fama and French in 1993, "portfolio size" and "book value/market value" factors were added to the CAPM (Guzeldere and Sarıoğlu, 2012). The model is built on the assumption that rational pricing and optimal portfolios are designed following the multi-factor minimum variance criterion (Yücel, 2013).

In 1997, Carhart built the "Four-Factor Asset Pricing Model" by adding the momentum factor (Winner minus loser-WML) to the related model, with the criticism that the momentum returns could not be explained by the FF3F. The model assumes that the markets are in equilibrium. In his study, Carhart calculated the momentum factor according to the high and low returns in the previous 11 months, from 1 year before the portfolio creation period to 1 month before. Then, by sorting the returns of the companies from the largest to the smallest, Carhart came to the conclusion by subtracting the returns of the companies in the last 30% from the returns of the companies in the first 30% (Carhart, 1997).

Profitability and investment variables were added to the 3-factor model in the study conducted by Fama and French and published in 2015. It is stated that the reason for adding

the related variables to the model is that the related variables affect the average returns of the stocks. In the related study, data of companies traded in NYSE, AMEX, and NASDAQ markets between July/1963-December/2013 were used. As a result of the study, it was concluded that FF5F performed better than FF3F (Fama and French, 2015).

2. Literature review

There are many studies on financial models in the literature. Studies on the models tested in the study were examined under two main headings, abroad and domestically.

Table 1. *Studies – Abroad*

Author/s	Publishing Year	Study Market	Study Period	Study Models	Brief Summary
Harshita, Singh and Yadav	2015	India	1999-2014	CAPM, FF3F and FF5F	- FF3F is more successful than CAPM - FF5F is more successful model in portfolios created according to the investment factor.
Chiah, Chai, Zong and Li	2016	Australia	1982-2013	FF3F, C4F and FF5F	- FF5F is more successful model
Taha and Elgiziry	2016	Egypt	2005-2013	FF3F and 5 Factor	- Momentum factor has no effect - The model which has factors of market risk premium, firm size, book to market ratio, P/E ratio and liquidity is more successful model
Jiao and Liti	2017	China	2010-2015	FF3F and FF5F	- Profitability and investment factors have not much descriptive power - There is no significant distinction between FF3F and FF5F
Machado, Faff and Silva	2017	Brazil	1997-2014	FF5F and 5 Factors	- Book to market ratio, momentum and liquidity factors are helpful to predict returns - Investment and profitability factors are not significant - Keene and Peterson's 5 factors model is more successful than others
Kubota and Takehara	2017	Japan	1978-2014	FF5F	- FF5F is not significant
Foye	2018	Asia, East Europe, and Latin America	1996-2016	FF3F and FF5F	- FF5F is more successful than FF3F in East Europe and Latin America - Investment and profitability factors are not significant in Asia market
Musawa, Kapena and Shikaputo	2018	Lusaka (Zambia)	2008-2014	FF3F and FF5F	- FF5F is more successful than FF3F
Dash	2019	India	2008-2016	FF3F	- HML factor has negative effect - β &SMB factors are insignificant
Nilsson and Ljungström	2019	Sweden	1998-2018	CAPM, FF3F and FF5F	- Related models are not significant regarding explanation of average earnings
Sonubi	2019	Ireland	2011-2015	CAPM and FF3F	- FF3F is more successful model - β &HML factors are significant, but SMB is not significant
Jansen	2019	Holland	2000-2017	CAPM, FF3F and FF5F	- FF5F is not significant and, CAPM and FF3F are more successful models regarding explanation of change in returns

Table 2. *Studies – Domestic*

Author/s	Publishing Year	Study Market	Study Period	Study Models	Brief Summary
Yolsal	2005	Türkiye	1999-2004	CAPM and FF3F	- FF3F is more successful than CAPM
Sultanov	2010	Türkiye (Real Estate Investment Companies and Securities Investment Trusts)	1997-2009	CAPM, FF3F and C4F	- FF3F is more successful - Momentum factor is not significant
Aydemir	2012	USA	2005-2011	CAPM, FF3F and C4F	- Real Estate Investment Companies have positive correlation with SMB and HML but they have negative correlation with momentum
Çakır	2012	Türkiye (12 Sectors)	2000-2009	APT	- APT is significant
Yücel	2013	Türkiye (4 Sectors)	2009-2011	CAPM and FF3F	- Both models are significant
Kakilli Acaravcı and Karaömer	2017	Türkiye	2005-2016	FF5F	- FF5F is significant
Karaömer	2017	Türkiye (4 Sectors)	2005-2016	CAPM, FF3F, FF4F and FF5F	- CAPM is not significant - FF3F, FF4F and FF5F are significant - The most successful model is FF5F
Sondemir	2018	Türkiye (Participation Banks 30)	2011-2017	FF3F	- FF3F is not significant
Karabay	2018	Türkiye	2008-2018	CAPM, FF3F and FF5F	- FF5F is not significant - Model with 2 factors is more successful than CAPM
Çömlekçi and Genç	2018	Türkiye (ISE Corporate Governance Index)	2010-2017	FF3F	- FF3F is not significant
Zeren, Yılmaz and Belke	2018	Türkiye (ISE Sustainability Index)	1995-2017	FF5F	- FF5F is not significant
Kirman Başpehlivan	2019	Czechia, Hungary, Russia, Poland and Türkiye	2007-2017	CAPM, FF3F and C4F	- CAPM is not significant - FF3F and C4F are significant
Aras, Çam, Zavalı and Keskin	2019	Türkiye	2005-2017	CAPM, FF3F and FF5F	- FF5F is more successful
Yayıkcı	2019	Türkiye	2011-2015	CAPM	- CAPM is not significant
Kartal	2019	Türkiye (Participation Banks 30)	2011-2018	FF5F	- FF5F is significant
Arı	2020	Türkiye	2006-2018	FF5F	- There is not adequate proof about significance of FF5F model

When we look at the these studies, it is seen that the results differ considerably according to the sample and period studied. According to this result, it has been observed that there is not a single model valid for every period and every sample.

3. Research

The purpose of the study, the methodology used, and the analysis part are discussed in this chapter.

3.1. Purpose of the research

This study, it is aimed to test the CAPM, FF3F, C4F, and FF5F models with panel regression using monthly data of stocks traded in ISE Information Technology Index between 2013/January-2019/December periods.

3.2. Methodology of the research

The models in the study were tested with panel data analysis methods. The methods of estimating economic relations with the help of models created using panel data are called panel data analysis (Yerdelen Tatoğlu, 2013).

In panel data analysis, firstly, hypothesis tests are performed based on variables to determine the model estimator. The most basic assumption about variables is the stationarity assumption. For this, first of all, the existence of a correlation between units in the variables is tested with the Pesaran CD (PCD) test. If the variables are not correlated between units, the I. generation unit root tests are performed, and if there is an inter-unit correlation, the II. generation unit root tests are used to test the assumptions of the variables. If the variables are stationary, then the existence of the multicollinearity problem related to the model is tested with the VIF test. Variables with a VIF value above 10 should be excluded from the model. Afterward, the panel data is subjected to some tests to determine the model estimator. Many tests can be done to decide whether the model is a classical model or a model with fixed effects. These tests are F test, the likelihood ratio test, Breusch-Pagan Lagrange multiplier, and adjusted Lagrange multiplier test, Score test, and Wooldridge's test. In this study, this control was carried out with the F test, the Breusch-Pagan Lagrange multiplier, and the corrected Lagrange multiplier test. The F test helps to understand whether the data differs according to the units. If the data does not differ by units, the classical model is suitable. To test the suitability of the pooled least squares model against the random-effects model, the Breusch Pagan LM test based on the residuals of the pooled least squares model was developed. In this test, the hypothesis that the variance of the random unit effects is zero ($H_0: \sigma_{\mu^2} = 0$) is tested. If the H_0 hypothesis cannot be rejected, it can be said that the classical model is suitable. After testing whether the model is classical, heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, and correlation between units, which are the basic assumptions about the model, are tested. Hypothetical tests differ depending on whether the model is classical, or unit rooted. In this study, since the model is a classical model, the autocorrelation assumption was tested with Wooldridge's test. In this test, the H_0 hypothesis is established as "There is no first-order autocorrelation.". Heteroskedasticity assumption was tested with the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weiesberg test. The H_0 hypothesis of the test is established as "There is no heteroskedasticity.". In the absence of autocorrelation in the model but heteroscedasticity, the model can be estimated with the Beck-Katz (BK) estimator.

3.3. Data set and theoretical model

In the regression analysis, the pooled ordinary least squares method was used. The relevant models were tested on both stock and portfolio basis, and the results were evaluated within the 95% confidence interval. Financial statements, stocks' daily prices, and 2-year government bond yield which were used for risk-free interest rate were used, in this study.

Financial statements were obtained from Public Disclosure Platform's (PDP) website, stock prices were obtained from İş Yatırım and bond yields were obtained from tr.investing.com. The government bond yield was used by converting it on monthly basis. There are 13 stocks operating continuously in the BIST during the relevant periods. Stata17, Gretl, and Microsoft Excel programs were used for data analysis.

In the data set, the average of the most recent returns has been taken instead of the missing returns since they coincide with the holidays. In the event that the financial statements are given comparatively by years in the PDP and there is inconsistency in the data in the financial statements published on different dates, the most up-to-date published data is used for the data found to be inconsistent. Since the provided data have been corrected, no additional calculations have been made regarding dividends and/or splits.

After the portfolios were created, the factors were calculated thanks to the relevant portfolios, and then models were created by using the portfolios and factors. Models were analyzed separately on both stock and portfolio basis.

Due to the small number of stocks, portfolios were formed with the 2x2 method. The stocks are named according to the 50% tranches based on the median value, annually factors are arranged from largest to smallest according to their status, and portfolios are formed from the overlapping stocks. The details of the portfolio formation method are given below. For the January rankings of the year "t", the December financial data of the year "t - 1" were used. Although studies are using approximately 6-month intervals in the literature, there was no need to use historical data since the financial data of the companies are published quarterly. The research was carried out under the precondition that the difference would not affect the results.

Table 3. *Portfolio formation method*

		Value Ratio		Momentum		Operational Profit		Investment	
		L	H	K	D	W	R	C	A
Size	S	SL	SH	SK	SD	SW	SR	SC	SA
	B	BL	BH	BK	BD	BW	BR	BC	BA

Source: Fama and French: A five-factor asset pricing model, 2015.

SL: It refers to the portfolio consisting of small size (S) stocks and low value ratio (L) stocks.

SH: It refers to the portfolio consisting of S stocks and high value ratio (H) stocks.

BL: It refers to the portfolio consisting of big size (B) stocks and L stocks.

BH: It refers to the portfolio consisting of B stocks and H stocks.

SK: It refers to the portfolio consisting of S stocks and low momentum (K) stocks.

SD: It refers to the portfolio consisting of S stocks and high momentum (D) stocks.

BK: It refers to the portfolio consisting of B stocks and K stocks.

BD: It refers to the portfolio consisting of B stocks and D stocks.

SW: It refers to the portfolio consisting of S stocks and weak operational profitability (W) stocks.

SR: It refers to the portfolio consisting of S stocks and robust operational profitability (R) stocks.

BW: It refers to the portfolio consisting of B stocks and W stocks.

BR: It refers to the portfolio consisting of B stocks and R stocks.

SC: It refers to the portfolio consisting of S stocks and conservative investment (C) stocks.

SA: It refers to the portfolio consisting of S stocks and aggressive investment (A) stocks.

BC: It refers to the portfolio consisting of B stocks and C stocks.

BA: It refers to the portfolio consisting of B stocks and A stocks.

The list of companies in the portfolios formed as a result of the studies carried out as stated above, by years is given below.

Table 4. Stocks in portfolios

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
SL	KRONT, LINK	KRONT	LINK, PKART	KRONT, LINK, PKART	KRONT, LINK	LINK	DESPC, DGATE, KRONT, LINK, PKART
SH	ARMDA, DESPC, DGATE, PKART	ARMDA, DESPC, DGATE, ESCOM, LINK	DESPC, ESCOM, KAREL, KRONT	DESPC, ESCOM, KAREL,	DESPC, ESCOM, KAREL, PKART,	ARENA, ARMDA, DESPC, ESCOM, PKART	ESCOM
SK	KRONT, LINK, PKART	DESPC, DGATE, ESCOM, LINK	ESCOM, KAREL, KRONT,	ESCOM, KAREL, LINK, PKART	KAREL, KRONT, PKART	ARENA, ARMDA, ESCOM, PKART	DGATE, ESCOM, KRONT
SD	ARMDA, DESPC, DGATE	ARMDA, KRONT	DESPC, LINK	DESPC, KRONT	DESPC, ESCOM, LINK	DESPC, LINK	DESPC, LINK, PKART
SW	DESPC, DGATE, KRONT, LINK, PKART	DGATE, ESCOM, KRONT, LINK	DESPC, ESCOM, KRONT, LINK, PKART	DESPC, ESCOM, KRONT, LINK, PKART	DESPC, ESCOM, KAREL, LINK, PKART	ARENA, DESPC, ESCOM, LINK, PKART	DESPC, ESCOM, KRONT, LINK, PKART
SR	ARMDA	ARMDA, DESPC	KAREL	KAREL	KRONT	ARMDA	DGATE
SC	ARMDA, DESPC, DGATE, KRONT, LINK	ARMDA, DGATE	DESPC, ESCOM, KAREL, LINK, PKART	DESPC, ESCOM, KRONT, PKART	DESPC, ESCOM, LINK	ARENA, ESCOM	DESPC, DGATE, ESCOM, PKART
SA	PKART	ARMDA, DESPC, ESCOM, KRONT	KRONT	KAREL, LINK	KAREL, KRONT, PKART	ARMDA, DESPC, LINK, PKART	KRONT, LINK
BL	ALCTL, INDES, LOGO, NETAS	ALCTL, INDES, LOGO, NETAS, PKART	ALCTL, DGATE, INDES, LOGO	ALCTL, DGATE, LOGO	ALCTL, DGATE, INDES, LOGO	DGATE, INDES, KAREL, KRONT, LOGO	LOGO
BH	ARENA, ESCOM, KAREL	ARENA, KAREL	ARENA, ARMDA, NETAS	ARENA, ARMDA, INDES, NETAS	ARENA, ARMDA, NETAS	ALCTL, NETAS	ALCTL, ARENA, ARMDA, INDES, KAREL, NETAS
BK	ESCOM, KAREL, NETAS	ALCTL, NETAS	ALCTL, NETAS	ARENA, INDES	ARMDA, DGATE, NETAS	ALCTL, LOGO	INDES, LOGO, NETAS

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
BD	ALCTL, ARENA, INDES, LOGO	ARENA, INDES, KAREL, LOGO, PKART	ARENA, ARMDA, DGATE, INDES, LOGO	ALCTL, ARMDA, DGATE, LOGO, NETAS	ALCTL, ARENA, INDES, LOGO	DGATE, INDES, KAREL, NETAS, KRONT	ALCTL, ARENA, ARMDA, KAREL
BW	ESCOM	ALCTL, PKART	ALCTL	ARMDA	ARMDA	KRONT	ARENA
BR	ALCTL, ARENA, INDES, KAREL, LOGO, NETAS	ARENA, INDES, KAREL, LOGO, NETAS	ARENA, ARMDA, DGATE, INDES, LOGO, NETAS	ALCTL, ARENA, DGATE, INDES, LOGO, NETAS	ALCTL, ARENA, DGATE, INDES, LOGO, NETAS	ALCTL, DGATE, INDES, KAREL, LOGO, NETAS	ALCTL, ARMDA, INDES, KAREL, LOGO, NETAS
BC	ALCTL	ARENA, INDES, KAREL, PKART	NETAS	ALCTL, ARENA	DGATE, INDES, NETAS	KAREL, KRONT, LOGO, NETAS	ARENA, INDES
BA	ARENA, ESCOM, INDES, KAREL, LOGO, NETAS	ARENA, LOGO, NETAS	ALCTL, ARENA, ARMDA, DGATE, INDES, LOGO	ARMDA, DGATE, INDES, LOGO, NETAS	ALCTL, ARENA, ARMDA, LOGO	ALCTL, DGATE, INDES	ALCTL, ARMDA, KAREL, LOGO, NETAS

The factors were created as follows (Fama and French, 2015).

$$\text{SMBT: } [(SL+SH+SK+SD+SW+SR+SC+SA)/8] - [(BL+BH+BK+BD+BW+BR+BC+BA)/8]$$

$$\text{SMB5: } [(SL + SH + SW + SR + SC + SA) / 6] - [(BL + BH + BW + BR + BC + BA) / 6]$$

$$\text{SMB4: } [(SL + SH + SK + SD) / 4] - [(BL + BH + BK + BD) / 4]$$

$$\text{SMB3: } [(SL + SH) / 2] - [(BL + BH) / 2]$$

$$\text{HML: } [(SH + BH) / 2] - [(SL + BL) / 2]$$

$$\text{WML: } [(SK + BK) / 2] - [(SD + BD) / 2]$$

$$\text{RMW: } [(SR + BR) / 2] - [(SW + BW) / 2]$$

$$\text{CMA: } [(SC + BC) / 2] - [(SA + BA) / 2]$$

3.4. Research model

The panel data regression analysis performed in this study, it is aimed to estimate the mean value of the dependent variable over the known or unchanged values of the independent variables by examining the dependence of the excess return of stocks or portfolios, which are the dependent variables, on one or more explanatory variables (such as SMB, HML). (Gujarati and Porter, 2009)

The models in which the hypotheses are tested in the study are as follows:

$$\text{Model 1 – FVFM : } R_{i,t} - R_{f,t} = \alpha_i + \beta_i(R_{m,t} - R_{f,t}) + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

$$\text{Model 2 – FF3F : } R_{i,t} - R_{f,t} = \alpha_{i,t} + \beta_{i,t}(R_{m,t} - R_{f,t}) + s_i(\text{SMB3})_t + h_i(\text{HML})_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

$$\text{Model 3 – C4F : } R_{i,t} - R_{f,t} = \alpha_{i,t} + \beta_{i,t}(R_{m,t} - R_{f,t}) + s_i(\text{SMB4})_t + h_i(\text{HML})_t + w_i(\text{WML})_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model 4 – FF5F : $R_{i,t} - R_{f,t} = \alpha_{i,t} + \beta_{i,t}(R_{m,t} - R_{f,t}) + s_i(SMB5)_t + h_i(HML)_t + r_i(RMW)_t + ci(CMA)_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$

Model 5 – 6F : $R_{i,t} - R_{f,t} = \alpha_{i,t} + \beta_{i,t}(R_{m,t} - R_{f,t}) + s_i(SMBT)_t + h_i(HML)_t + w_i(WML)_t + r_i(RMW)_t + ci(CMA)_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$

: It represents time.

SMB3: It represents the returns of the SMB portfolio formed for FF3F.

SMB4: It represents the returns of the SMB portfolio formed for C4F.

SMB5: It represents the returns of the SMB portfolio formed for FF5F.

SMBT: It represents the returns of the SMB portfolio formed for 6F.

: It represents the margin of error.

The hypotheses tested with the relevant models are as follows:

H₁: CAPM is valid for stocks in ISE IT Index.

H₂: FF3F is valid for stocks in ISE IT Index.

H₃: C4F is valid for stocks in ISE IT Index.

H₄: FF5F is valid for stocks in ISE IT Index.

H₅: 6F is valid for stocks in ISE IT Index.

H₆: CAPM is valid for portfolios formed from stocks in the BIST IT Index.

H₇: FF3F is valid for portfolios formed from stocks in the BIST IT Index.

H₈: C4F is valid for portfolios formed from stocks in the BIST IT Index.

H₉: FF5F is valid for portfolios formed from stocks in the BIST IT Index.

H₁₀: 6F is valid for portfolios formed from stocks in the BIST IT Index.

3.5. Analysis

After the research model and hypothesis were created, the analysis part was started. The descriptive statistics of the stocks included in the model are as follows:

Table 5. Descriptive statistics-stocks

	Mean	Med.	Min.	Maks.	S.D.	Skew.	Kurt.	n
ALCTL	0.0168	0.0019	-0.2659	0.8304	0.1707	2.0208	6.7944	84
ARENA	0.0127	0.0002	-0.1860	0.4000	0.1160	0.9159	1.3808	84
ARMDA	0.0243	0.0136	-0.2309	0.3371	0.1115	0.5843	0.3260	84
DGATE	0.0358	0.0149	-0.3612	0.7673	0.1873	0.8467	2.1110	84
ESCOM	-0.0041	-0.0225	-0.3972	0.4714	0.1389	0.6332	1.9250	84
INDES	0.0121	0.0222	-0.2774	0.3568	0.1134	0.1405	0.9602	84
KAREL	0.0251	0.0037	-0.3287	0.3610	0.1364	0.3531	-0.1202	84
LINK	0.0295	-0.0157	-0.2294	1.4057	0.2295	3.3498	15.2851	84
LOGO	0.0366	-0.0011	-0.1864	0.8791	0.1715	2.1337	6.7288	84
NETAS	0.0032	-0.0128	-0.2587	0.5162	0.1428	1.3566	2.7615	84
PKART	0.0137	-0.0072	-0.1990	0.4701	0.1119	1.6972	4.3152	84
DESPC	0.0106	0.0058	-0.1908	0.2802	0.1004	0.4039	-0.1119	84
KRONT	0.0292	0.0027	-0.2715	0.7383	0.1549	1.3015	3.8494	84

Looking at the average returns of the stocks, it is seen that only ESCOM stock has negative returns (-0.4%), while the others have positive returns for their investors. DGATE (3.6%) and LOGO (3.7%) are the stocks with the highest average returns.

Looking at the median returns, it is understood that LINK's (-1.6%), LOGO's (-0.1%), NETAS's (-1.2%) and PKART's (-0.7%) shares accompany ESCOM (-2.3%) in terms of negative returns. Stock of LINK also has the highest standard deviation (0.23), while DESPC has the lowest (0.1).

Descriptive statistics of the portfolios are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. *Descriptive statistics-portfolios*

	Mean	Med.	Min.	Maks.	S.D.	Skew.	Kurt.	N
SL	0.0114	-0.0116	-0.2326	0.3959	0.1233	0.8298	0.6511	84
SH	0.0275	0.0145	-0.1798	0.6027	0.1131	2.0117	7.4555	84
SK	0.0323	0.0085	-0.1975	0.7571	0.1398	2.0576	7.3916	84
SD	0.0192	0.0189	-0.2167	0.4390	0.1116	1.0056	2.8392	84
SW	0.0217	-0.0055	-0.2005	0.7661	0.1322	2.5708	11.0693	84
SR	0.0415	0.0093	-0.2710	0.7673	0.1612	2.0341	7.0864	84
SC	0.0263	0.0116	-0.1880	0.4249	0.1145	0.7940	1.4098	84
SA	0.0440	0.0163	-0.1568	0.5599	0.1313	1.3324	2.6866	84
BL	0.0161	0.0032	-0.1716	0.5346	0.1203	1.2512	2.9829	84
BH	0.0051	0.0030	-0.2061	0.3120	0.0988	0.7242	1.3841	84
BK	0.0100	-0.0085	-0.2419	0.4389	0.1228	1.0477	1.3816	84
BD	0.0179	0.0154	-0.2375	0.5320	0.1146	1.1901	4.2061	84
BW	0.0012	-0.0259	-0.3972	0.8305	0.1705	2.0140	7.5129	84
BR	0.0154	0.0064	-0.1696	0.4311	0.1077	1.0124	1.9801	84
BC	0.0066	-0.0023	-0.2659	0.5163	0.1291	1.3419	3.3449	84
BA	0.0192	0.0077	-0.2729	0.4496	0.1208	0.6213	1.4265	84

Looking at the average return of the portfolios, it is seen that there is no negative return, and the SR and SA portfolios provide the highest return to their investors with a return of about 4.4%. Although there is no negative average return, 5 portfolios have a negative median value. The highest standard deviation of 0.14 belongs to the SK portfolio, while the lowest standard deviation of 0.1 belongs to the BH portfolio.

Descriptive statistics of the factors are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. *Descriptive statistics-factors*

	Mean	Med.	Min.	Maks.	S.D.	Skew.	Kurt.	N
SMBT	0.0166	0.0275	-0.2121	0.2109	0.0850	-0.2110	-0.0530	84
SMB5	0.0182	0.0309	-0.2188	0.2147	0.0857	-0.2600	-0.0653	84
SMB4	0.0103	0.0192	-0.1462	0.2614	0.0808	0.0725	0.0623	84
SMB3	0.0089	0.0208	-0.1492	0.2272	0.0800	-0.0734	-0.4839	84
HML	0.0026	0.0030	-0.2809	0.2191	0.0843	-0.2222	0.9049	84
WML	-0.0071	-0.0054	-0.2992	0.4125	0.0988	0.8361	4.0630	84
RMW	0.0170	0.0114	-0.3877	0.4210	0.1263	0.1145	2.1849	84
CMA	-0.0152	-0.0057	-0.3833	0.2702	0.0977	-0.2733	1.6192	84
mf	-0.0030	-0.0013	-0.1188	0.1267	0.0608	-0.0156	-0.7916	84

On the other hand, it is seen that the factors do not have a negative mean value or median except for WML, CMA and mf. The highest standard deviation of 0.13 belongs to RMW and the lowest standard deviation of 0.6 belongs to mf.

Table 8. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test

	Firm					Portfolio				
	CAPM	FF3F	C4F	FF5F	6F	CAPM	FF3F	C4F	FF5F	6F
mf	1.00	1.01	1.02	1.05	1.05	1.00	1.01	1.02	1.05	1.05
SMB3		1.01					1.01			
SMB4			1.02					1.02		
SMB5				1.21					1.21	
SMBT					1.21					1.21
HML		1.03	1.22	1.35	1.41		1.03	1.22	1.35	1.41
WML			1.22		2.24			1.22		2.24
RMW				1.25	2.25				1.25	2.25
CMA				1.30					1.30	
Mean VIF	1.00	1.02	1.12	1.23	1.58	1.00		1.12	1.23	1.58

It was seen that there is no multicollinearity problem according to the test results.

Before the model analysis, the stationarity of the variables was tested. Since the variables are panel data, before performing the unit root test, whether the variables are correlated between units was tested with the PCD test. If the variables are not correlated between units, the I. generation unit root tests are performed, and if they are inter-unit correlated, the II. generation unit root tests are used to test for stationarity. The hypothesis of PCD test is as follows:

H_0 : There is no interdependence between the units.

H_1 : There is interdependence between units.

Table 9. CD test's results

Variable	Stock	Portfolio
Dependent Variable	23.311 (0.0000)	49.529 (0.0000)
Mf	(80.944) 0.0000	100.399 (0.0000)
SMB3	(80.944) 0.0000	100.399 (0.0000)
SMB4	(80.944) 0.0000	100.399 (0.0000)
SMB5	(80.944) 0.0000	100.399 (0.0000)
SMBT	(80.944) 0.0000	100.399 (0.0000)
HML	(80.944) 0.0000	100.399 (0.0000)
WML	(80.944) 0.0000	100.399 (0.0000)
RMW	(80.944) 0.0000	100.399 (0.0000)
CMA	(80.944) 0.0000	100.399 (0.0000)

According to the PCD test results for stocks and portfolios separately in Table 9, the null hypothesis suggesting cross-sectional independence is rejected. Since there is no independence between the cross-section units of the variables, the stationarity test of the variables can be performed with the I. generation unit root tests. In this study, the variables' stationarity test was done with the Im Pesaran Shin (IPS) unit root test.

Table 10. *IPS unit root test's results*

Variable	Stock	Portfolio
Dependent Variable	-8.4046 (0.0000)	-8.2770 (0.0000)
Mf	-9.1461 (0.0000)	-9.1461 (0.0000)
SMB3	-10.3283 (0.0000)	-9.6977 (0.0000)
SMB4	-10.5089 (0.0000)	-10.5089 (0.0000)
SMB5	-9.6838 (0.0000)	-9.6838 (0.0000)
SMBT	-9.6977 (0.0000)	-9.6977 (0.0000)
HML	-8.4986 (0.0000)	-8.4986 (0.0000)
WML	-8.6707 (0.0000)	-8.6707 (0.0000)
RMW	-8.0130 (0.0000)	-8.0130 (0.0000)
CMA	-8.8993 (0.0000)	-8.8993 (0.0000)

According to the IPS unit root test results, which are stated separately for stocks and portfolios in Table 10, H_0 is rejected because the p value of all the variables is less than 0.05, and according to this result, it is concluded that the factors are stationary at the level.

Regarding the model, existence of unit effect, autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity tests were performed, and the appropriate estimator was selected according to the results. Testing the existence of autocorrelation related to the model was done with Wooldridge test. P values of Wooldridge autocorrelation tests and hypotheses regarding the test are as follows:

H_0 : There is no autocorrelation.

H_1 : There is autocorrelation.

Table 11. *Autocorrelation test*

Model	Stock	Portfolio
	Test Statistics' Value	Test Statistics' Value
CAPM	0.000 (0.9909)	0.272 (0.6097)
FF3F	0.005 (0.9470)	0.039 (0.8466)
C4F	0.003 (0.9562)	0.005 (0.9431)
FF5F	0.015 (0.9036)	0.033 (0.8573)
6F	0.000 (0.9988)	0.153 (0.7009)

Looking at the autocorrelation test results, H_0 is rejected because the p values for both stocks and portfolios are higher than 0.05, and it is concluded that there is no autocorrelation problem.

Breusch-Pagan/Cook Weisberg test was used for heteroscedasticity test. P values of Breusch-Pagan/Cook Weisberg test results and hypotheses related to the test are given below.

H_0 : There is no heteroscedasticity.

H_1 : There is heteroscedasticity.

Table 12. *Heteroscedasticity test*

Model	Stock	Portfolio
	Test Statistics' Value	Test Statistics' Value
CAPM	8.66 (0.0032)	12.19 (0.0005)
FF3F	13.09 (0.0003)	29.46 (0.0000)
C4F	16.58 (0.000)	32.50 (0.0000)
FF5F	15.65 (0.0001)	27.51 (0.0000)
6F	16.40 (0.0001)	35.68 (0.0000)

When the test results of the models for stocks and portfolios are examined, it is understood that the null hypothesis is rejected and there is heteroscedasticity in the models because the p values for the related tests are less than 0.05 significance level.

According to the test results, it was seen that the model did not have autocorrelation but heteroskedacity. Therefore, models were estimated using the BK estimator, which is a heteroscedasticity resistant estimator.

Table 13. *Model results-firms*

		α	β	s	h	w	r	c	R^2	Chi ² (p)
CAPM	Value	0.0215	0.8783						0.1312	164.95 0.0000
	σ	0.0042	0.0683							
	Test Value	5.12***	12.84***							
FF3F	Value	0.0216	0.8603	0.0206	-0.1144				0.1353	170.85 0.0000
	σ	0.0042	0.0687	0.0532	0.0506					
	Test Value	5.12***	12.52***	0.39	-2.26**					
C4F	Value	0.0219	0.8554	0.0425	-0.1425	0.0572			0.1371	173.43 0.0000
	σ	0.0042	0.0688	0.0524	0.0553	0.0474				
	Test Value	5.15***	12.43***	0.81	-2.58**	1.20				
FF5F	Value	0.0219	0.8614	0.0335	-0.1297		-0.0653	-0.0332	0.1384	175.38 0.0000
	σ	0.0043	0.0695	0.0539	0.0577		0.0371	0.0488		
	Test Value	5.06***	12.39***	0.62	-2.25**		-1.76*	-0.68		
6F	Value	0.0218	0.8607	0.0403	-0.1328	0.0904	-0.0607	-0.0318	0.1386	175.67 0.0000
	σ	0.0043	0.0695	0.0542	0.0591	0.0639	0.0498	0.0488		
	Test Value	5.04***	12.38***	0.74	-2.25**	0.15	-1.22	-0.65		

* states that the relevant factor is significant in the 90% confidence interval.

** states that the relevant factor is significant in the 95% confidence interval.

*** states that the relevant factor is significant in the 99% confidence interval.

According to the results of the regression analysis of the CAPM model performed with firm-based data, it is understood that the relationship between the excess returns of the stocks and the excess returns of the fixed term and market risk premium (MF, β) variable in the model is significant at the 95% confidence interval. So, a one-unit change in the market risk premium variable changes the excess returns of stocks by 0.88 units in the same direction as the change.

In the Wald test results of the model, it is stated that the p value is significant at the 95% confidence level and the R2 value, which expresses the explanatory power of the model, is 0.13.

In the results of the FF3F model, it is understood that the only market value (SMB, s) factor's p value showing the relationship between the excess returns of the stocks and the excess returns of the other variables in the model is not less than 0.05 significance level, this means that there is a significant relationship between the other variables and the excess returns of the stocks. When the coefficients of the variables that are significant are examined, it is seen that there is a negative relationship between the excess returns of stocks and the book-to-market ratio (HML, h), while the MF has a positive relationship. So, in a one-unit change in MF and HML, the excess returns of stocks change by 0.86 and -0.11 units, respectively.

In the Wald test results of this model, similar to the results of the CAPM model, it is seen that the p value is significant at the 95% confidence level and the R2 value is 0.13.

In the results of the C4F model, it is stated that the market value factor is not as significant as in the FF3F model, and there is no significant relationship between the variable regarding the return in the last 1 year (WML, w) and the excess returns of the stocks at the 95% confidence interval. When the relationship between the other variables and the excess returns of the stocks is examined, it is stated that there is a significant relationship between the factors and the excess returns of the stocks. When the coefficients of the factors that have a significant relationship are examined, it is seen that only the HML has a negative relationship with the excess returns of the stocks, while the others have a positive relationship. So, the excess returns of stocks change by 0.85 and -0.14 units in a one-unit change in MF and HML, respectively.

In the Wald test results of this model, like the results in other models, the p value is significant at the 95% confidence level and the R2 value is 0.14.

According to the results of the FF5F model given in Table 13, it is seen that the relationship between the excess returns of the stocks and the fixed term, the market risk premium and the HML is significant at the 95% confidence interval. However, it was understood that the factor related to operational profitability (RMW, r) was significant only in the 90% confidence interval, while other factors did not have a significant relationship. When the coefficients of the variables that are significant at the 95% confidence interval are examined, it is seen that the HML is negative, and the others are positive. So, the excess returns of stocks change by 0.86 and -0.13 in a one-unit change in MF and HML, respectively.

In the Wald test results of the model, it is stated that the p value is significant at the 95% confidence level and the R2 value, which expresses the explanatory power of the model, is 0.14.

In the 6F model, it is seen that the significant relationship between the excess returns of stocks and the excess returns of other variables is only in the fixed term, MF and HML, and this situation is similar in other models. It is understood that there is no significant

relationship between other factors and the excess returns of stocks. When the coefficients of the variables that are significant are examined, it is seen that HML has a negative relationship and MF has a positive relationship in parallel with the results in other models. So, the excess returns of the stocks show a change of 0.86 and -0.13 units in a one-unit change in MF and HML, respectively.

As in other models, it is stated that the p value of this model is significant at the 95% confidence level in the Wald test results and the R2 value of the model is 0.14.

Table 14. Model results-Portfolios

		α	β	s	h	w	r	c	R ²	Chi ² (p)
CAPM	Value	0.0222	0.8530						0.1708	276.85 0.0000
	σ	0.0031	0.0513							
	Test Value	7.05***	16.64***							
FF3F	Value	0.0222	0.8199	0.0580	-0.2070				0.1895	314.19 0.0000
	σ	0.0031	0.0510	0.0395	0.0376					
	Test Value	7.08***	16.07***	1.47	-5.50***					
C4F	Value	0.0223	0.8151	0.0827	-0.2427	0.0775			0.1946	324.68 0.0000
	σ	0.0031	0.0510	0.0389	0.0410	0.0352				
	Test Value	7.17***	15.98***	2.13**	-5.92***	2.20**				
FF5F	Value	0.0218	0.8265	0.0758	-0.2064		-0.0351	-0.0147	0.1914	318.07 0.0000
	σ	0.0032	0.0517	0.0401	0.0429		0.0276	0.0363		
	Test Value	6.78***	16.00***	1.89*	-4.81***		-1.27	-0.40		
6F	Value	0.0218	0.8221	0.0707	-0.2298	0.1069	0.0214	-0.0185	0.1952	325.97 0.0000
	σ	0.0032	0.0516	0.0402	0.0439	0.0474	0.0369	0.0362		
	Test Value	6.80***	15.94***	1.76*	-5.24***	2.26**	0.58	-0.51		

According to the results of the regression analysis of the CAPM model performed with portfolio-based data, it is understood that the relationship between the excess returns of portfolios and the excess returns of the fixed term and market risk premium variable in the model is significant at the 95% confidence interval. So, a one-unit change in the market risk premium variable changes the excess returns of the portfolios by 0.85 units, in the same direction as the change. Although there is variation in values, the relevant results are consistent with the results in the firm-based study.

In the Wald test results of the model, it is stated that the p value is significant at the 95% confidence level and the R2 value is 0.17. Although there were differences in the values, it was seen that the results were compatible with the stock-based study.

In the results of the FF3F model, it is understood that the only market value factor's p value showing the relationship between the excess returns of the portfolios and the returns of the other variables in the model is not less than 0.05 significance level. When the coefficients of the variables that are significant are examined, it is seen that the excess returns of the portfolios have a negative relationship with HML and a positive relationship with MF. So, the excess returns of the portfolios change by 0.82 and -0.21 units in a one-unit change in MF and HML, respectively. The relevant results are similar with the results in the firm-based study.

In the Wald test results of this model, similar to the results of the CAPM model, it is seen that the p value is significant at the 95% confidence level and the R2 value is 0.19. Although

there are differences in the values in this model, as in the CAPM, it has been concluded that the results are compatible with the stock-based study.

In the results of the C4F model given in Table 14, it is stated that all factors in the model have a significant relationship with the excess returns of the portfolios at the 95% confidence interval. This situation differs from the stock-based study. When the coefficients of the factors that have a significant relationship are examined, it is seen that only the HML has a negative relationship with the excess returns of the portfolios and the others have a positive relationship. So, in a one-unit change in MF, SMB, HML and WML, the excess returns of portfolios change by 0.81, 0.08, -0.24 and 0.08 units, respectively.

In the Wald test results of this model, like the results in other models, the p value is significant at 95% confidence level and the R2 value is 0.19. In the firm-based study, the relevant model was also significant.

According to the results of the FF5F model given in Table 14, it is seen that the relationship between the excess returns of the portfolios and the fixed term, the market risk premium and the HML is significant at the 95% confidence interval. However, it was understood that the SMB was significant only in the 90% confidence interval, while other factors did not have a significant relationship. When the coefficients of the variables that are significant at the 95% confidence interval are examined, it is seen that the HML is negative, and the others are positive. So, the excess returns of portfolios change by 0.83 and -0.21 in a one-unit change in MF and HML, respectively.

In the Wald test results of the model, it is stated that the p value is significant at the 95% confidence level and the R2 value, which expresses the explanatory power of the model, is 0.19. It is understood that the relevant results are compatible with the results of the firm-based study.

Looking at Table 14, which contains the data for the last model, it is seen that only the fixed term, MF, HML and WML have a significant relationship with the excess returns of the portfolios, and this situation is not similar to the 6F model in the firm-based study. In the related model, it is understood that the WML factor is significant in accordance with the results in the C4F model, and unlike the C4F model, the SMB factor is not significant at the 95% confidence interval, but only at the 90% confidence interval. It is concluded that there is no significant relationship between the other factors and the excess returns of the portfolios. When the coefficients of the variables that are significant at the 95% confidence interval are examined, it is seen that HML has a negative relationship, and the others have a positive relationship in parallel with the results in other models. Accordingly, with a one unit change in MF, HML and WML, the excess returns of the portfolios change by 0.82, -0.23 and 0.10 units, respectively.

As in other models, it is stated that the p value of this model is significant at the 95% confidence level in the Wald test results and the R2 value of the model is 0.19. These results are also compatible with the firm-based study.

Table 15. *Summary results of the research*

	ModelVariable	F.T.	MF	SMB	HML	WML	RMW	CMA
Firm	CAPM	+	+					
	FF3F	+	+		-			
	C4F	+	+		-			
	FF5F	+	+		-			
	6F	+	+		-			
Portfolio	CAPM	+	+					
	FF3F	+	+		-			
	C4F	+	+	+	-	+		
	FF5F	+	+		-			
	6F	+	+		-	+		

+/- expresses the factors that are significant in the 95% confidence interval and have a positive/negative coefficient in the model it contains.

Looking at the table above, it is seen that although the models are valid, not every factor may be valid in every model. It is understood that the fixed term, MF and HML factors are significant in all models, regardless of firm-based or portfolio-based work, and the relationship aspects of the excess returns of stocks and portfolios do not change on the basis of model-based and dependent variable.

The SMB factor has a significant relationship only in the C4F model of portfolio-based work. Although there is no model in which the WML factor is significant in the firm-based study, it was found to be significant in both models in the portfolio-based study and its relationship with the portfolio returns was found to be positive.

4. Conclusion

Studies have been carried out for years on the return and risk of financial assets and models have been created. Today, these studies continue without losing their importance and interest. Although models with a single index/factor were developed at first, multi-factor models were created over time with the influence of the criticisms brought to the relevant models. The purpose of developing the relevant models is to predict the risks and returns of financial assets, valid under all conditions. For this reason, the models created so far are tested for various conditions and periods.

The aim of this study is to test the CAPM, FF3F, C4F, FF5F and 6F Model whether they are valid for stocks in BIST IT Index by panel data regression analysis method. Testing was carried out with portfolios created and stocks included in the scope. 13 companies traded in the BIST IT Index in the 2013/January-2019/December period formed the scope of the study. Due to the scarcity of stocks, portfolios were created with the 2×2 method.

Although there was no autocorrelation problem in the models, regression analyzes were performed using the BK estimator, which is resistant to varying variance, because of the varying variance problem. Accordingly, although all models are valid, it has been observed that there are models where all factors are not valid and the explanatory power of the models is limited.

Although all the variables of the CAPM gave significant results both in the firm-based study and in the portfolio-based study, all the variables of the C4F model gave significant results only in the portfolio-based study. Although these models are valid like other models, they differ from other models because the factors they include in the above-mentioned studies are significant in the model. Although the variables included by CAPM and C4F are significant in the above-mentioned conditions, the fact that the explanatory value of the models, R2, does not change significantly between the other models and themselves is another important result of the study. When viewed on a factor basis, it was understood that the MF and HML factors, together with the fixed term, were significant in all models, and the relationship aspects with excess returns did not show a model-based change. Apart from this, although the SMB factor is significant only in the C4F model in the portfolio-based study, and the WML factor in the C4F and 6F models in the portfolio-based study, it is not significant in the other models they include.

As a result, with the increase of companies participating in the BIST Informatics Index over time, it is concluded that the studies that can be carried out with the data of more companies in a wider date range may have clearer and healthier results, and it is hoped that this study will shed light on the present. Although it is considered that the CAPM can be used for the relevant index in firm-based studies, and the CAPM and C4F models in portfolio-based studies, the low explanatory value of the models is an important issue to consider.

References

- Acaravci, S.K. and Karaomer, Y., 2017. Fama-French five factor model: Evidence from Turkey. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 7(6), pp. 130-137.
- Aras, G., Çam, İ., Zavalı, B. and Keskin, S., 2019. Fama-French Çok Faktör Varlık Fiyatlama Modellerinin Performanslarının Karşılaştırılması: Borsa İstanbul Üzerine Bir Uygulama. *Istanbul Business Research*, 47(2), pp. 183-207. <<https://doi.org/10.26650/ibr.2018.47.02.0026>>
- Ari, G., 2020. *Fama French Beş Faktörlü Varlık Fiyatlama Modelinin Geçerliliği : Türkiye Örneği*. Istanbul University.
- Aydemir, M., 2012. *A test of multi-index asset pricing models: the US REIT market*. Middle East Technical University. <<https://open.metu.edu.tr/handle/11511/21595>>
- Chiah, M., Chai, D., Zhong, A. and Li, S., 2016. A Better Model? An Empirical Investigation of the Fama-French Five-factor Model in Australia. *International Review of Finance*, 16(4), pp. 595-638. <<https://doi.org/10.1111/irfi.12099>>
- Çakır, A., 2012. *Arbitraj Fiyatlama Teorisi ve İMKB Sektör Endeksleri Üzerine Uygulanması*. Istanbul Kadir Has University. <<https://acikbilim.yok.gov.tr/handle/20.500.12812/640732>>
- Dash, M., 2019. Testing the Fama-French Three-factor Model for Banking Stocks in the Indian Stock Market Using Panel Regression Analysis. *Asian Journal of Economics Finance*

- and Management*, 1(3), pp. 127-133. <<http://globalpresshub.com/index.php/AJEFM/article/download/791/735>>
- Foye, J., 2018. A comprehensive test of the Fama-French five-factor model in emerging markets. *Emerging Markets Review*, 37, pp. 199-222. <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ememar.2018.09.002>>
- Genç, E. and Çömlekçi, İ., 2018. Fama-French Üç Faktörlü Varlık Fiyatlama Modeli Ni Geçerliliği: Borsa İstanbul Üzerine Bir Araştırma. *Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 40, pp. 257-276. <<https://dergipark.org.tr/yyusbed/issue/43698/536126>>
- Harshita, Singh, S. and Yadav, S.S., 2015. Indian Stock Market and the Asset Pricing Models. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 30, pp. 294-304. <[https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671\(15\)01297-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671(15)01297-6)>
- Holton, G.A., 2004. Defining risk. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 60(6), pp. 19-25. <<https://doi.org/10.2469/faj.v60.n6.2669>>
- Jansen, E.T.J., 2019. The five-factor model in The Netherlands. In thesis.eur.nl. <<https://thesis.eur.nl/pub/49650/Bsc-Thesis-Eduard-Th.J.-Jansen.pdf>>
- Jiao, W. and Lilti, J.J., 2017. Whether profitability and investment factors have additional explanatory power comparing with Fama-French Three-Factor Model: empirical evidence on Chinese A-share stock market. *China Finance and Economic Review*, 5(1). <<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40589-017-0051-5>>
- Karabay, A., 2018. *Fama- French Beş Faktör Varlık Fiyatlama Modeli Türkiye Geçerliliğinin Test Edilmesi*. Istanbul University.
- Karaömer, Y., 2017. *Fama-French Beş Faktör Varlık Fiyatlama Modeli: BİST Üzerine Uygulama*. Mustafa Kemal University. <<https://acikbilim.yok.gov.tr/handle/20.500.12812/669463>>
- Kartal, O., 2019. *Fama French 5 Faktör Modelinin Katılım Endeksi Üzerinde İncelenmesi*. Duzce University.
- Kirman Başpehlivan, B.N., 2019. *Fama – French Dört Faktörlü Modelin Gelişmekte Olan Piyasalarda Test Edilmesi*. Pamukkale University.
- Kubota, K. and Takehara, H., 2018. Does the Fama and French Five-Factor Model Work Well in Japan? *International Review of Finance*, 18(1), pp. 137-146. <<https://doi.org/10.1111/irfi.12126>>
- Ljungström, F. and Nilsson, S., 2019. *An Empirical Study of CAPM, the Fama-French three-factor and the Fama-French five-factor Model-A Study Performed on the Swedish Stock Market*. <<https://gupea.ub.gu.se/handle/2077/60618>>
- Machado, M.A.V., Faff, R. and Silva, S.C. de S.e., 2017. Applicability of Investment and Profitability Effects in Asset Pricing Models. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*, 21(6), pp. 851-874. <<https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-7849rac2017170027>>
- Musawa, N., Kapena, S. and Shikaputo, C., 2018. A comparative analysis of Fama-French Five and Three-Factor model in explaining stock returns variation. *International Journal of Economics*, 3(1), pp. 30-48. <<https://iprjb.org/journals/index.php/IJECON/article/view/690>>
- Reilly, F.K. and Brown, K.C., 2002. Investment Analysis and Portfolio Management. In *Cengage Learning*. <<https://doi.org/10.2307/2327255>>
- Sondemir, S., 2018. *İslami Üç Faktör Varlık Fiyatlama Modeli; Katılım Endeksi Üzerine Bir Uygulama*. Düzce University.
- Sonubi, Y., 2019. *Size and Value Effect: Application of the Fama French Three-Factor Model in the Irish Stock Market*. <<http://norma.ncirl.ie/3972/>>
- SPL, 2019. 1382 *Dar Kapsamlı Sermaye Piyasası Mevzuatı ve Meslek Kuralları*. pp. 14-15.

- Sultanov, R., 2010. *An Analysis of the Performance of Investment Companies: Evidence from the Istanbul Stock Exchange*. Middle East Technical University. <<https://open.metu.edu.tr/handle/11511/19637>>
- Taha, R. and Elgiziry, K., 2016. A five-factor asset pricing model: Empirical evidence from Egypt. *International Journal of Business*, 21(4), pp. 342-372. <https://www.academia.edu/download/59284015/A_FiveFactor_Asset_Pricing_Model_Empirical_Evidence_from_Egypt-International_Journal_of_Business20190517-48977-14el6r.pdf>
- TÜSİAD, 2008. Kurumsal risk yönetimi. In TÜSİAD.
- Yayıkcı, G., 2019. *Sermaye Varlıkları Fiyatlama Modeli: Borsa İstanbul Uygulaması*. Kütahya Dumlupınar University.
- Yolsal, H., 2005. Hisse senetlerinin beklenen getiri ve risklerinin tahmininde alternatif modeller. *Maliye Araştırma Merkezi Konferansları*, 47, pp. 179-199. <<https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/iuamk/issue/745/8045>>
- Yücel, Ö., 2013. *Sermaye Varlıklarını Fiyatlandırma Modellerinin İstanbul Menkul Kıymetler Borsası Üzerinde Uygulanabilirliğinin Analizi*. Ankara University.
- Zeren, F., Yılmaz, T. and Belke, M., 2018. Fama French Beş Faktör Varlık Fiyatlama Modelinin Geçerliliğinin Test Edilmesi:Türkiye Örneği. *Uluslararası Katılımlı 22. Finans Sempozyumu*, 5. <https://www.academia.edu/download/57855946/fama-french_five_factor.pdf>

Dynamic relationship between external debt and unemployment in Sub-Saharan Africa

Samuel Erasmus ALNAA

Bolgatanga Technical University, Ghana
sam.alnaa@gmail.com

Juabin MATEY

Bolgatanga Technical University, Ghana
e.juabin@gmail.com

Abstract. *The struggle to reduce cyclical unemployment by Sub-Saharan African countries is as a result of their inability to integrate fiscal policies into macroeconomic goals and establish independent, well-resourced bodies to manage borrowed funds. We examine the dynamic relationship between external debt and unemployment in Sub-Saharan Africa using data from 25 countries. This study demonstrates a direct relationship between foreign debt and unemployment, which is attributed to the erroneous application of discretionary fiscal policy decisions and the inefficient use of borrowed funds. Evidence also suggests a nonlinear relationship between external debt and unemployment across the countries studied.*

Keywords: external debt, investments, unemployment, job opportunity, fiscal policy discipline.

JEL Classification: E17, F34, F35, G18, J21, J64.

1. Introduction

A recent report by the International Labour Organization (ILO) indicates that there are more than half a billion unemployed and underemployed people worldwide (ILO, 2020). This situation is exacerbated by a resurgence of the financial squeeze through excessive external fund borrowing and its misappropriation. It is essential to have a fiscally disciplined approach to public investments that can guarantee the creation of new jobs using external borrowing. Externally sourced funds create money for development initiatives in an economy; however, when these funds are misappropriated, they worsen a country's macroeconomic vulnerability (Gill and Pinto, 2005; Manasseh et al., 2022). The national debt in Sub-Saharan Africa has witnessed steady growth, with debt servicing costs alone accounting for 15% of foreign exchange income – measured in-terms of revenue from exports of goods and services together with inflows from foreign remittances – (The Economic Intelligence Unit – EIU, 2022). Average public debt in the region hovered around 57% of GDP, in 2017, estimated to have swollen by 20% in just five years, raising concerns as the situation does not have a contractionary effect on unemployment (see, e.g., Selassie, 2018).

The COVID-19 pandemic and the Russian-Ukrainian war caused the global total debt (GTD) to rise rapidly, adversely affecting global economies in several dimensions. Global unemployment has risen to 6.5 percent, resulting in a decline in living standards (UNSTATS, 2020). Several studies, including Manasseh et al. (2022) and Iyola (1999), have found that external debt has contributed to an increase in African unemployment. Corroborating this revelation, Idenyi, Efeyinwa, and Gabriel (2016) discovered that an increase in public debt by one percent increases unemployment by 1.6 percent. Shuaibu, Muhammad, Abdullahi, and Qwazawa's (2021) research also shows a direct link between public debt and unemployment. It is also worth noting that none of these studies finds evidence of an inverse relationship between government debt and unemployment, which leaves a literature gap for investigation using a cross-national sample.

Research shows that increasing public debt, particularly in Africa, has little or no positive impact on employment creation (Ehikioya et al., 2020; Al-Tamimi and Jaradat, 2019). A surge in unjustified external borrowing is evident in most African countries with no positive results on employment creation. It is apparent that funds borrowed from external sources are largely spent on recurrent items at the expense of job-producing investments or diverted to unspecified "destinations". (Ehikioya et al., 2020; Al-Tamimi and Jaradat, 2019; Chimezie et al., 2020; Senadza et al., 2017). As a result of the unrestrained misappropriation of externally borrowed financial resources, the need for external credit has sparked heated debate. According to Ehikioya et al. (2020), obtaining external credit is practically a curse for Africans. Indeed, over 70% of borrowed funds that should have been invested in projects that reduce poverty through job creation go "missing" as a result of poor governance (n.d.).

This current study attempts to provide answers to the following questions: What is the impact of external debt on unemployment in the twenty-five sampled countries in Sub-Saharan Africa? Is the relationship between external debt and unemployment linear or non-linear? Having obtained relevant results from the analysis, we would be capable of

providing informed national policy directions. Policymakers can use these analyses to design policies that would ensure long-term economic stability and growth. The uniqueness of this study lies in its contribution to the literature on external borrowings and its short- and long-term impacts on employment creation. It also draws the attention of stakeholders to the dire consequences of the misappropriation of borrowed funds on the real economy.

Again, the novelty of this research is the use of sys-GMM to analyze the external debt-unemployment nexus with a cross-country sample, unlike a couple of sighted studies that are a single-country sample (Evans, 2022; Asafo and Matuka, 2019; Ogonna et al., 2016). The bulk of the identified areas researched in the literature have been the debt-growth nexus, faintly capturing unemployment issues or in different continent using different econometric approaches (Cahyadin and Ratwianingsih, 2020; Altvater and Vale, 1988). This study goes a step further by controlling for the annual GDP, inflation, and population growth rates. These macroeconomic variables have been proven to influence the outcome of unemployment in study models that have incorporated them.

Under the golden rule of national indebtedness, borrowed funds are expected to be invested in areas where jobs can be created. This will eventually boost household and national consumption, with multiplier effects on national purse (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. *External debt circuit*

Source: Adapted and modified from Mihaiu (2014).

This paper is organized into five sections. The rest of the sections are as follows: a review of the literature in Section II; methods and model specifications in Section III; presentation of results and subsequent discussion in the fourth (IV) section; and finally, in Section V, the conclusion is drawn, and recommendations are made for policy implementation.

2. Literature review

2.1. Theoretical literature

The majority of the literature on external debt concentrates on the link between external debt and economic growth (Dey and Tareque, 2020; Asafo et al., 2019; Manasseh et al., 2022; Ohiomu, 2020; Al Kharusi and Ada, 2018). This trend of research has gained acceptance by some development economists (e.g., Nafziger, 1993) for its growth and developmental prospects, although some economic theories (the Debt Overhang and Liquidity Constraint Theories) argue that external debt, unless prudently invested in productive sectors of the economy to promote economic growth in both developing and the developed countries through job creation, could constitute a source of worry as a result of the crowding-out effect (Krugman, 1988; Al Kharusi and Ada, 2018). A debt overhang-investment analysis performed by the International Monetary Fund (1989) suggests that the liquidity constraint and debt overhang theories explain slump investments in debt-mutilated countries.

Thus, with macroeconomic implications, hiring temporary labour with externally borrowed funds relaxes the liquidity constraint hypothesis. Although the provision of permanent employment is expensive, it is rather productive, especially if employment is in the vocational, industrial, and technical sectors of the economy, as it reduces the urge to borrow excessively to attend to the ever-increasing unemployment rates. This typically holds in the long run, when investments in human capital begin to yield positive results and reduce pressure on the national wage bill, as self-employment would have gained firm ground. Thus, fixed contractual bills on savings and foreign reserves are reduced considerably (Al Kharusi and Ada, 2018). Following Presbitero's (2012) study, countries that invest in the industrial sector become much more productive than their peers and tend to prudently apply borrowed funds, thereby curbing the tendency toward capital flight.

2.2. Empirical literature

2.2.1. External debt and unemployment

The empirical literature finds mixed results for external debt-unemployment nexus, either implicitly or explicitly. An indirect relationship (positive impact) is particularly evident in terms of the national government's ability to use borrowed funds to create jobs through sustained investments in the industrial sector. For instance, the implicit negative external debt-unemployment relationship was confirmed in a study by Sanchez-Juarez and Garcia-Almada (2016), who assessed public debt, public investment, and economic growth in Mexico. Indirectly, a good investment strategy targeting the industrial sector could create job opportunities for the youth in particular. Senadza et al. (2017) theoretically assert the relevance of external debt in terms of a country's making funds available for capital investment when borrowing to finance a budget deficit. Employment opportunities are created by making funds available for capital investment. In this manner, external debt positively and implicitly affects job creation. It is becoming increasingly impossible to find a single study that explicitly links external debt to unemployment or employment, either by reducing or increasing it respectively.

In theory, Ehikioya et al. (2020) appreciate governments' fiscal policies to invest in human resources and income-generating projects. Available idle but willing labour could be trained to take up technical jobs in the industrial sector, as most external funds are provided with strings attached. They indirectly linked external debt to employment creation. As (Ehikioya et al., 2020) stated earlier, when borrowed funds are judiciously invested with employment as the benchmark, the teeming unemployed will be offered the opportunity to have either temporary or permanent jobs, depending on the sector of investment. Matthew and Mordecai (2016) observed an indirect relationship between external debt and economic performance. Their argument finds solace in the neoclassical tradition of macroeconomic policy decisions that favour improved economic output through profitable investment. And as we do know, job creation is a direct function of viable investments in the country. In his appraisal of the effect of debt on an economy, Cohen (1992) alludes to the indirect relationship between external debt and investment. This, he emphasised, will only be possible when borrowed funds are prudently applied to fetch adequate returns to meet debt-interest-servicing obligations.

Studies, including those of Mihaiu (2014), find that public debt is proportionally related to public investment, thus discouraging national governments from increasing public debt because it does not simulate investment with the prospects of job creation in the economy. National governments require external funding to invest in profitable sectors to create employment opportunities. The challenge is that many externally sourced funds are misappropriated by bad governance. Another study that buys into the inverse external debt-unemployment relationship is that of Ehikioya et al. (2020), which bemoans the suboptimal use of externally borrowed funds in debt servicing to the detriment of productive investments where the idle labour force could have otherwise obtained temporary or permanent self-employed jobs. This finding is implicitly linked to the debt overhang hypothesis. As a result of these inconclusive deliberations on whether external debts serve the interests in which they were contracted, policymakers and academics alike continue to encourage writers to go the extra mile to find the ultimate results.

2.2.2. GDP-Unemployment nexus

Economic growth (using GDP as a proxy) and unemployment trends are important macroeconomic variables that are closely tracked by policymakers and the public because they help form a picture of a country's economy and level of development. Although quite aged, Okun's (1962) study acknowledges that there is usually a less than two percent increase in unemployment, caused by a percentage decrease in economic growth (proxied by GDP). Levine (2013) articulates this position of Okun's law by emphasising the negative relationship between the real GDP growth rate and unemployment. The negative unemployment-economic growth (GDP as a proxy) nexus has a long standing in the empirical literature (Hjazeen et al., 2021; Dayioglu and Aydin, 2021; Basnett and Sen, 2013; Melamed, Hartwig and Grant, 2011). It is worthy of note that growth should occur in sectors that can create employment, such as the construction, service, and manufacturing industries. Except for studies that struggled to disengage the reality of Okun's Law by illuminating the disproportionate change in unemployment resulting from a change in economic growth (e.g., Sanchez and Liborio, 2012), this study has failed to establish empirical evidence suggesting that real GDP growth can result in a deteriorating unemployment situation. Even in the case of Levine (2013), she emphasises that a shred of contrary evidence defusing the traditional inverse GDP-unemployment nexus may only look at where employment growth is less rapid than the growth in the labour force. Until then, the conventional negative unemployment-real GDP relationship will be upheld.

2.2.3. Inflation and unemployment

There is a well-established inverse relationship between unemployment and inflation, two macroeconomic variables that economists frequently use to assess an economy's health (see Perera and Wickramanayake, 2016). Lui (2008) finds a negative relationship between unemployment and inflation. As a result, as prices rise, entrepreneurs are encouraged to produce more in order to benefit from higher prices. This is accomplished by hiring more workers to supplement existing employee strength, thereby lowering unemployment.

2.2.4. Relationship between population growth and unemployment

Although the population-unemployment relationship is rife with hypotheses, common sense dictates that as the population grows, so does the unemployment rate, with the defused effects frequently overlooked. According to Skold and Tesfay (2020), there is a negative correlation between population growth and unemployment in this common-sense scenario. They believe that population growth drives consumption and encourages entrepreneurs to produce goods and services with increased demand. Singh and Kumar (2014) demonstrate a clear link between population growth and unemployment. Population growth has a positive effect on the labor force, leaving the majority of people unemployed. There is a mismatch between the labor supply and job opportunities. Population is regarded as the supply factor, whereas the economic conditions of a country are regarded as the demand factor. A similar study by Ali, Omar, and Yusuf (2021) revealed a 5.2 percentage point increase in unemployment resulting from an increased population in Tanzania.

3. Methods and model specification

We obtained data from the World Bank Development Indicators (WDI) made possible by the International Monetary Fund (IMF). These balanced panel data were collected from twenty-five (25) Sub-Saharan African countries that had a complete dataset for the variables under study, spanning 2010 to 2020 (annual frequency). The objective of this study was to establish the dynamic relationship between external debt and unemployment in these twenty-five Sub-Saharan African countries. As a result, we used the natural logarithm of two fundamental variables variance (External Debt Stock and Unemployment); taking a log of your data may result in transformed data with homogeneous as the independent and response variables, respectively. The paper incorporated three control variables (annual Gross Domestic Product-Growth Rate [GDP-GR], annual Inflation Rate [INFL-R], and annual Population Growth Rate [POP-GR]) to provide evidence of a hypothesised negative relationship (positive impact) between external debt and unemployment.

3.1. Empirical model

$$\ln UEMPL - R_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln UEMPL - R_{(1-t)} + \beta_2 \ln EXT DTS_{it} + \beta_3 \ln X_{it} + \eta_i + \lambda_t + \xi_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$\ln UEMP - R_{it} = \omega_\sigma + \omega_1 \ln UEMP - R_{(1-t)} + \omega_2 \ln EXT DTS_{it} + \omega_3 (\ln EXT DTS)_{it}^2 + \omega_4 \ln X_{it} + \eta_i + \lambda_t + \xi_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$\ln UEMP - R_{it} = \omega_\sigma + \omega_1 \ln UEMP - R_{(1-t)} + \omega_2 \ln EXT DTS_{it} + \omega_3 \ln (EXT DTS)_{it}^2 + \omega_4 (\ln GDP - GR + \ln INFL - R + \ln POPG - R)_{it} + \eta_i + \lambda_t + \xi_{it} \quad (3)$$

(This model above is adapted from Ehikioya et al., 2020.)

3.2. Robustness model specification

$$\begin{aligned} \ln UEMP - R_{it} = & \omega_{\alpha} + \omega_1 \ln UEMP - R_{(1-t)} + \omega_2 \ln EXT DTS_{it} + \omega_3 \ln (EXT DTS)_{it}^2 \\ & + \omega_4 (\ln GDP - GR + \ln INFL - R + \ln POPG - R)_{it} + (\mathbf{lnINT} - \mathbf{R})_{it} + \eta_i + \lambda_t + \xi_{it} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

To verify the robustness of the model, Equation (4) was developed to include interest rates (italicized and bold in Equation (4)) and redefine the GDP portion of the model into real GNI (formerly GNP) (see Results and discussion).

UMP-R is the annual unemployment rate in selected countries, EXT DTS is the external debt stock of respective countries (defined as the proportion of sovereign debt tied to GNI), \mathbb{X} represents all standard control variables, with country-specific effects represented by η , and the time effect represented by λ . The error term is proxied by ξ_{it} , with "it" denoting country "i" in period "t" for the sample space. The one-year lagged UEMPR is given by $UEMPR_{(1-t)}$ and $EXTSTS^2$ connotes the external debt stock squared term to GNI to test for a nonlinear relationship between the external debt stock and unemployment in the selected countries. The annual inflation rate, GDP growth rate, and population growth rate are control variables represented by \mathbb{X} .

This study used the two-step system generalized method of moments (sys-GMM) estimator of Holtz-Eakin, Newey, and Rosen (1988), Arellano and Bond (1991), and Blundell and Bond (1998) to estimate a dynamic panel model from twenty-five (25) Sub-Saharan African countries. The sys-GMM technique was adopted because of its ability to isolate the inefficiencies of the first differences of instruments that are uncorrelated with the fixed effect, using the difference GMM estimator modelled by Blundell and Bond (1998). Consequently, the generalized least squares (GLS) model was augmented to address the validity and robustness of the results using GMM. It is important to emphasize that the use of GMM allows for the correction of autocorrelation and endogeneity challenges arising from panel data.

A variety of data tests were performed to check data stationarity, as the data obtained were time-series. Therefore, a test for unit roots using the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) methods is conducted (see Table 4). Therefore, the ADF and PP unit test models are specified as follows.

$$\Delta \lambda_t = \delta \lambda_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i \Delta \mathbb{X}_{t-i} + \xi_t \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta \lambda_t = \pi \lambda_{t-1} + \beta_i \mathbb{D}_{t-1} + \xi_t \quad (6)$$

Where Δ – the first difference, P – the lag operator, t – the time subscript, ξ – error term, \mathbb{D}_{t-1} – deterministic trend component.

The decision is made when the test statistic is greater or < the ADF critical value. The cointegration test was performed once the data were confirmed to be integrated in Order I(1). The reason for the test performance was to establish the presence of a long-run relationship between external debt stock and unemployment in the 25 African countries, using Johansen's (1991) cointegration test. The Johansen cointegration test is preferred

because of its ability to resolve the measurement challenges associated with Eagle and Granger techniques (see Ehikioya et al., 2020). Following this, the restricted vector autoregressive (VAR) model defined in the error correction parlance, the Johansen model, is specified as follows:

$$\Delta \Pi_t = \Omega + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \mu_j \Delta \Pi_{t-j} + \Theta \Pi_{t-k} + \xi_t \quad (7)$$

where Δ represents the first difference notation, Π_t refers to $p \times 1$, the vector of the n variable, Ω denotes $p \times 1$ (a constant vector representing a direct movement in a system), and k is the lag structure. The Gaussian white noise residual vector is represented by ξ_t , while μ_j is defined as; $p \times (k-1)$ matrix explaining the short run changes between and among variables across the " p " equation at the " j^{th} " lag. Π is a $(p \times p)$ coefficient matrix that represents the cointegration vectors. The vector error correction model by Johansen (1991), which employs the trace statistic, was used to evaluate the reduced rank of matrix Π . Thus, the following model was formulated:

$$\lambda_{\text{Trace}} = -T \sum_{i=r+1}^p \ln(1 - \lambda'_i), \text{ and the Maximum Eigenvalue method;}$$

$$\lambda_{\text{max}} = -T \ln(1 - \lambda'_{r+t}) \quad (8)$$

The model positions T as the number of observations in the 25-country sample and r as the number of independent series. Lambda (λ) in the model denotes the eigenvalues. This study posits that the null hypothesis should be rejected if the trace or max-eigen-statistic p -value is greater than 5 per cent. If there is an established fact that the time series has a long-run relationship, then variables are cointegrated; in this case, in an event where the economy experiences a shock in the short term, there is a high probability of reconvergence of these variables in the long run (Ehikioya et al., 2020). In real economic terms, if the economy becomes destabilized as a result of unexpected events, normalcy is assured as the economy will get back on track.

4. Results and discussion

Data properties

Table 1. Unit root test results

Variable			ADF-Fisher Chi-square					
	Level		First Difference		Level		First Difference	
	Const.	Const. & Trend	Const.	Const. & Trend	Const.	Const. & Trend	Const.	Const. & Trend
lnUNEMPLR	43.0438	53.0906	120.176***	91.6878***	24.753	20.5896	129.010***	90.9328***
lnEXTDT	43.422	16.2582	134.714***	134.636***	58.0734	15.7647	258.323***	241.326***
lnGDPGR	120.640***	102.481***	313.993***	245.712***	231.846***	200.035***	1327.86***	2515.63***
lnINFLR	183.095***	171.600***	440.901***	350.723***	281.494***	315.083***	1402.17***	2499.21***
lnPOPGR	351.233***	521.075***	338.209***	568.979***	76.5752**	43.4915	125.247***	340.450***

Note: *** and ** denote significance at the 1% and 5% levels, respectively.

Source: Authors' computation from WDIs (2020).

Time series data were used to analyze the external debt-unemployment nexus by employing the two-step system GMM. This study assumes the presence of a unit root (null hypothesis). To establish this, this study adopted augmented Dickey (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests. The tests revealed nonstationary data at levels (see Table 2). Having ascertained this, there was a need to integrate all variables used in the study at the first difference. After the first difference, the variables were stationary in order one (I[1]).

Table 2. Johansen Fisher panel unrestricted cointegration rank test results (trace and maximum eigenvalue)

Hypothesised No. of CE(s)	Fisher Stat.* (from trace test)	Prob.	Fisher Stat.* (from Max-eigen test)	Prob.
None*	1539	0.0000	843.3	0.0000
At most 1	1169	0.0000	1312	0.0000
At most 2	723.7	0.0000	406.6	0.0000
At most 3	402.2	0.0000	240.1	0.0000
At most 4	202.4	0.0000	202.4	0.0000

* Probability test performed using asymptotic chi-square distribution.

Source: Authors' computation from WDIs (2020).

According to the establishment of order one (see Table 1), it is necessary to ascertain the long-run equilibrium between the variables (Johansen, 1991) after adjusting Fisher's (1932) cointegration test, as shown in Table 2. The Johansen-Fisher cointegration test rejected the null hypothesis of no cointegration relationship between the variables; hence, a long-run relationship exists. Therefore, the results show that external debt could affect unemployment in all the sampled countries in the long run.

4.1. Regression results

Table 3. Two-step system generalised method of moments (sys-GMM) results

Variable	Model 1-Linear		Model 2-Nonlinear		Model 3-Combined	
	Coeff.	Std. Error	Coeff.	Std. Error	Coeff.	Std. Error
UNEMPLR _{t-1}	0.6233**	0.198	0.6785**	0.028	0.3699**	0.051
lnEXTDTS	0.4172**	0.003			0.0123**	0.007
ln(EXTDTS) ²			0.6156***	0.001	0.8496***	0.005
lnGDPGR	0.0307**	0.008	0.2672***	0.008	0.2604***	0.008
lnINFLR	0.1306**	0.008	0.5809**	0.019	0.0949**	0.017
lnPOPGR	0.0127*	0.091	0.7544**	0.062	0.1073*	0.086
Constant	0.3931**	0.013	0.4185***	0.029	0.5832***	0.024
Observations	575		575		575	
No. of Countries	25		25		25	
Hansen OIR Test (p-value)	0.308		0.137		0.263	
Wald chi-sq.(6) p-value	0.000		0.000		0.000	
AR(1) p-value	0.082		0.691		0.071	
AR(2) p-value	0.062		0.551		0.362	

Source: Authors' computations based on WDIs (2020). ***, **, and * denote significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively.

The study set out to determine the dynamic relationship between external debt and unemployment in 25 countries in Saharan Africa. Before the robustness check for the validity of the results using the generalized least squares (GLS) method, we ran the analysis on the linear and nonlinear specifications using sys-GMM (see Table 3). To achieve the general objective, this study began by estimating the linear relationship between external debt and unemployment using the full variable sample controlled for GDP, INFLR, and POPGR in Column three of Table 3 (Model 3-Linear). Model 1 shows that external debt has a statistically significant positive relationship with unemployment. At the outset of this

study, we hypothesize that external debt stock has a positive impact on unemployment. Thus, as governments borrow and apply for these funds judiciously, the economic burden is reduced through job creation, which positively affects unemployment. The results of the linear model are in sharp contrast with our earlier hypotheses.

The finding in this study is in contrast with the negative relationship established by Sanchez-Juarez and Garcia-Almada (2016), who explained that borrowed funds strategically invested to target the industrial sector could serve as an employment cow for youth in particular. Ideally, external debt should positively affect unemployment (a negative relationship); however, the misapplication of borrowed funds negatively reflects citizens' welfare. In line with the reports in columns 2 and 3 of Table 3, we find that the coefficients of external debt squared are still statistically positive at the one per cent, reiterating the negative impact of external debt unemployment on the citizenry of these countries.

Column 2 shows the case of nonlinear analysis, while column 3 reflects the combined or full-sample scenario. These results re-echo the gravity of fund misappropriation, to the detriment of economic growth. This is a panacea for economic instability, with attendant effects on citizenry. As an objective of the study, the results confirmed that the external debt-unemployment nexus is nonlinear. The economic sense is that the application of borrowed funds by the sampled countries is not uniform across board. Therefore, the effects are not linear for the individual countries. Mathematically, a unit increase in external borrowing deteriorates the already volatile unemployment situation by approximately 0.62%, on average. These results are consistent with those reported by Ehikioya et al. (2020), Al-Tamimi and Jaradat (2019), Chimezie et al. (2020) and Senadza et al. (2017), that externally borrowed funds neglect job-providing investments or are diverted to unexplained "destinations". As put forth by Ehikioya et al. (2020), the eminence of debt overhang is glaring when external borrowings are unreasonably accumulated without positively impacting employment creation.

The statistically significant positive relationship between GDP growth rate and unemployment established in this study suggests that not all GDP growth is translated into the required purpose. Theoretically, the implication is that an increase in GDP does not necessarily positively impact employment, as confirmed by the results in Table 3. This revelation is in opposition to the postulates by Okun (1962) that a percentage increase in GDP would result in a 3-percentage increase in job creation. The results of this study contradict Okun's law by presenting a contrary result. Although quite unsuspected, the established positive relationship points to stakeholders being wary that mere increases in absolute figures are insufficient for a positive impact on macroeconomic stability through improved job creation.

As the prices of goods and services increase, producers take advantage of manufacturing to compete with rising prices for profit. This study reveals a significantly positive relationship between inflation and unemployment. As indicated earlier, producers need to increase productivity to compete with the rising prices of goods and services, and there is a need to employ more labor to help in the production processes, thereby positively impacting employment (reduction in unemployment rates). This positive relationship can

be explained in two ways. The established significant positive relationship here means that as prices increase persistently, the cost of raw materials/inputs becomes expensive for producers, thereby deteriorating purchasing power. Fewer inputs are now acquired, which will require relatively few labor forces to work on these inadequate inputs, which theoretically worsens the unemployment situation. In other words, when inflation is spiral, the cost of living has an equal direct effect: workers demand an increase in wages or salaries, which tends to increase the cost of labor. Employers, going by this trend will be compelled to reduce the amount of labour hired, thus, increasing the unemployment rate in the system.

4.2. Robustness check

Table 4. Robustness check results – Generalised Least Square (GLS)

Variable	Model 1-Linear		Model 2-Nonlinear		Model 3-Combined	
	Coeff.	Std. Error	Coeff.	Std. Error	Coeff.	Std. Error
UNEMPLR _{t-1}	0.1036***	0.198	0.1034***	0.002	0.1035***	0.002
lnEXTDTS	0.0449**	0.022			0.0122***	0.003
ln(EXTDTS) ²			0.7098**	0.028	0.5951***	0.004
lnGDPGR	0.0132**	0.021	0.0138**	0.008	0.0141***	0.021
lnINFLR	0.0194	0.015	0.0131	0.016	0.0137*	0.016
lnPOPGR	0.1278*	0.029	0.1270***	0.029	0.1262***	0.029
lnINT-R	0.4211**	0.032	0.3301*	0.021	0.4112**	0.033
Constant	0.8444***	0.013	0.9919***	0.053	0.9481***	0.125
Observations	575		575		575	
No. of Countries	25		25		25	
R ²	0.751		0.751		0.751	
Adjusted R ²	0.749		0.749		0.749	
Durbin-Watson	1.9646		1.9625		1.9634	
F-Statistics	371.129		372.655		310.142	
Prob (F-Statistic)	0.0000		0.0000		0.0000	

Source: Authors' computations based on WDIs (2020). ***, **, and * denote significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively.

To authenticate the results produced by the GMM system, researchers employed the generalized least squares (GLS) approach to establish a possible link between external debt stock and unemployment in selected countries in Sub-Saharan Africa. A test is performed to verify the robustness of the obtained results. The interest rate was added as a control variable, while GDP was redefined as the real GNI. After performing this test, the results remained significantly unchanged with only negligible variations (Table 4). The two main variables (external debt stock and unemployment) maintain statistical significance with the same signs, although unemployment becomes significant at the 5% level. The nonlinear relationship between external debt stock and unemployment was validated as they showed statistically significant results (see Tables 3 and 4). All control variables reflected similar results, as shown in Table 4, indicating consistency.

The model explains the variability in unemployment using the *p*-value (1%) of the 371 F-statistic. The explanatory variables in the model explain their contribution to determining the effect of external debt stock on unemployment by approximately 75 per cent. Invariably, 25 per cent of the causes of unemployment are attributed to different sets of variables outside the model. These results confirm that external debt is a positive game

changer in the useful application of borrowed funds. However, other external influences work together to offset the positive effects of external debt. These externalities could include the unmonitored disbursement processes of funds and weak legal and bureaucratic institutions. In both Tables 4 and 5, the results speak volumes of the fact that the hypothesised negative relationship between external debt and unemployment is one reality if a proper governance system in terms of fund disbursement and monitoring is implemented.

Table 5. *Diagnostic test*

Null Hypothesis	Test	F-statistic	P-value	Chi (X^2)/ <i>T – statistic</i>	P-value
No serial correlation	Breusch Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test	1.031411	0.3522	2.67246	0.2256
No conditional Heteroskedasticity	Heteroskedasticity test: Breusch-Bagan- Godfrey	1.2331634	0.3151	8.13931	0.2599
There is normality	Jarque-Bera	-	-	0.05679	0.8966
No significant specification error	Ramsey RESET test	0.665116	0.3948	0.87725	0.3821

Source: Researchers' computation (2022).

With a Jarque-Bera test statistic of 0.05679 and a p -value of 0.8966, the null hypothesis of the presence of normality was confirmed. Thus, the residual series is normally distributed. In addition, a serial correlation test was conducted using the Breusch Godfrey serial correlation LM test, which demonstrated the absence of serial correlation among variables and error terms. The heteroscedasticity test indicates that there is a constant variance property, inferring the presence of homoscedasticity.

4. Conclusion and recommendations

As African economies continue to accumulate debt, it is necessary to study how external debt affects unemployment. This empirical cross-country study provides evidence of a dynamic relationship between external debt stock and unemployment in Sub-Saharan Africa, using the sys-GMM approach. A linear exploration of the relationship between external debt and unemployment revealed a direct relationship. Unsustained external borrowing affects national governments' ability to engage in public investment, which has an indirect effect on employment creation.

It is important to note that some countries have achieved positive results from the judicious application of externally borrowed funds in several ways, including improved job creation and macroeconomic stability. Evidence also suggests a nonlinear relationship between external debt and unemployment across nations. The implication is that external debt has no uniform ramifications because of the differences in governance systems and autonomy-granted offices in charge of managing national debt across countries. The effectiveness of debt management by the occupants of these offices also stems from how well they are resourced.

The theoretical implication for the positive external debt-unemployment relationship is that, as national governments engage in unsustainable external debt levels (above the 50% threshold of GDP at face value), public investments in capital projects that indirectly

provide employment are thwarted. The more national governments seek foreign funds, the more likely it is that unemployment rates will increase in the economy. Practically, foreign borrowed funds not invested in job creation sectors, such as the vocational and industrial sectors, invite economic hardship and insecurity into the system, as currently pertains to Ghana.

Another implication is that a sustained increase in capital flight and external debt accumulation would decrease governments' capacity to raise additional tax revenue because capital escaping the country cannot be taxed, thereby limiting their ability to make public investments. Since capital leaving the country cannot be taxed, this would decrease the capacity of the government to increase spending. A high debt service ratio may constitute a drain on domestic revenue mobilization, which will stifle domestic investments and negatively impact the continent's growth prospects through government spending.

This study encourages policymakers to employ proper strategies to disburse borrowed funds to target sectors that have the potential to generate job opportunities of either a temporary or permanent nature, such as the technical and vocational arms of the economy. It is also necessary that borrowed funds are not spent on recurrent expenditures or used to service existing debts. Another area that needs attention is resourcing offices that are earmarked for managing external debt to permit independent operations.

It is suggested that further study of the external debt-economic development nexus of all Sub-Saharan countries will provide another policy direction for sustained economic development. Economic growth is not necessarily economic development; therefore, studies on the external debt-economic growth nexus deny the laxity of going a step further to consider the welfare of the citizenry as a whole.

References

- Ali, O., Omar, M. and Yusuf, S., 2021. Population growth and unemployment in Zanzibar. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research*, 59(2), pp. 36-47. Retrieved from <<https://www.gssrr.org/index.php/JournalOfBasicAndApplied/article/view/1276>>
- Al Kharusi, S. and Ada, M.S., 2018. External debt and economic growth: the case of emerging economy. *Journal of Economic Integration*, 33(1), pp. 1141-1157, <<https://doi.org/10.11130/jei.2018.33.1.1141>>
- Al-Tamimi, K.A.M. and Jaradat, M.S., 2019. Impact of external debt on economic growth in Jordan for the period (2010-2017), *Int. J. Econ. Finance*, 11, pp. 114-118, <<https://doi.org/10.5539/ijef.v11n4p114>>
- Altvater, E. and Vale, M., 1988. The two sides of the coin: the relationship between unemployment and debt in the world economic crisis. *International Journal of Political Economy*, 18(2), pp. 85-101, <<http://www.jstor.org/stable/40470479>>
- Arellano, M. and Bond, S., 1991. Some tests of specification for panel data: Monte Carlo evidence and an application to employment equations. *Review of Economic Studies*, 58(2), pp. 277-297, <<http://www.jstor.org/stable/2297968>>

- Asafo, S.S., Matuka, A. and Dominic, N., 2019. External debt and economic growth: two-step system-GMM evidence for Sub-Saharan Africa Countries. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Management*, 6(1), pp. 39-48, <<https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.62.2019.61.39.48>>
- Basnett, Y. and Sen, R., 2013. *What do empirical studies say about economic growth and job creation in developing countries?* Institute. Economic and Private Sector, <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/57a08a2340f0b652dd005a6/Growth_and_labour_absorption.pdf>
- Blundell, R. and Bond, S., 1998. Initial conditions and moment restrictions in dynamic panel data models. *Journal of Econometrics*, 87, pp. 115-143, <[http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4076\(98\)00009-8](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4076(98)00009-8)>
- Chimezie, P.O., Omankhanlen, A.E. and Eriabie, S., 2020. Nexus between public finance and economic growth in Nigeria. *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, 17, pp. 184-194, <<https://doi.org/10.37394/23207.2020.17.20>>
- Cohen, D., 1992. Large external debt and (slow) domestic growth: a theoretical analysis. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, 19(5-7), pp. 1141-1163 <[https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1889\(94\)00822-Y](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1889(94)00822-Y)>
- Dayioglu, A. and Aydin, Y., 2021. Relationship between economic growth, unemployment, inflation, and current account balance: theory and case of Turkey. Chapters, in: Terzioğlu, M. K. and Djurovic, G., (Eds.), 2021. Linear and nonlinear financial Econometrics-theory and practice. *Intech Open*, <<https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.88099>>
- Dey, S.R. and Tareque, M., 2020. External debt and growth: role of stable macroeconomic policies. *Journal of Economics, Finance, and Administrative Science*, 25(50), pp. 185-204, <<https://doi.org/10.1108/JEFAS05-2019-0069>>
- Ehikioya, I. B., Omankhanlen, A.E., Osuma, G.O. and Inua, O.I., 2020. Dynamic relations between public external debt and economic growth in African countries: a curse or blessing?. *Journal of Open Innovation, Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(3), p. 88, <<https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc6030088>>
- EIU, 2022. Debt repayment costs are rising fast for many African countries: They are unlikely to default this year, but face trouble by 2024, <https://www.economist.com/middle-east-and-africa/2022/04/30/debtrepayment-costs-are-rising-fast-for-many-african-countries>
- Fisher, R.A., 1933. *Statistical Methods for Research Workers*. *Nature*, 131, 383, <<https://doi.org/10.1038/131383b0>>
- Gill, I. and Pinto, B., 2005. Public debt in developing countries: has the market based model worked? Policy Research Working Paper series (3674), World Bank, Washington, DC, <<https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/8632>>
- Hjazeen, H., Seraj, M. and Ozdeser, H., 2021. The nexus between the economic growth and unemployment in Jordan, *Future Business Journal*, 7(1), pp. 1-8, <<https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-021-00088-3>>
- Holtz-Eakin, D., Newey, W. and Rosen, H.S., 1988. Estimating vector autoregressions with panel data. *Econometrica*, 56, pp. 1371-1395, <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/1913103>>
- ILO, 2020, 20th January. Insufficient paid work affects almost half a billion people, new ILO report shows, <https://www.ilo.org/global/about-theilo/newsroom/news/WCMS_734454/lang-en/index.htm>

- ILOSTAT, 2022, 10th March. Inflation more than doubled between March 2021 and March 2022, <<https://ilostat.ilo.org/inflation-more-than-doubled-between-march-2021-and-march-2022/>>
- IMF, (1989. IMF World Economic Outlook. Supplementary Note 1 Washington, D.C., IMF, 1989, <<https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/ar/archive/pdf/ar1989.pdf>>
- IMF Global Database, 2021, January. 2021 updates IMF Global Debt Database, <<https://www.imf.org/en/News/Seminars/Conferences/2021/12/15/2021update-of-the-imf-global-debt-database>>
- Johansen, S., 1991. Estimation and hypothesis testing of cointegration vectors in Gaussian vector autoregressive models. *Econometrica*, 59(6), pp. 1551-1580, <<https://doi.org/10.2307/2938278>>
- Krugman, P., 1993. Financing vs. forgiving a debt overhang. *Journal of Development Economics*, 29(3), pp. 253-268, <[https://doi.org/10.1016/03043878\(88\)90044-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/03043878(88)90044-2)>
- Levine, L., 2013. Economic growth and unemployment rate. CRS Report for Congress 7-5700, R42063, <<https://www.crs.gov>>
- Liborio, C.S. and Sanchez, J.M., 2012. The relationships among changes in GDP, employment, and Unemployment: This time it was different. Economic Synopsis, (13), <<https://files.stlouisfed.org/files/htdocs/publications/es/12/ES20120518.df>>
- Lui, L.Q., 2008. Inflation and unemployment: the roles of goods and labour markets institutions, <<http://qed.econ.queensu.ca/pub/students/phds/liuqian/JMP.pdf>>
- Manasseh, C.O., Abada, F.C., Okiche, E.L., Okanya, O., Nwakoby, I.C., Offu, P., (...), Nwonye, N.G., 2022. External debt and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa: does governance matter? *PLoS ONE*, 17(3), <<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0264082>>
- Matthew, A. and Mordecai, B., 2016. The Impact of public debt on economic development of Nigeria. *Asian Research Journal of Arts & Social Sciences*, 1(1), pp. 1-16, <<https://doi.org/10.9734/ARJASS/2016/27263>>
- Melamed, C., Hartwig, R. and Grant, U., 2011. *Jobs, growth, and poverty: what do we know, what don't? What should we know of this?.* Background note. London: Overseas Development Institute, <<https://cdn.odi.org/media/documents/7121.pdf>>
- Mihaiu, D.M., 2014. Analysis of public debt in the European Union-issues related to its sustainability. *Journal of International Studies*, 7(2), pp. 25-32, <<https://doi.org/10.14254/2071/8330.2014/72/2>>
- Nafziger, W.N., 1993. Debt, adjustment, and economic liberalization in Africa, *Journal of Economic*, 27(2), pp. 429-439, <<https://doi.org/10.1080/00213624.1993.11505426>>
- Ogonna, I.C., Idenyi, O., Ifeyinwa, A. and Gabriel, N., 2016. The Implications of rising public debt on unemployment in Nigeria: an auto regressive distributed lag approach. *Asian Research Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 1(1), pp. 1-15, <<https://doi.org/10.9734/arjass/2016/26394>>
- Ohiomu, S., 2020. External debt and economic growth nexus: empirical evidence from Nigeria. *The American Economist*, 65(2), pp. 330-343, <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0569434520914862>>
- Okun, A.M., 1962. Potential GNP: its measurement and significance. In Proceedings of the Business and Economics Statistics Section. Alexandria, VA: American Statistical Association, pp. 89-104, <<http://www.sciencedirect.com/reference/294493>>
- Perera, A. and Wickramanayake J., 2016. Determinants of commercial bank retail interest rate adjustments: evidence from a panel data model. *Journal of International Financial Markets Institutions and Money*, 45, pp. 1-20, <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intfin.2016.05.006>>
- Presbitero, A., 2012. Total public debt and growth in developing countries. *European Journal of Development Research*, 24(4), pp. 606-626, <<https://doi.org/10.1057/ejdr.2011.62>>

- Sánchez-Juárez, I. and García-Almada, R., 2016. Public debt, public investment and economic growth in Mexico. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 4(2), (6), <<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs4020006>>
- Selassie, A.A., 2018. The Debt Challenge to African Growth, <<https://www.projectsyndicate.org/commentary/sub-saharan-africa-rising-debt-levels-by-abebe-aemro-selassie-2018-05>>
- Senadza, B., Fiagbe, A.K. and Quartey, P., 2017. The effect of external debt on economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Business and Economic Sciences Applied Research*, 11(1), pp. 5917-5929, <<https://doi.org/10.25103/ijbesar.111.07>>
- Singh, H. and Kumar, S., 2014. Population growth, poverty, and unemployment in India: a contemporary state level analysis. *European Academic Research*, 1(12), <<http://euacademic.org/UploadArticle/409.pdf>>
- Sköld, E. and Tesfay, K., 2020. The relationship between inflation and unemployment in Sweden, thesis submitted to Mälardalen University, NAA305, <<https://www.divaportal.org/smash/get/diva2:1438547/FULLTEXT01.pdf>>
- The World Bank, 2022. Global growth to slow through 2023, adding risk of ‘hard landing’ in developing economies, <<https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/pressrelease/2022/01/11/global-recovery-economics-debt-commodity-inequality>>
- UN Report, 2020. Half a billion unemployed or underemployed world, <<https://www.dw.com/en/half-a-billion-unemployed-or-underemployed-worldwide-un-report/a-52081744>>
- UN Statistics, 2020. Promote sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work. COVID-19 has led to massive job losses particularly among youth and women, <<https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2021/goal-08/>>
- World Bank Development Indicators, 2022. International Labour Organisation, ILOSTAT database, <<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SL.UEM.TOTL.ZS>>

An analysis of factors influencing empowerment of rural women through Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana – National Rural Livelihood Mission (SGSY)

Dr. Ravi Kumar GUPTA

Madan Mohan Malaviya University of Technology, Gorakhpur, India
raviguptaeco@gmail.com

Udit MAHESHWARI

Madan Mohan Malaviya University of Technology, Gorakhpur, India
uditmaheshwari1035@gmail.com

Dr. Debendra Nath DAS

Mahatma Gandhi National Council of Rural Education, Hyderabad, India
dash.mgncre@gmail.com

Abstract. *Self-employment plays a prominent role in the improvement of the condition of unemployment. Those members who are engaged in self-employment are in a much better situation compared to wage-earning women members. The findings are based on 2 surveys conducted in 2005 and 2009 with the same members of Self Help Groups (SHGs), and the data collected from North Twenty-Four Parganas in the Southern region of West Bengal state of India. This study also analyzed economic and social demographic factors affecting the probability of both factors related to employment and empowerment.*

Keywords: women empowerment, self-help groups, self-employment, bivariate Probit, rural development.

JEL Classification: E24, H53, R58.

1. Introduction

Empowerment of women can be explained as resources and pre-conditions which assist the process that enhances the ability of women to take decisions and make their independent choices. These choices will influence outcomes which will have a direct impact on their welfare. Empowerment of women requires more active involvement in all activities, whether related to the private or public sphere of life either by an equal or full level of participation in social, economic, political and cultural decisions (Khaki, 2017, pp. 1040-1042).

The empowerment of women is a crucial factor in the economic development of any country, more specifically in developing and underdeveloped countries. Following the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the Indian government implemented the National Policy for Empowerment of Women in the year 2001, which created a feasible environment for the development, empowerment and promotion of the social and economic status of women to make them capable of utilizing their full potential along with supportive social and economic policies. To economically empower women, the concerned policy kept its focus on the micro-credit structure to create a provision of production and consumption-related credit facilities for women entangled in poverty. Earlier, adopting this policy, the Indian government implemented Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY) on 1st April 1999, which is also based on a micro-credit structure (Sud, 2003, pp. 4085-4087). This policy also puts an emphasis on Self Help Groups (SHGs) to create self-employment opportunities for poor rural people. This scheme attempted to associate poor rural women with institutional credit-granting institutions by using SHGs as a medium. This scheme included many dimensions of women's empowerment like institutional credit facilities, technical and non-technical training, technology, marketing and infrastructural facilities. Thus, these aspects empower poor rural women to act independently in all areas of eradication of poverty. Although financial facilities are the major determinant of the well-being of poor women and their families socially and economically, it will not be sufficient to empower poor women automatically, but it should be coupled with other related interventions like health and education, which can create radical changes which will bring real empowerment.

Many types of research have been done on the matter of microfinance schemes and the empowerment of women and some studies have indicated a positive influence of these microfinance schemes to uplift women while some studies have shown negative aspects of microfinance (Pati, 2009, pp. 277-280). Data from southern India was collected through a survey of various households when compared with the lending of credit by an institutional bank to individual rural women and men under the Integrated Rural Development Program (IRDP) along with the support of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) which creates provision of credit facility to women. It indicates lowering domination of males in the decision-making process and increasing involvement and giving an important role in the decision-making process to women. This is noticed after the joining of SHGs by women. The long-term impact of groups on women of various things, such as long-term involvement in groups, regular meetings of the group, and rigorous training, has provided strong support to reinforce the positive effects. The data of various SHGs collected from 5

Indian states analyzed by the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) also indicated that factors which help to reinforce latent empowerment of women members of SHGs are control of managerial activities, changes in behaviour and economic aspects.

However, a few research studies also revealed mere participation in schemes related to microfinance will not work in favour to empowering of rural women. Two main advantages of credit facilities to members of SHGs are the creation of assets and lower risk (Ray, 2008, pp. 212- 2014), but there is not strong enough evidence of guaranteed empowerment of women. Most of the time, the credit allocated to them is utilized to add to the income and assets of households. This leads to the dis-empowerment of women due to the absence of ownership in assets of the family, so just being a member of SHGs and availing of credit facilities will not improve the level of empowerment of women.

This study is built on primary data collected 2 times, first in the year 2005 to 2006 and secondly in the year 2009 to 2010, but with the same sample of members of SHGs set up under the SGSY scheme from the West Bengal Region and North twenty-four Parganas, India. Under the 1st survey, data was gathered regarding the structure of occupation and economic and social attributes of SHGs' members, but no data was gathered regarding the empowerment of women. After four years, the same SHGs were interviewed again who was around 6 years older at that particular time, to collect information about empowerment and economic and social attributes of the selected sample size of SHGs (Dasgupta, 2009, p. 24). The data obtained from 2 successive surveys make the understanding of different aspects of employment of members of SHGs and its relationship with the empowerment of women over time. Empowerment has an interconnection with the status of employment of a person, but it is also influenced by a few similar economic and social demographic factors which influence both factors. One hypothesis adopted in this study states about the possibility of being empowered and simultaneously employed at the time of the 2nd survey is in conjunction resolved by a pattern of occupation noticed in the 1st survey. To analyze this particular hypothesis, a bivariate Probit regression was applied which separates demographic factors related to economic and social aspects affecting the probability jointly of SHGs' members being employed and empowered and also the impact of various explanatory variables on employment and empowerment of women. It was important because existing studies have not attempted to analyze the factors affecting the probability jointly of being employed and empowered.

Another hypothesis formulated is demographic factors related to economic and social aspects and also training provided to members impacted their indicators of empowerment when they were engaged in SHGs under the SGSY scheme for a time duration of around greater than 6 years. To analyze the concerned hypothesis, we applied logistic regression in many sets to find out those factors impacting members' empowerment indicators (Pathak and Pant, 2008, pp. 477-486).

The remaining study is structured as follows: A description of the design of the survey and other related variables included in the study through the survey is performed in the 2nd section. The problems encountered while measuring levels of empowerment of women are

included as the sample is done in the 3rd section. The 4th section deals with empirical findings and the final section represents the conclusion of this research study.

2. Survey of members of SHGs

The data collected was collected 2 times from the same district after a pre-defined period in the North Twenty-Four District of southern West Bengal. 1st time data collection data was collected for a period started from October in the year 2005 to March 2006, and data was again collected for the 2nd time from the previously sampled members of SHGs from October in the year 2009 to March 2010 (Panda et al., 2012, pp. 243-247).

During the 1st time of data collection, data was obtained from members of SHGs who are beneficiaries of the SGSY scheme using a simple random sampling method through 3 steps. North Twenty-Four District of southern West Bengal was split into 5 sub-areas such as Barasat, Bongan, Basirhat, Bidhannagar and Barackpur. Due to the categorization of Bidhannagar as an urban area, it was eliminated from this survey. From the remaining 4 sub-areas 6 different blocks were selected on a random basis, and one gram panchayat was selected from every selected block. The chosen gram panchayats are Kashimpur from the Barasat region, Dulduli from the Hingalgang area, Palla from the Bongaon area, Makalgacha from the Hasnabad area, Nimdaria-Kdalia from the Basirhat region and Panpur-Keutia from Barackpur area. 4 SHGs were chosen on a random basis from every region of gram panchayat as per the data given by the District Rural Development Committee (DRDC) of North Twenty-Four District of southern West Bengal (from Hingalgang only 7 SHGs were chosen from the region of Hingalgang as they contain lower than 8 SHGs' members out of selected 3 members of SHGs). Consequently, only 51 SHGs were chosen out of 400 members. Although it was revealed that 1 SHG containing only male members, this SHG was eliminated from further analysis because this study has focused its aim on analyzing the impact of SHGs on poor rural women (Belavatagi, 2005, p. 416). At the first time of primary data collection, data was collected from 295 female members of 37 SHGs belonging to four split-ter sub-regions of the North Twenty-Four District of southern West Bengal. In 2nd time the survey was conducted in the year 2009 when all the sampled SHGs were around 6 years older compared to 1st time the survey allocated institutional credit. At the time of the 2nd survey, 276 members out of 295 sampled members of SHGs included in the 1st survey were tracked down. Out of these 276 members, 5 women members were falling in the category of single females so they were eliminated from the current research study, as these women are not falling into the category specified in the objectives of this study as an influence on single women will be different from those on women who are married in terms of decisions regarding employment, usage pattern in the long term and indicators of empowerment. That is why the data of only about 271 women members included those who belonged to matured 37 SHGs.

The above data which are collected 2 different times contained demographic and social and economical information of selected members of SHGs, which is based on sex, age, religion, caste, education and the number of members in the family, dependents in the family, occupation details of husband, details of occupation, level of saving, the average income

of the family (Sharma et al., 2012, pp. 84-85), amount of agricultural land, the income of members of SHGs and amount spent on medicines, food and family. Further details were collected in the 2nd survey regarding indicators of empowerment and the health of economic status of families.

On analyzing data related to occupation, the selected sample was distributed into 3 distinct groups namely animal husbandry (breeding of cattle and farming related to poultry-related activities), Self-employed (members of SHGs engaging in the production of baskets, making cigarettes for local area consumption (beedis), handicraft activities, sewing activities, activities related to handicraft activities, activities related to fisheries and horticulture), labour employed on wage (members of SHGs employed in non-agricultural and agricultural activities to earn some wages). Table one indicates the pattern of occupation of members of SHGs in the year 2005 and year 2009.

Table 1. Classification of members of SHGs based on occupational structure

Occupational Structure	Labor (2005)	Self-Employment (2005)	Activities Related to Animal Husbandry (2005)	Gross Value
Self-employment (2009)	2	49	14	65 (23.98%)
Labour (2009)	20	8	15	43 (15.87%)
Unemployed housewives (2009)	51	49	51	151 (55.72%)
Husbandry of Animals (2009)	5	1	6	12 (4.43%)
Gross Value	78 (28.77%)	107 (39.51%)	86 (31.72%)	271 (100%)

Source: Survey based on primary data used in this study.

An important feature indicated by table one is that 1st survey revealed a full employment rate among that whole number of respondents, around 55.72% out of the total selected SHG members have changed toward engagement at home as housewives and were not falling under the status of employment at the time of 2nd survey while most of the members who fell in the category of self-employment in the year 2005 are still in a situation of employment in the year 2009. The succeeding study studies in the section of 'Factors Determining levels of Empowerment and Status of Employment', will indicate patterns of occupation structure and the presence of benefits of non-monetary nature such as the effect of effective and training programme influencing regularity of current status of employment and regularity of employment (Kumar et al., 2015, p. 7).

Table 2. Few prominent variables and statistics of descriptive nature

	Value of Mean	Value of Standard Deviation
Yearly price-adjusted income of the family (₹) for the year 2005	5,582.80070	2,562.08027
Yearly price-adjusted income of the family (₹) of the year 2009 *	5,704.60	4,472.7900
The current age of members of SHGs at the time of 2 nd survey	37.33	7.89
Number of members in the family	2.89	2.02
Agricultural land owned by the family (in Kottah) **	8.72	26.476
The total value of the wealth of the family at the time of 2 nd survey	31,083.34	61,245.755
Gross observations: 271		

*Observations showed that the income of the family rose enormously measured on a constant price basis through the T-test at the time of the second survey.

** One cottage (Kottah) = seven twenty sq. ft. = zero point zero sixty seven sq. Ft.

Source: Survey based on primary data used in this study.

Tables 1 and 2 indicate that even though levels of income of SHG members have risen in a significant manner, a majority number of SHG members had fallen into the category of unemployment at the time of 2nd survey.

3. Empowerment dimensions

This segment states problems concerning quantification regarding the level of empowerment of members of SHGs. This problem has two different aspects that are a measurement of the level of empowerment SHGs' female members concerning pre-specified components and spotting dimensions and components regarding the empowerment of women. At the time of spotting components concerning the empowerment of women is specific to the context and also specific to a country, while the 2nd issue is kind of more methodological.

Some researchers provide helpful and practical empowerment definitions: "Enhancement in abilities of people to make choices in life of strategic nature which they were unable to make before empowerment."

Researchers recount empowerment as a process which indicates changes in 3 dimensions which are inter-related Agency (which helps to make decisions regarding choices and it is the central part of the process), Achievements (these are the results of choices made), and Resources (This help to shape the condition which is considered while making choices) (Shylendra and Bhirdikar, 2005, pp. 205-207).

Researchers also indicated that they conder only two factors more important for the empowerment of women's agency and various resources and these are known by many names and forms such as power, voice, awareness, and control. Few researchers also considered resources, not as a factor measure of empowerment, but they are considering it as a kind of catalyst for women's empowerment or a favourable environment for the empowerment of members in an easy manner. Many researchers in various empowerment-focused studies considered agency as the closest factor for capturing the capability to make choices of strategic nature and those decisions which influence prominent consequences of life. Empowerment of women requires simultaneous growth in various other dimensions such as social and cultural, economic, legal, interpersonal/familial, psychological and political. Although every dimension contains various sub-dimensions in which empowerment of women can also be done. Different researchers adopt various empowerment components which are most of the time specific to the context and particular country.

This presently succeeding research study is the opposite of the backdrop which this study adopted the successive components concerning the empowerment of women and the components are awareness of political activities, couple interaction, participation in political activities, awareness regarding legal activities, making of decisions regarding domestic activities, self-esteem and movements related freedom (Roy, 2014, pp. 6-7).

Researchers recognized that components related to awareness about legal and political activities regarding the resources and capabilities of women. Other indicators adopted in this concerned study are related to the agency of women. These indicators are elaborated on in table three in detail. A few indicators such as freedom regarding vote casting, freedom regarding income spending, freedom regarding purchasing of necessities of a household, freedom regarding decisions concerning health, education and issues concerning nutrition of children, and decisions regarding measures of family planning, are the indicators adopted by some other studies.

This research study also adopted a few indicators which are more prominent concerning West Bengal. Various other research indicated the role of movements concerning land reforms in West Bengal state to help in getting land to poor rural peoples. These lands are settled by the government through the typical process of ownership deeds (pattas) and pattas which are issued jointly to some couples in case both married, then they both can apply for the ownership of land. Consequently, rights of property are given to poor rural people through joint pattas. A 2009 report of District Human Development (DGD) which is based on south twenty-four Parganas stated that in West Bengal state about 15.6% share out of aggregate patta owners owned by holders of joint patta and single women. We inquired from members of SHGs concerning the distribution of the patta program in the state of West Bengal and surveyed them about awareness regarding joint pattas' existence to find insights into their awareness concerning legal activities (Pandey and Gupta, 2022, pp. 19-27).

In the state of West Bengal, the system used is the 3 tier system of panchayat concerning the local level of self-governance. It has adopted the decentralization method democratic system, apex level is of Zila Parishad working at the district level, the next preceding level is of panchayat samitis operating at the block level acting as 2nd tier, and after that Gram Panchayats (GPs), these members are chosen through voters who will select members of Legislative Assembly of State for a tenure of a duration of 4 years. The members who are engaged in Gram Panchayat include around 7 to 25 members. They are chosen from various villages and may be a candidate for separate political parties, previous literature also indicates the prominent role of Panchayati raj in various poverty reduction and rural developmental activities in any particular state region. A conducted interviews of members of SHGs regarding the significance of the system of Panchayati raj in any state region and awareness regarding their participation in parliament of village meetings.

Gram Sabha and Sansad, are 2 added tiers, which are implemented at the level of gram panchayat by the government of West Bengal in the year 1994, to reinforce decentralization in rural areas and to fix the transparency, inclusiveness, and accountability in the governance of local regions. At the level of the village, it is obligatory in the case of gram Sansad to hold meetings two times a year along with a one-tenth attendance at the forum by members. Gram Sansad must give advice and guide the member's gram regarding the schemes and programs for social justice economic growth and development in the area of gram panchayat (Dasgupta, 2021, pp. 223-229). The terms for identification of various government scheme beneficiaries, the gram Sansad is liable and accountable for it, for doing economic growth and development in village area as per its jurisdiction. These are prominent insights to find out the level of awareness among members of SHGs regarding these institutions.

This study also adopted indicators of psychological nature to figure out the status of self-sufficiency economically after becoming a member of SHGs formed under the SGSY scheme which focuses on giving support to poor rural people, to get them into a situation of self-sufficiency. Lastly, through indicators related to family and its members, this study

inquired about their perception concerning their status in their own family compared to the status of their husband. The measurement was done through certain indicators like have any women faced any domination by members of the family, and those women who have been dominated by their family members and husbands will have higher chances of lower status compared to their husbands.

3.1. Empowerment measurement

To measure empowerment as per the pre-defined indicators through making indices. This technique is dependent on arbitrarily random weights, the score was earmarked by researchers to the selected answers by chosen sample regarding questions based on empowerment. A study utilized the same technique earmarking scores to the various answers given by a selected sample of members of SHGs. This used method is questioned based on its subjective nature. Some researchers indicated some unsuitable weightings of arbitrary nature.

Few studies adopted the model of factor analysis for analyzing latent variables of women empowerment, which is not appropriate in the case of considering empowerment indicators as discrete and binary variables. To find out the influence of credit facilities on empowerment on empowerment of women. Researchers also used data from the household of the selected sample based on a cross-sectional basis along with responses of binary in nature concerning the attitude of women members. Some studies also employed ordinal longitudinal and subjective data reported by members of SHGs and this data is used through a general model of the structural equation to analyze the changes that occurred empowerment of women of the whole SHGs. The current research study has not used longitudinal data. The set of binary responses is reported by female members in the time duration from the year 2009 to the year 2010, which is indicated in table three regarding various dimensions of empowerment of women members (Chava et al., 2020, p. 4).

Table three shows about few prominent features. The female members selected as samples in the present study have an age of no less than six years, majority of the respondents have given answers in an affirmative way to the questions provided which are based on a few indicators such as movements concerning freedom, freedom to make an expenditure out of your income at your own will, freedom to buy necessity goods of your choice, but some respondents also reported in a non-affirmative way such as 62.36% are not independent after becoming a member of SHG, 40.59% are not free to make decisions related to birth control without husband's permission. Political awareness levels were also found to be very low among all the members of SHGs sampled.

Table 3. Various dimensions concerning empowerment of women and pattern of response

Various dimensions concerning empowerment	Predefined questions	Respondents who answered affirmatively	Respondents who answered negatively
Awareness Regarding Political Activities	Have you any awareness regarding politics and also attending gram Sansad meetings?	132 (48.71)	139 (51.29)
Interaction of Couple	(a) - are your status and role equivalent to your husband's?	236 (87.07)	35 (12.93)
	(b) - are you free to make decisions related to birth control without your husband's permission?	161 (59.41)	110 (40.59)

Various dimensions concerning empowerment	Predefined questions	Respondents who answered affirmatively	Respondents who answered negatively
Awareness Regarding Legal Activities	Do you have any knowledge regarding women's legal rights which empower them for a buying a joint patta from a land?	177 (65.30)	94 (34.70)
Participation in Political Activities	Do you have the freedom on casting a vote of your choice?	168 (61.91)	103 (38.09)
Decision Regarding Domestic Activities	(a) - do you have the freedom to make an expenditure out of the income of your own will?	239 (88.18)	32 (11.82)
	(b) - do you have the freedom to buy the necessary goods of your choice?	263 (97.05)	8 (2.95)
	(c) - have you liberty in deciding the health, nutrition and education of your children?	226 (83.38)	45 (16.62)
Self Esteem	Are you independent after becoming a member of SHG?	102 (37.64)	169 (62.36)
Movements Concerning Freedom	Do you have the freedom to visit any house of your relative as per your will?	197 (72.68)	74 (27.32)

Source: Report of survey of the year 2009.

This study further introduced ten questions based on dummy variables, each variable assigned a value of one in case members provided positive answers to the inquired questions. The ten dummy variables adopted in this study are birth control, the status of a family, vote, gram Sansad, information of joint patta, spending of income, purchase on an independent basis, to make decisions concerning children, movements concerning freedom and self-dependency. The introduced dummy variables were assigned a value of one in case members of SHGs gave positive answers to the asked questions shown in table three.

In the fourth table, regression of binary logistics was applied to analyze the formulated hypothesis which says economic, social, and factors of demographic nature impact the indicators of empowering women members belonging to different households. Some dummy variables were also eliminated from regression analysis regarding independence concerning daily purchasable goods of household's needs as about six per cent of female members gave non-affirmative answers to the given questions (Gupta and Nair, 2020, p. 3). Various independent variables incorporated in this study are education, religion, age of members of SHGs at the time of 2nd survey, members in the family of the respondent, and the dummy variable for training in which 1 will indicate training received is productive and after becoming a member of an SHG, agricultural land owned by families, at the level of gram panchayat and village same ruling political party. The final dummy variable adopted talks about the environment of politics among the village of members. Appendix two shows the relationship among many explanatory variables included in this study. In every logistic regression, independent variables were selected as per least values concerning information basis.

Table four indicates that religion has a remarkable influence on various aspects of the empowerment of women. Comparatively to those members who belonged to the Hindu religion, women belonging to the Muslim religion are less probably knowledgeable regarding joint patta or casting their vote. Contrasting to, the majority of Hindi members,

are not privileged regarding movements concerning freedom or liberty of making decisions regarding their children, and the status of female members in the family is less probably equivalent to the social status of their husbands. So it can be concluded that women belonging to the Muslim religion are not so much empowered compared to Hindu members, but data shows Muslim members are probably found to be empowered in terms of self-dependence after becoming a member of an SHG as compared to Hindu members (Goswami et al., 2021, pp. 164-165). The data found in the primary survey revealed that about 29.18% of members belonging to the Hindu religion are self-dependent after becoming a member of SHGs, comparatively about 39.02% of respondents belonging to the Muslim religion accepted the role of SHGs making them self-dependent. These outcomes indicate that members of an SHG can boost the confidence of Muslim women simultaneously with the presence of social hindrances.

Table 4. To find out factors affecting various empowerment dimensions through logistic regression

	Awareness regarding legal activities		Awareness regarding political activities		Decision regarding domestic activities		Self esteem	Movements concerning freedom		Interaction of couple	
	Dummy variable of patta land	Dummy variable of gram Sansad	Dummy variable of vote	Dummy variable of spending of income	Dummy variable of the decision of children	Dummy variable of self-dependency	Dummy variable of liberty to movement	Dummy variable of the status of family	Dummy variable of birth control		
Dependent and also independent variables											
Dummy variable of education	0.07	0.36	0.1	0.26	0.33	0.51	0.12	- 0.05	-0.23		
Religion	- 1.09	0.08	- 69**	- 0.53	0.92**	0.58**	- 0.81*	- 0.85***	0		
Total number of members in the family	-0.02	0.08	0.07	- 0.31***	- 0.03	- 0.03	0.32***	- 0.03	- 0.23		
Age	-0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.02	- 0.02	0.08*	0		
Dummy variable of agricultural land ownership	0.68***	-	-	-	-	-	- 0.79**	-	-		
Dummy variable of training	1.36*	-	1.32*	- 0.33	- 0.47	1.12*	- 0.36	- 0.57	0.86*		
constant	0.68	- 1.21	- 0.74	1.25	2.39	- 2.97	1.08	4.87	1.19		
Common party	-	1.08*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Homer chi ² (eight) Lemeshow	6.8	12.87	9.18	1.12	3.87	11.2	6.08	7.2	12.29		
Pseudo R ²	0.23	0.12	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.09		
Sig.	0.52	0.08	0.32	0.85	0.76	0.06	0.62	0.39	0.55		
BIC	401	415.32	352.56	198.86	329.19	267.22	462.65	213.67	358.01		
AIC	352.78	375.96	384.01	324.41	302.73	243.22	242.33	206.12	409.01		

* at a 1% level of significance;

** at a 5% level of significance;

*** at 10% level of significance.

Source: Results of Logistic regression which are obtained through primary data used in this study.

On the second number, it was discovered that the environment related to politics in any village is ascertained by the choice of participation by members in meetings of gram Sansad which has an important role in making policies related to the development of the areas of gram panchayat of the member. The probability of a member of the group being involved in meetings of gram Sansad in case an elected member of the panchayat of that particular village is a part of the dominant party at the level of the gram panchayat.

The status of women members in their families is affected by age of a member of an SHG, in the case of the age of a member of the group, the less probability of having an equal level of status as the husband has compared to their wife. The members of the family are also influencing the level of freedom regarding spending out of her income, although the women members enjoy more mobility.

Additionally, those members of SHGs who have got training after becoming a member of SHGs and those members who know joint patta, to personally cast their vote, to make themselves more self-dependent, to make decisions related to birth control without their husband's permission, training play important in the empowerment of women as they gained more confidence (Kamala et al., 2018), awareness and improvement in independent behaviour. The dummy variable of agricultural land ownership was also made a part of 2 logistic regressions based on criteria of information. The findings revealed that female members who belong to those families who hold agricultural land have more knowledge regarding joint patta but the probability is lower to attend meetings of the group independently, the freedom to visit any house of your relative as per her will.

The examination demonstrates the negative influence concerning members' religious identification on different aspects of empowerment of women which are simultaneously depicting the agency of women despite having experience of 6 years in the engagement of the group. The impact of participation in the group on Muslim women is that it helped them to become more self-dependent compared to members belonging to the Hindu religion. The outcome of taking training through SHGs made them more self-dependent and confident and also enhanced their awareness level regarding political and legal rights. The further portion highlights the association between the status of employment and empowerment of women and also the pattern in the use of loans by the member of SHGs (Kamala Devi et al., 2018, pp. 281-292).

4. Various determinants of status of employment and level of empowerment

This part analyzes the pre-defined hypothesis in which the current status of employment and level of empowerment of female members are interconnected. The probability of a member of a group regarding employed and empowered is determined in conjunction, with and also few usual economic and social factors related to demographic characteristics which influence both factors.

Table 5. Statistics calculated from variable count

Counting		
Value of mean		6.124935
Value of median		5
Value of mode		5

Counting		
Value of minimum		0
Value of maximum		8
Value of percentile	31	4
	48	7
	69	6

Source: Primary data used in this study.

Table five indicates about the median value obtained is six, which means on an average basis about fifty per cent of members of the group gave a positive response to six selected questions. The goal was to find out the variable's set which influences the probability on a joint basis for being employed and empowered through a model of bivariate Probit. Consequently employed variable of binary nature "women empowerment" assumes equal value to unity if the count of variable alike to a single member of the group was found greater than six, the value of the median. The empowerment variable shows that individual members gave more positive answers regarding questions related to empowerment compared to those members who are average (Galab and Rao, 2003, pp. 1278-1280).

Table 6. Outcomes obtained from bivariate Probit regression

Dependent variable used women empowerment = one	Various independent variables used	Value of coefficients	Huge standard error obtained
	Size of group	0	0.12
	Dummy variable of Religion	0.23	0.31
	Dummy variable of education	0.34	0.28
	Number of embers in the family	- 0.13	0.10
	Age	- 0.11	0.08
	Dummy variable of training	0.64*	0.41
	Members self-employed in the year 2005	0.25	0.32
	Members working in animal husbandry in the year 2005	0.09	0.42
	Dummy variable of ownership of agricultural land	0.22	0.12
	Value of constant	- 0.39	0.73
Status of employment = one			
	Size of group	0.07**	0.16
	Dummy variable of Religion	0.46	0.12
	Dummy variable of education	0.24	0.10
	Number of members in the family	- 0.10	0.02
	Age	- 0.21	0.13
	Dummy variable of training	0.86*	0.28
	Members self-employed in the year 2005	0.79*	0.31
	Members working in animal husbandry in the year 2005	0.43**	0.32
	Dummy variable of ownership of agricultural land	0.28	0.33
	Value of constant	- 2.11	0.78
	Value of rho	0.37	0.16
	Value of anthro	0.51	0.21
	Value of rho through Wald test + Zero chi ² (1) = 13.3148	Probability is greater than chi ² = 0.0001	
	Value of AIC = 659.48	Value of Log pseudo-likelihood = - 298.87	

* at a 1% level of significance;

** at a 5% level of significance.

Source: Results of bivariate Probit regression which are obtained through primary data used in this study.

It was also noticed that members of the group who were engaged in business-related animal husbandry during the year 2005 were more probably employed in the year 2009 compared to those members who were employed as labourers during the year 2005. The findings of the survey revealed that eleven members of the group who were engaging in animal husbandry related activities during the year 2005, had moved to self-employment-related projects due to which they remain unemployed.

The survey conducted during this study revealed that all the members of the group engaged in availing credit-related activities when they were a member of SHGs. The latter analysis examines the kind of usage this loan was employed by members of SHGs from the year 2008 to the year 2009. The relationship among patterns in usage of loans and women empowerment variables (Mohapatra and Sahoo, 2016, pp. 60-69).

Table 7

		The pattern of Credit Usage				
		Members not availed of credit facility	Expenses of family	Business related to family or husband	Personal business	Gross value
Members who are empowered	1	43	70	41	32	187
	0	11	21	26	50	108
Gross value		53	91	67	82	
Chi-square of Pearson = 41.279				Sig = 0, df = 2		
Sig = 0	Phi = 0.233				Sig = 0	Cramer's V = 0.233

Source: Data report in the survey of the year 2009.

About 84% of credit users obtained loans in the year 2009 through SHGs, and as per the data, about 31% (who were employed somewhere) of the members of the group invested the credit into business-related activities. 71% of respondents from SHGs who belonged to the category of non-empowered members, were not able to control their loan amount and spend the credit money on unproductive activities such as fulfilling consumption-related needs of family or needs of working capital in any other person's business such as family and friends. Table number 7 indicates that around 39.02% of members who are empowered employed credit amount into their own business to expand it, while around 15.34% of members who did not fall into the category of empowered members. Consequently, those women who are empowered are in better condition to drive the usage of loans into more productive places. The outcome found through cross-tabulation among dummy variables of training and usage pattern of the loan indicated that female members who got training (61% of members) were in a condition to using their credit in extending their business, while the members who have not got any training were employing credit amount in unproductive activities such as transferring the credit amount to relatives. In adding these findings and results of bivariate Probit regression, this study concluded that those members who received proper training are more probable to be in the status of employment for a long period, and consequently they will become more empowered. These members are also in a situation to control the amount of credit and invest in their businesses for growth perspectives (Alemu et al., 2018, pp. 310-315).

So, the training of members of SHGs worked as a catalyst in making better the agency between female group members.

5. Conclusion

This study is based on data collected two times in the survey conducted to find out various aspects of employment which govern female members of groups (SHGs) created through the SGSY scheme. The findings of this study indicated that occupation choice is an important factor for continuity in terms of employment of members of groups, and also other factors of non-monetary nature such as training. The majority number of members of the group who were falling in the category of self-employment at the time of 1st round of the survey was also employed at the time of 2nd round of the survey. Additionally, it was also found that the current status of employment is ascertained by both factors such as the level of employment of members of the group, and another thing is employment in case the members have received full training under the SGSY scheme. Consequently, training may be considered as a resource which works as a catalyst in empowering the women members of SHGs or those conditions in which women empowerment will probably happen (Puhazhendhi and Satyasai, 2001, pp. 3-7), as well as it was also observed that female members who are getting training are utilizing loan in an optimum manner and this allocated credit is invested in productive activities related to own business.

This study also identified those factors which influence various indicators of the empowerment of women. The findings revealed that the religious image of members of the group influenced a few dimensions of the empowerment of female members. Those female members belonging to the Muslim community were seen as less knowledgeable regarding joint patta, casting individual votes as their choice, making decisions concerning children, having freedom in movement, and the status of women in their family are less probably equivalent to the status of their husband. Women members belonging to the Muslim community are more self-dependent after becoming a member of SHGs.

Acknowledgements

Dr. Ravi Kumar Gupta is the awardee of MGNCRE Research Projects (Major Research Project). This paper is largely an outcome of the Research Project sponsored by the Mahatma Gandhi National Council of Rural Education (MGNCRE). However, the responsibility for the facts stated, opinions expressed, and the conclusions drawn is entirely that of the author.

Declaration of competing interest

All the authors associated with this study declare that they have no conflicts of interest concerning the publication and authorship of this research study.

References

- Alemu, S.H., Van Kempen, L. and Ruben, R., 2018. Women empowerment through self-help groups: The bittersweet fruits of collective apple cultivation in highland Ethiopia. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 19(3), pp. 308-330.
- Belavatagi, M.B., 2005. Impact of Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY) on Poverty Alleviation and Rural Indebtedness. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 60(3), p. 408.
- Chava, L.D., Buggineni, P. and Rani, P.U., 2020. Integration of Health and Nutrition into Livelihood Programs under DAY-NRLM.
- DasGupta, M., 2021. Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana-National Rural Livelihood Mission (DAY-NRLM) and Tribal Livelihood Promotion: An Indian Experience in Pre-post COVID-19 Pandemic Era. *New Business Models in the Course of Global Crises in South Asia: Lessons from COVID-19 and Beyond*, pp. 221-241.
- Dasgupta, R., 2009. SGSY: Need for a paradigm shift. *Economic and Political weekly*, pp. 21-23.
- Galab, S. and Rao, N.C., 2003. Women's self-help groups, poverty alleviation and empowerment. *Economic and Political weekly*, pp. 1274-1283.
- Goswami, P., Rajan, P. and Jaiswal, D.K., 2021. Effectiveness of Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana-national rural livelihoods mission on empowerment of women in Sagar district of Madhya Pradesh. *Indian Journal of Extension Education*, 57(2), pp. 162-165.
- Gupta, A. and Nair, V., 2020. Transforming Rural Non-Farm Livelihoods.
- Kamala Devi, A., Sarangi, T.K. and Lal, R., 2018. Functioning of SHGs with a Special Focus on an Indian State. *Reflecting on India's Development: Employment, Skill and Health*, pp. 271-292.
- Khaki, A.R. and Sangmi, M.U.D., 2017. Does access to finance alleviate poverty? A case study of SGSY beneficiaries in Kashmir Valley. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 44(8), pp. 1032-1045.
- Kumar, A., Yogi, R.K., Jaiswal, A.K. and Singh, A.K., 2015. Impact of special project on lac cultivation & processing in the Mahasamund divisional forest area of Chhattisgarh under Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY).
- Mohapatra, S. and Sahoo, B.K., 2016. Determinants of participation in self-help-groups (SHG) and its impact on women empowerment. *Indian Growth and Development Review*.
- Panda, N., Mahapatra, A.S. and Samal, R., 2012. Impact evaluation of SGSY on socio-economic development of women in aquaculture in Eastern Hills of Orissa. *Aquaculture International*, 20, pp. 233-247.
- Pandey, V. and Gupta, A., 2022. Can Multi-Sectoral Development Interventions Boost Livelihoods and Women's Labor Supply? Evidence from NRLM in India. *Feminist Economics*, pp. 1-30.
- Pathak, D.C. and Pant, S.K., 2008. Micro finance matters...? Impact evaluation of SGSY: a case study of Jaunpur District. In Lazar and Palanichammy (eds.), *Micro Finance and Poverty Eradication: Indian and Global Experiences*, pp. 469-491.
- Pati, A.P., 2009. Subsidy impact on sustainability of SHGs: An empirical analysis of micro lending through SGSY scheme. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 64(2).
- Puhazhendhi, V. and Satyasai, K.J.S., 2001. Economic and social empowerment of rural poor through self-help groups. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 56(3), p. 450.
- Ray, S., 2008. Alleviating poverty through micro-finance: SGSY experience in Orissa. *Sociological Bulletin*, 57(2), pp. 211-240.

- Roy, J., 2014. IRDP to NRLM: A brief review of rural development initiatives in India. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 3(4), pp. 05-08.
- Sharma, A., Roy, B. and Chakravorty, D., 2012. Potential of Self Help Groups as an Entrepreneur: A Case Study from Uttar Dinajpur District of West Bengal. *Journal of social sciences*, 30(1), pp. 83-87.
- Shylendra, H.S. and Bhirdikar, K., 2005. 'Good Governance' and Poverty Alleviation Programmes: A Critical Analysis of the Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana. *International Journal of Rural Management*, 1(2), pp. 203-221.
- Sud, N., 2003. Experiences of SGSY in Gujarat: from process-oriented theory to deterministic practice. *Economic and Political weekly*, pp. 4085-4087.

The impact of Covid-19 payment moratoria on the Romanian banking system

Eugen-Marian VIERESCU

Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
vierescueugen@gmail.com

Abstract. *This paper shows the impact of the payment moratoria on the Romanian banking system in the first months after the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic. In the first part, which presents the synthesis of specialized literature on moratoria, it is described how the pandemic affected the population and the authorities, as well as the banking prudential regulatory measures introduced to reduce the economic effects that threatened the very financial stability of the state. The work continues, in the second part, with a presentation of the data regarding the results of the application of this measure and the impact on the banking sector in Romania. The results suggest that the moratorium tends to be used by companies that were already struggling to meet their obligations to creditors, which led to an increase in the rate of non-performing loans after the grace period expired. They also show that such measures are not viewed with good eyes by the banking sector, as they increase the uncertainty weighing on it.*

Keywords: payment moratoria, Covid-19, non-performing exposures, forborne exposures.

JEL Classification: G21, G28, G35.

Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic represents an event with a distant precedent, precisely in 1918, against which humanity did not have a perfect solution, and even the one it identified came late, due to the sophisticated medicinal processes that must be completed to create an effective vaccine. All this time, the states of the world had to take emergency measures (for example lockdown, activity restrictions, economic support, etc.).

When the activity restrictions were introduced, the question arose as to what the people who worked in those companies would survive with, or with what they would be able to fulfill their obligations to suppliers or banks. The public authorities tried as much as possible, even at the cost of burdening the state budgets, to come to the support of the people. Credit deferrals were granted, technical unemployment was paid, as well as other measures aimed at taking over the pressure felt by the affected public.

The purpose of this paper is to explore how the measure to postpone the payment of credits, known as the moratorium, impacted the banking system in Romania. The paper begins with the synthesis of specialized literature on the subject, after which, in the second part, I will show, in numbers, how high the degree of recourse to moratoriums was and how much this measure affected the liquidity inflows of the banks. The last part presents the conclusions and recommendations for possible undesirable situations in which moratoria will be used again.

1. The concept of payment moratorium. Synthesis of specialized literature

The Covid-19 pandemic is an event that we can easily fit into what Mervyn King (2020) calls "radical uncertainty". A sanitary shock of unprecedented intensity since the Spanish flu (1918) which, by the need to impose the "great closure" (Dăianu et al., 2020) as a way to prevent the spread of the virus, caused an economic collapse to say the least severe.

Panic over the virus caused the biggest weekly drop in US financial markets since the 2007-2009 crisis, signaling the economic problems ahead. A very good example of the speed with which the new crisis was advancing is the Dow Jones Industrial Average, which was facing a 12% decline after a record high in the same month. This as the markets were not interested in anything but cash. Another example is the unemployment rate, which, in the US, recorded the highest increase in history, 11%, in just 2 months (Bernanke, 2022). Unlike previous crises, this one was happening at an unprecedented speed.

The Covid-19 pandemic has had catastrophic effects on the incomes of families around the world. The economies of both industrialized and emerging countries have struggled to adapt to the new normal, which has put intense pressure on public budgets, difficulties in supply chains and caused, among other causes, the inflationary crisis we are facing today. This *sui generis* war, as the pandemic was called in a Euromonitor report (2020), meant unforeseen and non-permanent expenditures from public budgets to support economic activity, or, in some cases, to compensate for its lack.

In the economic struggle, public institutions supported the activity of companies and maintained financial stability, and the banking system did not stand aside either, bringing crucial support in stabilizing economies since the first months of the lockdown that brought irreversible changes to our society. For many prophets of the financial crisis, the mission of protecting people's incomes and financial stability seemed impossible.

With the support of national banks, which acted without delay, credit institutions provided the necessary liquidity to families and companies and absorbed the shock felt by the entire economy by granting state-guaranteed loans and deferring the payment of installments, a process known as the moratorium. Called by Adrian Vasilescu (2020) "an institution of civil law that is activated in the conditions where it is necessary to take measures to postpone payments from debt contracts", the moratorium does not lead to the reclassification of the credit by the banks, which would imply also making provisions for outstanding amounts.

Nor did the regulatory authorities remain passive and made the prudential framework more flexible. As the moratorium has been adopted in several EU jurisdictions, the European Banking Authority (EBA) has issued several guidelines to clarify how banks should apply it, without the need for automatic reclassification of loans as non-performing. Thus, even if any credit restructuring automatically means the application of default status, being associated with the notion of financial difficulty, in the case of moratoriums, whether public or private, "such an operation is not considered a restructuring measure" (NBR Communication, 2020), not being associated with a financial difficulty on the part of the debtor.

What is important so that the measure of introducing a moratorium does not generate a shock in the banking system is the prudential treatment that will be applied to the loans that will benefit from such a measure. In this sense, the EBA supported the banks with clarifications and application guidelines in order to have unitary provisions at the European level.

Immediately after the outbreak of the pandemic, at the beginning of 2020, the EBA came to the support of borrowers and conveyed that a moratorium does not automatically lead to a deterioration in the quality of exposures and, implicitly, to a significant increase in credit risk, taking into account the general exceptional conditions caused by the pandemic. If the purpose of moratoria, be they public or private, is to respond to factors that can cause systemic risks and to reduce potential risks, then it is considered that the moratorium does not address the specific situation of a single debtor, but responds to a broad need, of an extended group of borrowers, with a wide range of purchased banking products. Therefore, the automatic classification of these exposures as distressed restructuring or non-performing strictly for this reason is not envisaged. However, inclusion in the category of non-performing exposures is possible if the moratorium also changes other contractual terms (for example, the interest rate), in this case being pursued more than the change in the repayment schedule.

This specific treatment was transposed by Guideline EBA/GL/2020/02, which precisely states that general payment moratoria introduced as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic do

not automatically lead to the conclusion that a restructuring measure caused by financial difficulties has been applied and thus avoid treating these exposures as distressed restructuring in the context of default. It is important to know that this was a treatment specific to the Covid-19 moratoria and produced effects only in the case of those applied before March 31, 2021.

Next, it is the duty of the credit institutions to continuously assess the credit quality for those exposures to which installment deferral has been applied and to identify, as a consequence, any situation in which the debtor could end up in improbability of payment, according to the provisions of the Regulation (EU) no. 575/2013 (CRR). It should be noted that if credit institutions decide to grant new loans to debtors benefiting from the moratorium, this fact does not automatically lead to a restructuring situation following the financial difficulties of the debtors. The classification is made after analyzing the situation of each individual debtor according to the provisions of the CRR.

It is essential to mention that the provisions of these Guidelines do not come to complete the mandatory regulatory framework, but only have the role of clarifying the application of the existing flexibility in the CRR. In this context, according to the prudential regulatory framework, credit restructuring follows idiosyncratic risks and involves granting some facilities to those debtors who are either already experiencing or are about to experience difficulties in repaying their loans, by adopting measures specific to each individual debtor, on the basis of the individual assessment of their financial situation.

Due to the nature of the health crisis and the measures imposed, the highest pressures were, in a first phase, felt at the level of debtors' liquidity.

The Covid-19 pandemic led the Romanian authorities to introduce a series of facilities to support debtors who were facing payment difficulties, as other countries in the region have done. Starting from Guidelines EBA/GL/2020/02, in March 2020 a public moratorium was introduced regarding the suspension of payment of installments for a maximum period of 9 months.

The National Bank of Romania adopted a series of measures aimed at limiting the effects of the crisis on the banking sector and on financial stability. Through monetary policy measures, along with those of a prudential nature, the reduction of interest rates and the preservation of adequate liquidity in the banking system were favored.

The interest in payment moratoria was an early concern for the Romanian economic space, in this sense the work of Marinescu (1924), *Payments in Strong Currency – The Moratorium*, which describes the general moratorium (commercial or civil companies, banks, merchants, any other persons) was discovered for currency payments, which was granted more than a century ago. As at present, the justification of the general moratorium was based on a generalized crisis that indiscriminately affects all debtors: "The war between the great states that surround us had, from an economic point of view, a strong and immediate impact on us. From the very beginning, two phenomena manifested themselves: the crisis of means of payment and the credit crisis." (excerpt from the Government's Statement of Reasons regarding the Special Law authorizing the taking of exceptional measures, published in Official Journal No. 217 of December 27, 1914).

2. Research methodology

The present research focuses on the impact of payment moratoria adopted during the Covid-19 period on the banking system in Romania. As a method of research, we started from the data reported by credit institutions, synthesized in the financial stability reports issued by the National Bank of Romania, through which we showed what was, in terms of value and number of beneficiaries, the degree of affecting the activity of banks in Romania, as a result of the application of this public facility.

The objective of the research was to observe the level of attractiveness towards this type of facility for Romanian debtors and to determine the period of maximum use of it. The starting point is the idea that the payment moratoria during the Covid-19 period had a positive influence on debtors, achieving their goal, that of reducing the pressure on incomes caused by the restrictive measures imposed, although at the level of credit institutions, the underlying premise is that measures of this type are burdensome and cause uncertainty.

3. Results and discussions

The purpose of the moratorium introduced in March, by GEO no. 37/2020 was to moderate the impact on debtors' liquidity. A number of 16.4 thousand companies had requested the postponement of installments until June 5, 2020, equivalent to 21% of all companies with loans. For the majority of suspended amounts, representing 3.2 billion of the total 3.6 billion, suspension requests were submitted for periods between 6 and 9 months.

The data for March 2021 show that the call for the moratorium was a massive one, in the number of 537 thousand debtors, representing a volume of 38.9 billion lei, equivalent to 12.7% of the total credits granted.

Graphic 1. Evolution of payment moratoria requests

Most requests to postpone installments came from companies providing services to the population and those active in the real estate field (46%, respectively 23%), at the opposite pole being those active in fields such as commerce or utilities. Despite the extension of the

deadline for appealing to the moratorium until March 31, 2021, requests have dropped considerably, with less than 1% of debtors being the beneficiaries of this facility, which heralded the first signs of the resumption of economic activity.

The expiration of grace periods for loans that benefited from the moratorium led to an increase in the rate of non-performing loans, up to 3.9% (the EU average was 2.5% in March 2021), but also in the restructuring rate, up to 2.8%, compared to the EU average of 2%. For non-financial companies, the loan default rate was 12.3% as of March 2021, as opposed to 5.2% for companies that did not use the moratorium. For individual borrowers, this value was 7.4% and 3.1%, respectively. Thus, the support measure also led to a possible manifestation of moral hazard, with high-risk loans resorting to moratoriums to a greater extent.

Graphic 2. *NPL rate after Covid-19 payment moratoria*

In this context, it becomes extremely important that risk assessment continues to be conducted in a prudent manner that accurately reflects the quality of credit portfolios. But the banking system began to take precautionary measures, and the degree of coverage of non-performing loans by provisions increased to 63.8%, compared to only 44.7% at the EU level (March 2021). Moreover, according to the data as of December 2021, approximately 50 percent of the loans that resorted to moratoriums are classified in stages 2 or 3 of impairment according to IFRS 9, with banks recognizing an increased risk in their case.

The moratorium on installment deferrals was complemented by other legislative initiatives to extend the applicability and benefits to affected borrowers, which led to increased uncertainty in the banking system, with negative effects in particular on NPL provisions and bank profitability. The challenge of legislative changes is a constant one for the banking system, at least in recent years. In addition to the facility granted to debtors to defer payment of installments, introduced by GEO no. 37/2020 and extended by GEO no. 227/2020, we count the amendments made to Law no. 77/2016 regarding payment and changes to the effective annual interest ceilings for loans granted to natural persons.

Another negative effect can also be reflected on the credit risk, through the delayed recognition of the negative effects of the shock felt by borrowers, which can become permanent.

The measure of suspending the payment of installments can generate an effect of the type of self-fulfilling prophecy. Thus, the uncertain economic and social climate can be enhanced by measures that indirectly confirm the population's fears. At the same time, the operational capacity of credit institutions will be affected by new exceptional rules, which must be introduced shortly into the operational infrastructure. The suspension of delinquent days makes it difficult to take a prudent risk-based lending approach at the borrower level, given a new window of missing data.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

The present research sought to evaluate the impact that the measure to postpone the payment of credits, known as the moratorium, had on the banking system in Romania. The moratorium for deferring the payment of loans is a support measure addressed to both companies and individuals, which has become better known and studied following the Covid-19 pandemic. This allowed borrowers faced with the shock of a sudden drop in income to postpone their payment obligations for a limited period, during which they could obtain the necessary liquidity.

The main conclusion that emerges from the data analysis is that this measure enjoyed extensive use, with hundreds of thousands of applicants, from most fields of activity, the main one being that of services addressed to the population.

Another conclusion is that legislative initiatives such as payment moratoria, even if they come with the aim of supporting debtors in difficulty, increase the risk of uncertainty and may have negative effects on the prudential situation of credit institutions, by affecting their ability to carry out financial intermediation.

Given the poor financial quality of borrowers who have applied for moratorium, credit institutions are forced to continuously assess borrowers' ability to honor their loan agreement after the end of the grace period, as there is an increase of the rate of non-performing loans among these borrowers.

Despite some clear disadvantages (e.g. the uncertainty created in the banking sector, depriving banks of an important part of short-term liquidity), the moratorium is a measure with a strong positive social impact, which has proven its usefulness in times of deep crisis. However, this must be accompanied by continuous assessments of credit risk, in order to minimize possible situations of default.

References

- Guidelines on legislative and non-legislative moratoria on loan repayments applied in the light of the Covid-19 crisis, 2020. Available at <https://www.eba.europa.eu/regulation-and-policy/credit-risk/guidelines-legislative-and-non-legislative-moratoria-loan-repayments-applied-light-covid-19-crisis> [Accessed on 07.10.2022].
- Jiménez, G., Asenjo, E., Vegas, R. and Trucharte, C., 2021. Support measures in the banking sector: loan moratoria. [pdf] Madrid. Available at https://www.bde.es/f/webbde/Secciones/Publicaciones/InformesBoletinesRevistas/InformesEstabilidadFinancera/21/1_Moratorias_FS_R.pdf [Accessed on 12.10.2022].
- National Bank of Romania, 2021. O revenire economică puternică are loc, însă lupta cu pandemia continuă. [pdf] Bucharest. Available at: <https://www.bnr.ro/Studii,-analize,-puncte-de-vedere-4009.aspx> [Accessed on 25.11.2022].
- National Bank of Romania, 2020. Economia și pandemia: de la suferință la redresare. [pdf] Bucharest. Available at: <http://www.bnr.ro/DocumentInformation.aspx?idInfoClass=30485&idDocument=36975&directLink=1> [Accessed on 28.11.2022].
- National Bank of Romania, 2022. Ieșirea din pandemie, dar intrarea într-un nou război rece. [pdf] Bucharest. Available at: <https://www.bnr.ro/Studii,-analize,-puncte-de-vedere-4009.aspx> [Accessed on 03.12.2022].
- National Bank of Romania, 2020. Comunicat de presă al Comitetului de Supraveghere al Băncii Naționale a României. Bucharest. Available at <https://www.bnr.ro/page.aspx?prid=17639> [Accessed on 05.12.09.2022].
- Voican, M., 2020. Adrian Vasilescu (BNR) ne spune unde au greșit guvernele ultimilor ani. Available at: <https://www.money.ro/adrian-vasilescu-bnr-ne-spune-unde-au-gresit-guvernele-ultimilor-ani/> [Accessed on 12.12.2022].

Uncertainty and monetary policy during the Covid-19 pandemic in Tunisia: Evidence from a Bayesian VAR

Dorra TURKI

University of Sfax, Tunisia
dorra.turki93@gmail.com

Foued Badr GABSI

University of Sfax, Tunisia
fouedbadr.gabsi@gmail.com

Abstract. *This paper aims to examine the impact of the uncertainty shock on the Tunisian economy and the effectiveness of monetary policy during the Covid-19 pandemic. For this purpose, we employ a Bayesian VAR model considering the world uncertainty index (WUI) as a new proxy for uncertainty measure and the short-term interest rate as the main instrument of monetary policy. The results indicate that the Covid-19 uncertainty shock has a negative consequence on economic activity and on aggregate demand in Tunisia. Moreover, we show that conventional monetary policy is ineffective in times of high uncertainty period.*

Keywords: Covid-19, uncertainty, monetary policy, BVAR model, impulse response.

JEL Classification: D8, E52.

1. Introduction

The recent health crisis caused by the coronavirus disease (Covid-19) has affected the global economic and financial environment. The rapid propagation of the virus has contributed to an increase in the number of confirmed cases and deaths all over the world. In this regard, public authorities have adopted drastic measures such as social distancing, quarantine for confirmed and probable cases, as well as general containment. While this strategy was effective in containing the spread of the Covid-19 virus, it had disastrous consequences for the global economy. In fact, the containment measures affected the attitudes of economic agents and plunged some developed and emerging countries into deep economic recessions.

The IMF (2020) mentioned that this health crisis is like no other to such an extent that the economic recession exceeds that of the 2008 financial crisis. Indeed, this exceptional situation is explained by the ambiguity surrounding the duration, severity and future repercussions of this crisis. The period of increased uncertainty is followed by a significant recession in economic activity across sectors and countries in the world, in particular emerging economies that suffer from limited resources to overcome health, financial and economic crises (Pinshi, 2020; Sharif et al., 2020; Ho and Gan, 2021).

According to statistics published by the World Health Organization, the Covid-19 pandemic has been officially appearing in Tunisia since March 2020. It is noted that at the beginning of the crisis, Tunisia did not experience the same health disaster as some of the world's most developed countries. Moreover, Tunisian authorities put in place early measures and a response plan to attenuate the risk of the pandemic. Nevertheless, the effect of the crisis has been severe and has started to impact the national economy immediately due to the rapid propagation of the virus and the fragility of the economic system.

Since the pre-Covid-19 period, the Tunisian economy has been weakened reacting to the revolution of 2011, the political assassinations of 2013, and the terrorist attacks of 2014 and 2015. In addition, the rapid spread of the Covid-19 pandemic and the necessity to ensure drastic containment measures at the international and national levels has aggravated the economic situation in Tunisia. According to the national institute of statistics of Tunisia, economic growth plunged into a strong recession (-8.8%) in 2020, which is worse than that of 2011 (-1.9%). This recession has affected different elements of national demand. The inflation rate rose from 3% in 2016 to over 6.2% in March 2020, a level that it had not reached since 2000. Moreover, the current economic situation in Tunisia is characterized by an increase in the pressure on public finances. So, measures linked to the explosion of sanitary expenditure led to an important increase in the budgetary deficit and an excessive recourse to the public debt. According to the statistics published by the Tunisian ministry of finance, the budget deficit has widened to more than 11% of GDP in 2020, taking government debt to 88% of GDP.

The uncertainty linked to the Covid-19 crisis poses unprecedented challenges for monetary authorities. In fact, the economic impact of the pandemic depends on the effectiveness of measures that policymakers have put in place to support global demand and to finance health infrastructure. In this context, the Central Bank of Tunisia (CBT) decides to act

proactively by implementing a series of exceptional measures (CBT, 2019). Monetary authorities intended to face up to the ultimate consequences of the health crisis on economic activity and to support businesses as well as the most affected social categories. Thus, the CBT decided to lower its key rate by 100 basis points, bringing it down to 6.75% in March 2020 and then by 50 points in October 2020 in response to the economic repercussions that followed the second wave of the pandemic. Also, monetary policymakers have recourse to other measures, such as providing liquidity to the banking sector and applying prudential norms, notably the credit/deposit ratio. These measures aim to ensure the standard operations of banks and to support businesses by granting exceptional funding. The measures adopted by the Tunisian monetary authorities prioritize the rescue of human lives while making sure that economic stability is preserved. However, the high level of uncertainties and the limited monetary and budgetary room for maneuver didn't make the decision of the monetary authorities easy.

According to the literature, several proxies are proposed to measure the level of uncertainty (Altig et al., 2020). For example, forecast disagreement (Bachmann et al., 2013), stock market volatility (Leduc and Liu, 2016; Caggiano et al., 2020) and economic policy uncertainty (Sharif et al., 2020; Lyke, 2020), among others. Recently, many studies have used the World Uncertainty Index (WUI) developed by Ahir et al. (2019) as the main measure of aggregate uncertainty linked to different events such as financial crises, terrorist attacks and health outbreaks (Gozgor et al., 2019; Avom et al., 2020; Rjiba et al., 2020).

This article addresses new contributions to the literature related to the impact of Covid-19. First, this research sheds new light on the health pandemic in an emerging country such as Tunisia, alongside recent empirical studies (Jeribi and Snene Manzli, 2020; Kokas et al., 2020). In fact, this study offers new insights into the effect of uncertainty by using a new measure of WUI from Ahir et al. (2019). Second, we use a novel estimation technique called Bayesian vector auto-regression (BVAR) to examine the impulse responses of uncertainty and monetary shocks to a large number of macroeconomic variables.

This article is organized as follows: section 2 presents a description of the data and the empirical model. Sections 3 discuss the empirical results and section 4 concludes that we draw from this research.

2. Materials and methods

In this section, we present the empirical methodology and describe the variables of the model used to examine the macroeconomic effects of uncertainty and monetary policy shocks in Tunisia during the period of the Covid-19 crisis.

2.1. Methodology

We adopt a BVAR model referring to recent research about the economic impact of the Covid-19 pandemic (Djurovic et al., 2020; Evgenidis and Papadamou, 2020; Pinshi, 2020; Anton, 2022).

The model is represented by the following equation:

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n A_i Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

Where the vector A is a matrix of regression coefficients for the selection of all macroeconomic variables included in the Y vector, such as uncertainty, production, inflation, export, import, investment, exchange rate and interest rate.

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ A_1 \\ \vdots \\ A_i \end{bmatrix}; Y = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{t-1} \\ \vdots \\ Y_{t-i} \end{bmatrix}$$

Also, a_0 is the intercept vector and $\varepsilon_t : N(0, \Sigma)$ is a vector of residuals.

In order to simplify the model, it can be written as follows:

$$Y = (L_n \otimes A)\theta + e$$

While, $A = (A_1, \dots, A_i)'$, L_n is the identity matrix of n dimension and $\theta = \text{Vec}(A)$

The advantage of estimating a BVAR model is that it leads to coping with the problem of over-parameterization by imposing prior beliefs on the parameters (Adjemian and Pelgrin, 2008). In setting the prior distribution, we use the Minnesota prior introduced by Litterman (1986) to reduce the problem related to the high dimension of a priori distribution.

2.1. Data and variable description

In the last decade, the degree of uncertainty has augmented significantly in Tunisia due to the revolution of 2011, the political assassinations of 2013 and the period of terrorist attacks in 2014 and 2015. In fact, this period of political transition has caused a fairly persistent uncertain environment. Besides, we notice in the Figure 1 below that the high level of uncertainty index arises during the global spread of Covid-19 disease and persists because the health crisis is not over yet.

Figure 1. Plot of logarithmic world uncertainty index for Tunisia

Source: By authors, worlduncertaintyindex.comdatabase

The WUI is formulated by counting the frequency of the word “uncertainty” (or its variants) in the Economist intelligence unit country reports and multiplying it by 1,000.

The other data for real gross domestic production (Real GDP), consumer price index (CPI), export (EXP), import (IMP), investment (INVEST), real effective exchange rate (REER) and monetary market interest rate (MMR) are extracted from the database of the national institute of statistics of Tunisia and the CBT. We use the MMR as a main instrument of the monetary policy of CBT for studying the effects of the monetary shock.

The sample covers data from 2009 m1 to 2020 m9 at a monthly frequency. Except for the policy interest rate, which is expressed as a percentage, the majority of the series are expressed in logarithms.

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the main variables of our model mentioned above. The average WUI of the total sample is 3.6%. The Kurtosis test is a measure of the tailedness of a probability distribution. All of the variables are platykurtic with a Kurtosis less than 3. However, WUI is leptokurtic relative to the normal, with a Kurtosis of 3.082. Besides, the Jarque-Bera test determines whether a series follows a normal distribution. It is important to note that the Jarque-Bera statistic rejects the null hypothesis of normal distribution.

Table 1. *Descriptive summary statistics*

Variables	Observations	Mean	Std. Dev.	Kurtosis	Jarque-Bera
WUI	141	0.365	0.299	3.129	0.000
MMR	141	5.062	1.281	2.935	0.000
Real GDP	141	3.747	0.029	1.962	0.028
CPI	141	2.091	0.074	1.868	0.014
EXP	141	3.386	0.108	2.421	0.216
IMP	141	3.537	0.116	2.651	0.617
REER	141	1.961	0.039	2.442	0.000
INVEST	141	1.764	0.284	2.840	0.001

3. Results and discussions

The aim of this section is to analyze the obtained results of impulse responses of uncertainty and monetary policy shocks to large macroeconomic variables such as output, inflation, export, import, exchange rate and investment. Firstly, we investigate the properties of the series by checking the stationary of each variable. Then, we made impulse response functions of macroeconomic variables to uncertainty and monetary shocks.

3.1. Unit root tests

The analysis of the unit root test is an important step for the application of the BVAR model (Silvia and Iqbal, 2012). Therefore, we apply the ADF test (Dickey and Fuller, 1981) to study the stationary of the series. This test covers the null hypothesis that validates the presence of the unit root meaning that the process is not stationary. The results reported in Table 2 show that the ADF test rejects the null hypothesis in the first difference of all the macroeconomics variables.

Table 2. Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test

Variables	Level		First difference	
	Intercept	Trend and intercept	Intercept	Trend and intercept
WUI	-1.910 (0.326)	-2.053 (0.566)	-4.963*** (0.000)	-4.999*** (0.000)
MMR	-0.947 (0.773)	-1.998 (0.596)	-4.008*** (0.001)	-4.008*** (0.008)
Real GDP	-1.906 (0.304)	-1.157 (0.914)	-8.023*** (0.000)	-8.131*** (0.000)
CPI	2.839 (1.000)	-1.488 (0.829)	-5.29*** (0.000)	-6.127*** (0.000)
EXP	-1.749 (0.403)	-2.984 (0.140)	-7.233*** (0.00)	-7.237*** (0.000)
IMP	-2.155 (0.226)	-2.054 (0.566)	-8.983*** (0.000)	-9.211*** (0.000)
REER	-1.478 (0.541)	-1.905 (0.646)	-4.400*** (0.000)	-4.427*** (0.002)
INVEST	-0.463 (0.893)	-2.595 (0.283)	-3.239** (0.019)	-4.141** (0.007)

Note: *, ** and *** indicate the significance level at the 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively. The number of lags was chosen based on the reporting criteria of Akaike and Schwartz.

Following the existence of the discontinuities and structural breaks in the time series, the one-regime unit root test becomes misidentified, and it is not informative enough of non-stationarity. In this regard, we examine the unit root properties of a series to determine the break-year in each variable. To do this, we use the procedure developed by Zivot et Andrews (1992) to test the null of unit root against the break-stationary alternative hypothesis. A structural break test is required to approve this proposal, and the results of this test are given in Table 3. The obtained results indicate that the series presented in the model are stationary by specifying the year of break for each variable.

Table 3. Unit root test of Zivot and Andrews

Variables	T-Statistic	Year of break
WUI	-7.689***	2020
MMR	-10.017***	2019
Real GDP	-29.674***	2020
CPI	-10.544***	2017
EXP	-10.850***	2020
IMP	-10.993***	2020
REER	-9.558***	2017
INVEST	-8.711***	2020

Note: *, ** and *** indicate the significance level at the 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively. Optimal lag length is determined according to the Schwarz information criteria (SIC). The breaks are in both intercept and trend.

3.2. Impulse response functions

We focus our study on the responses of macroeconomic variable to uncertainty and monetary shocks. In this regard, we use the BVAR model of Minnesota-Litterman prior based on the following values of hyper-parameters ($\lambda_1 = 0.1$; $\lambda_2 = 0.99$; $\lambda_3 = 1$) extracted from Pinshi (2020).

The figures below represent the impulse responses of these shocks. All graphs have an axis of abscissas that represents the monthly time horizon and a vertical axis that specifies the amplitude of the impulse response for each variable.

First of all, Figure 2 presents impulse responses to an uncertainty shock in Tunisia during the last 12 months. We observe a significant drop in production activity, which stabilized at the end of the period. This severe recession is accounted for by the cessation of economic activity following the containment measures. Therefore, the Tunisian economy has plunged into a phase of depression in the long term. Also, the inflation rate increased until the 4th month. Then, it got down slightly in the short time period of 2 to 3 months. After that, inflation started to grow again from the 6th month until it reached a high level. This augmentation is due to the decision of the monetary authorities to reduce the interest rate.

According to the literature, Krol (2014) shows that uncertainty makes the exchange rate volatile. We remark in the graphic that the exchange rate is volatile since the 4th month because of the uncertainty linked to the Covid-19 crisis. This situation generates difficulty in making decisions on international trade and investment for economic agents. So, the level of exports started to drop in the 3rd month following the interruption of exporting businesses' activity during the containment period. Then, exports increased again, with a slow recovery expected in line with the impact of the health situation on tourism and related activities.

According to the responses of investments, they have plunged significantly because of the increase in uncertainty and the fall in economic agents' income. Overall, we suggest that an uncertainty shock has a negative impact on the different macroeconomic variables. Thus, the uncertainty and the suspension of some economic activities and businesses affect the economic situation in Tunisia.

Furthermore, Figure 3 plots impulse responses to monetary policy shocks in Tunisia during the last 12 months. From these graphics, we examine the impact of the reduction in the interest rate. Firstly, we note that the production activity has started to decrease gradually from the third month. Then, it has continued to deteriorate significantly. Secondly, we observe that the inflation rate increased until it reached a high level. This augmentation is due to the reduction in the interest rate. In fact, controlling the level of inflation has long been considered a challenge for the CBT, especially in times of crisis.

Moreover, we note a strong decline in international trade in response to the monetary shock. Thus, we remark a significant drop in the level of exports until the 4th month. Then, it continued to decrease slowly in the long term. As to the response of the exchange rate, it has accentuated since the 4th month in the long term. Finally, we observe a tragic drop in investment in response to the reduction in interest rates.

In conclusion, we note that a monetary policy shock has negative repercussions on the principal macroeconomic variables in Tunisia, during the Covid-19 period. Indeed, the reduction in the interest rate has increased the severity and persistence of inflationary pressures without necessarily stimulating Tunisian economic activity.

The finding results suggest that the conventional measures adopted by the monetary authorities are insufficient to overcome the economic repercussions of the Covid-19 crisis. Therefore, the CBT should reexamine its monetary policy strategy and replace it with the unconventional operational framework.

Figure 2. Impulse response to uncertainty shock

Note: Impulse response to an uncertainty shock in Tunisia obtained from a BVAR model of Minnesota-Litterman prior. The value of hyper-parameters ($\lambda_1 = 0.1$; $\lambda_2 = 0.99$; $\lambda_3 = 1$).

Figure 3. Impulse response to monetary shock

Note: Impulse response to a monetary shock in Tunisia obtained from a BVAR model of Minnesota-Litterman prior. The value of hyper-parameters ($\lambda_1 = 0.1$; $\lambda_2 = 0.99$; $\lambda_3 = 1$).

4. Conclusion

In this article, we analyze the effects of an uncertainty shock on the Tunisian economy during the period of the Covid-19 pandemic and examine the effectiveness of the monetary policy responses to overcome the economic consequences of this crisis. In this regard, we simulate both uncertainty and monetary shocks on a large range of macroeconomic variables, including economic activity, inflation, the exchange rate, export, import, and investment. Also, we consider the WUI as a proxy to measure the degree of uncertainty and the interest rate as the main instrument of monetary policy. By contributing to better understanding of the impacts of an uncertainty shock, we use the BVAR approach.

Specifically, better identification of economic characteristic during the period of the health pandemic found that an environment of uncertainty would generate persistent macroeconomic instability in Tunisia. We suggest that a shock of uncertainty has a negative impact on the different macroeconomic variables. Thus, the uncertainty related to the duration and severity of Covid-19 as well as the suspension of some economic activities and businesses affects the Tunisian economic situation.

During the period of uncertainty due to the Covid-19 crisis, the response of monetary policy by reducing interest rates appears ineffective. So, the CBT failed to control inflation and regulate national economic activity. This result suggests that conventional measures of monetary policy are insufficient to overcome the economic repercussions of uncertainty linked to the health crisis.

In summary, given the finding, our research highlights the policy implications. Tunisian authorities should reexamine their monetary policy strategy to overcome the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic on the national economy. They should extend its action to unconventional measures adopted in advanced economies since the global financial crisis.

References

- Adjemian, S., and Pelgrin, F., 2008. Un regard bayésien sur les modèles dynamiques de la macroéconomie. *Économie & prévision*, 183-184(2), pp. 127-152.
- Ahir, H., Bloom, N., and Furceri, D., 2019. The World Uncertainty Index. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, WP 19-027, pp. 1-87.
- Altig, D., Baker, S., Barrero, J.M., Bloom, N., Bunn, P., Chen, S., Davis, S.J., Leather, J., Meyer, B., Mihaylov, E., Mizen, P., Parker, N., Renault, T., Smetanka, P., and Thwaites, G., 2020. Economic uncertainty before and during the Covid-19 pandemic. *Journal of Public Economics*, 191, pp. 104-274.
- Anton, G., 2022. The importance of demand, uncertainty and monetary policy shocks from the euro area for the Romanian economy. *Theoretical and Applied Economics*, 29(2), pp. 25-38.

- Avom, D., Njangang, H., and Nawo, L., 2020. World Economic Policy Uncertainty and Foreign Direct Investment. *Economics Bulletin*, 40(2), pp. 1457-1464.
- Bachmann, R., Elstner, S., and Sims, E.R., 2013. Uncertainty and Economic Activity: Evidence from Business Survey Data. *American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics*, 5(2), pp. 217-249.
- Caggiano, G., Castelnuovo, E., and Kima, R., 2020. The global effects of Covid-19-induced uncertainty. *Economics Letters*, 194, pp. 109-392.
- Central Bank of Tunisia, 2019. Annual report.
- Dickey, D., and Fuller, W.A., 1981. Likelihood Ratio Statistics for Autoregressive Time Series with a Unit Root. *Econometrica*, 49(4), pp. 1057-72.
- Djurovic, G., Djurovic, V., and Bojaj, M.M., 2020. The macroeconomic effects of Covid-19 in Montenegro: a Bayesian VARX approach. *Financial Innovation*, 6(1), pp. 1-16.
- Evgenidis, A., and Papadamou, S., 2020. The impact of unconventional monetary policy in the euro area. Structural and scenario analysis from a Bayesian VAR. *International Journal of Finance and Economics*, 26(4), pp. 5684-5703.
- Gozgor, G., Demir, E., Belas, J. and Yesilyurt, S., 2019. Does economic uncertainty affect domestic credits? An empirical investigation. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 63, pp. 101-147.
- Ho, L.T., and Gan, C., 2021. Foreign Direct Investment and World Pandemic Uncertainty Index: Do Health Pandemics Matter?. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14(3), pp. 1-15.
- IMF, 2020. A Crisis Like No Other, An Uncertain Recovery, *Perspectives de l'économie mondiale*, Juin.
- Iyke, B.N., 2020. Economic Policy Uncertainty in Times of Covid-19 Pandemic. *Asian Economics Letters*, 1(2), pp. 1-4.
- Jeribi, A., and Snene Manzli, Y., 2020. Can Cryptocurrencies Be a Safe Haven during the Novel Covid-19 Pandemic? Evidence from the Tunisian Stock Market. *Journal of Research in Emerging Markets*, 3 (1), pp. 14-31.
- Kokas, D., Lopez-Acevedo, G., El Lahga, A., and Mendiratta, V., 2020. Impacts of Covid-19 on Household Welfare in Tunisia. Policy Research Working Papers No. 13978, World Bank, pp. 1-21.
- Krol, R., 2014. Economic Policy Uncertainty and Exchange Rate Volatility: Economic Policy Uncertainty and Exchange Rate Volatility. *International Finance*, 17(2), pp. 241-256.
- Leduc, S., and Liu, Z., 2016. Uncertainty shocks are aggregate demand shocks. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 82, pp. 20-35.
- Litterman, R., 1986. Forecasting with Bayesian Vector Autoregressions-Five Years of Experience. *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics*, 4(1), pp. 25-38.
- Pinshi, C., 2020. Covid-19 uncertainty and monetary policy. *Journal of Applied Economic Sciences*, 69, pp. 579-593.
- Rjiba, H., Jahmane, A., and Abid, I., 2020. Corporate social responsibility and firm value: Guiding through economic policy uncertainty. *Finance Research Letters*, 35, pp. 101-553.

-
- Sharif, A., Aloui, C., and Yarovaya, L., 2020. Covid-19 pandemic, oil prices, stock market, geopolitical risk and policy uncertainty nexus in the US economy: Fresh evidence from the wavelet-based approach. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 70, pp. 101-496.
- Silvia, J., and Iqbal, A., 2012. A Comparison of Consensus and BVAR Macroeconomic Forecasts. *Business Economics*, 47(4), pp. 250-261.
- Zivot, E., and Andrews, D.W.K., 1992. Further Evidence on the Great Crash, the Oil-Price Shock, and the Unit-Root Hypothesis. *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics*, 10(3), pp. 25-44.

Research on the evolution of migration in Romania after the fall of the communist regime

Ioana Manuela MÎNDRICAN

University of Economic Studies, Bucharest, Romania
mindrican.ioanamanuela@gmail.com

Elena Florentina MATEI

University of Economic Studies, Bucharest, Romania
matei.elena96@gmail.com

Abstract. *Migration is one of the oldest socio-economic phenomena, which have inevitably influenced and continues to influence today's society because millions of citizens of different states decide to migrate to another country for various reasons. The migration process never stopped, even more it gradually expanded taking on new forms. Consistent with the studies and economic research that has been carried out over the years, it has come to the idea that migration must be seen as a normal phenomenon of today's society, which has undergone various changes throughout history. One of the most important and significant characteristics of the population is the movement from one geographical area to another geographical area.*

This paper entitled "Study on the evolution of migration phenomenon in Romania" highlights the migratory flows that took place in Romania after the fall of the communist regime and so far, putting there is a special emphasis on the economic and social impact on the migration that brought with it. During the period considered in the analysis, Romania knew various forms of this phenomenon through the fact that it made the transition from a centrally planned economy to a market economy and later joined the European Union in 2007. In this situation, the circulation of Romanians became complete. The problems resulting from this phenomenon are major: on the one hand the financial consequences and on the other hand the social impact that could be observed on the families of migrants.

The novelty element of this paper is the forecast on the migration phenomenon in the coming years, more precisely during the years 2021-2026, in Romania. Through this research we want to identify and analyze the future trend taking into account the fact that migration can be considered one of the sources of problems in the labor market or can even be its solution. An important aspect to mention is the idea that the temporary nature of travel, as well as the transnational nature of flows offers the possibility to reorient migrants to the state of origin. In order to achieve an ideal reality in terms of balance in the labor market, it is necessary to adopt and implement effective measures that offer benefits to each employee.

Keywords: migration, socio-economic phenomena, market economy, European Union, labor market.

JEL Classification: H26, J61, P25, R23.

Introduction

After 1989, when the border barriers fell, the migration phenomenon reached its peak in Eastern Europe, but especially in Romania. Regarding the opening of Eastern Europe in relation to other countries globally after 1990, it brought with it a number of significant advantages, such as: capital inflows and investments in innovation, which materialized through the creation of institutions much more complex, much more efficient management of economic activity, as well as higher efficiency. At the same time, a number of negative effects could be identified, such as the considerable exodus of the population and the loss of intelligence.

Migration is now an increasingly complex phenomenon that is attracting more and more interest for economists, sociologists, researchers, geographers and last but not least, for government circles at the level of several states. In these circumstances, it is particularly important to carry out a multidisciplinary analysis and the innovative element of this paper is the treatment of labor migration in Romania from an economic, demographic and social perspective. Regarding the present research, it is a qualitative one, because it is based on a series of criteria that were studied in order to analyze the complexity of the migration phenomenon in Eastern Europe in the period 1989-2020, among them being:

- The main reasons that influence individuals in making this decision (age, marital status, level of qualification from a professional point of view, background, professional perspectives, etc.);
- Migration has become a social phenomenon over the years. This is mainly highlighted by the fact that most people who have settled in another country have created real migration networks, which have facilitated the access of many families to the labor market. Through these migration networks, people find much faster essential information about available jobs in that state, labor market conditions, wage levels and so on.
- The level of remittances is closely in line with the educational and occupational level.

The biggest challenge in the current context of the migration phenomenon is the ability and insight of people to accurately describe and predict the dynamics and magnitude of such a process. The objective of this research is to identify and present the evolution and effects of migration in Romania since 1990. The structure of the paper aims on the one hand to highlight the literature in this field of activity and case study. At the end of the paper is presented a set of conclusions relevant to the present research.

Literature review

In a world in constant change, in which periods of economic growth alternate to some extent with periods of crisis, the most important strategic resource of society and the economy remains the human resource. According to the economic literature, the general movement of the population consists of two fundamental processes, namely: the natural movement which is determined by the actual demographic events (birth rate, mortality) and

the migratory movement. This involves changing the residential, social and last but not least, professional state of the people who decide to take such a decision. In contrast to demographic phenomena, migration is considered to be the "black sheep of demography".

Over the years, many empirical studies have been conducted on this field of activity, but the perspectives are contradictory. An eloquent example is Barro and Sala-i-Martin, who argue that the migration phenomenon in the United States and Japan has "positive effects, especially on the long-term growth rate" (European Commission, European Agenda on Migration: continued efforts to support progress, Brussels, 14 March 2018).

The analysis of the migration phenomenon has been carried out over the years both from the perspective of the emigration countries and of the immigration countries. A topic that aroused the curiosity and interest of economists was the "brain drain" that occurs in the states of emigration. This was mainly influenced by demographic and social pressures, which resulted from the expansion of the migration phenomenon. According to Bonin's scientific research, these measures are due to the "impact that this process had at European level after 1990, when it was wanted to attract as many young immigrants as possible, who are considered competitive economically speaking, thus having the capacity to alleviate to some extent the problems resulting from the aging population" (Massey et al., 2005). Another study that highlighted the importance of migration on emigration states is conducted by Louka T. Katseli, Robert E.B. Lucas and Theodora Xenogiani. Consistent with the before mentioned study, the idea was reached that "remittances significantly influence both the microeconomic and macroeconomic contexts" (Louka et al., 2006). Temporary migration is what causes an increase in the flow of remittances to the country of origin, in relation to permanent migration, especially of people who are poorly qualified from a professional point of view and aim to return to their country of origin. Undoubtedly, studies focusing on the effects of migration in Romania have shown that in the context in which "Western states will continue to attract human resources from our state, this action will materialize by reducing the gross domestic product and implicitly, the rate of economic growth" (Dăianu, 2009).

The theory of migrant networks was developed by Taylor and Massey in 1952 and involves the idea that migration is mainly influenced by kinship, friendship that manifests itself with people from other states. Most people who decide to migrate base their choice on the presence of other individuals in the state of migration. According to the specialized economic literature, "migrant networks form a set of interregional relations that unite migrants through the state of origin, the state of destination, family ties, friendships, etc." (Massey et al., 2005). More specifically, this concept highlights "the way in which people who have continued to maintain social relations with the community from which they left, regardless of the economic, social, demographic context in which they find themselves" (Massey et al., 2005). "The evolution and extent of migrant social networks has been determined by several factors, such as: the priority and need for family reunification, the development of various clandestine forms of migration, the inability of public policies to manage this situation optimally" (Petersen, 1958). According to the American economist

Michael Joseph Piore, he argues that "international migration has spread more and more globally, due to the increase in labor demand in developed economies" (Kritz et al., 1992).

Compared to the demographic phenomena that describe the natural movement of the population, the theme of migration is known as "the black sheep of its demography" (Rotariu, 2009, p. 146). Over the years, different personalities have expressed their views on migration, such as the demographer Vladimir Trebici who argues that "immigration has the same meaning as births, emigration is a loss". (Trebici, 1991).

Romanian psychologist Adrian Neculau is of the opinion that migration is "a process of transforming a social reality into a mental object, a process involving selection according to the position occupied by the individual, his social status". (Neculau, 1996, pp. 34-51). At the same time, he perceives the migration process in a distinct way compared to the other approaches mentioned above "a relational process because mental development is dependent on the situation of the person, group, institution, social category in relation to another person, group, institution, social category". (Neculau, 1996, pp. 34-51)

According to a study conducted by the European Commission, in Romania the discussions referring to the demographic crisis, the labor market, the effects of the migration phenomenon, including the labor market, immigration have intensified considerably in recent times. The consequences of human capital movements for countries of origin "externalities" concern: the phenomenon of "brain drain", which negatively affects, at least in the first phase, the economic performance of the country of origin; the educated workforce is a factor in attracting FDI and development flows through research and development. Remittances are also considered as amounts sent by migrant workers, usually to their families or friends, and are presented the factors that influence the volume and frequency of remittance flows (number of migrant workers; wages; economic activity in the country of origin/recipients exchange rate, political risk, facilities for transferring funds, marital status, level of education of migrants, whether the migrant is accompanied by a wife/children, time elapsed since the date of migration, level of family income). Research on the use of remittances shows that most of it is used for food, clothing and health services, construction or rehabilitation of housing, land acquisitions or other durable goods and only to a small extent for "productive investments" (with multiplier effect of creating new jobs). (Perspectives on migration policy in the current demographic context in Romania, European Institute of Romania).

According to research conducted by Monica Roman and Bogdan Ileanu, entitled "Modeling the remittance decision of eastern European emigrants" income is a decisive factor that positively influences both the decision to remit and the amount remitted. Also important is personal attachment to the country of origin, as well as the degree of integration into society. Demographic factors, such as: age, sex or education, most often does not influence the probability of remittance or the amount remitted. More specifically, it can be said that factors that show strong attachment to relatives and origin have a positive impact on remittances from net income, while factors related to a strong integration of migrants into society have a negative impact on remittances.

Research methodology

In this paper we used a mixed research methodology, because it includes both a descriptive analysis used to achieve the stage of knowledge and a dynamic macroeconomic analysis used to analyze the evolution of the migration phenomenon in the period 1990-2020.

Also, to carry out this work we used the database taken from the website of the National Institute of Statistics (INS) on the evolution of the unemployment rate, for the analyzed period 1990-2020. At the same time, in order to identify the future evolution of the migration rate, we also made a forecast in its Excel program for the period 2021-2026.

Migration in Romania during 1989-2020

At the level of Romania, in the last half of the century, two periods of the migration phenomenon were registered, characterized by economists as being of great intensity.

The first period took place between 1971-1981, when about two million citizens of the state moved from rural to urban areas, thus registering an annual average of about 180 thousand changes of address. The second wave was recorded after 1989, during which time about 100,000 people permanently migrated to Germany. The last period considered in this analysis is the most important, namely, post-December emigration. Initially, departures were from rural to urban areas and later expanded by migrating to different destinations. The migration phenomenon began to increase significantly over the years, with the identification of the advantages and benefits that other states offer, but also when eliminating the visa requirement for Romanians in the Schengen area. Thus, the idea can be stated that Romanians have gradually begun to orient themselves towards states that are much better developed from an economic point of view and at the level of which they will have the possibility to obtain a proper living in accordance with the effort made. At the same time, according to a study conducted by INS, the temporary external migration that took place after 1989 significantly exceeded the internal migration, known as village-town migration from the communist period of the 1970's.

At the time of the fall of the communist regime, more precisely in 1989, the migration phenomenon in Romania was characterized as a worrying one, due to its international expansion. According to studies conducted by Eurostat, in an article entitled "Migration and migrant population statistics", at that time about 96,929 people left the territory of the Romanian state, this being an effect of opening borders, and later, in the first 3 years, more precisely 1989-1991 reached the number of 170,000 people. An important aspect to mention is the fact that 75% of the emigrants were Hungarians, Germans and Jews. This was mainly due to the fact that the former Soviet states had been in an economic and social crisis for more than a decade and were therefore isolated on the international stage, and the only way for citizens to escape from these prisons it was represented by the flight across the border to the west.

Taking into account the information presented by Eurostat in the article "Migration and migrant population statistics", we can affirm the idea that during the 32 years post-communism, two fundamental periods could be identified that characterize the migration at the level of the Romanian state, namely:

- The first period took place between 1989-1995, which was mainly characterized by a migration rate of 7 individuals per 1000 inhabitants. In this context, the destination countries were represented by: Turkey, Hungary, Italy, Israel and last but not least, Germany.
- The second period took place between 1996 and continues until today, the emigration rate being identical to the one mentioned above, of about 7 people per 1000 inhabitants, but this time, other states were considered by emigrants, more precisely: the United States of America, which has become "the land of all possibilities", Canada and Spain. Also, this process continue even today due to the appearance of Schengen visas and Romania's accession to the European Union in 2007. An important aspect to mention is that the emigration rate it increased significantly, reaching 28 people per 1000 inhabitants. Currently, the states considered by emigrants are: Italy, which holds about 40% of active migrants in the labor market, Spain 18%, Hungary 5%, being equal to Germany and Israel by one percentage point more much, 6%.

Graph 1. *Definitive emigrants*

Source: Graph made by the author based on information published on the official INS website.

According to the graph presented above, which shows the number of permanent emigrants from Romania during the years 1990-2020, it can be seen that the highest value was recorded in 1990 by 96929 people and the lowest in 2010 by 7906 people.

During the period considered the values fluctuated significantly. Along with the negative natural increase, migration is in the current context in Romania a major cause of the constant decrease of the population on the territory of the state. The citizens' perspective on the short-term and medium-term evolution of economic and social indicators gradually leads to a significant increase in departures from the country of origin. The main cause that

determined the magnitude of this phenomenon during the analyzed period is the need to improve the quality of life for both them and the whole family, in their conception, in another country you can get many more advantages compared to the state of residence. At the same time, the stability of family relations aims at their reunification with those abroad and this aspect had and continues to have a fairly large influence on the migration balance.

Graph 2. *Definitive immigrants*

Source: Graph made by the author based on information published on the official INS website.

During the period considered, the value of this indicator fluctuated quite a lot, the lowest value being recorded in 1990 (1587) and the highest in 2018 (65678).

According to statistical data published by the NIS, since 2008, the year of the economic and financial crisis, there has been a downward trend of temporary emigrants and subsequently, in 2012, the lowest migration balance was registered. In this situation, the difference between immigrants and emigrants was 2920 people. Two years later, the trend of migration began to increase gradually. An eloquent example to highlight the idea mentioned above, is represented by the fact that in 2007, the year of Romania's accession to the European Union, the average monthly net salary was about 1042 lei, later in 2017, it reached 2383 lei. This increase was 128% compared to Romania's accession to the European Union. Although the salary level increased, Romanian employees continued to have much lower salaries compared to other European countries and this led them to adopt the decision to migrate, the gap being significant. It should be mentioned that the salary increases did not have a direct correspondent in the evolution of the living standard of the population because the inflation rate was quite high, thus leading to the increase of expenses and the decrease of the purchasing power.

In Romania, but also in other European countries, not only the salary level influences the decision to migrate, another significant factor is the socio-economic context as a whole, which in our country is characterized by a high instability. In terms of immigration, it

reached 20 percentage points, being represented mainly by pupils and students, as a result of advantageous scholarships and the field of research, development and innovation offered by other states.

Forecast of the migration rate in Romania in the period 2021-2026

Forecasting is known in the economic literature as a technique by which future trends are projected using conclusive statistics. Also, the forecast is a very complex and important process, because it offers the possibility to obtain some probabilities and which would represent in the current context the best course of action.

In this article, a forecast was made using Excel, as it offers a variety of tools in this area, while having a high capacity to store calculations and view data. The evolution of the migration rate both at the level of Romania and at the level of the member states of the European Union is an intensely debated issue, which has a significant impact on the decision-making process.

To obtain this prediction of the future evolution of migration, the quantitative method Exponential Smoothing was used, abbreviated ETS, which is based on an algorithm for identifying, but also for detecting seasonal patterns and confidence intervals.

Graph 3. Forecast on the evolution of definitive emigrants for the period 2021-2026

Years	Definitive emigrants	Forecast(Definitive emigrants)	Lower Confidence Bound(Definitive emigrants)	Upper Confidence Bound(Definitive emigrants)
2010	7906			
2011	18307			
2012	18001			
2013	19056			
2014	11251			
2015	15235			
2016	22807			
2017	23156			
2018	27229			
2019	26775			
2020	21031	21031	21031,00	21031,00
2021		26814,87345	17414,83	36214,92
2022		28166,92465	18475,30	37858,55
2023		29518,97584	19542,06	39495,89
2024		30871,02704	20614,58	41127,48
2025		32223,07824	21692,39	42753,77
2026		33575,12943	22775,08	44375,18

Source: Graph made by the author based on information published on the official INS website.

According to the graph resulting from the forecast, the average level of permanent emigrants in the following years will be:

- 2021 – 26814.87;
- 2022 – 28166.92;
- 2023 – 29518.97;
- 2024 – 30871.02;
- 2025 – 30195.01;
- 2026 – 33575.12.

It can be seen in accordance with the chart presented that the level of the indicator was around 20220.75. With 95% confidence, the expected result will be between upper and lower 20220.75-37550.97.

Graph 4. Forecast on the evolution of definitive immigrants for the period 2021-2026

Years	Definitive immigrants	Forecast(Definitive immigrants)	Lower Confidence Bound(Definitive immigrants)	Upper Confidence Bound(Definitive immigrants)
2010	7059			
2011	15538			
2012	21684			
2013	23897			
2014	36644			
2015	23093			
2016	27863			
2017	50199			
2018	65678			
2019	64479			
2020	32250	32250	32250,00	32250,00
2021		65233,7247	39631,96	90835,49
2022		69425,96747	43322,20	95529,74
2023		73618,21024	46422,38	100814,04
2024		77810,45302	48777,40	106843,51
2025		82002,69579	50314,06	113691,33
2026		86194,93856	51035,09	121354,79

Source: Graph made by the author based on information published on the official INS website.

According to the graph resulting from the forecast, the average level of permanent immigrants in the coming years will be:

- 2021 – 65233.72;
- 2022 – 69425.96;
- 2023 – 73618.21;
- 2024 – 77810.45;
- 2025 – 82002.69;
- 2026 – 86194.93.

It can be seen in accordance with the chart presented that the level of the indicator was around 20220.75. With 95% confidence the expected result will be between upper and lower 46583.85-104844.81.

Taking into account the predictions made, it can be stated that the level of migration in Romania will be in an appropriate and normal range taking into account the magnitude of the phenomenon in the European Union. The characteristics of the process in Romania reveal that our state is both a destination and an origin of international migration, but nevertheless, its primary status is a country of net emigration, and this could be proven for the coming years, more precisely until 2026, with the help of the forecast.

With regard to the COVID-19 pandemic, it has had a number of negative consequences for human activity globally, and the most affected category is migrants, as confirmed by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, abbreviated OECD. At the same time, migrants are those who would have managed to contribute to the proper functioning of important sectors, such as: the medical, commercial, logistics sector, even during the period of restrictions.

At the same time, migrants are more affected by the economic consequences of the pandemic than other groups. Many of them work in gastronomy, in hotels, in tourism – so exactly in the industries that are now fighting for survival. In the so-called HORECA sector in the EU, about a quarter of employees come from third countries, twice as many as in the

rest of the economic sectors. Employment contracts in the field are often very short-term. As such, migrants are the first to be sent into unemployment.

According to the economic literature "a situation similar to that encountered during the COVID-19 pandemic was encountered in the case of the Spanish flu, which occurred between 1918 and 1920, affecting one third of the global population at that time, more precisely, about 500 million people, causing the appearance of about 50 million deaths, in three recurrent phases" (World Bank Group and Knomad, 2020, p. 2). In this context, it is pointed out that, if the pattern of the twentieth century were to be repeated, the pandemic and the COVID-19 crisis could have a much longer duration than that predicted by the governments of the states.

Research conducted at European level indicates that the measures adopted in the Member States and at the level of the European Union, implicitly in Romania in an attempt to reduce the impact of COVID-19 on citizens' health have led to the establishment of real challenges on intra-EU labor mobility, implicitly, on the European labor market which, of course, generates interdependent effects on the economy as a whole. Specifically, the majority of those working in the different EU Member States whose citizenship they do not have are affected by the impact of the pandemic, whether we are talking about long-term workers settled in another Member State or cross-border workers, seconded or seasonal.

In the context of the existence and development of the Covid-19 pandemic, more precisely in 2020, the conduct of migration policies continued to be prudent from the perspective of economic recovery following the severe contraction due to the pandemic shock, in order to reduce and consolidate the migration rate.

The evolution of the migration rate in the coming years, more precisely until 2026 according to the forecast, is influenced by a multitude of interconnected sources of risks, especially uncertainties that are mainly associated with developments in public health, which are also gaining weight with the onset of the second pandemic wave in the fall of 2020 and the possibility of a new wave in the fall of 2021.

In this context, until a normalization of the situation in the medical system, in relation to the prospects for the evolution of economic activity, it is expected that downward risks will continue unquestionably.

The effects of migration in Romania

The increasing trend of the migration phenomenon was felt mainly after 1989 and was influenced by a number of factors:

1. Objectives:

- The economic situation at the state level.
- The political context.
- Social situation.

2. Subjectives:

- The hope and desire of citizens to get a job that is remunerated as expected.

The impact of the migration phenomenon on the state of origin is a broad and complex process, which involves not only knowing the costs, but also the benefits of this process from an individual, local, national and international point of view. Migration, as previously mentioned, is one of the most complex processes, which has the ability to generate both positive and negative effects, for the country of origin and for the destination. According to specialized studies, one of the advantages of migration for the country of origin is the reduction of the unemployment rate, as well as the decrease of the tension manifested in the labor market, a result that will materialize later by reducing the balance of social expenditures in total state budget expenditures.

Graph 5. *Personal remittances, received (current US\$) – Romania*

Source: Chart taken from the official website of the World Bank.

Another effect that could be observed at the level of the Romanian state is the increase of remittances. These remissions are in the current context an external source of funding for the state budget. Also, the financial resources sent by emigrants to the country of origin were for their families perhaps the only source of livelihood, it is known that most Romanian emigrants are those who live in rural areas and who adopted this decision out of a desire to satisfy one's own and families' needs. In view of these remittances, the living standards of emigrants have increased considerably over the years, due to the fact that their families have managed to build houses and invest in various areas so that at the time of their return, these people have the opportunity to live properly in accordance with the effort

made. More specifically, these remittances essentially represent savings of people who have migrated, savings that thus become a source of investment in the home country.

According to the graph presented above, it can be stated that the volume of remittances has increased more and more, the highest value being reached in 2019 of \$ 7,692 billion. According to article conducted by the United Nation, "Migration", the Romanian state was characterized as the second country with the highest population growth of the diaspora of about 7.3% per year, an increase that was mainly influenced by the mobility of the force, but also in view of the fact that a significant part of it was related to the development and evolution of some regions in Romania.

Also, according to the World Bank (World Bank, Migration and Remittances, September 26, 2019, <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/labormarkets/brief/migration-and-remittances>) Romania for about 10 years is among the first states to receive remittances at the level of the European Union, exceeding the value of 6 billion euros of remittances per year. The National Institute of Statistics states in the article "Exploratory study on migration stocks", that over 5 million Romanians work in another country, of which about 68% send financial resources to their families. The main states considered for migration are: Italy, which registers more than 1 million Romanian migrants, Spain with approximately 650 thousand Romanian citizens and last but not least, Germany with 590 thousand Romanian migrants.

However, the migration of family members leads in most cases to emotional imbalances. There are situations when one of the children stays with a parent or there are situations when they remain under the tutelage of grandparents or other relationships, which later affects their behavior, decisions and actions. In this situation, the idea can be stated that the most affected by the migratory phenomenon over time were children, because no other person can take the place of the mother. Another important aspect to highlight is the fact that many young Romanians decide to migrate to another country for various reasons: the possibility to obtain a higher salary and to be remunerated in accordance with the educational level they have, the possibility of professional ascension, because sometimes Romania imposes certain barriers, the need to satisfy one's own and family's needs, as well as offering much more advantageous scholarships than those in Romania. A positive side of Romanian migration is the cultural impact, which is reflected in the fact that living in states with a higher cultural level, but also with a different civilization, people tend to borrow from behaviors.

Conclusion

In this article we analyzed the evolution of emigrants, respectively immigrants from Romania in the period 1990-2020, as well as the impact felt as a result of this phenomenon. The consequences that have been identified are both economic and social. The effects felt from the economic and financial point of view are: the accentuation of the imbalances of trade balance, which thus favors the imports of goods, as well as the loss of human capital.

The context that brings with it the most problems is the one related to the temporary abandonment of children and families in the country of origin and in these conditions public authorities are required to develop and implement policy measures to support and monitor the situation of minors. These actions thus lead to an increase in government spending.

Taking into account the predictions made, it can be stated that the level of migration in Romania will be in an appropriate and normal range taking into account the magnitude of the phenomenon in the European Union. The characteristics of the process in Romania reveal that our state is both a destination and an origin of international migration, but nevertheless, its primary status is a country of net emigration, and this could be proven for the coming years, more precisely until 2026.

In conclusion, we can affirm the idea according to which the migration of Romanians has evolved during these years due to the economic evolution of other states, which opens new possibilities for future analyzes.

References

- Barro, R.J. and Sala-i-Martin, X., 1995. *Economic Growth*, New York, MacGraw-Hill.
- Blanchard, O. and Katz, L., 1992. Regional evolutions, *Brookings Papers on Economic Activity*, 1, pp. 1-61.
- Borjas, G., 1989. Economic Theory and International Migration, *International Migration Review*, Special Silver Anniversary Issue: International Migration an Assessment for the 90's, The Center for Migration Study of New York, Vol. 23, No. 3.
- Dăianu, D., 2009. *Where is capitalism?*, Iași, Polirom Publishing House.
- Kritz, M.M., Lim, L.L. and Zlotnik, H., 1992. *International migration systems: A global approach*, Oxford, Clarendon Press.
- Louka, T.K., Robert, E.B.L. and Xenogiani, T., 2006. Effects of migration on sending countries: What do we know?, OECD.
- Massey, D.S., Arango, J., Hugo, G., Kouaouci, A., Pellegrino, A. and Taylor, J.E., 1993. Theories of International Migration: A Review and Appraisal, *Population and Development Review*, 19, pp. 431-466.
- Massey, D.S., Arango, J., Hugo, G., Kouaouci, A., Pellegrino, A. and Taylor, E.J., 2005. *Worlds in motion: Understanding international migration at the end of the millennium*. New York, Oxford University Press.
- Menz, G. and Caviedes, A., 2010. *Labor migration in Europe*, Palgrave Macmillan.
- Neculau, A., 1996. *Social Representations – Current Developments, Social Psychology. Contemporary aspects*, Iasi, Polirom Publishing House.
- Petersen, W.A., 1958. General typology of migration, *American Sociological Review*, 23(3), June

- Roman, M. and Ileanu, B., Modelling the remittance decision of eastern European emigrants, University of Economic Studies, Bucharest, Munich Personal RePEc Archive (MPRA). Available at <<https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/31776/>>
- Rotariu, T., 2009. *Demographics and sociology of population. Demographic structures and processes*. Iasi, Polirom Publishing House.
- Trebici, V., 1991. *Population of the Earth – world demography*, Bucharest, Scientific Publishing House.
- Zimmermann, K.F., 2005. *European migration: What do we know?*, New York, Oxford University Press.
- European Commission, 2018. European Agenda on Migration: further efforts needed to support progress, Brussels, 14 March.
- European Commission, 2021. Migration and migrant. Available at <<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/pdfscache/1275.pdf>>, 21 March.
- European Commission, EUROSTAT Database. Available at <<http://ec.europa.eu>>
- International Office for Migration, 2006. Liberalization of the labor market in Romania. Opportunities and risks.
- National Institute of Statistics, Exploratory study on migration stocks. Available at <<https://insse.ro/cms/ro/content/studiu-exploratoriu-privind-stocurile-de-migra%C8%9Bie>>
- National Institute of Statistics, Migration Database. Available at <<http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/#!/pages/tables/insse-table>>
- United Nation, Migration. Available at <<https://www.un.org/en/global-issues/migration>>
- World Bank and Knomad, 2020. COVID-19 Crisis through a Migration Lens. Available at <https://www.knomad.org/sites/default/files/2020-11/Migration%20%26%20Development_Brief%2033.pdf>
- World Bank, 2012. Migration Database. Available at <www.wb.org>
- World Bank, Migration and Remittances, 26 September 2019. Available at <<https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/labormarkets/brief/migration-and-remittances>>

Annex**Table 1.** *Definitive emigrants and definitive immigrants*

Year	Definitive emigrants	Definitive immigrants
1990	96929	1587
1991	44160	1602
1992	31152	1753
1993	18446	1269
1994	17146	878
1995	25675	4458
1996	21526	2053
1997	19945	6600
1998	17536	11907
1999	12594	10078
2000	14753	11024
2001	9921	10350
2002	8154	6582
2003	10673	3267
2004	13082	2987
2005	10938	3704
2006	14197	7714
2007	8830	9675
2008	8739	10030
2009	10211	8606
2010	7906	7059
2011	18307	15538
2012	18001	21684
2013	19056	23897
2014	11251	36644
2015	15235	23093
2016	22807	27863
2017	23156	50199
2018	27229	65678
2019	26775	64479
2020	21031	32250

Source: Made by the author based on information published on the official INS website, <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/#!/pages/tables/insse-table>

Black Sea and East Mediterranean approach on sustainable development

Elena-Iulia CHITA

The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
iulia_elena95@yahoo.com

Silvia DUMITRESCU-POPA

The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
silviapopa997@gmail.com

Abstract. *The Black Sea is at the intersection of Europe, Central Asia and the Middle East, being an important center of transport for steel, agriculture goods and energy. A connection between different cultures, a region with political, social and economic fragmentation. It is linked to the Mediterranean, through the Bosphorus and Dardanelles Strait, which is a region vulnerable to the impact of global warming. Historically, it has also constituted a convenient route with the west, as it is today. The trades that are made in this area are ones of high value not only for each country that surrounds it, but as well for the global market.*

Innovative approaches are needed in order to implement policies and measures to ensure sustainable development in order to adapt for the future, whether it is to minimize the effects of climate changes or different crises this area may face. Adaptation and development of each country is important in order to sustain these challenges, not to mention that in these modern times, imbalances have occurred and strategies need to be rethought by each country.

Keywords: sustainable development, investments, competitiveness, trade, global warming.

JEL Classification: F53, F64, O19, Q56.

Introduction

The sea, through all the problems it poses to the spirit and through all the possibilities offered to the material development of peoples and civilizations, is a very suitable framework for dealing with the great currents of universal history.

In the opinion of Gheorghe I. Brătianu, history can be divided into stages, in relation to a determining criterion that can be the geographical setting of a sea or an ocean. Thus, he appreciated that ancient history is centered around the Mediterranean, while modern history is, above all, a problem of the Atlantic. The Mediterranean Sea (called the Mediterranean for short) is located between Europe, North Africa and West Asia. It is highly dependent on the Atlantic Ocean, which is connected to the Strait of Gibraltar; The Suez Canal connects it to the Red Sea and therefore to the Indian Ocean.

The adjective "Mediterranean" is widely used in the description of peoples, countries, climate, vegetation; for many, the concept of "Mediterranean" is associated with a certain way of life or with an entire period in human history. The term "Mediterranean" itself is used to refer to a climate with long, hot, clear, dry summers and short, cold, humid winters.

There is a long list of small seas in which the Mediterranean Sea is divided. Each corresponds to specific geographical locations or areas where the characteristics, whether due to flora, fauna or geology, change.

List of subdivisions of the Mediterranean Sea:

- Alboran Sea, between Spain and Morocco.
- Minor Sea, southeastern Spain.
- At Mar Chica in northern Morocco.
- Adriatic Sea, between the Italian peninsula and the coasts of Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Montenegro.
- Ionian Sea, between the Italian peninsula, Greece and Albania.
- Libyan Sea in Tunisia.
- Cilicia Sea between Turkey and Cyprus.
- The Levantine Sea off the coasts of Egypt, Lebanon, Cyprus, Israel, Syria and Turkey.
- The Ligurian Sea, between Corsica and Liguria.
- Tyrrhenian Sea, between the east coast of Sardinia, the Italian peninsula and the northern Sicilian coast.
- The Balearic Sea between the east coast of the Iberian Peninsula and the island of Sardinia.
- Aegean Sea, between Greece and Turkey.

Both EU and non-EU countries have coasts on the East Mediterranean. The EU countries are Italy, Slovenia, Croatia, Greece and Cyprus. The non-EU countries are Albania, Montenegro, Bosnia-Herzegovina (with coasts on the Adriatic Sea) and Turkey, Syria, Lebanon, Israel, Gaza Strip, Egypt, Libya (with coasts on the Aegean and/or Levantine Seas).

The Black Sea is a sea in the Atlantic basin, located between Europe and Asia, which borders Russia, Ukraine, Romania, Bulgaria, Turkey and Georgia. The Cherci Strait reaches the Sea of Azov, the Bosphorus into the Marmara Sea, and the Dardanelles Strait

into the Aegean Sea and thus the Mediterranean. The Black Sea connects Europe and Asia. The border established by geographers between the two continents, the Caucasus and the Bosphorus Strait, cuts this sea into two unequal parts, most of which are European.

Due to its position, the Black Sea is the only, main or one of the seas of many peoples who have lived on its shores since ancient times or newer.

Romania is a founding member of the Bank for Trade and Development of the Black Sea (BCDMN), along with the other member states of the Black Sea Economic Cooperation (BSEC), namely Albania, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Georgia, the Hellenic Republic, Moldova, the Russian Federation, Turkey and Ukraine.

The Black Sea is a semi-enclosed sea in the Atlantic basin, part of the Mediterranean Sea, to which it is connected by the Marmara and Aegean seas and the Bosphorus and Dardanelles straits. The Black Sea is the eastern gateway to the EU, an intersection between Europe, Central Asia and the Middle East, an important center of transport and energy, an intersection of different cultures, a region with political, social and economic fragmentation. The Black Sea is one of the most endangered in Europe, considered a "closed" river basin, with unique, dynamic and sensitive ecosystems, threatened by continental pressures and conflicting coastal and maritime activities. It has a geopolitical and strategic importance for the stability, cohesion and prosperity of the region and a great potential for development, to achieve the "Europe 2020" goals for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, including "blue growth", in a wise and integrated way.

Despite numerous international European, regional and local initiatives, programs and documents developed since the early 1990s, including the Convention on the Protection of the Black Sea from Pollution (Bucharest, 1992), the World Bank and the GEF / UNDP ICZM Black Sea Program (1994-1997) and the EU recommendations for a common integrated approach through a series of communications and strategies, the region suffers from a lack of synergy and sufficient coordination.

The Mediterranean region should be one of its major priorities, with a focus on conflict prevention and addressing the root causes of fragility in the southern neighborhood. While stabilizing the region from a security perspective is a top priority for Europe, harnessing the economic and human potential of the Mediterranean region is also key to ensuring lasting peace and prosperity for the benefit of both Europeans and their neighbors.

The Mediterranean Sea is known for being an important historical trade and a powerful factor in the development of the region around it.

We can look over the area's development using a PESTLE analysis, where we can show the major assets for each category.

Political analysis

The Pontic problem is considered to be a more complex issue, as it is an almost closed sea that communicates with the Mediterranean only through the Bosphorus and Strait Dardanelles. However, due to the rivers flowing into the Black Sea, on the one hand, but

also due to the trade routes that reach its ports, on the other hand, it has been called the hub of the great traffic and international trade. The character of the transition zone and the crossroads between Europe and Asia, imprinted on the peoples and states established on the Black Sea coast, made it an important plan for analysis and geopolitical interest.

The Black Sea Basin was the meeting place of flourishing civilizations, imperial ambitions, confrontations for domination and control, economic and cultural synergies. Most countries in the wider Black Sea region (including the Balkans) have long faced serious vulnerabilities in terms of energy security due to their dependence on a secure source of gas supply in Russia, and are thus exposed to political pressure and blackmail. They have, however, learned to cope with the inconvenience caused by this situation and have sought ways to accommodate it, while trying to diversify their sources and improve their energy balance.

Aware of its own vulnerabilities, the EU has adopted and is in the process of implementing a coherent set of legislative and regulatory measures to improve its position on energy and reduce the effects of monopolistic practices: EU Energy Strategy (June 2014), Package Energy Union (March 2015) and the European Commission's Initiative to Connect Gas Grids in Central and South-Eastern Europe – CESEC (July 2015). Despite the slow progress and persistence of political and financial uncertainties in the EU since the 2008-2009 crisis, these political decisions have given Member States and regional partners a certain amount of confidence that they will be able to cope with the turmoil.

A country's access to the sea can greatly influence its economic and political power, and in the case of Russia there is no doubt that access to the sea is a vulnerability. The Western border is another vulnerability of Russia and is of critical importance to it. Control over the Black Sea is one of Russia's most important strategic goals in terms of NATO and EU borders, as part of Russia's policy of regaining international power and limiting NATO's presence. On the other hand, it is clear that the EU is dependent on Russian gas, but also on other energy imports, just as Russia is dependent on Europe, which is the largest export market for gas, investment and technology.

Russian security experts have called this dependence an "asymmetric interdependence", as Russia can last at least a year without European and Western investment, while Europe cannot survive more than 30 days without Russian gas.

The need for a maritime strategy in the Mediterranean area is part of a 25-year program of integrated action in the Mediterranean, given the new challenges posed by the changing situation in the Arab countries of the Mediterranean basin. The Union has developed legislation and a strategy aimed at promoting the sustainable use of the seas, the conservation of marine ecosystems and the protection of basic resources that support economic and social activities related to the sea.

Politically, there has always been a contradiction between the need to reform the political systems of some Mediterranean countries and maintaining, at least apparently, the EU's *status quo* out of a desire to avoid open confrontation. Addressing positive impact of migration policy is a constant goal of the Mediterranean states, as any success of the new initiative depends on the effective management and resolution of the Arab-Israeli conflict.

The gradual change of the EU's borders has provoked reactions from Russia and created new security risks, but also new opportunities for the states in the areas adjacent to the Union, which have had to adapt their strategies and adjust their foreign policy. Of course, these trends have also manifested themselves at the level of the states that have joined the EU. Romania, with the accession, was forced to redefine its priorities in relations with its neighbors and to generate special strategies for the consolidated neighborhood, being at the eastern border of the organization.

At the same time, as a maritime state with a Eurasian extension, it has integrated into the major defining programs and aligned itself with the constructive initiatives on the Black Sea Synergy, the Union for the Mediterranean and the Eastern Partnership.

The EuroMed model sought, like the partnership developed in the Black Sea, to aim for the gradual achievement of an area of peace, prosperity and stability in the region, especially for states that did not have a prospect of EU membership.

EuroMed wanted to be a multilateral partnership designed to increase the potential for regional integration and cohesion, bringing to the sphere of influence of the European Union African states such as: Mauritania, Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, Egypt, but also those in the East. Middle, such as Jordan, the Palestinian Authority, Israel, Lebanon, Syria, Turkey and Albania. At the same time, a number of European countries, such as Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro and Monaco, were drawn to the model of the Extended Black Sea Cooperation Area.

Market share trends indicate that the EuroMed trade liberalization process has not had the expected effects on trade between the two areas. On the contrary, not only their shares respective market conditions have not been improved, but they tended to erode under the effect of a stronger international competition from emerging countries and countries with low wage costs. The geographical proximity does not seem to have constituted a significant determinant of trade integration Euro-Mediterranean.

Similarly, the positive impact of trade openness on the economic growth of the SEMCs is not EuroMed trade liberalization had a limited macroeconomic and sectoral impact during the 2000s, as shown by the lack of a convergence economy with European countries.

Economic analysis

The Black Sea region is of particular economic importance, in view of the future transport corridors for goods and resources, on the one hand, but also in terms of concerns about the deposits of natural resources that the Black Sea has, on the other hand.

On the other hand, the Black Sea region is extremely important for the West, from at least two perspectives:

- is an area of vulnerability for NATO's eastern flank;
- has a special economic importance.

The economic importance of the Black Sea for the West is given by the need to diversify energy sources, diversification possible only in the context in which the networks and transmission lines of energy resources in and through the Black Sea are out of Russia's control.

The European Union is a major provider of assistance to the Mediterranean countries. The region's dependence on exports and external assistance make it a sensitive area, vulnerable to any fluctuations in the foreign market. Foreign direct investment is asymmetrically distributed in the Mediterranean region.

Energy has played an important role in the Euro-Mediterranean Partnership. In its regulation, by part of regional cooperation, funds have been allocated to support regional energy projects. The Mediterranean area has differences and inequalities in terms of energy, both between the northern part where countries are energy consuming and the southern part, as well as in terms of energy resources, the most important being concentrated in three countries: Algeria, Libya, and Egypt.

The Mediterranean area has potential resources of renewable energy (solar, wind) which could be an alternative to classical resources.

Social analysis

The SRIA was developed on the basis of the objectives already agreed, as mentioned in the Burgas Vision Sheet to address the challenges. The initiative has identified four main pillars on which a new set of actions can be developed research and innovation:

- Addressing the fundamental challenges of Black Sea research – the Black Sea Knowledge Bridge.
- Development of products, solutions and clusters to support the Blue Growth and Blue Economy of the Black Sea.
- Creation of critical support systems and innovative infrastructures – Common Key Infrastructure and Policy Facilitators.
- Education and capacity building – Skilled Citizens and Improved Blue Workforce.

Technological analysis

The investments in research, development, education and skills constitute a key policy element to an economic growth and to the development of a knowledge-based economy, leading to a growing interest in the role and measurement of skills. In this context, there is an increased need to measure and analyze the most highly skilled parts of the labor force.

General development of the fuel and transport industry as in electric vehicles are becoming more important. Consideration of starting a biofuel production company at this time should include the expected life cycle of the industry.

If the evolution of the electric vehicle industry increases significantly, investments in biofuels could be unprofitable due to declining demand. The technological influence on the biofuels industry highlights the importance of expected demand and raises the question: Is the expected time to biofuel demand that will decrease due to other technologies long enough to be profitable investment? On the other hand, the ability to convert the production process or use it for other applications will influence the estimated life of the investment.

Also, it is well known that technology development helps Europe's leading firms boost their productivity, failure to adopt new technologies is holding many firms back. As a result, productivity and wage gaps are widening.

The Black Sea region is an area of production and distribution of strategic importance for EU energy security. It has a significant potential for diversification of energy supply and is therefore a key element of the EU 's external strategy in the energy sector. Diversifying security of energy supply is of great interest for partners in the region as well as the EU.

Legal analysis

The Council of Europe and the OSCE have established rules on human rights and democracy applies to all Black Sea states. In this respect, EU actions are mainly bilateral in nature. However, actions taken at regional level can play an important role in consolidating and boosting national measures.

In recent years, organizations Black Sea regional governments have committed themselves to creating democratic institutions to promote good governance and the rule of law. The EU supports these regional initiatives by sharing the experience gained in the field of promoting and defending human rights and democracy by proposing programs for training and exchange and by stimulating regional dialogue with civil society.

Improving external border management and regional customs cooperation increases security, helps fight organized cross-border crime, such as trafficking in human beings, arms and drugs, and helps prevent and manage illegal migration. The EU Border Assistance Mission to Moldova and Ukraine, is a success in this area and demonstrates that such measures can contribute equally in conflict resolution.

The Global Approach Method approach to immigration to eastern and southeastern neighbors that provides for new initiatives for better migration management and to combat illegal migration.

The Black Sea region is traversed by important colors of illegal migration, regional cooperation on issues described above becoming, therefore, all the more important. It's encouraging that countries in the region continue to develop cooperation practices to combat cross-border crime in general through channeling experience gained in other similar initiatives in South East Europe and the Baltic area.

Intensifying regional cooperation will strengthen law enforcement capacity especially in the fight against corruption and organized crime. It could be useful as regional actors in the Black Sea region to establish best practices, to develop common rules for the rescue and exchange of information, to establish alert systems for cross-border crime and develop training programs.

In other aspects of legal matter, it's important to mention that in the majority of the region, the following are priority areas for social grow:

- Equal economic independence for women and men.
- Reconciliation of private and professional life.

- Equal representation in decision-making.
- Eradication of all forms of gender-based violence.
- Elimination of gender stereotypes.
- Promotion of gender equality in external and development policies.

Environment analysis

The Black Sea region is an area of production and distribution of strategic importance for EU energy security. It has a significant potential for diversification of energy supply and is therefore a key element of the EU 's external strategy in the energy sector. Diversifying security of energy supply is of great interest to partners in the region as well as the EU. And also supports countries in the region to focus more on sources of alternative energy, on energy efficiency and on energy saving, in order to release significant energy resources.

Energy stability is desired through modernization of the existing energy structure and by building new infrastructures. In this context, the Commission is developing, in collaboration with its partners, a new energy corridor on the axis Caspian Sea – Black Sea. The aforementioned corridor offers several possibilities for additional exports of natural gas from Central Asia through the region Black Sea, in the EU. Moreover, taking into account the increase in the amount of oil that Transit the Black Sea, a concern for safety and the environment, the EU is interested to provide a sustainable and environmentally friendly oil dimension in its activities cooperation in the region. Several Bosphorus Bypass projects are already underway. Investments with significant impact are needed.

There are many regional processes in the environmental area, but there are delays in their implementation. The need to address marine issues at regional level is recognized in the EU Marine Strategy and the proposal for a Directive on marine strategy. In line with the EU Marine Strategy, EU Member States must cooperate with all countries in the region in all regional seas where the EU is riparian. To this end, Member States will be encouraged to work in the framework of regional conventions on the seas, including the Black Sea Commission.

The Black Sea countries need to improve the implementation of multilateral environmental agreements and establish more strategic environmental cooperation in the region. In this regard, the approach adopted by the DABLAS Working Group, which consists in cooperating to improve investment in the water sector, can be applied to other environmental issues at regional level such as nature protection, waste management, industrial pollution or pollution.

In the context in which the regional approach would bring real benefits. Furthermore, the Commission should promote regional activities to combat climate change, in particular through the joint application of the clean development mechanism established by the Kyoto Protocol and involve the countries of the Black Sea Region in international discussions on future actions. Other mechanisms could be considered, such as the long-term development of national emissions trading programs in the region.

Conclusions

There are several other ways that the Black Sea and East Mediterranean regions can promote sustainable development:

Infrastructure development: Investment in infrastructure, such as transportation, communication, and energy networks, can help to promote economic growth and improve the quality of life for people in the regions.

Education and skills development: Investing in education and training can help to build a skilled workforce and promote technological innovation, which are key drivers of economic growth and sustainable development.

Water management: The Black Sea and East Mediterranean regions are facing water scarcity and degradation, which can have negative impacts on human health, agriculture, and the environment. By working together, the regions can promote sustainable water management practices that ensure the availability of clean and safe water for all.

Natural resource management: The Black Sea and East Mediterranean regions are rich in natural resources, including forests, fisheries, and minerals. By working together, the regions can promote the sustainable management of these resources, which can help to protect the environment and generate economic benefits.

Environmental protection and biodiversity conservation: The Black Sea and East Mediterranean regions are home to many important ecosystems, including wetlands, forests, and marine environments. By working together, the regions can protect these ecosystems and promote biodiversity conservation, which can help to ensure the long-term sustainability of the regions.

Climate change mitigation and adaptation: The Black Sea and East Mediterranean regions are vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, including sea level rise, increased frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, and changes in precipitation patterns. By working together, the regions can promote climate change mitigation and adaptation measures that reduce the risks and impacts of climate change.

Through regional cooperation, the Black Sea and East Mediterranean regions can promote sustainable development and ensure that their growth and development benefits all members of society and protects the environment for future generations.

The configuration of the Black Sea region has changed considerably in recent years and will continue to evolve. Under these circumstances, the new EU regional cooperation initiative would complement this way. The very wide range of activities currently carried out at bilateral and sectoral level is useful.

The presence of the European Union in the Black Sea region opens the way to new perspectives and possibilities. This requires consistent, long-term action making the most of these possibilities and bringing greater stability and prosperity in the region. Greater EU involvement in regional cooperation on the Black Sea contributes to this goal.

The Black Sea has had and still has a status in the scientific world, depending on the geographical, geopolitical and geostrategic orientations of Russia, Turkey, the Euro-Atlantic or Germany. In any case, from the Greco-Roman domination to the Euro-Atlantic one, it had the status of a closed lake or sea, of small or great geostrategic importance, depending on the historical events that manifested in this area. What is certain is that it has always been a Eurasian bridge and a strategic rift between European and Asian civilizations.

References

- Agenda strategică pentru cercetare și inovare la Marea Neagră, 2020. Available at <http://connect2blacksea.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/2019.12.03_Black_Sea_SRIA_Final-RO.pdf> Black Sea Synergy | EEAS Website, Black Sea CONNECT CSA financed by EU H2020.
- Comolet, E. and Madariaga, N., 2013. Euro-med growth and trade integration: can we talk of a cost of the non-mediterranean?. Available at <<https://www.afd.fr/en/ressources/euro-med-growth-and-trade-integration-can-we-talk-cost-non-mediterranean>>, MACRODEV.
- Goulding C., Stobberup, K. and O'Higgins, T., 2014. Potential economic impacts of achieving good environmental status in Black Sea fisheries. Available at <<https://www.ecologyand society.org/vol19/iss3/art32/>>
- Toucas B., 2017. The Geostrategic Importance of the Black Sea Region: A Brief History. Available at <<https://www.csis.org/analysis/geostrategic-importance-black-sea-region-brief-history>>

An economic analysis of trade war and deglobalization in current international relations within the paradigm of globalization

Altaf Hussain PADDER

Annamalai University, Chidambaram Tamil Nadu, India
altaf057@gmail.com

Abstract. *The purpose of the article is on the deglobalization processes currently taking place in international economic interactions, and also attempts to examine how the trade blocs of the major economies affect the rest of globalization. The Kinked Exponential Model was used to determine decadal growth rates based on 31 years of panel data from 1990 to 2020 for 15 large countries (gross domestic product). Three different regression models i.e., Pooled OLS, Fixed- and Random-effect models were estimated to examine the effects of trade blocs and wars between nations on the world economy. Over the study period, disparities and increasing economic inequality between variables have widened. In addition, international conflicts have had a negative impact on international trade and have significantly affected globalization. More importantly, trade blocs, particularly the OECD, APEC, and BRICS have slowed trade with the rest of the world, reflecting a process known as regionalization, in which countries cooperate rather than at the global level. In particular, during the third decade of the twentieth century, when the growth rate of trade flows among major countries declined rapidly by 8.8 per cent, this regionalization did not stop and expanded significantly.*

Keywords: globalization, deglobalization, trade war, trade impact, trade blocs, economic integration, kinked exponential model.

JEL Classification: F1, F6, F15, F62.

Introduction

The trade disputes between two or more largest economies on the world stage are currently a hot topic. The current state of tensions does not suggest that they will ease anytime soon, nor does it suggest that they will quickly escalate and spiral out of control. Whatever the economic justification for competitive protectionism, including the use of tariff barriers, the formation of trade blocs, and wars between nations, it is undeniably a factor in the downturn of the world economy. According to scholars, factors contributing to deglobalization include trade imbalances, political pressure, populism, high unemployment, and trade conflicts between nations. As the movement of goods and services has been restricted due to the coronavirus pandemic, the global economy has contracted in the first half of 2020. Due to these factors, there is a high probability that the global economy will experience a slump (Kim et al., 2020).

Globalization is the target of the trade war's impact. The structure of the world economy, which affects how social development unfolds in all areas, forms the basis of globalization theory. The world economy is currently facing new difficulties, such as overcoming the global economic slowdown and reducing the dangers associated with it. In addition, nations need to conduct international business and trade in the face of developing deglobalization. Increasing interdependence and integration towards a global society is the process of globalization. Deglobalization is the process of reducing interdependence and integration among specific global entities, often nation-states, and is the opposite of globalization.

From a practical point of view, the current phenomenon of deglobalization is not only a trend but also a very clear governmental behaviour and policy in several countries. Other scholars believe that the original central role of the United States and other rich countries in the development of globalization has been influenced by the emergence of some emerging economies, such as China. The world's largest economies, China and the United States are currently engaged in a trade war that has drawn attention to the trend toward deglobalization. Meanwhile, the United States' movement toward deglobalization reflects the country's internal socioeconomic problems (Yinan, 2021). Some factors contributing to deglobalization processes originate in economic laws, but there is one factor that unites all the segments studied and is likely to be a key factor: the political will of major players, as evidenced by the expansion of the scope and number of restrictions. Growing protectionism in some ways inhibits international trade, investment, and production, and also plays a role in the unpredictability and mistrust that characterize international relations (Stanojevi, 2020).

The effects of the trade war are directed against globalization. The structure of the world economy, which affects how society develops in each sector of the economy, is the basis of globalization theory. This paradigm shift toward a less interconnected world economy has significant implications for economies and cultures around the world (An et al., 2020). The argument about economic dependence and deglobalization that persisted after former U.S. President Donald Trump began trade conflicts with China and other U.S. trading partners several years ago has been reignited by the Russia-Ukraine crisis. Trump at the time, similar to some others, blamed foreign nations, including China, India, Mexico, and Germany, for the problems of the U.S. economy (Weihua, 2022). More realistically,

neutrals are unsure because they have yet to observe any significant long-term impact on the continent. Based on their analysis of the circumstances, the pessimists believe that Africa will suffer some form of direct or indirect collateral damage from the trade war (Huang et al., 2019).

The number of trading blocs has increased significantly throughout the global economy. Multinationalism and worldwide economic integration are closely linked to globalization. The importance of standard operating procedures, open trade, international conformity, and foreign investment is indicated by globalization. International organizations such as the World Trade Organization (WTO), the International Monetary Fund (IMF), and the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) have been seen as critical to global trade and economics. However, the criticism of globalism was triggered by great difficulties with injustice and inequality among trading nations (Michalak and Gibb, 2010). This triggered regionalism and led to an increase in regional cooperation, such as free trade agreements (FTAs), at the national level. In addition, regional integration agreements show a shift away from multinationalism and globalism, such as the Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership (CPTPP), the European Union (EU), and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) (Kim et al., 2020).

In the context of the globalism paradigm, the paper is devoted to an examination of deglobalization processes in current international economic interactions. The main causes of deglobalization are declining trade growth and global trade; the use of trade barriers to spark trade wars or hostilities between nations and groups of countries; the formation of trade or economic blocs; religion; etc. The main causes of this trend are the unequal distribution of the benefits of globalization, rising inequality, job losses, especially in developing countries, the rise of protectionist measures, and the rise of populist leaders around the world. The least developed countries are the most affected by deglobalization because they have had to make the most difficult adjustments to their economies to accommodate the process due to the rapid changes that have, by and large, been initiated by the most developed countries (Reznikova and Ivashchenko, 2018). Taiwan, the Philippines, Korea, Brazil and the U.S. markets were most affected by the U.S.-China trade war, especially through the supply chain. However, India can benefit from positive spill over effects and production relocation due to the high similarity between Chinese and Indian exports in the U.S. market (Abdal and Ferreira, 2021; Misra and Choudhry, 2020; Stephen, 2022).

In the wake of globalization, there have been significant changes and liberalizations in the trade and commerce sectors. However, even there, the benefits of globalization have not been equitably distributed. The practice of persistent discrimination against goods that are particularly important to low-income countries persists today and has for many years (Trois, 2015). If globalization slows or stops altogether, most nations and most socioeconomic classes will suffer severe consequences. The incomes of both the rich and the poor will fall and the number of people living in poverty will rise, even though a retreat into protectionism may improve income equality in some countries (Hillebrand, 2010). This article examines the impact of trade wars and deglobalization on the 15 largest economies selected based on their size. It also recommends an empirical model to examine how these

blocs, religion, international conflict, and other factors have affected globalization and whether there is deglobalization in the world economy. To determine the international economic linkages under the globalization paradigm, The Kinked exponential model and the log-linear regression model were applied.

1. Methodology and source of data

In this article, both the kinked exponential model and the log-linear regression model of trade are analysed. The approach was chosen in accordance with the design of the study. The study relies on secondary data from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Development Indicators (WDI). The sample size for this study is 15 countries with panel data spanning 31 years from 1990 to 2020 presented in Table 1. Table 2 explains the sources and explanations for the data.

Table 1. List of countries

Top 15 Countries in terms of the size of the economy (gross domestic product, 2020) in trillions			
United States (\$20.89)	China (\$14.72)	Japan (\$5.06)	Germany (\$3.85)
United Kingdom (\$2.67)	India (\$2.66)	France (\$2.63)	Italy (\$1.89)
Canada (\$1.64)	South Korea (\$1.63)	Russia (\$1.48)	Brazil (\$1.44)
Australia (\$1.32)	Spain (\$1.28)	Indonesia (\$1.05)	

Source: World Development Indicators.

Table 2. List of variables

Name of Variables	Measurement	Source of Data
Trade	Exports plus Imports of Counties to the world	DOTS
GDP of Countries	GDP at 2015 constant US dollar	WDI
Per-Capita GDP of Countries	GDP Per-Capita at 2015 constant US dollar	WDI
World GDP	GDP of the world economy at 2015 constant US dollar	WDI
Population of Countries	Population of countries from 1990 to 2020	WDI
Landlocked	If the country is completely landlocked, it is 1 or otherwise	Dummy Variable
Religion	If the country is Christian majority, it is 1 or otherwise	Dummy Variable
War hit countries	If the country is hit by war in a particular year or years, it is 1 or otherwise	Authors own calculation
APEC	if the country is a member of APEC, it is 1 or otherwise	Dummy Variable
ASEAN	if the country is a member of ASEAN, it is 1 or otherwise	Dummy Variable
OECD	if the country is a member of OECD, it is 1 or otherwise	Dummy Variable
BRICS	if the country is a member of BRICS, it is 1 or otherwise	Dummy Variable
First Sub-Period	The sub-period growth rates were estimated by using the Kinked Exponential Model; explained in the model specification	See formulation of Kinked exponential model
Second Sub-Period		
Third Sub-Period		

Note: DOTS (Directorate of Trade and Statistics, IMF). WDI (World Development Indicators, World Bank Database).

Source: Author.

1.1. Formulation of kinked exponential model

Fitting separate exponential trend lines using ordinary least squares to each segment of the series is the standard method for estimating growth rates in the subperiods of a time series (Boyce, 1986). The kinked model assumes that patterns between subperiod growth rates fluctuate and diverge, leading to irregularities and inconsistencies in the overall growth rate over the entire period. These types of anomalies and inconsistencies are often inherent in time series data. In this regard, Boyce (1986) has recommended that the discontinuities

between segments be removed from the piecewise regression when calculating the growth rates of the subperiods of the Kinked Exponential Model.

This study covers the period from 1990 to 2020, divided into three sub-periods, namely 1990-1999, 2000-2009, and 2010-2020. For this purpose, an extended version of the Kinked exponential model was used to calculate the growth rates within sectors for the sub-periods. The procedure in the extended version of the Kinked exponential model is expressed as follows:

The discontinuous growth for the three periods can be estimated using the dummy variable method in the model as follows:

$$\text{Log}Y = a_1 + a_2d_2 + a_3d_3 + (b_1d_1 + b_2d_2 + b_3d_3)t + \mu_t \quad (1)$$

Where:

$d_1 = 1$, for the first period

0, otherwise

$d_2 = 1$, for the first period

0, otherwise

$d_3 = 1$, for the first period

0, otherwise.

The discontinuity is eliminated by a linear restriction at the two breakpoints k_1 and k_2 such that;

$$a_1 + b_1k_1 = a_2 + b_2k_1 \text{ and } a_2 + b_2k_2 = a_3 + b_3k_2.$$

$$\text{i.e., } a_2 = a_1 + (b_1 - b_2)k_1 \text{ and } a_3 = a_1 + (b_1 - b_2)k_1 + (b_2 - b_3)k_2 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Also } d_1 + d_2 + d_3 = 1$$

Hence, substituting equation (2) into equation (1) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Log}Y = & a_1 + b_1(d_1t + d_2k_1 + d_3k_1) + b_2(d_2t - d_2k_1 - d_3k_1 + d_3k_2) + \\ & + b_3(d_3t - d_3k_2) \end{aligned}$$

Here, b_1 , b_2 and b_3 are the growth rates of the first period (1990 to 1999), the second period (2000 to 2009) and the third period (2010 to 2020) with the kinks at the points k_1 and k_2 respectively. This method has two advantages over the discontinuous methods. Firstly, the sub-period growth rates which are consistent with the overall period, the growth rate can be estimated and secondly, the sample size and the degrees of freedom can be increased as a result of combining the sub-periods.

1.2. Formulation of regression model

The model follows the theoretical formulation of an extended version of Viner (1950). Seven dummy variables (d_{ij}) are introduced to examine the impact of the top 15 countries on world trade, which is one of the salient features of deglobalization as described in

Stanojevic (2020). Moreover, this approach differs from Viner's (1950) approach to empirical analysis. The details of the variables, measurement, and list of countries are described in Tables 1 and 2. The nonlinear equation appears to be:

$$\ln y_{ij} = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln x_1 + \beta_2 \ln x_2 + \beta_3 \ln x_3 \dots \dots \beta_n \ln x_n + \varepsilon_{ijt} \quad (3)$$

Where: Y_{ij} is the dependent variable, α is an intercept, β_i 's ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) are the regression coefficients, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are independent or explanatory variables, and e_{ijt} is the model's error term or residuals.

As mentioned above, a consistent and significant decline in the share of countries in the exports and imports of the world economy is a symptom of a tendency toward deglobalization of the world economy. We believe that the declining growth of world trade, increasing trade barriers, conflicts between nation-states, and the formation of trade blocs - which may be based on race, religion, or ancestry - are the main causes of today's deglobalization. Based on the size of the economies (gross domestic product) of the top 15 countries, the model variables are measured as exports plus imports (total trade) into the global economy. More specifically, one can assume that the larger an economy's share of world trade is (measured by gross domestic product), the larger it will be, and that this will have a significant positive effect on total trade for world trade. Similarly, we might predict that trade blocs will have a significant positive effect on total trade. On the other hand, we can infer that trade disputes, nation-state conflicts, and religious conflicts may impede international trade, signalling a trend away from globalization. Therefore, we cannot predict whether the impact of each variable on these countries will be positive or negative. Moreover, no matter how open tiny economies may be, we cannot assume that these global phenomena will have statistically significant effects on them.

The model takes the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln y_{ijt} = & \alpha + \beta_1 \text{gdp_con}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{pcgdp_con}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{world_gdp}_{jt} + \beta_4 \text{pop_con}_{it} \\ & + \beta_5 \text{landlock}_{it} + \beta_6 \text{religion}_{it} + \beta_7 \text{war}_{it} + \beta_8 \text{APEC}_{it} + \beta_9 \text{ASEAN}_{it} \\ & + \beta_{10} \text{OECD}_{it} + \beta_{11} \text{BRICS}_{it} + \beta_{12} 1^{\text{st}}_{\text{sub-period}_{it}} + \beta_{13} 2^{\text{nd}}_{\text{sub-period}_{it}} \\ & + \beta_{14} 3^{\text{rd}}_{\text{sub-period}_{it}} + \varepsilon_{ijt} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Where y_{ijt} is the volume of trade (exports plus imports) between countries (i) and the world economy (j) at time (t), $(\text{GDP})_{(i)(j)}$ represents the positive relationship with trade reflecting an economy's productive capacity and a higher volume of trade with the world economy, followed by other independent variables as also described in Table 1, see also (Mishra et al., 2015). The variables highlighted as subperiods indicate the decadal growth rates and represent the intensity of countries' trade volume with the global world. The variables considered as one of the main indicators of trade flows were neglected in the panel data analysis due to the high multicollinearity problem, i.e., world population, world GDP per capita, and WTO. Three different models are estimated: the pooled OLS model, the fixed effect model, and the random effect model from equation 4 (see above) using STATA.

Table 3. Results of Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg Test for Heteroskedasticity

Ho	Constant variance
chi2(1)	1.31
Prob > chi2	0.2532

Source: Author.

Before running these models, equation 4 was tested for heteroskedasticity. For this purpose, the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity is estimated over time. The null hypothesis for the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test is that the model is free of heteroskedasticity and the variances are constant over the period. The alternative hypothesis is that the model is affected by heteroskedasticity and is not suitable for further analysis. The results of the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 shows that the series is free of heteroskedasticity and is suitable for further analysis because the probability value was found to be not significant at a 5 per cent level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis could not be rejected at a 5 per cent confidence level.

2. Analysis and empirical results

Table 4 shows the descriptive statistics of the panel data from 1990 to 2020. The average trade flow of the countries (exports plus imports) to the global world is 751252.06 million dollars and varies between a minimum value of 34306.81 and a maximum value of 4094855.28 million dollars during the period from 1990 to 2020. The average GDP per capita of the 15 countries and the world is almost the same, 9.65 and 9.06, but varies in terms of minimum and maximum values during the period. The average GDP of the top 15 countries is 28.24 which is only slightly lower than the world GDP by 3.41 during the same period. This is also one of the reasons for choosing the top 15 economies as the sample size in terms of the size of their economies (GDP) for this study during the period from 1990 to 2020. Similarly, the average of the country's population and the world population is just below 4.03 during the period from 1990 to 2020.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Trade	465	34306.81	4094855.28	751252.06	731839.81
lnTrade	465	10.44	15.23	13.10	0.98
lnCountries PCGDP	465	6.27	11.01	9.65	1.24
lnWorld PCGDP	465	8.82	9.31	9.06	0.16
lnCountries GDP	465	26.32	30.62	28.24	0.87
lnWorld GDP	465	31.21	32.07	31.65	0.27
lnCountries Population	465	16.65	21.07	18.56	1.17
lnWorld Population	465	22.39	22.77	22.59	0.11

Source: Author.

In addition, to understand the basic relationship, the bivariate correlation of coefficient was calculated among the variables. The results of the correlation coefficient are shown in Table 5, where we can see that the per capita GDP of the countries and the world, the GDP of the countries and the world and the world population have a positive relationship with the trade flow of the countries to the global world (exports plus imports) and the natural logarithm

of the trade flow of the countries to the world (lnTrade) has shown an insignificant association with the population of the countries. Similarly, an insignificant relationship was found between world GDP per capita and country population (lnCPOP). Nevertheless, world GDP, GDP per capita, and world population are closely related. For this reason, world population (lnWPOP) and world GDP per capita (lnWPGDP) were excluded from the analysis due to high collinearity, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Correlations

Variables	lnTrade	lnCPGDP	lnWPGDP	lnCGDP	lnWGDP	lnCPOP	lnWPOP
lnTrade	1						
lnCPGDP	0.626	1					
lnWPGDP	0.582	0.183	1				
lnCGDP	0.774	0.433	0.302	1			
lnWGDP	0.581	0.183	0.999	0.303	1		
lnCPOP	-0.075	-0.739	0.055	0.287	0.055	1	
lnWPOP	0.576	0.183	0.993	0.302	0.998	0.056	1

Source: Author.

Table 6 shows the empirical results of the model for equation 4. The results are divided into (1) pooled OLS, (2) fixed-effect model, and (3) random-effect model. The first model describes the expected signs of GDP of the top 15 countries and the world-on-world trade over the period. However, the effects of a country's GDP per capita and population have shown negative signs on trade flows between countries and the global world. Also, it does not matter whether the country is landlocked or has a different religion for international relations and has shown a positive impact on trade flow from selected major economies to the global world. Nevertheless, wars between countries and trade blocs have a negative impact on global trade, except the OECD, which had a positive impact on global trade during this period. In addition, the pooled OLS model shows that as the size of the economy increases, the flow of trade from countries to the global world has also increased.

Table 6. Results on regression models

Variables	Pooled OLS		Fixed Effect Model		Random Effect Model	
	Coef.	P>t	Coef.	P>t	Coef.	P>t
lnCountries PCGDP	-31.989	0.000	-23.473	0.000	-19.855	0.001
lnCountries GDP	32.434	0.000	23.913	0.000	20.324	0.000
lnWorld GDP	3.493	0.000	3.233	0.000	3.361	0.000
lnCountries Population	-31.732	0.000	-22.161	0.000	-19.211	0.001
Landlock	0.577	0.000	0.000		0.825	0.014
Religion	0.373	0.003	0.000		1.175	0.004
War	-0.135	0.003	-0.089	0.007	-0.105	0.001
APEC	-0.200	0.000	0.000		-0.398	0.012
ASEAN	-0.452	0.000	0.000		-0.574	0.229
OECD	0.296	0.000	0.000		-0.345	0.039
BRICS	-1.245	0.000	0.000		-2.269	0.000
1 st Sub-Period	-4.9	0.000	-5.4	0.000	-5.3	0.000
2 nd Sub-Period	-1.5	0.016	-1.5	0.000	-1.5	0.000
3 rd Sub-Period	-9.0	0.000	-8.9	0.000	-8.8	0.000
_cons	-114.026	0.000	-125.164	0.000	-117.588	0.000
Number of obs	465	465	465	465	465	465
F_STAT	351.130		552.130		4346.240	
Prob > F	0.000		0.000		0.000	
R-squared	0.918		0.911		0.909	

Source: Author.

However, the results of the pooled OLS model are not relatively reliable because the series is affected by collinearity. So, before going through the fixed effect and random effect models, it is very useful and important to determine the estimation model between FEM and REM. For this purpose, the Hausman test was estimated and the results are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Hausman test (fixed vs random)

Variables	Fixed	Random	Difference
lnCountries PGDP	-23.47289	-19.85525	-3.617632
lnCountries GDP	23.91315	20.32395	3.5892
lnWorld GDP	3.233359	3.360995	-.1276354
lnCountries POP.	-22.16105	-19.21064	-2.950404
War	-.0888724	-.1053381	.0164658
1 st Sub-Period	-.0536475	-.0527069	-.0009405
2 nd Sub-Period	-.0149318	-.0149625	.0000308
3 rd Sub-Period	-.0892341	-.0884546	-.0007795
Chi-Sq. Statistics	15.35		
Prob>chi2	0.0527		

Source: Author.

The null hypothesis of the Hausman test is that both FEM and REM give similar results, whereas the alternative hypothesis is that FEM is more appropriate. The results of the Hausman test show that we cannot reject the null hypothesis because the probability value of the Hausman test is greater than a significance level of 5 per cent. Moreover, the results of FEM described in Table 6 are strongly affected by multicollinearity. So, based on the above results, we can consider the random effects model as more appropriate. The obtained results can be considered statistically reliable and valid according to all criteria. The coefficient of determination (R^2) is very high in all countries, 0.909, and the F-statistic is also significantly high in the random-effects model, 4346.240.

Thus, the results of the random effects model portrayed in Table 6, shows that the GDP of the top 15 countries and the world GDP have a significant impact on trade flows to the global world. Obviously, during the period from 1990 to 2020, the size of the economy plays a significant role in world trade, which indicates that the integration of countries into the global world has led to globalization. In contrast, trade flow decreases when countries' per capita GDP and population have increased. This shows that the size of economies and the world only matters for trade, while it has had a negative effect on countries' GDP per capita and population. On the one hand, the trade flow of countries into the global world leads to strong integration of economies, which we can call growing globalization in the world. On the other hand, globalization also leads to more inequalities and inequities between countries and has widened the gap between rich and poor (Postrel, 2002).

In addition, landlocked countries and religions do not seem to be obstacles to the flow of trade from countries to the global world that can hinder global trade; rather, they have had a positive effect on global trade over time. Nevertheless, wars between countries, which occurred frequently in the third period after the 1990s, have greatly affected the flow of trade of countries to the global world and led to deglobalization, whether they are economic, trade or political wars (see List of wars between 1990 and 2022). Trade blocs

have aided the process of globalization, i.e., the increasing interconnectedness of the world as a result of increased trade with factors such as economic, social, political, and cultural, as they have helped countries to remove economic barriers, allowing for more trade and the free movement of capital and labour (Campa et al., 1996). In contrast, the selected trade blocs have had a negative impact on countries flow of trade to the global world, showing that trade over the period flows only within the member countries of the trade blocs. Among them, APEC and OECD are the most significant trade blocs, consisting of 21 and 38 countries, respectively, most of which are among the top 15 countries in terms of the size of the economy (GDP). Similarly, out of the 5 countries, 4 important member countries of BRICS are among the most important countries selected in this study. However, ASEAN consisted of 11 countries has shown an insignificant impact on the global trade except all the major trade blocs. It may be that among the 15 major countries selected for this study, only one country is the member of ASEAN bloc i.e., Indonesia. Based on the above results, the study shows that both a war between countries and trade blocs have influenced deglobalization at the global level.

The results of the decadal growth rates, divided into three subperiods and estimated with the kinked exponential model (see Table 6), shows that the trade flows of the major economies to the global world declined by 5.3 per cent in the first sub-period from 1990 to 1991. In the second sub-period, it declined slightly by 1.5 per cent. However, in the third sub-period from 2010 to 2020, the growth rate of trade flows of selected countries to the global world declined rapidly by 8.8 per cent. Moreover, the third sub-period (2010-2020) was the most conflict-ridden decade; (see the list of wars between 1990 and 2022). In addition, regionalization - a process in which nations cooperate and conduct all their trade within a single trading bloc-could replace globalization as the preferred economic strategy. Regionalization reinforces interdependence at the local level rather than on a global scale. Moreover, trade disputes or wars have negatively impacted countries' ability to trade with each other, which has greatly slowed globalization and led to the process by which rich countries get richer and poor ones to get poorer.

3. Conclusion and discussions

The article is devoted to the study of deglobalization processes in contemporary international economic relations in the context of the paradigm of globalism. The main drivers of deglobalization are defined as follows: the slowdown of trade growth and the decline of world trade; the application of trade restrictions that provoke trade wars or wars between countries and groups of countries; the creation of trade or economic blocs; religion, etc. However, the results reflect that there is no doubt that as the size of an economy increases, so does trade. Nevertheless, inequalities and income disparities among the selected countries have increased during the study period. Countries' GDP per capita and population has had a negative impact on world trade. In addition, the wars between countries, especially from 2010 to 2020, have negatively affected the trade flow of countries to the global world and have led the paradigm of deglobalization. More

importantly, the trade blocs (especially OECD, APEC, and BRICS) have abridged the flow of trade to the global world, reflecting regionalization, which is a process in which countries work among themselves rather than at the global level. This regionalization has not ceased but has increased rapidly, especially in the third decade of the twentieth century, during which the growth rate of trade flows among major countries has declined rapidly by 8.8 per cent.

The international agreements that have guided the world economy for many years are increasingly giving way to bilateral interactions between economic nations. Some factors contributing to deglobalization processes originate in economic laws, but there is one factor that unites all the segments studied and is probably a key factor: the political will of the major players, as evidenced by the expansion of the scope and number of restrictions. Globalization will be severely damaged by the formation of trade blocs and a worldwide decline in international trade. As a result of globalization, some countries benefit while others are left behind and experience growing inequality. According to Hans Rosling, globalization is often blamed for the rise of "the West and the rest" (Rosling et al., 2018). While the poor benefit from neoliberalism, the richest are getting richer and the wealth gap is not getting smaller. Taking a broader view, we find that while China and India are reducing poverty rates, other emerging economies are still lagging behind and are not treated equally in the process of global economic integration. As a result, Joseph Stiglitz's assertion that regional integration has suffered disproportionately from globalization seems to hold true. The analysis of the impact of globalization on inequality and poverty in developing countries falls short. The problem with globalization is not the term itself, but the way it is managed and implemented is highly problematic (Stiglitz, 2017).

References

- Abdal, A. and Ferreira, D.M., 2021. Deglobalization, globalization, and the pandemic current impasses of the capitalist world-economy. *Journal of World-Systems Research*, 27(1), pp. 202-230. <<https://doi.org/10.5195/jwsr.2021.1028>>
- An, J., Mikhaylov, A. and Richter, U.H., 2020. Trade war effects: evidence from sectors of energy and resources in Africa. *Heliyon*, 6(12). <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05693>>
- Boyce, J.K., 1986. Kinked Exponential Models for Growth Rate Estimation. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, pp. 385-396.
- Brada, J.C. and Mendez, J.A., 1983. Regional economic integration and the volume of intraregional trade: A comparison of developed and developing country experience. *Kyklos*, 36(4), pp. 589-603.
- Campa, J.M., Sorenson, T.L. and Campa, J.M., 1996. Are Trade Blocs Conducive to Free Trade? *The Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 98(2), p. 263. <<https://doi.org/10.2307/3440858>>
- Hillebrand, E.E., 2010. Deglobalization Scenarios: Who Wins? Who Loses? Deglobalization Scenarios: Who Wins? Who Loses?. *Global Economy Journal*, 10(2), pp. 1-19.

- Huang, W., Shuai, B. and Antwi, E., 2019. A two-stage optimization approach for subscription bus services network design: the China case. *Public Transport*, 11 (3), pp. 589-616.
- Kim, H.-M., Li, P. and Lee, Y.R., 2020. Observations of deglobalization against globalization and impacts on global business. *International Trade, Politics and Development*, 4(2), pp. 83-103. <<https://doi.org/10.1108/itpd-05-2020-0067>>
- Michalak, W. and Gibb, R., 2010. Trading Blocs and Multilateralism in the World Economy. *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, 87(2), pp. 264-279. <<https://doi.org/10.1111/0004-5608.872053>>
- Mishra, A.K., Gadhia, J.N., Kubendran, N. and Sahoo, M., 2015. Trade Flows between India and Other BRICS Countries: An Empirical Analysis Using Gravity Model. *Global Business Review*, 16(1), pp. 107-122. <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150914553523>>
- Misra, R. and Choudhry, S., 2020. Trade War: Likely Impact on India. *Foreign Trade Review*, 55(1), pp. 93-118. <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0015732519886793>>
- Postrel, V., 2002. Economic Scene; The rich get rich and poor get poorer. Right? Let's take another look. *The New York Times*. <<https://www.nytimes.com/2002/08/15/business/economic-scene-rich-get-rich-poor-get-poorer-right-let-s-take-another-look.html>>
- Reznikova, N. and Ivashchenko, O., 2018. Projections of Deglobalization in The Contemporary International Economic Relations in The Context of The Paradigm of Globalism. *Світове Господарство Та економіка Зарубіжних Країн*, ВІП (15), pp. 98-106.
- Roach S.S., 2022. Deglobalization's China Wild Card. *Project Syndicate*. <<https://www.project-syndicate.org/commentary/china-hit-hard-by-slowing-world-trade-by-stephen-s-roach-2022-07>>
- Rosling, H., Rosling, O. and Rosling Rönnlund, A., 2018. *Factfulness*. London: Sceptre.
- Sanso, M., Rogelio, C. Sanz, F., 1993. Bilateral trade flows, the gravity equation, and functional form. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 75(2), pp. 266-275.
- Stanojević, N., 2020. Deglobalization of the World Economy and its Effects on the Western Balkan Countries. *Economic Themes*, 58(3), pp. 343-362. <<https://doi.org/10.2478/ethemes-2020-0020>>
- Stiglitz, J., 2017. *Globalization and its discontents*. W.W. Norton, New York and London. pp. 1-304. <<https://www.anderson.ucla.edu/faculty/sebastian.edwards/Stiglitz.pdf>>
- Summary, R.M., 1989. A political-economic model of U.S. bilateral trade. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 71(1), pp. 179-182.
- Trošić, S.J., 2015. Economic globalization-advantages and disadvantages: the place of Serbia and Japan in the globalized World. <[http://globalthinking20.jimdo.com/food-for->](http://globalthinking20.jimdo.com/food-for-)
- Viner, J., 1950. *The Customs Union Issue*. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, New York.
- Weihua, C., 2022. Deglobalization and decoupling risk causing more global damage. Retrieved from China Daily: <<http://www.chinadaily.com.cn/a/202207/15/WS62d0a5b2a310fd2b29e6c6d8.html>>
- Yinan, Y., 2021. Sino-US trade war under deglobalization. *International Journal of Social Sciences in Universities*, 4(2), pp. 50-53.
- List of wars: 2003 – present. (2022, November 13). In Wikipedia. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_wars:_2003%E2%80%93present>
- The Advantages and Disadvantages of trade blocs. (n.d.). Retrieved November 19, 2022, from <<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/9cf98320c8ca48fa841b969ddc496b97>>

Financial difficulties and economic recession: Evidence from Canadian seniors

Samir AMINE

Université du Québec en Outaouais, Canada
samir.amine@uqo.ca

Wilner PREDELUS

Université du Québec en Outaouais, Canada
wilner.predelus@uqo.ca

Abstract. *Pressured by financial difficulties and the relatively low income from participating in the labour market, many seniors become insolvent. In this article, we analyze the financial situation facing Canadian seniors who have accessed the insolvency system due to a deterioration in their socio-economic and financial conditions, particularly since the 2008 economic crisis. Using federal statistical data, we observed that seniors who used the insolvency system during the recession period were more indebted than those who accessed it before, and less indebted than those who accessed it after the recession.*

Keywords: seniors, income, asset, debt, recession.

JEL Classification: C32, G33, G51.

1. Introduction

The empirical and theoretical literature has extensively studied the effects of the economic crisis on the various socio-professional categories especially young and the less skilled (Agarwal et al., 2003; Garrett and Wall, 2014; Livshits et al., 2010; OECD, 2016; Mian et al., 2017; Piketty, 2019; Rampini, 2005). Nevertheless, the impact of an economic recession on the financial situation of the seniors has been little discussed in the literature (Amine and Predelus, 2020).

Indeed, western countries have embarked on a process of reforms to absorb the budget deficit and reduce the accumulation of public debt (OECD, 2013). Pension reforms, which are part thereof, have been readjusted without taking into account the financial consequences of the aging workforce as observed in most developed countries.

In this context, faced with financial difficulties and barriers to higher returns from their professional engagement, many seniors find themselves unable to meet their obligations with respect to mortgage and living expenses. As such, they turn towards the insolvency system in search of relief from their debt load. The Canadian insolvency system provides two solutions: outright bankruptcy or proposal, with the latter allowing insolvent debtors to keep most of their asset while paying only a portion of their debts. Filing for bankruptcy, on the other hand, requires insolvent debtors to hand over the portion of their asset that is not exempt by law to a Licensed Insolvency Trustee (LIT), who will in turn liquidate the assets and distribute the proceeds among eligible creditors. In the Canadian insolvency system, the decision to file either for bankruptcy or proposal rests solely with the insolvent debtor, though failure to file a proposal where it can be established they were financially capable of doing so, is ground for opposition of their discharge in bankruptcy under Canada's Bankruptcy and Insolvency Act (BIA) (Predelus and Amine, 2022). However, the maximum debt allowed in a consumer proposal is \$ 250,000 – minus the outstanding debt on principal residence. While first time bankrupts can be eligible for an automatic discharge after nine months in the absence of surplus income, and twenty-one months where surplus income is required, the terms of a proposal cannot go beyond sixty months.

In this article, we determine and analyze the factors characterizing Canadian seniors who accessed the insolvency system around the period of the 2008-2009 recession to assess impact of the crisis on their financial situation. Using federal data on insolvencies filed in Canada, we observed that seniors who used the insolvency system during the recession period were more indebted than those who accessed it before, and less indebted than those who accessed it after the recession. When we look at their income, we further observed that those who live in high and middle-income neighbourhoods or with higher income tend to carry more debt.

The rest of the article is organized as follows. We explain the data used before presenting the main results of our empirical analysis. Finally, the paper is concluded in section 4.

2. Data

The data used in this article was collected from two different sources. The data on the population comes from Statistics Canada, whereas the insolvency data is produced by the Office of the Superintendent of Bankruptcy (OSB). The OSB is the federal agency responsible for supervising the administration of insolvency files in Canada. It processes insolvency filings and collects socioeconomic data (age, gender, marital status, employment status, etc.), financial data (asset, liability, income, expenses, etc.) and geographic data (province, city, postal code, etc.) from insolvent debtors who access the insolvency system.

The part of the data that covers insolvency volumes, assets and liabilities comprises all consumer debtors who accessed the insolvency system between 2003 and 2017. Data on the income of seniors is taken from a sample of 4,510 insolvencies filed by Canadians aged 65 or over. This data is extracted from a sample of 58,948 insolvencies filed between 2007 and 2011 by individuals of all age groups. All the monetary variables have been adjusted for inflation based on 2003 dollars.

The primary objective of the Canadian insolvency system is to offer a fresh start to honest but unfortunate debtors. However, it is virtually impossible for seniors to take advantage of the “second chance” following an insolvency filing given their old age. It follows that the situation is even grimmer for seniors who are obliged to choose bankruptcy over proposal because.

In fact, while a proposal enables them to keep most of their asset while paying back only a percentage of their debt, filing for bankruptcy requires that they turn over the share of their asset that is not exempt to the Licensed Insolvency Trustee (LIT).

Figure 1. Share of seniors in the population and in insolvency files (2003-2017)

Source: Statistics Canada and the Office of the Superintendent of Bankruptcy.

Over the last 15 years, while the share of insolvencies filed by seniors in Canada has increased at a relatively identical pace as their share in the total population aged of 18 years old and over (Figure 1), the share of proposals in insolvencies filed by seniors has decreased relative to that of the population average (Figure 2).

In 2003, no less than 11.3% of insolvencies filed by seniors in Canada were proposals, compared to 16.5% for the total population aged of 18 years old and over. However, by 2017, the proportion of proposals filed seniors who sat at 35.2% while that of the total population was 52.6%. The gap then grew from 5.2 percentage points to 17.4 percentage points. This thus indicates that Canadian seniors are proportionally less likely to file for proposals than the general population, which in turn means that they are in fact more likely to file for bankruptcy, turning over almost all their asset to the LIT. Of note, the deterioration of the senior's financial well-being does not seem to be related to the performance of the financial market, which was enjoying an all-time high during the same period.

Given that proposals, in general, require that a debtor have sufficient income to pay periodic payments as a result of the agreement with the creditors, the lower percentage of seniors who choose to file for proposals instead of bankruptcy indicates that they face a more dire financial situation than the average debtor. Therefore, if we assume that the behaviour of seniors is not different from the rest of the population, we may conclude that the purchasing power of senior is weaker than the population average.

Figure 2. Share of proposals filed by seniors and the general population (2003-2017)

Source: Statistics Canada and the Office of the Superintendent of Bankruptcy.

2.1. The asset of insolvent seniors

Although the asset declared by insolvent seniors increased faster than their debt up until 2015, they have been in a worse financial shape than the general insolvent population in Canada for over 10 years. Moreover, relatively to their asset, seniors are in general more indebted than the rest of the Canadian population who accessed the insolvency system over the period in question. Despite a deceleration observed in the asset-debt ratio starting in 2016, the financial situation of the both the seniors and the general population has worsened over the recent years, a trend which is even more pronounced for seniors when compared to the rest of the population (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Evolution of the asset-debt ratio of insolvent seniors in Canada (2003-2017)

Source: Office of the Superintendent of Bankruptcy.

Figure 3 shows that the drop in the asset-debt ratio (Figure 3) seems to be the result of a decrease in the average asset declared by insolvent seniors over the last two years. In addition, both the average debt level and asset were at a peak for insolvent seniors around 2009 at the height of the last economic crisis in Canada. This suggests that the economic crisis was so severe that relatively wealthy people, who had previously managed to remain solvent due to their assets, ended up being insolvent during this period. Not surprisingly, the volume of insolvencies filed by seniors remained high until 2013, as shown in Figure 4, as many only accessed the insolvency system as the last resort following a prolonged period of financial distress.

Figure 4. Evolution of debt and asset of insolvent seniors in Canada (2003-2017)

Source: Office of the Superintendent of Bankruptcy.

2.2. The income of insolvent seniors

An analysis of the income and expenses declared by seniors who accessed the insolvency system from 2007 to 2011 reveals that between 32% and 38% of them live with a net income grossly insufficient to cover their expenses excluding debt and interest repayment. While between 42% and 54% of these debtors declared an income that was just enough to cover their living expenses, only 14% to 21% were able to cover their living expenses and continue to service, at least partly, their debts. In fact, between the years 2007 and 2008, the average income of insolvent seniors remained stable at \$23,389 before rising by 11% in 2009 to \$25,760 (see Figure 5).

This sudden and relatively significant increase in the income declared by insolvent seniors can be understood as a direct consequence of the 2008-2009 recession, which, inevitably, led the relatively wealthier seniors down the path of insolvency (Amine and Predelus, 2019). This cohort of insolvent seniors actually reported a higher income than their counterparts who filed for insolvency before the recession. If the relative decrease in the average income of insolvent seniors observed in 2010 may explain a slow return to the pre-recession trend, the increase registered in 2011 sends an alarming signal about the state of financial well-being of seniors in Canada: the successive cohorts of senior citizen debtors report a rising level of income. It therefore follows that not only have the financial woes worsened among seniors, but they have also spread to a much wider range of income groups.

Figure 5. Evolution of average income and expenses of insolvent seniors in Canada (2007-2011)

Source: Office of the Superintendent of Bankruptcy.

In light of these facts, we look at the sources of income declared by insolvent seniors who accessed the insolvency system. Between 2007 and 2011 the share of insolvent seniors who declared an income from labour market activities fluctuated between 11.5% and 14.8%. These numbers indicate a deterioration in the financial well-being of seniors who, in some instances, had to return to the labour market to earn an income in a bid to avoid insolvency.

On the other hand, when we look at the reasons for financial difficulties mentioned by insolvent seniors, there is no doubt that, due to the liberalization of credit, even seniors with sufficient income remain financially vulnerable if they are not financially literate. In fact, among the most common reasons for financial difficulties declared by senior citizen debtors between 2007 and 2011, “financial mismanagement” is cited by no less than 72% of them, which is followed by “loss of income” (25%) and “medical reasons” (22%). While insufficient income alone could lead inevitably to insolvency, when it is coupled with financial mismanagement, it would be a financial disaster. This may explain why individuals who are supposed to be retired indicate “loss of income” as main reason for financial difficulties in no less than 25% of the cases.

3. Empirical analysis

Now that we have observed the trends in seniors’ asset and income before, during and after the great recession, we are going to determine the factors associated with their indebtedness. To do so, we use the Ordinary Least Square method to estimate the following model:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik} + \varepsilon$$

where:

Y : represents the total debt reported by seniors at filing;

$x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_k$: represent the explanatory variables, such as: region of residence, income, expenses, homeownership, gender, marital status, age, official language, etc.;

i : the individuals.

Given there is no established theory on the factors associated with indebtedness, we decide to use the income and expenses, the reasons for financial difficulties, the sources of income declared by seniors in their statement of affairs and their statement of income and expense. We also look whether situations like homeownership or business ownership can explain indebtedness among Canadian seniors. The results of the model are provided in the annex section.

After controlling for their neighbourhood of residence, their gender, their marital status and their reasons for insolvency, we observe that seniors' indebtedness has been on the rise since the last recession. In fact, compared to the recession period, seniors who filed for insolvency were less indebted before and more indebted after the recession period. For instance, while those who filed for insolvency had on average 13.9% less debt before the recession than during the recession, post-recession filers had 3.2% more debt than those who filed during the recession. The rise in seniors' indebtedness is consistent with the trends observed in overall consumer's debt in Canada over the last decade.

On the geographical side, the results show that insolvent seniors in the region of Quebec had on average higher debt than seniors in any other part of the country. For instance, while those in the Atlantic region had on average 32.1% less debt than those in the Quebec region, those in the Western region had 22.5% and those in Ontario 12.4% less indebted. These results unveil a rather troubling picture for seniors in the Quebec region where general statistics oftentimes show Quebecers carrying less debt than other Canadians.

When we look at the presence of immigrant in insolvent seniors' neighbourhood, we further observe that the more immigrants in the neighbourhood, the lower the level of debt reported in seniors' insolvency files. For example, while seniors from the lowest tercile of foreign-born population had on average 8.3% less debt than those from the middle tercile, those from the highest tercile had 9% more debt than the latter. When read in light of the findings of Picot and Lu (2017) regarding the rampant poverty observed among immigrant seniors in Canada, these results exhibit a positive correlation between indebtedness and asset, which is very intuitive. In fact, the findings reveal that seniors who declared a house in their insolvency files had 114.4% more debt than those with no house. As for those who operated a business within the five years leading up to the insolvency, they had 51.1% more debt.

Likewise, while seniors from the lowest income quintile neighbourhood carry 17.2% less debt than those living in the middle-income quintile neighbourhood, those living in the highest income quintile neighbourhood had 20.4% more debt. Furthermore, it is observed

that the higher the senior's family income the more indebted they are, which reinforce the results for the correlation between asset and indebtedness. For instance, a 10% increase in senior's family annual income is associated with 4.4% in total debt. In fact, this shows that not only seniors with higher income have a greater access to credit, but they are more inclined to accumulate more debt.

On the expense side, seniors' indebtedness is significantly driven up by car lease payments, condominium fees and dental care expenses. In fact, although these expenses' marginal effects are not very high and none of them is essential to seniors' survival, they are nonetheless necessary to maintain a certain quality of life. Therefore, it can be said that insolvent seniors who turn to the insolvency system for solution to their debt are in big financial trouble.

4. Final remarks

In a mass consumption society where the liberalization of credit is the norm, the notion of insolvency is surely not a paltry matter that only applies to reckless and inveterate consumers. When financially vulnerable senior citizens, who are unlikely to have a true "*fresh start*" after declaring for insolvency, due to their age, the plight of these senior citizens should be a policy concern. In fact, seniors who are chronically short of adequate income would not be able to get long-term financial relief by declaring insolvency. In this paper, we showed that the number of insolvencies filed by seniors grew proportionally to their share in the total population as the society ages. Therefore, this may eventually lead to pressures on public health expenditures. Consequently, a proactive approach to senior indebtedness would be required: we should consider increasing the retirement benefits for seniors instead of paying into the health system, which would have to deal with seniors' physical and psychological problems due to indebtedness.

References

- Agarwal, S. and Liu, C.J., 2003. Determinants of credit card delinquency and bankruptcy: Macroeconomics factors, *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 27, pp. 75-84.
- Amine, S. and Predelus, W., 2019. The persistence of the 2008-2009 Recession on Personal Insolvency Filings in Canada, *Economics Bulletin*, 39, pp. 84-93.
- Amine, S. and Predelus, W., 2020. How employment insurance recipients make decision about insolvency?, *Research in Economics*, 74, pp. 344-348.
- Garrett, T.A. and Wall, H.J., 2014. Personal-Bankruptcy Cycles, *Macroeconomic Dynamics*, 18(7), pp. 1488-1507.
- Livshits, I., MacGee, J. and Tertilt, M., 2010. Accounting for the Rise in Consumer Bankruptcies, *American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics*, 2(2), pp. 165-193.

- Mian, A., Sufi, A. and Verner, E., 2017. Household Debt and Business Cycles Worldwide, *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 132(4), pp. 1755-1817.
- Picot, G. and Lu, Y., 2017. *Chronic Low Income among Immigrants in Canada and its Communities*, Analytical Studies Branch Research Paper Series, Statistics Canada.
- Piketty, T., 2019. *Capital and Ideology*, Seuil.
- Predelus, W. and Amine, S., 2022. The insolvency choice during an economic crisis: the case of Canada, *Quantitative Finance and Economics*, 6(4), pp. 659-668.
- Rampini, A.A., 2005. Default and Aggregate Income, *Journal of Economic Theory*, 122(2), pp. 225-253.
- OECD, 2013. *Panorama des pensions 2013: Les indicateurs de l'OCDE et du G20*, OECD Press.
- OECD, 2016. *Income inequality remains high in the face of weak recovery*, OECD Press.

Annex. Results of the seniors indebtedness regression model

Residuals:				
Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.8455	-0.4382	0.0019	0.4170	5.7073
Coefficients:				
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	9.583763	0.763838	12.547	< 2e-16***
Pre Recession	-0.13872	0.028661	-4.84	1.35e-06***
Post Recession	0.032076	0.026367	1.217	0.223856
Region – Atlantic	-0.32059	0.066928	-4.79	1.73e-06***
Region – Ontario	-0.12376	0.058912	-2.101	0.035724*
Region – West	-0.22473	0.061791	-3.637	0.000279***
Gender (Male)	0.15324	0.025341	6.047	1.61e-09***
Age at Filing (ln)	-0.84944	0.16566	-5.128	3.07e-07***
Debtor Language (French)	0.31015	0.058306	5.319	1.10e-07***
Marital Status (with a partner)	0.052623	0.028195	1.866	0.062060.
Place of Residence (Urban)	0.031161	0.028664	1.087	0.27704
Mono-parental (Yes)	-0.0515	0.240554	-0.214	0.830504
Family Annual Income (ln)	0.440521	0.034838	12.645	< 2e-16***
Business Ownership (Yes)	0.51084	0.042021	12.157	< 2e-16***
Previous Bankruptcy (Yes)	-0.1184	0.082827	-1.43	0.152932
Previous Insolvency (Yes)	-0.09391	0.081147	-1.157	0.247244
Home Ownership (Yes)	1.144118	0.036661	31.208	< 2e-16***
Immigrant (Foreign-Born) Tercile				
Lowest Tercile	-0.08253	0.032573	-2.534	0.011330*
Highest Tercile	0.089529	0.045966	1.948	0.051518.
Neighborhood Income Quintile (National)				
Lowest Quintile	-0.17238	0.03393	-5.08	3.94e-07***
Medium-Low Quintile	-0.03064	0.035347	-0.867	0.386091
Medium-High Quintile	0.05699	0.040801	1.397	0.162557
Highest Quintile	0.203575	0.044141	4.612	4.11e-06***
Expenses				
RENT/MORTGAGE (ln)	-0.0026	0.006226	-0.417	0.67688
PROPERTY/CONDO Fees (ln)	0.019698	0.008553	2.303	0.021323*
Dining, Lunches Restaurants (ln)	0.008491	0.006249	1.359	0.174304
Allowances (ln)	0.007301	0.013094	0.558	0.57715
Drug Prescriptions (ln)	-0.00978	0.006499	-1.505	0.132329
Dental (ln)	0.02269	0.010059	2.256	0.024152*
Smoking (ln)	-0.03434	0.005851	-5.87	4.72e-09***
Alcohol (ln)	0.009836	0.009396	1.047	0.295234
Entertainment/Sports (ln)	-0.00613	0.006166	-0.995	0.319979
Other Medical Expenses (ln)	0.011829	0.011187	1.057	0.290391
Food-Groceries (ln)	-0.008	0.009666	-0.828	0.407662
Laundry, Dry cleaning (ln)	-0.01069	0.007723	-1.384	0.166451
Grooming, Toiletries (ln)	0.001273	0.007409	0.172	0.863576
Clothing (ln)	-0.00147	0.006884	-0.214	0.830505
Car Lease Payments (ln)	0.034223	0.005167	6.623	3.98e-11***
Repair, Maintenance, Gas (ln)	0.006261	0.008165	0.767	0.443264
Vehicle Insurance (ln)	-0.02829	0.00946	-2.99	0.002805**
Gift, Donation (ln)	-0.00408	0.007621	-0.535	0.592902
Automobile-Value (ln)	0.022135	0.003641	6.079	1.32e-09***
Source of Income				
Employment Income (Yes)	0.012098	0.037543	0.322	0.747277
Pension/Annuities Income (Yes)	-0.04771	0.046436	-1.027	0.304332
Child Support Income (Yes)	-0.15119	0.106612	-1.418	0.156226
Spousal Support Income (Yes)	0.02924	0.134802	0.217	0.828291
Employment Insurance Income (Yes)	0.032761	0.09114	0.359	0.71927
Social Assistance Income (Yes)	-0.02027	0.108592	-0.187	0.851913

Self-employment Income (Yes)	-0.02565	0.06836	-0.375	0.707475
Reasons for Financial Difficulties				
Financial Mismanagement (Yes)	-0.06149	0.026884	-2.287	0.022224*
Loss of Income (Yes)	0.017373	0.027118	0.641	0.521796
Medical Reasons (Yes)	0.007973	0.027845	0.286	0.774627
Business Failure (Yes)	0.393736	0.054269	7.255	4.78e-13***
Gambling (Yes)	0.210557	0.06325	3.329	0.000879***
Addiction Other than Gambling (Yes)	-0.11156	0.208868	-0.534	0.593275
Relationship Breakdown (Yes)	0.087746	0.06903	1.271	0.203757
Tax Liabilities (Yes)	0.249305	0.052157	4.78	1.82e-06***
Financial Support of Others (Yes)	0.160241	0.056825	2.82	0.004827**
Student Debt (Yes)	0.272358	0.272826	0.998	0.318201
Legal Matters (Yes)	0.530079	0.112352	4.718	2.46e-06***
Moving Relocation Expenses (Yes)	-0.21653	0.116281	-1.862	0.062657.
Failed or Rejected Proposal (Yes)	0.159695	0.127546	1.252	0.210621
Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1 Residual standard error: 0.7161 on 4037 degrees of freedom Multiple R-squared: 0.5206, Adjusted R-squared: 0.5134 F-statistic: 71.88 on 61 and 4037 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16				

Inflation targeting and exchange rate pass-through in India: Lessons from international experience

Arshid Hussain PEER

Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi, India
arshideco62@gmail.com

Dr. Mirza Allim BAIG

Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi, India
mabaig@jmi.ac.in

Abstract. *This paper surveys the existing literature on the relationship between inflation targeting (IT) and exchange rate pass-through (ERPT), with a focus on drawing lessons for future IT countries and estimating ERPT in India. The study finds that the main lessons emerging from the experience of IT in reducing pass-through are (a) monetary policy should focus on future inflation, (b) coordination between monetary and fiscal policy is important, and (c) IT is not a panacea. Furthermore, ERPT varies across countries and depends on the composition of the inflation index. The paper also presents a case study of Indian using Vector autoregression model. The study finds decline in ERPT during the IT period.*

Keywords: inflation targeting, exchange rate pass-through, monetary policy, VAR.

JEL Classification: E31, E52, E58, F41, F45.

1. Introduction

Inflation is one of the economic challenges affecting every individual (Reddy, 1999). The primary policy response to the management of inflation is thought to be monetary policy. The Washington Consensus emphasised the importance of low and steady inflation for market-driven prosperity. The most important element affecting inflation, according to Bernanke and colleagues (1999), is monetary policy. As a result, central banks throughout the globe struggle to develop policies that will check inflation while fostering the growth and stability of their respective economies. Inflation targeting (IT), a recent innovation in the monetary policy framework, in which price stability is the main objective.

External shocks that affect an open economy through currency rates also have an influence on consumer inflation. Changes in the exchange rate's effect on local prices have a significant impact on domestic monetary policy. The level of pass-through demonstrates the degree of monetary policy's control over inflation. The commitment of the central bank to keep the price level at a certain target in the case of IT makes the amount of pass-through more significant.

In this context, we make an effort to examine the extant literature on IT and ERPT. This will enable us to identify the aspects of the IT framework that are contributing to the drop in pass-through. We then draw conclusions for potential adopters of IT, particularly those in emerging economies.

The remainder of the paper is divided into the following sections. The second section discusses the definition of the IT framework, the justification for IT, and a few empirical research on the macroeconomic impact of IT. The third part briefly addresses the factors that affect pass-through before surveying the literature on the link between ERPT and IT and a few chosen studies on ERPT in India. The fourth portion is divided into two subsections; the first discusses the characteristics of the IT framework that make it more efficient, and the second discusses lessons for Indian IT. The research comes to an end in this part.

2.1. Inflation targeting

Inflation targeting, in its broadest sense, is a monetary policy strategy that explicitly recognises price stability as the primary long-term aim of monetary policy, as well as the public declaration of quantitative targets for the inflation rate over a defined time period. Other aspects of the operational framework include the independence of the tools and procedures, the openness of the decision-making process, and the responsibility of the monetary authority. The fundamental components of the IT framework are policy independence, a defined inflation target, transparency, and accountability (Kamber et al., 2015; Walsh, 2015). The IT framework, according to Bernanke et al. (1999), performs two crucial tasks in an economy: first, it improves communication between policymakers and the public; and second, it provides accountability and discipline in the formulation of monetary policy. These functions minimise uncertainty, allowing economic actors to make better judgements.

New Zealand was the first country to adopt the IT framework in 1989, followed by the United Kingdom, Israel, and Canada. Throughout the last three decades, around 45 nations (details in the appendix) have embraced inflation targeting (IT). The framework was also adopted by India in February 2015, when the Government of India (GoI) and the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) signed the Monetary Policy Framework Agreement. Under this agreement, the RBI is required to keep consumer price inflation (CPI) within a band of 4 +/- 2 percent.

2.2. Rationale for inflation targeting framework

In general, macroeconomic policy pursues a variety of objectives in addition to price stability. The following arguments support the notion that price stability should take precedence over other monetary policy goals in the long run. First, the majority of economists concur that inflation is the sole long-term problem that impacts monetary policy. This unanimity among economists is the outcome of monetary economics breakthroughs during the 1960s. Long-term, there is no trade-off between inflation and unemployment; the rational expectations hypothesis and the problem of time inconsistency all contribute to the consensus. Second, price stability is vital not just for its own purpose, but also to foster long-term economic expansion, productivity, and employment. The ramifications of rising inflation are well-known. Thirdly, the IT framework serves as the nominal anchor for monetary policy activity. By making inflation the nominal anchor, the central bank can communicate with the general public more effectively. Fourthly, the efficacy of the central bank in achieving the inflation objective strengthens the credibility of monetary policy.

2.3. Macroeconomic performance under IT

On the IT framework, several empirical investigations have been done. The studies cover a wide variety of topics, including macroeconomic performance within this framework and the circumstances and causes that influence a country's decision to adopt IT. To demonstrate how effective IT has been, we bring up a few studies.

Ball and Sheridan (2003) use data on inflation, output, and interest rates to assess the effect of IT on economic performance. The research utilises data with a quarterly frequency from 20 advanced economies collected between 1960 and 2001. Seven of the twenty are inflationary and thirteen are non-inflationary (NIT). To comprehend how well the IT framework is doing, the OLS approach is applied. When regression to the mean is taken into account, the analysis reveals no performance difference between IT and NIT nations, indicating that IT is not important in this case. Nevertheless, a number of later research that came to contrary results have questioned the paper. The sample, which only covers advanced economies, and the time frame of the study are further issues with this study.

Yet, the study highlights the crucial distinction that IT is an endogenous decision. Moreover, the association between inflation targeting and strong economic success does not imply that IT improves performance. Mishkin and Schmidt-Hebbel (2005) used instrumental variables to address the endogeneity problem, and they obtained positive results.

The author contends that there were no negative repercussions with the introduction of IT. The research, which had a larger sample and a longer time frame, may have provided a more comprehensive response to this query, the author adds. The author concludes by pointing out that because IT encourages transparent policymaking that is consistent with a democratic society, it may be more desirable from a policy standpoint.

IT's impacts on GDP growth, short-term policy rates, and core inflation were studied by Mishkin and Posen in 1997. Early IT countries like New Zealand, Canada, and the United Kingdom were represented in the sample.

According to the study, disinflation was achieved before the development of IT. The study also discovered that, compared to before IT, interest rates and inflation stayed low over the business cycle upturn. The outcome is seen as proof that the IT framework corrects the gains from disinflation. The study's reliance primarily on visual inspection is a weakness.

The first comprehensive investigation on inflation targeting was carried out by Bernanke et al. (1999) utilising a case study methodology. Because the IT strategy clearly offers advantages over conventional policy, the authors support it. The central bank can respond to changes in output and inflation thanks to the limited discretion provided by this strategy. In this paradigm, accountability and communication offer a further benefit in terms of central bank credibility.

In the countries of the IT, the study discovered low inflation and inflation expectations. This affects the low nominal interest rates. Therefore, the small pass-through effect of one-time shocks on the price level was reduced, resulting in a shock with a persistently low influence on the price level. A decrease in persistence, a low nominal interest rate, and a low ERPT, according to the authors, enhance the business environment and hence promote economic growth.

The authors stress that operational aspects like the definition and announcement of the inflation target are crucial to the effectiveness of inflation targeting. The authors warn that IT is not a magic bullet for making inflation completely predictable.

Four different methodological approaches are used by Mishkin and Schmidt-Hebbel (2007) to investigate the effect of IT on macroeconomic performance. Initially, the authors utilise quarterly data from 34 countries – 21 of which are IT and 13 of which are NIT – for the years 1989 to 2004. Second, by integrating both established and emerging economies, the sample size is balanced. Lastly, the advanced economies that performed best on the macroeconomic frontier but did not use the IT framework make up the study's control group. For statistical inference, the paper employs panel data estimates, vector autoregressive panel models, and panel impulse responses.

The study offers evidence of enhanced macroeconomic performance with the adoption of inflation targeting. For emerging markets and economies where inflation targeting becomes stationary, the advantages are greater. It has been shown that temporary shocks caused by changes in the exchange rate or oil price have less of an impact on inflation. Also, it is discovered that nations with IT seem to perform similarly to the control group, particularly during the maturity phase.

Hu (2003) makes an effort to comprehend the variables involved in an economy's choice to implement inflation targeting. The author evaluates the macroeconomic consequences of IT assessed by output (level and variability), inflation, and the trade-off between output and inflation.

3. Determinants of exchange rate pass-through

It is possible to think of the exchange rate pass-through to domestic inflation as a two-stage process. First, (i) the shift in import costs as a result of the unit shift in the exchange rate; then, (ii) the shift in consumer prices as a result of the shift in import costs. ERPT is an important area of concern for monetary policy. First, it informs the policymakers about the control they have on inflation. Second, it influences the degree of freedom with which the central bank can pursue an independent monetary policy with an exclusive focus on domestic objectives.

Traditionally it was assumed that the prices of tradable goods, when expressed in the same currency, were equal. However, this assumption finds little empirical support as ERPT is incomplete (Dornbusch, 1987; Krugman, 1987; Gagnon and Ihrig, 2004). Moreover, the pass-through depends on the basket's composition used for estimating the consumer price, openness of the economy and structure of imports, persistence of exchange rate shocks, and finally, the hedging for exchange rate shocks is also important.

4.1. Exchange rate pass-through and inflation targeting

Edwards (2006) investigates the relationship between IT and ERPT by using quarterly data from 1985-2005 from seven countries- two advanced and five emerging economies. The author addresses three issues related to IT: (i) the effectiveness of a nominal effective exchange rate as a shock absorber; (ii) impact of IT on exchange rate volatility and (iii) role of the exchange rate in monetary policy reaction function post IT adoption. The author uses the ordinary least square (OLS) method to estimate the effectiveness of NEER as a shock absorber.

The author finds high pass-through coefficient for tradable goods than for non-tradable ones, implying the effectiveness of NEER as a shock absorber. However, the pass-through coefficient has been found to be low under IT.

In the case when pass-through to tradable is larger than non-tradable, the research contends that NEER functions as a reliable shock absorber. Unless the economy employs a higher percentage of imported input in the manufacture of non-tradable, it is typical to assume a stronger pass-through for tradable than non-tradable. The study, however, does not offer a justification or historical illustration of a situation where pass-through was higher for non-tradable than tradable.

Eichengreen (2002) investigates the viability of IT for open and emerging economies by focusing on key policy issues – response of monetary policy to external shocks; fear of float as a result of exchange rate movements; higher level of pass-through; a greater

percentage of debt in foreign currencies; and the credibility of monetary policy due to public debt and forecasting of inflation.

The author suggests adopting a flexible version of IT so that there is less variability in inflation and output due to external shocks. The better way to incorporate exchange rate changes in modelling is to target CPI inflation rather than domestic inflation.

The author further argues that emerging economies are more sensitive to commodity prices. Moreover, the volatile component has a significant weight in the inflation index. These two factors combined make inflation forecasting difficult in these economies. IT is also not a good policy option when there is a fear that an increase in policy rate may result in maturity mismatch and hence increase the default rate among the borrowers. The Central Banks of emerging countries also lack credibility as a result of their various goals being pursued, their budgetary domination, and their inadequate institutional strength.

The paper suggests that the credibility of central banks can be enhanced by making central banks more independent in policy making, enhancing transparency by communicating with the public, and targeting the index which the public understands more clearly.

Gagnon and Ihrig (2004) explore the relationship between monetary policy and exchange rate pass-through (ERPT) in several industrialised countries. The authors find a decline in ERPT at the macroeconomic level in these countries. The theoretical model is developed in which the decline in ERPT is attributed to the shift in the responsiveness of monetary policy towards inflation. The model hypothesis is tested by employing quarterly data from 1971-2003 from twenty industrialised economies. Out of these, five are explicit inflation-targeting economies (IT).

The paper uses the ordinary least square (OLS) method to estimate the pass-through coefficient. The pass-through is examined for an individual as well as for cross-sectional data. However, there is the problem of endogeneity in the sense that the relationship between price and exchange rate is bidirectional. To address the problem, bivariate vector autoregression (VAR) is employed to compare the results with those obtained from the OLS method. The pass-through is also estimated by splitting the sample either on the date of adoption of the inflation targeting regime or on the observed behaviour of inflation.

The key findings of the research may be summed up as follows: (a) In nations with low and steady rates of inflation, there is a low estimated pass-through from currency rate to consumer prices. (b) Compared to the first sub-sample period, the average long-run pass-through decreases in the second one, even though inflation's level or standard deviation decreased at the same time. (c) In the majority of nations whose monetary policy has decisively switched towards stabilising inflation, the pass-through is observed to be declining.

Lamia and Djelassi (2017) investigate the impact of the IT regime on ERPT in six emerging economies from January 1993 to July 2013. The paper uses the ARDL model to estimate the consumer price and producer price equations. According to empirical data, ERPT for both price indices has decreased with the implementation of IT. Because of the fall in ERPT, the study contends that applying the IT regime helps to maintain price stability.

The question of whether and how inflation targeting modifies the approach of exchange rate adjustments to domestic inflation is addressed in Lopez and Pourroy (2019). The Kalman filter, which permits the parameter to fluctuate without limitations, is used by the authors to estimate ERPT for a significant number of nations. The authors contend that endogeneity and self-selection bias in earlier studies of monetary policy regimes are problems. These issues are sorted by using propensity matching scores methodology. The authors find the drop in ERPT in countries with IT framework.

The study demonstrates that nations that have achieved disinflation or have a stable inflation objective have targets that fall within a tolerance range, and those with targets that are near to their targets – even if they are higher than 2% – perform better than those without these elements. These findings are consistent with those of Mishkin and Schmidt-Hebbel (2007) and Svensson (1998).

Maertens et al. (2012) examine the response of different price indices to exchange rates under IT in Peru. The paper presents a simple dynamic stochastic general equilibrium model in which adopting IT increases exchange rate volatility. The paper argues that an increase in exchange rate volatility results in decline in the number of firms setting prices in foreign currency as the share of firms setting prices in foreign currency has a direct relation with the pass-through.

The paper provides empirical evidence on the Peruvian economy's decline in pass-through after IT adoption. The study uses monthly data from April 1994-December 2007 and the time-varying vector autoregression model. The impulse response function reveals the decline in ERPT to price indices, with the highest decline for consumer prices, followed by producer and import prices.

The main thesis of the study is that exchange rate volatility leads to a reduction in pass-through. However, the authors do not provide the estimation of the coefficient of volatility before and after IT and their statistical significance. This makes the volatility argument very weak, particularly in the context of the Peruvian economy.

According to Blanchard (2004), a government with a high likelihood of defaulting on its debt may manage inflation quite well using fiscal policy. The author creates a model that includes interactions between the interest rate, the likelihood of defaulting on debt, and the currency rate. The model demonstrates that fiscal policy is a suitable instrument for reducing inflation.

The study then verifies the predictions made by the model to test the assertion using data from the Brazilian economy. Brazil's inflation control measures during the 2002 crisis were found to be consistent with the model's projections.

Svensson (1998) developed the model to address three questions about IT in an open economy. The paper compares the targeting of domestic and consumer inflation; whether to adopt a strict or flexible IT framework.

According to the model, flexible inflation targeting combined with CPI inflation is more efficient. The model also indicates a reduced responsiveness of inflation to shocks related to oil and currency rates. The credibility of monetary policy as a shift in reaction to inflation

is argued by the author. The impact of inflation is too complicated to be reflected by a single index, hence the model offers minimal support for employing MCI. Eichengreen (2002) brought attention to this issue by demonstrating that MCI might occasionally provide an erroneous message to decision-makers. The best strategy for dealing with this is to focus on CPI inflation, which includes some international inflation.

Taguchi and Sohn (2014) examine the pass-through in three East-Asian economies- South Korea, Thailand and the Philippines- using quarterly data from 1990 to 2009. The paper employs OLS and VAR methods.

The study then estimates the pass-through for each country before and after the adoption of IT. Only South Korea is affected by the pass-through loss, according to the results. The outcomes for Thailand and the Philippines are unclear. The study makes the claim that only when the policy is forward-looking does the IT framework exhibit a substantial drop or loss in pass-through. By measuring the response function for each nation, the study gives proof. The only country with a forward-looking monetary policy is determined to be Korea.

4.2. Effectiveness of the IT framework under different circumstances

Since there is no unique definition of IT, ERPT has been found to vary under different versions of the framework (Lopez, 2019). In this section, we discuss the feature under which ERPT declines more.

Strict versus Flexible IT

One of the issues the policy makers face is whether to adopt strict or flexible IT. Flexible IT is better for minimising variability in output. This is because monetary policy puts some positive weight on output. However, flexible targeting has been found to be a good policy option as far as exchange rate volatility and ERPT are concerned. Svensson (1998) showed that by adopting flexible targeting, the central bank could minimise the variability not only in output but also in the exchange rate. This will result in a low ERPT. Eichengreen (2002) also the IT framework of emerging and open economies at length. The author also supports the framework of flexible IT. Similarly, Edward (2006) argues for flexible IT with a weight depending on macroeconomic characteristics to ensure less volatility in the economy.

Monetary Condition Index

In an open and emerging economy, consumer inflation also includes some components of foreign inflation. The foreign component of inflation is transmitted through exchange rate changes. Under IT, the central bank commits to maintaining inflation around a target. The exchange rate changes make forecasting inflation and achieving targets difficult. The central banks designed the monetary condition index (MCI) to incorporate the change in exchange rate into the monetary policy reaction function. Svensson (1998) showed that such an indicator is not good for capturing the dynamics of the exchange rate change. He further argues that the exchange rate is a complex phenomenon that is caused by different factors at different times. Therefore, using MCI for each shock without understanding the source and nature of the shock is not a good way to model monetary policy.

Eichengreen (2002) also highlighted the issues of MCI and showed that it is not optimal to use it. He further shows the situation under which the index sends the wrong signal. The paper argues that the IT central bank should adjust policy instruments less in response to the same shocks. Further, the central bank should only smooth the exchange rate movements but not prevent the exchange rate from adjusting.

Targeting CPI inflation

One of the important decisions in IT is regarding the index that monetary policy should target. Initially, there was debate about targeting headline inflation or core inflation; however, with the increase in openness and globalisation, the consumption basket of consumers also changed. The monetary policymakers now face the additional challenge of imported components of consumer inflation. Most authors who are critical of using MCI emphasise targeting CPI inflation, not domestic inflation. Svensson (1998) argued in favour of targeting consumer inflation rather than domestic inflation. The benefits, according to him, are two-fold. First, it is the appropriate index of inflation that the consumers face. Second, the monetary policy does not have to consider the exchange rate exclusively by targeting CPI inflation. Eichengreen (2002) is also in favour of using CPI inflation.

Inflation target with tolerance band

One of the debates in inflation targeting is credibility versus flexibility. Credibility is enhanced when monetary policy can hit the target with a minimum deviation. However, flexibility is also needed to enhance the policy outcomes regarding low variance in output and the exchange rate. Many IT countries announce their targets with the band to benefit from flexibility and credibility. Lopez and Pourroy (2019) found low exchange rate pass-through in countries having inflation targets with tolerance bands even if the target was greater than 2%. This is important in that emerging economies should target a level of inflation compatible with the macroeconomic fundamentals of the economy. However, the tolerance band should be there to allow monetary policy flexibility.

4.3. Lessons from international experience for future targeters

Forward-looking monetary policy

One of the important features of IT is that monetary policy should be made in a forward-looking manner rather than responding to past conditions. However, in some cases, Taguchi and Sohn (2014) found loss in pass-through only in the case of Korea and not in Thailand and the Philippines though all three were IT economies. While estimating the reaction functions of these economies individually, the author found forward-looking policy-making in Korea but not in the other two East Asian economies. The forward-looking nature of the monetary policy is important because the difference between IT and price level targeting is that IT bygones are bygones, while the same is not the case with price level targeting. Therefore, the monetary policy is more concerned with future inflation than target misses in the previous period.

Co-ordination of fiscal and monetary policy

Under IT, the debate on monetary and fiscal policy coordination becomes more important. The Central Bank cannot control inflation when the fiscal policy is not supportive of the framework. Blanchard (2004) discussed the problem of fiscal dominance under IT. He finds that when an economy has a high level of debt, most of which is in foreign currency then under this situation, fiscal policy, not monetary policy, controls inflation appropriately. The paper argues that this happens when the central bank increases interest rates in anticipation of an increase in future inflation. The domestic debt becomes more appealing due to the increase in interest rates, which might lead to an increase in the exchange rate. However, if the probability of default is high, the increase in interest rates will only increase the level of debt and inflation due to exchange rate depreciation. The case of Brazil's economy was discussed when it faced the same situation, but the policymakers responded with fiscal policy. The interest rate was kept constant despite an increase in inflation to avoid an increase in the level of debt. Eichengreen (2003) discusses the problem of having the obligations of banks, corporations, and governments in foreign currency while their revenues are in domestic currency. The depreciation of domestic currency results in a decline in revenues. This will manifest in decline in output and employment and increasing inflation. The main lesson emerging from this paper is that the central bank should take note of foreign liabilities and the development of the domestic financial market to make inflation targeting more effective by reducing the impact of exchange rate changes.

ERPT depends on the nature of imports and the composition of the inflation index:

The literature also shows that the degree of ERPT depends on the nature of imports and the inflation index. Campa and Goldberg (2008) have found high ERPT for energy imports.

Empirical investigation of ERPT in India

In this section, we investigate the ERPT in India using the data from January 2011 to December 2021. The variables used are Consumer price index-combined (CPI-C), Nominal Effective exchange rate (NEER) and quarterly real GDP series converted to monthly frequency by employing the proportional Denton method on the seasonally adjusted index of industrial production (IIP). The data is sourced from Database on Indian Economy, RBI and is of monthly frequency. This Study is improvement of Peer and Baig (2021) by including the first full term of IT period of India.

The study employs vector autoregression (VAR) model for investigating the dynamic interaction between exchange rate and inflation. In the VAR model, all variables in the model are endogenous variables, and each variable is a function of its own lags, as well as current and lags of other endogenous variables and residual terms over time (Sims, 1980).

The following VAR model is applied:

$$Y_t = \alpha + \sum_{j=1}^J A_j Y_{t-j} + e_t \quad (1)$$

where Y_t is endogenous variables vector of 3 x 1 - GDP (GDP_t), exchange rate ($NEER_t$) and inflation (CPI_t), e_t is residual vector which captures the contemporaneous relation

between exchange rate and inflation. J is the number of lagged endogenous variables. Since the theories do not define about the number lags to be taken, so we let the data to decide on the lag, which is based on the Akaike information criterion (AIC). The optimum lag length of $K = 2$ is employed for estimation.

Further, to illustrate the tri variate VAR model for GDP_t , $NEER_t$ and CPI_t is written in matrix form for a regression equation with multivariate outcomes. Therefore, the equation (1) is written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} GDP_t \\ NEER_t \\ CPI_t \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{GDP} \\ \alpha_{NEER} \\ \alpha_{CPI} \end{bmatrix} + \sum_{j=1}^2 A_j \begin{bmatrix} GDP_{t-j} \\ NEER_{t-j} \\ CPI_{t-j} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} e_{GDP,t} \\ e_{NEER,t} \\ e_{CPI,t} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

We also employ Structural Vector autoregression (SVAR). This is a data driven approach which lowers the emphasis on channels of pass-through. We split the sample into two periods. The period before IT is labelled as Pre-IT period and other as IT period. The impulse response of $\Delta NEER_t$ on ΔCPI_t is used as the estimate of ERPT in this framework. The structural identification restrictions for the SVAR estimation are based on a lower triangular matrix with the following assumptions: a) output growth does not respond immediately to inflation and exchange rate movements; and b) exchange rate and output growth cycles affect inflation contemporaneously. The Lagrange multiplier test for residual auto correlation is found to be satisfactory All the Eigen values are inside the unit circle, confirming the stability condition. The results show that during pre IT period, the response of one unit shock to NEER results in 0.12 percent change in CPI. The impact of shock remains significant till 5 month. However, in IT period, our results show that CPI has become insensitive to NEER changes.

The other tool employed for interpreting the relationship between variables of VAR models is forecast error variance decomposition or simply variance decomposition (Lütkepohl, 2005). We also utilised this tool to understand the impact of exchange rate shocks on inflation. The results in Tables 1 and 2 show the same. In pre-IT period, the exchange rate shocks explains around 11 percent variation in inflation. However, during IT period it only explains around 4 percent variations. These results clearly point towards the fact that exchange rate pass-through has declined after the adoption of IT in India.

As already mentioned above, ERPT depends upon a number of factors of which monetary policy is one. However, the most of the studies have found the decline in ERPT after the adoption of IT, provided the policy making role is forward looking and there is effective communication with the public. Since it actually works on the expectations of economic agents such that they are less predisposed to change prices in response to a given exchange rate shock under the IT as monetary authority has a mandate to maintain price stability.

Figure 1. Impulse response function of pre-IT period

Source: Authors estimation.

Table 1. Variance decomposition of CPI-C (January 2011- October 2016)

Period	S.E.	D(GDP)	D(NEER)	D(CPI)
1	0.030874	0.051939	4.179599	95.76846
2	0.032460	0.046224	9.532358	90.42142
3	0.032622	0.047322	10.44094	89.51174
4	0.032639	0.047349	10.54632	89.40633
5	0.032641	0.047373	10.55636	89.39627
6	0.032641	0.047373	10.55721	89.39541
7	0.032641	0.047374	10.55728	89.39535
8	0.032641	0.047374	10.55728	89.39534
9	0.032641	0.047374	10.55728	89.39534
10	0.032641	0.047374	10.55728	89.39534
11	0.032641	0.047374	10.55728	89.39534
12	0.032641	0.047374	10.55728	89.39534

Source: Authors estimation.

Figure 2. Impulse response function of Pre-IT period

Source: Authors estimation.

Table 2. Variance decomposition of CPI (November 2016-December 2021)

Period	Standard error	GDP	NEER	CPI
1	0.004279	28.66967	1.988028	69.34230
2	0.004625	26.14071	2.177398	71.68190
3	0.004793	25.74548	3.866373	70.38814
4	0.004916	26.17951	3.939131	69.88136
5	0.004925	26.16503	4.182470	69.65250
6	0.004943	26.63922	4.153216	69.20756
7	0.004949	26.74235	4.143521	69.11413
8	0.004953	26.80484	4.160540	69.03462
9	0.004955	26.83824	4.167433	68.99433
10	0.004956	26.83184	4.181383	68.98678
11	0.004956	26.83630	4.184133	68.97957
12	0.004956	26.83613	4.186313	68.97755

Source: Authors estimation.

5. Conclusion

This paper conducted a global literature study on the relationship between IT and ERPT. The framework of IT and its distinctive traits were initially covered in the article. The literature on IT and exchange rate pass-through is then investigated. The argument that pass-through decreased with the shift to an IT-based monetary policy framework is supported by the literature. According to the study, the IT framework with flexible IT, consumer inflation as an objective, and a target with a tolerance band is more efficient at lowering ERPT. The review also shows that ERPT decline only when monetary policy is formulated in a forward looking manner. There is also a need for co-ordination between monetary policy and fiscal policy.

In the India context, The ERPT is found to have declined after the adoption of IT framework. However, India imports more than 80% of its crude oil. The crude oil prices being volatile and have implications for ERPT. Therefore, there is a need and developing a strategy in consultation with the government for managing the adverse impacts of crude oil prices.

Acknowledgements

The author is grateful to the University Grants Commission for providing the financial support to the research scholar.

The earlier version of this paper was presented at the 3rd International Conference on Economics and Finance.

Organised by Nepal Rastra Bank, Nepal on 28-29 February 2020. The draft greatly benefitted from comments during discussion.

References

- Baig, M.A., Narasiman, V. and Ramachandran, M., 2003. Exchange market pressure and the Reserve Bank of India's intervention activity, *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 25(8), pp. 727-748.
- Bernanke, B.S., Laubach, T., Mishkin, F.S. and Posen, A.S., 1999, *Inflation Targeting: Lessons from the International Experience*, Princeton University Press, New Jersey.
- Bhattacharya, R., Patnaik, I. and Shah, A., 2008. Exchange rate pass-through in India, *New Delhi: National Institute of Public Finance and Policy*, Available at <http://macrofinance.nipfp.org.in/PDF/BPS2008_erpt.pdf>
- Blanchard, O.J., 2004. Fiscal Dominance and Inflation Targeting: Lessons from Brazil (No. 10389), Cambridge.
- Campa, J.M. and Goldberg, L.S., 2005. Exchange rate pass-through into import prices, *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 87(4), pp. 679-690.
- Campa, J.M. and Goldberg, L.S., 2008. Pass-through of exchange rates to consumption prices: what has changed and why?, in Ito, T. and Rose, A.K. (eds.), *International Financial Issues in the Pacific Rim: Global Imbalances, Financial Liberalization, and Exchange Rate Policy*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago, pp. 139-176.
- Dilla, S., Achsani, N.A. and Anggraeni, L., 2017. Do inflation targeting really reduced exchange rate pass-through? *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 7(3), pp. 444-452.
- Dornbusch, R., 1987. Exchange Rates and Prices, *American Economic Review*, 77, pp. 93-106.
- Edwards, S., 2006. The relationship between exchange rates and inflation targeting revisited, in *NBER Working Paper Series* (No. 12163). Cambridge.
- Eichengreen, B., 2002. Working Paper Series Can Emerging Markets Float? Should They Inflation Target?, Vol. 36, Brasilia.
- Gagnon, J.E. and Ihrig, J., 2004. Monetary policy and exchange rate pass-through, *International Journal of Finance and Economics*, 9(4), pp. 315-338.
- Ghosh, A. and Rajan, S.R., 2007. How high is exchange rate pass-through in India? Has it changed over time?, *The Journal of International Trade & Economic Development*, 16(3), pp. 373-382.
- Hu, Y., 2003. Empirical Investigations of Inflation Targeting, *IIE Working Papers Series WP*, No. 03-6.
- Hutchison, M. and Pasricha, K.G., 2016. Exchange rate trends and management in India, in Ghate, C. and Kletzer, M.K. (Eds.), *Monetary Policy in India: A Modern Macroeconomic Perspective*, Springer, India.
- Kamber, G., Karagedikli, I. and Smith, C., 2015. Applying an inflation-targeting lens to macroprudential policy 'institutions', *Journal of Central Banking*, 11(4), pp. 395-429.
- Khundrakpam, J., 2007. Economic reforms and exchange rate pass-through to domestic prices in India, Bank for International Settlements working paper No. 225.
- Krugman, P., 1987. Pricing to Market when the Exchange Rate Changes, NBER Working Paper, No. 1926.
- Lamia, B. and Djelassi, M., 2017. The Relationship Between Exchange Rate and Inflation Targeting in Emerging Countries, *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 7(11), pp. 1028-1038.

- López-Villavicencio, A. and Pourroy, M., 2019. Does Inflation Targeting always matter for the ERPT? A robust approach, *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 60, pp. 360-377.
- Lütkepohl, H., 2005. *New introduction to multiple time series analysis*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Maertens, O., Castillo, P. and Rodriguez, G., 2012. Does the exchange rate pass-through into prices change when inflation targeting is adopted? The Peruvian case study between 1994 and 2007, *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 34(4), pp. 1154-1166.
- Mishkin, F.S. and Posen, A.S., 1998. Inflation targeting: lessons from four countries, NBER (National Bureau of Economic Research) Working Paper Series, No. 6126.
- Mishkin, F. and Schmidt-Hebbel, K., 2002. A decade of inflation targeting in the world: What do we know and what do we need to know? In N. Loayza, R. Soto and K. Schmidt-Hebbel (Eds.), *Inflation targeting: Design, performance, challenges*, Central Bank of Chile, Santiago.
- Mishkin, F.S. and Schmidt-Hebbel, K., 2007. Does inflation targeting make a difference?, NBER (National Bureau of Economic Research) Working Paper Series no. 12876.
- Mohan, R. and Ray, P., 2019. Indian Monetary Policy in the Time of Inflation Targeting and Demonetization, *Asian Economic Policy Review*, 14, pp. 67-92.
- Peer, A.H. and Baig, M.A., 2021. Inflation Targeting and Exchange Rate Pass-Through in India: An Empirical Investigation, in Mishra, A.K., Arunachalam, V., Patnaik, D. (eds.) *Critical Perspectives on Emerging Economies: Contributions to Economics*. Springer.
- Patra, M.D., Khundrakpam, J. and John, J., 2018, Non-Linear, Asymmetric and Time-Varying Exchange Rate Pass-Through: Recent Evidence from India Michael (No. 02/2018), Mumbai.
- Reddy, Y.V., 1999. Inflation in India: status and issues, Retrieved 27 September 2019, from <<https://rbidocs.rbi.org.in/rdocs/Speeches/PDFs/8431.pdf>>
- Sims, C.A., 1980. Macroeconomics and Reality, *Econometrica*, 48, pp. 1-48.
- Taguchi, H. and Bolortuya, J., 2019. Inflation targeting and the pass-through Effect in Mongolia, *Business and Economic Research*, 9(2), p. 57.
- Taylor, B.J., 2000. Low inflation, pass-through and the pricing power of firms, *European Economic Review*, 44(7), pp. 1389-1408.
- Walsh, C., 2015. Goals and rules in central bank design, CESifo Working Paper Series 5293, CESifo Group Munich.

Appendix

List of the inflation targeting countries

Country	Exchange rate-regime	Year	Target
New Zealand	Floating	1990	1--3
Canada	Free floating	1991	2+/-1
United Kingdom	Free floating	1992	2
Australia	Free floating	1993	2---3
Sweden	Free floating	1993	2
Czech Republic	Floating	1997	3+/-1
Israel	Floating	1997	2+/-1
Poland	Free floating	1998	2.5+/-1
Brazil	Floating	1999	4.5+/-2
Colombia	Floating	1999	2---4
Chile	Free floating	1999	3+/-1
South Africa	Floating	2000	3---6
Thailand	Floating	2000	0.5---3
Hungary	Floating	2001	3+/-1
Iceland	Floating	2001	2.5+/-1.5
Korea	Floating	2001	3+/-1
Mexico	Free floating	2001	3+/-1
Norway	Free floating	2001	2.5+/-1
Peru	Floating	2002	2+/-1
Philippines	Floating	2002	4+/-1
Romania	Floating	2005	3+/-1
Guatemala	Stabilised arrangement	2005	5+/-1
Indonesia	Stabilised arrangement	2005	5+/-1
Armenia	Floating	2006	4.5+/-1.5
Turkey	Floating	2006	5.5+/-2
Serbia	Crawl-like Arrangement	2006	4---8
Ghana	Floating	2007	8.5+/-2
Uruguay	Floating	2007	3--7
Albania	Floating	2009	3+/-1
Georgia	Floating	2009	3
Paraguay	Floating	2011	4.5
Uganda	Floating	2011	5
Dominican Republic	Crawl-like Arrangement	2012	3--5
Moldova	Floating	2013	3.5--6.5
Japan	Free floating	2013	2
India	Floating	2015	2--6
Kazakhstan	Floating	2015	4
Russia	Free floating	2015	4
Ukraine	Floating	2016	6+/-2
Jamaica	Floating	2017	4--6
Costa Rica	Crawl-like Arrangement	2018	2--4
Seychelles	Floating	2021	.
Sri Lanka	Stabilised arrangement	2021	4- 6
Uzbekistan	Crawl-like Arrangement	2020	5 (10% for 2021)
Kenya	Other managed Float	2013	2.5 - 7.5%

Source: Authors compilation based on various annual report on exchange arrangements and exchange restrictions of IMF and central bank websites.

The circular economics of constructions

Rareș-Mihai NIȚU

Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
niturares18@stud.ase.ro

Abstract. *Construction has been and represents one of the most targeted areas of activity in the economy, starting from the market value and reaching the economic policies that regulate them. This paper analyzes the evolution of the construction sector and brings into discussion a new concept, namely that of recycling constructions that are restructured, demolished or undergoing technical changes (Mahpour, 2018). This new principle was launched with the new approaches specific to the green and circular economies due to the need to reduce the gap between needs and resources (Liu et al., 2021). Moreover, the most important factor that determines the permanent development of the real estate and construction field is the growth of the population in the last 30 years at a global level, which has been an ascending one, but also the formation of developed economic centers such as the big capitals or the already developed areas. People have been prone to access the already existing infrastructure in the logistically and economically evolved areas, rather than focusing on the formation of new areas, which has led to the migration and centralization of the workforce in certain geographical areas (Hossain et al., 2020).*

Keywords: construction, recycling, development, policies, regulation.

JEL Classification: L70, L74, L78, L79, L80.

1. Introduction

The process of development, of building a building can be characterized by three main cycles. The first cycle represents the beginnings of the construction plan. At this stage it is determined what elements will or will not be kept from the old building and what are the infrastructure elements that the company needs to carry out the plan to the final. This includes elements characteristic of a building such as providing the necessary distancing between the adjoining buildings, the foundation large enough to have stability, as well as the analysis of the soil and the environment. In the second cycle, the architecture of the building develops (Bao et al., 2019). This includes elements such as the materials used to carry out the necessary infrastructure, but also factors such as the remodeling of the elements needed to build the infrastructure (Christensen, 2021).

The third cycle is that of actual development, in which the materials are used to build the building itself. At this stage, the specific elements of the circular economy appear by reintroducing the materials that can still be used to recover part of the old building (Mahpour, 2018). All these elements depend, to achieve the place, on 4 large factors. The most important is the human factor, which is represented in this situation by the population in society that determines the demand in this market. The second important factor is the economic one, which requires a healthy and stable economic environment that allows builders to carry out the plan (Benachio et al., 2020).

This is one of the most important factors, being the one that will subsequently lead in unfavorable situations to price increases. Given the long period of time that a construction needs to be completed, the possibility of changing certain prices increases significantly, hence the need for stability and forecasting (Çimen, 2021). The third factor is related to the construction environment, which is the most volatile element of all four. It is about the environmental policies adopted, about the safety rules that the state imposes, but most importantly about the environmental policies adopted by the authorities. Even if it is not directly about a price increase, those changes have the ability to reduce the flexibility of the companies in the field and to reduce their capacity for response and flexibility, leading in certain situations even to the bankruptcy of the company. The fourth and determining factor for the work in question is that relating to the quality and quantity delivered (Liu et al., 2021). Currently there are a lot of economic agents looking to reduce the quality of materials to increase the amount they can offer. The lack of security and control policies are key elements of the acceptance and propagation of these elements (Benachio et al., 2020).

The possibility of accessing materials already used previously, of saving time and resources by collecting real estate waste and attracting it into the new form of use may lead to the formation of a framework conducive to increasing the quality and discouraging unfair practices by resorting to materials that are inferior in quality (Mahpour, 2018).

The main problem of housing is that a record of decreasing volume will lead to an increase in the total value of construction production, due to an increase in living space for a person.

The other types of constructions are influenced by the change in technologies, of the old industrial buildings that no longer have utility in the modern economy and can no longer bring added value only by dismantling them (Bao et al., 2019).

Moreover, the development of this market segment in the modern economy is also influenced by factors such as the growth of foreign investments, loans granted from banking or investment institutions at European level such as BEARD, access to substantial, European or national or local, or private ones. To be able to organically develop such an infrastructure requires large investments and balance in the market (Hossain et al., 2020). For this reason, the reuse of poor construction materials, being currently already high constructions, the machines and the prolonged working times being factors that generate additional costs that most investors do not agree to pay (Mahpour, 2018). In order to bridge this gap between what is wanted to be done and what is actually happening, the cost of using building materials already integrated in certain areas must be lower than that of purchasing new raw materials. In the case of a contract, the economic law shows that economic agents will continue to use the most financially efficient possibilities. This does not require investment in infrastructure, but in research into equipment, machinery and mechanisms for processing new concepts.

2. Literature review

The construction sector generates a considerable volume of waste every year that can reach up to 40% in industrialized countries, almost all of which comes from rehabilitation or demolition of buildings. Therefore, this waste is a key issue, and changing the way we manage the use of building materials is crucial (Ruiz et al., 2020). There are, however, raw materials, waste, that can be recycled indefinitely. But recycling is a process that requires a high level of expertise and innovation, as recovered materials can often be contaminated. First of all, this waste must be sorted and subjected to special treatments, such as glass (Çimen, 2021). In theory, it can be melted over and over again, without changing its properties, but specialists in the field state that several types of glass should not be recycled at once. It is important to take into account the different characteristics of the material depending on each application, which should not be altered. Flat glass used in construction or windscreen glass must retain high transparency following the recycling process, so they cannot be mixed with tinted glass.

Thus, the recycling process of building materials is governed by a number of factors: the composition of the product, the level of contamination and the ability of the industrial process to turn the waste into a secondary raw material identical in terms of properties to the initial one (Hossain et al., 2020). The circular economy is a priority and is now focused on developing new solutions for the recycling of materials. The major challenge is the use of our materials in the construction or renovation of as many buildings as possible, while reducing the waste of resources and contributing to the protection of the environment. The transition to the circular economy is not just a necessity. This is an opportunity to provide

solutions and products that meet the needs of current and future generations, related to performance, sustainability or well-being, and to protect the future of our planet (Çimen, 2021).

The raw materials present on the planet are a scarce and, in many cases, unrecoverable resource, which is why the current consumption model destroys many of these resources. Investment in research is therefore necessary and, in this way, new production models should be promoted, where possible, based on the reassessment and re-use of industrial waste, encouraging the study and search for new markets for these resources recovered, considered as waste (Çimen, 2021). In this way, industries are encouraged to adapt to the circular economy model with the environmental, social and economic benefits so necessary for our planet.

Traditionally, the productive model that has supported the growth system of our society has been based on the use of various available resources that, after their introduction into the production chain and their subsequent incorporation into the consumption chain, have lost their properties becoming waste, the inevitable destination of which is the landfill. This is where the paradigm of the linear economy that prevails in today's productive industry comes from.

The main problem behind this linear system is the commitment to the capacity to assimilate resources, through consistent pollution, the accumulation of waste without use, the exploitation of resources that exceed the regeneration rate and the depletion of resources due to excessive consumption (Liu et al., 2021). The fundamental key to initiating the waste transition process is the synergy between waste generated by a technological process and renewable useful waste. Waste avoidance, greening, reuse and other similar measures could save EU companies 8% of their annual turnover, while reducing total annual greenhouse gas emissions by 2-4%.

The main objectives currently of the circular economy promoters are to raise awareness about the circular economy in the construction sector, to reduce the production of waste from construction materials, to reduce construction waste by re-incorporating it into the value chain, to provide information on the possibility of re-evaluation of each element, free access to software for consultation and use of techniques or methods of re-use of building materials (Benachio et al., 2020).

3. Data analysis

At the expense of recent economic conditions and economic imbalances that have arisen as a result of labor market volatility, be it technological development or the impact of the pandemic on social stability, the number of buildings that have been sold has increased significantly (Górecki et al., 2019). Mostly, the data show that this happened relatively uniformly across the geographical area of a country, being about the possibility and encouragement of working from home by most companies, but also from the need for individuals to invest in assets with a high safety risk. Moreover, in the period 2019-2012,

the price of real estate decreased significantly, which encouraged the population to access loans in order to become owners. The countries where the construction sector has developed the most are those in eastern and south-eastern Europe, being about policies and legislation that are more accessible to the rest of the member countries (Ruiz et al., 2020). At the same time, the countries that have the highest construction rate recorded are recognized as the countries that also have the highest share of owners for their own homes, with the majority of constructions in economically developed countries at European level consisting of office space and areas for commercial activities and less for areas intended for residential complexes (Christensen, 2021). A good indicator is the nature of the types of constructions, in particular the destination they have for their daily activity. The market economy implies an environment favorable to the development of economic activity and automatically of entrepreneurship, which is why it is normal that in most of the European Union, the most numerous constructions are intended for office spaces. Moreover, the mobility of the human factor has led to an increase in demand for living spaces, which leads to a higher volatility and to the need for builders to foresee the need for free apartments (Bao et al., 2019).

Source: Authors own processing of data from Eurostat database.

Mirrored, the two graphs display the countries from side to side in different order. The most economically developed countries also have the most complete and clear set of laws for the construction sector. As a result, it is normal to identify developed areas with a high degree of collection and recycling of raw or residual materials (Liu et al., 2021). It is important to note that most of the reuse processes of raw materials consist of modern buildings, which can be reused, such as glass buildings or those that are in the process of being executed and have not been completed. A share of about 27% at European level is represented by different buildings, dwellings or construction sites that have not come together to be

completed, thus being seen by the performing economies as a clear source of raw materials that can be reintroduced into the circuit. There can be no equate between developed and early economies. Countries such as Romania, Bulgaria, Hungary, Slovakia or Slovenia have the highest number of interwar buildings, as these are buildings made of stone or massive materials that contain several defects or sections that are severely damaged and cannot be recovered or upgraded. These buildings are of the nature of those administered by the State, which are no longer the object of work of some institutions, nor can they be redeveloped for financial reasons. These objects represent an opportunity only by their simple land, by their simple settlement, being of great importance.

Source: Authors own processing of data from Eurostat database.

The circularity of constructions largely depends on how they are designed in the first instance, on how they were designed and built. In order to reuse the materials from the current constructions, they must be thought out from the design stage in order to be able to find them in a later direction from the beginning. As a result, the circular economy-specific process is now gaining importance (Christensen, 2021). The focus should be on how the work will be carried out from now on, without focusing on how things have been done. From a technical point of view, a process is designed to have effects based on a predominant cause, in this case being the nature of the raw material.

4. Conclusion

The idea of a circular construction sector is based on an economic model that aims to use products for as long as possible and reduce waste - through reuse and recycling - while stimulating social, economic growth and prosperity. All over Europe, architects consider

the reuse of materials by other users and the recycling of waste, which are the main qualities of a circular construction economy (Christensen, 2021). A third of them even expect to achieve a fully circular construction economy by 2030.

The development of the construction sector based on the circular economy presents a long-term plan, which is influenced by several factors such as the current legislation, both at European and national level, but also the volatility of prices, the technological evolution, the capacity of the control bodies for the careful supervision of the activity and many others (Górecki et al., 2019). Being a dynamic field, which is in a permanent change and change, but also considering the fact that the recurrent activity is a long-term one, taking a longer period of time to be able to align the periods of change – regardless of their constraint nature – with the business model and the trajectory that the big companies draw.

References

- Adams, K.T., Osmani, M., Thorpe, T. and Thornback, J., 2017, February. Circular economy in construction: current awareness, challenges and enablers. In Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers-Waste and Resource Management, 170(1), pp. 15-24. Thomas Telford Ltd.
- Bao, Z., Lu, W., Chi, B., Yuan, H. and Hao, J., 2019. Procurement innovation for a circular economy of construction and demolition waste: Lessons learnt from Suzhou, China. *Waste Management*, 99, pp. 12-21.
- Benachio, G.L.F., Freitas, M.D.C.D. and Tavares, S.F., 2020. Circular economy in the construction industry: A systematic literature review. *Journal of cleaner production*, 260, 121046.
- Christensen, T.B., 2021. Towards a circular economy in cities: Exploring local modes of governance in the transition towards a circular economy in construction and textile recycling. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 305, 127058.
- Çimen, Ö., 2021. Construction and built environment in circular economy: A comprehensive literature review. *Journal of cleaner production*, 305, 127180.
- Ginga, C.P., Ongpeng, J.M.C. and Daly, M.K.M., 2020. Circular economy on construction and demolition waste: A literature review on material recovery and production. *Materials*, 13(13), 2970.
- Górecki, J., Núñez-Cacho, P., Corpas-Iglesias, F.A. and Molina, V., 2019. How to convince players in construction market? *Strategies for effective implementation of circular economy in construction sector*. *Cogent engineering*, 6(1), 1690760.
- Hossain, M.U., Ng, S.T., Antwi-Afari, P. and Amor, B., 2020. Circular economy and the construction industry: Existing trends, challenges and prospective framework for sustainable construction. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 130, 109948.

- Liu, J., Wu, P., Jiang, Y. and Wang, X., 2021. Explore potential barriers of applying circular economy in construction and demolition waste recycling. *Journal of cleaner production*, 326, 129400.
- Mahpour, A., 2018. Prioritizing barriers to adopt circular economy in construction and demolition waste management. *Resources, conservation and recycling*, 134, pp. 216-227.
- Ruiz, L.A.L., Ramón, X.R. and Domingo, S.G., 2020. The circular economy in the construction and demolition waste sector – A review and an integrative model approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 248, 119238.

Market mood index and stock market. Evidence from National Stock Exchange

Neha SETH

Central University of Rajasthan, India
neha_seth01@yahoo.com

Yogesh KUMAR

Central University of Rajasthan, India
yogeshkumardse@gmail.com

Abstract. *This study examines the time-series relationship between investor sentiment and the Indian stock market. Investor sentiment is measured through the market mood index (MMI); MII is a tool that shows the investor's emotions regarding the market and helps the investor, traders, etc., to know the current state of the market, i.e., extreme fear, fear, greed, extreme greed. Empirical results show that market sentiment generally lies between fear and greed mood. To check long-run relationships, we apply the Autoregressive Distributed lag test; the result shows a long-term relationship. Empirical results also show a bi-directional Granger causality relationship exists between the variables.*

Keywords: investor sentiment, market mood index, market return, ARDL, Granger causality.

JEL Classification: G11, G15, G17, G40, G41.

Introduction

Traditional finance theories consider the market participants to be the rational economic agents who make decisions by trading off the cost and benefits. It is based on the assumption that the market is efficient and the stock market cannot deviate from its intrinsic or fundamental value. But this is not the case with behavioural finance. According to behavioural finance theory, market participants are irrational and are prone to psychological and sociological biases. Due to these biases, prices of the securities deviate from their intrinsic values, and arbitragers enjoy profits. But the arbitragers are risk-averse, and their risk appetite is limited against the noise traders. Due to the limit of arbitrage, the role of investor sentiment increases in determining the price of the securities. Brown (1999) suggests that if the noise signal affects the price of the securities, then the noise signal is sentiment and the risk cause becomes volatility. Hence the sentiment is related to volatility in the market.

Investor sentiment plays a vital role in determining the prices of assets. Jiang and Jin (2021) found that an increase in investor sentiment also increases the volatility in the Istanbul stock exchange. Hence investor sentiment causes both, i.e., price and volatility in the stock market.

We use MMI as a proxy for measuring investor sentiment. It is a market-based measure that helps the investors understand the market's current mood, and investors can make buy and sell decisions. The study examines the relationship between the MMI and the Nifty index. It is a 100-point scale divided into four equal parts, i.e., extreme fear, fear, greed, and extreme greed. The lowest value suggests extreme fear, and the highest value suggests extreme greed in the market. Extreme fear (below 30) suggests an excellent opportunity to open a new position because during the extreme fear zone market is oversold, and there is a high chance that the market will bounce back in the upward direction. The fear range (30-50) shows investors are worried about the market. If the indicator further drops to extreme fear or from greed to fear, it shows that the market is more fearful. The greed range lies between 50-70, suggesting that investors behave irrationally while taking a trade. If the market comes down from extreme greed to greed, it suggests market greediness is decreasing, and if it comes from the fear to greed, then it shows that the market greediness is increasing. Also, in the Extreme greed zone (above 70) market is overbought, and it is suggested that investors should avoid to open a fresh position because there might be the possibility that the market will turn downwards. So, it shows the overall psychology of the investor or traders or the mood or tone of the market.

1. Market mood index

The market mood index includes six crucial factors to present a clear market picture, based on these factors, MMI is calculated. It includes foreign institutional investors (FII) activity, volatility and skew, momentum, market breadth, price strength, and demand for gold. Each indicator is assigned equal weight, and then MMI is formed.

FII activity: In this the interest is checked in the Indian market and is tracked through their net open position in the future index on the national stock exchange (NSE). If their net open position in the future index is more than the average value, then FIIs have a bullish view of the market.

Volatility and skew: It is based on out of the money (OTM) call options and OTM put options of nifty. If the difference value is higher, then it represents high average value skew. It means there is a high chance that the market will show a downward movement, and the market will come in a fearful mood.

Momentum: It is based on an exponential moving average of nifty. In this, the difference of 90 and 30 days exponential moving average of nifty is divided by 90 days moving average. The positive result shows positive momentum, and it shows a bullish trend, and MMI is going into the greed zone.

Market Breadth: It is calculated on the basis of the Advance-Delay (AD) ratio and Advance decline is calculated by price and volume. If both the ratios are more than one, it means AD price is supported by AD volume and market movement is real, and it will stay for a long time.

Price strength: It is calculated on the basis of the difference between the percentage of 52-week high stock and 52-week low stock. A positive result shows that the market is moving toward a bullish trend and vice versa.

Demand for gold: If the price return from the nifty is less than the price return from the gold over the last 2 weeks, it shows investors prefer investing in gold over equity. It shows MMI in the fear zone because investors are shifting towards other investments.

MMI is based on different market indicators and investor trading habits, so it shows both the state of the market and investor mood, so it is used as a sentiment for the study. The empirical data found a long-run relationship between nifty and the market mood index. Also, there is a bi-directional Granger causal relationship between them.

The rest of the study describes in the following section. The next section of the paper provides the literature review. In section 3, we discuss the Data of the study. Section 4 of the paper is related to the analyses of the data. Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. Review of literature

Several researchers studied investor sentiment and its effects on the share market. Researchers used different proxies for investor sentiment. Several studies suggest different proxies for measuring investor sentiment. Khan and Ahmad (2018) suggest two approaches for measuring investor sentiment, i.e., direct and indirect. The direct approach includes the information received through the survey, getting information through social media and the internet regarding their feelings or mood about the stock market and economic situation. The indirect approach includes the economic and financial variables other than the investors' mindset.

Researchers use both approaches in estimating investor sentiment. Fisher et al. (2015), Otoo (1999), Jansen and Nahuis (2003), Ferrer et al. (2016), Balwani et al. (2017) use consumer sentiment index (CSI) as a proxy for investor sentiment while Khan and Ahmad (2018) used both the methods for sentiment analysis and analysis its effect on Pakistan stock market. Kumari Mahakud (2015). Dash and Mahakud (2013) used financial indicators as a proxy for investor sentiment like put-call ratio, advance-decline ratio, turnover ratio, dividend premium, number of initial public offerings, turnover velocity, etc. Chakraborty and Subramaniam (2020) take the consumer confidence index and market mood index to examine the cross-sectional effect in the Indian stock market. Beyaz et al. (2019) use the volatility index as a market mood indicator for investor sentiment.

Gude et al. (2017) studied the impact of CSI on Indian nifty volatility. This study shows that a short- and long-term relationship exists between CSI and the national stock exchange (NSE) nifty. Indian investors behave so quickly in response to CSI that this short-run relationship adjusts quickly, and the stock market returns to equilibrium. Ferrer et al. (2016) investigated the time-varying pattern of consumer confidence and the stock market post the dot-com bubble and during the financial crisis in the USA and European countries. He observed that the Stock market and consumer confidence relationship is decreased in European countries and unaffected in the USA post the dotcom bubble crash, concluding that consumer confidence is not a suitable proxy for investor sentiment. Hsu et al. (2011) find a granger causal relationship between consumer confidence and the stock market in 21 countries. He finds that in globalization, news and information spread quickly, which may lead the stock prices and consumer confidence to behave in the same pattern in all the countries. It shows that investors' behaviour is common in all the nations. Fisher et al. (2015) find that higher consumer confidence leads to lower stock returns as there is a negative relationship between them. Empirical results also show a positive relationship between the CCI change and contemporaneous stock return. Otoo (1999) finds that consumer sentiment and stock price have a contemporaneous relationship.

Khan and Ahmad (2018) study the emerging market of Pakistan to check the relationship between investor sentiment and stock return. He used ten proxies for measuring the investor sentiment and found that seven proxies positively relate to the investor sentiment while the other three are negatively related. Also, he used both the direct and indirect methods of sentiment for measuring the investor sentiment and found the bio-directional causal relationship between them. The result also shows that contemporaneous relation between them also exists and suggests that the sentiment immediately affects stock return and vice versa. Beyaz et al. (2019) use machine learning techniques to forecast the state of the market. He uses market mood indicators i.e., the volatility index (VIX), for identifying and forecasting the market state for various companies. Jansen and Nahuis (2003) study 11 European countries, showing that investor sentiment and stock return in nine countries are positively correlated. He takes consumer confidence as a proxy for investor sentiment and establishes the relationship with the stock market. Nguyen et al. (2015) studied the impact of consumer and business confidence on stock market risk premium. He found that consumer confidence has a significant positive effect on stock market risk premium, but he has not found any evidence of business impact on stock market risk premium. Hsu et al. (2011) Sum (2013) also studied the effect of consumer and business confidence on the

stock market premium. Yelamanchili (2019) examines the impact of CCI on the Indian stock market. He checks the effect index of consumer sentiment (ICS) on nine sectoral indices and six market indices. He finds that ICS has predictive power on some market indices returns (small-cap, mid-cap, and BSE 500 index); however, the effect is negative. Chakraborty and Subramaniam (2020) study the stock return and volatility using the market mood index and index of consumer sentiment as sentiment indicators. He finds stock volatility caused due to the asymmetric effect on the Market mood index.

2.1. Objective and hypothesis

The researcher used various indicators for measuring investor sentiment and its effect on the stock market. The most commonly used indicators are Put call ratio, advance-decline ration, dividend premium, interest rate, price-earning ratio, turnover, consumer confidence index, etc. Numerous papers show the fluctuation in the stock market through different sentiment indicators. Only a few studies are based on market indicators, i.e., market mood index. It is a novel indicator for measuring investor sentiment, and limited studies exist.

The market mood indicator shows the mindset of the investor with respect to the stock market. It shows the level of fearness and greediness among the investors. In this study market mood index is used to measure the investor sentiment and check its relationship with the Indian stock market. In this, we will also check, is there any causal relationship between the MMI and Stock return?

H01: There is no long-run relationship between the Market mood index and the Nifty index.

H02: The market mood index does cause the Nifty Index or vice versa.

3. Research methodology

This paper examines the relationship between the market mood index and the Indian nifty index. This study use multiple econometric tests for further analysis. First of all, the unit root test was applied to check the stationarity of the data so we could avoid spurious results. Based on the unit root test long-run relation is checked through ARDL long-run bound test post lag selection. This study also employed Granger's causality for short-run causal and effect relationships. All the test related to this study is discussed below.

3.1. Unit root test

As this study is based on time series data, the basic condition for time series data is that it is free from the unit root and should be stationary. Stationary data means that data has a constant mean, variance, and covariance with respect to time. If data do not follow this condition, then it is said to be a non-stationary series, and the series does not follow any trend. A non-stationary series gives spurious results, so it is necessary series is stationary (Baumohl and Lyocsa, 2011).

As this study is based on time series data, it is important to check the stationary properties of the data. For this purpose, we employed Fisher's Phillips-Perron and augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root tests (Phillips and Perron, 1988). The null hypothesis of both tests is that the series has a unit root or is non-stationary.

3.2. Lag length selection

An optimal lag length selection is important for the analysis as Johansen's cointegration and granger causality test results are sensitive to lag length. The lag length selection is based on the Final prediction error(FPE), and the Akaike information criterion(AIC) as both criteria are considered superior to the other criteria (Khim and Liew, 2004), and lag eleven is used for further analysis.

3.3. Autoregressive distributed lag long run bound test

This study would apply the Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) test to check the long-run relationship (Pesaran, 2008). As our series is stationary at a different order of integration, i.e., the market mood index is stationary at the level, in contrast, the nifty index is stationary at the first level. The null hypothesis for the ARDL long-run bound test assumes no cointegration between the variables. In this test, we compare the f statistics value with upper and lower bound and gets three type of results, viz., cointegration between the variables, inconclusive results and no cointegration. If the value of f statistics is greater than the upper bound, in that case, the cointegration exists or series is cointegrated in long-run, but if the value is less than or in between the lower and upper bound, then the results are no cointegration, and inconclusive respectively.

3.4. Granger's causality test

The Granger causality test helps us to determine the cause-and-effect relationship between the two variables (Granger, 1969). This test is carried out to predict the current value of one variable based on the lag responses. The causality gives us three results: uni-directional causality, bi-directional causality, and no causality between the variables. For example, if there are two variables, x, and y, if any increase or decrease in variable x due to variable y, then it is uni-directional Granger causality. Also, if both variables affect each other, then it is called bi-directional. If neither x nor y affects each other, it is called no granger causality between the variables. The null hypothesis of the test assumes that there is no granger causal relationship between variables. As our study is based on two variables, we follow a simple two-variable model of granger causality explained in his study (Granger, 1969). The below equation determines whether the X series granger causes the Y series or vice versa and ε_t , and η_t , shows the error term.

$$X_t = \sum_{j=1}^m a_j X_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^m b_j Y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t,$$

$$Y_t = \sum_{j=1}^m c_j X_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^m d_j Y_{t-j} + \eta_t,$$

3.5. Data

This study measures Investors sentiment through the Market mood index. The data is published by Economics times now small case. This data is also available on the tickertape application that Zerodha owns. It is a 100-point scale divided into four equal parts, i.e.,

extreme fear, fear, greed, and extreme greed. The index is based on six parameters: foreign institutional investors (FII) activity, volatility and skew in the market, momentum, market breadth, price strength, and demand for gold. Each indicator is assigned equal weight, and then MMI is formed. The daily data of the market mood index is used from May 2012 to May 2022.

Daily data of Nifty is obtained from the national stock exchange website (NSE). The index's closing value is used to check the effect of market mood on the trading day. The nifty closing value shows all the sentiment for that day that's why the closing value of the nifty is chosen for the study. Hence, 10 years of MMI and Nifty data is considered to examine the relation between them.

4. Data analysis and interpretation

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of the MMI and Nifty index. The result indicates that investors normally behave rationally as it lies between fear and greed. Investors are in extreme fear in April 2018 as the MMI value is lowest in this month and are in extreme greed in June 2021 as the value of the index is highest in this month. A normal distribution has a kurtosis value is 3. The Kurtosis value of Nifty index is more than 3, which shows that the distribution is more peaked and has a fatter tail, whereas the market mood index value is less than 3, which shows the distribution has a thinner tail and is less peaked. Such distribution is called leptokurtic and platykurtic, respectively.

Further, the null hypothesis of the Jarque-Bera test is data is normally distributed. But the probability value of our result is less than 0.05. It means the Nifty 50 and BEER is not normally distributed.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	Nifty_Index	Market_Mood_Index
Mean	9900.721	50.38099
Median	9256.675	51.16382
Maximum	18477.05	88.17933
Minimum	4835.65	12.35739
Std. Dev.	3311.057	17.68799
Skewness	0.778944	-0.090193
Kurtosis	3.012615	2.079707
Jarque-Bera	248.785	90.14649
Probability	0	0
Sum	24355774	123937.2
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.70E+10	769334.9
Observations	2460	2460

Source: Author's compilation.

4.1. Unit root test

Before performing an econometric analysis, it is necessary to check the stationary of the data. The data must be free from the unit root. Table 2 shows the stationary test result. Data should be stationary for a reliable result. The stationary of the series is checked through the augmented dickey fuller test ADF and Phillip Perron (PP) test. The market mood index is stationary at level I(0), and the Nifty index is at the first difference I(1). In stationary, we get the mixed result as one variable is stationary at the level and another at first.

Table 2. Unit root test

Unit Root Test				
ADF Test			PP Test	
At I (0)	t-Statistic	Prob.*	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Market_Mood_Index I (0)	-9.058597	0	-9.050842	0
Infity Index I (0)	-0.400541	0.9067	-0.222264	0.9332
At I (1)				
D(Nifty_Index)	-12.04669	0	-49.39712	0.0001

Source: Author's compilation.

4.2. Lag selection

Table 3 shows the lag selection criteria. Lag selection was based on Akaike information criterion (AIC) and finite sample (FPE). The lag length was selected for a model where the value of AIC is less. Here the AIC value (18.32152) and FPE (310446.9) is minimum at 11 lags. So, lag 11 is selected for further test.

Table 3. VAR lag selection

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-25403.21	NA	3823696.	20.83248	20.83724	20.83421
1	-22427.46	5944.180	334324.9	18.39562	18.40989	18.40081
2	-22407.69	39.47137	330027.7	18.38269	18.40646	18.39133
3	-22361.43	92.25426	318787.0	18.34803	18.38132*	18.36013
4	-22349.8	23.15810	316800.8	18.34178	18.38458	18.35734
5	-22332.32	34.80541	313317.9	18.33073	18.38304	18.34974
6	-22322.21	20.12202	311750.7	18.32571	18.38753	18.34819*
7	-22319.11	6.159506	311981.2	18.32645	18.39778	18.35238
8	-22319.05	0.122177	312990.5	18.32968	18.41053	18.35907
9	-22314.03	9.955128	312729.7	18.32885	18.41920	18.36169
10	-22301.28	25.28285	310493.7	18.32167	18.42154	18.35797
11	-22297.1	8.288765	310446.9*	18.32152*	18.43090	18.36128
12	-22293.41	7.289416	310527.9	18.32178	18.44067	18.36500

Source: Author's compilation.

4.3. ARDL long run form and bounds test

As the unit root shows, one variable is stationary at the level $I(0)$ and another at the first difference $I(1)$, so the Autoregressive Distributed lag (ARDL) test is applied for cointegration. Table 4 shows the result of the ARDL long-run bound test. The test shows the long-run relationship that exists between MMI and Infity index. The f-statistic value 12.91801 is greater than the upper bound value $I(1)$. So the long-run relationship significantly exists at 5% level. Hence we reject the null hypothesis (H_0), and there is a long-run relationship between MMI and the Nifty index.

Table 4. ARDL long run form and bounds test

F-bound Test				
	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	12.91801	10%	3.02	3.51
k	1	5%	3.62	4.16
		2.5%	4.18	4.79
		1%	4.94	5.58

Source: Author's compilation.

4.4. Granger causality test

To check the causal relationship between MMI and the nifty index, we apply the pairwise granger causality test. Table 5 shows the result of the pairwise granger causality test. In the granger test, the null hypothesis is market mood index does not Granger cause nifty index, and the second null hypothesis is nifty index does not granger cause. The result shows that the p-value is less than 0.05, so we reject the null hypothesis. The result shows MMI granger causes the nifty index and vice versa. It shows a bio-directional granger causality because both variables cause each other.

So, we reject H02: Market mood does not cause nifty index, and both the variables cause each other in the short run.

Table 5. Pairwise Granger causality tests

Null Hypothesis:	Obs.	F-Statistic	Prob.
Market Mood Index does not Granger Cause Nifty_Index	2449	3.02734	0.0005
Nifty Index does not Granger cause Market Mood Index		10.9296	6.00E-20

Source: Author's compilation.

5. Conclusion

Sentiment plays a powerful role in deviating the price of securities from its intrinsic value. When sentiment leads in the market, the fundamental and technical indicators do not work accurately. This study shows that MMI deviate the market from its intrinsic value but it seems investor mood usually lies between fear and greed. It is found that the market mood index and nifty index are negatively correlated. It shows that when investors are in extreme fear, the stock market is oversold, and prices of the securities come below their intrinsic value. When prices of the securities come below their fundamental value, then rational investors start buying, and the stock market returns to its fundamental value and vice versa in case of extreme greed.

The study examines the long-run and short-run relationship between the market mood index and the nifty index. The sentiment index, i.e., the Market mood index, is constituted by six market variables, so this indicator shows the broad area of the market. The study indicates that MMI has a long-run relationship with the Indian nifty index. In the long-run market, the mood index affects the share market. Our empirical result shows that the market mood index granger-cause the change in the nifty index and vice versa. Granger causality test shows that there is a bi-directional causal relation between them.

This study is beneficial for investors, academicians, and traders. As per the behavioural theory, the market is inefficient, and it's beneficial for them to make profits and good investments. This study also helps the arbitrageur to make a profit due to the inefficiencies in the market. This study uses only one indicator for sentiment measure, i.e., the market mood index. MMI is a new indicator for sentiment measure, but it is recommended that researchers use other sentiment indicators for future research. Some of the variables on which less study is published in the Indian context are consumer confidence index, Business confidence index, etc. sector-wise impact is not examined in this research so researchers can work in this area also.

References

- Balwani, N., Vellasamy, M., Reddy, K.M., Reddy, A.D. and Gude, R., Impact of Consumer Sentiment Index on Equity Market Index: A Study on Indian Stock Market. *International Journal of Economic Research*, 14(15/4), pp. 85-91.
- Baumohl, E. and Lyocsa, S., 2009. Stationarity of time series and the problem of spurious regression. Available at SSRN 1480682.
- Beyaz, E., Tekiner, F., Zeng, X.J. and Keane, J., 2018, June. Stock price forecasting incorporating market state. In 2018 IEEE 20th International Conference on High Performance Computing and Communications; IEEE 16th International Conference on Smart City; IEEE 4th International Conference on Data Science and Systems (HPCC/SmartCity/DSS), pp. 1614-1619. IEEE.
- Brown, G.W., 1999. Volatility, sentiment, and noise traders. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 55(2), pp. 82-90.
- Brown, G.W. and Cliff, M.T., 2004. Investor sentiment and the near-term stock market. *Journal of empirical finance*, 11(1), pp. 1-27.
- Chakraborty, M. and Subramaniam, S., 2020. Asymmetric relationship of investor sentiment with stock return and volatility: evidence from India. *Review of Behavioral Finance*, 12(4), pp. 435-454.
- Dash, S.R. and Mahakud, J., 2013. Investor sentiment and stock return: do industries matter?. *Margin: The Journal of Applied Economic Research*, 7(3), pp. 315-349.
- Ferrer, E., Salaber, J. and Zalewska, A., 2016. Consumer confidence indices and stock markets' meltdowns. *The European Journal of Finance*, 22(3), pp. 195-220.
- Fisher, K.L. and Statman, M., 2003. Consumer confidence and stock returns. *The Journal of Portfolio Management*, 30(1), pp. 115-127.
- Granger, C.W., 1969. Investigating causal relations by econometric models and cross-spectral methods. *Econometrica: journal of the Econometric Society*, pp. 424-438.
- Hsu, C.C., Lin, H.Y. and Wu, J.Y., 2011. Consumer confidence and stock markets: The panel causality evidence. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 3(6), pp. 91-98.
- Jansen, W.J. and Nahuis, N.J., 2003. The stock market and consumer confidence: European evidence. *Economics letters*, 79(1), pp. 89-98.
- Jiang, S. and Jin, X., 2021. Effects of investor sentiment on stock return volatility: A spatio-temporal dynamic panel model. *Economic Modelling*, 97, pp. 298-306.
- Khan, M.A. and Ahmad, E., 2018. Measurement of investor sentiment and its bi-directional contemporaneous and lead-lag relationship with returns: Evidence from Pakistan. *Sustainability*, 11(1), p. 94.
- Kumari, J. and Mahakud, J., 2015. Does investor sentiment predict the asset volatility? Evidence from emerging stock market India. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance*, 8, pp. 25-39.
- Liew, V.K.S., 2004. Which lag length selection criteria should we employ?. *Economics bulletin*, 3(33), pp. 1-9.
- Liew, V.K.S., 2004. Which lag length selection criteria should we employ?. *Economics bulletin*, 3(33), pp. 1-9.
- Nguyen, N.K., 2015. The impact of business and consumer confidence on stock market risk premiums: Evidence from Vietnam. *Asian Journal of Management Sciences*, 3(7), pp. 10-13.
- Otoo, M.W., 1999. Consumer sentiment and the stock market. Available at SSRN 205028.
- Perron, P., 1988. Testing for a unit root in time series regression. *Biometrika*, 75, pp. 335-346.
- Sum, V. and Chorlian, J., 2013. Stock market risk premiums, business confidence and consumer confidence: dynamic effects and variance decomposition. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 5(9), pp. 45-49.
- Yelamanchili, R.K., 2019. Impact of consumer sentiment on defensive and aggressive stock returns: Indian evidence. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 9(4), p. 109.

Analysis of the effects of social and fiscal policy on incomes during the COVID-19 pandemic in Romania

Eva MILITARU

National Scientific Research Institute for Labour and Social Protection
eva.militaru@incsmmps.ro

Amalia CRISTESCU

National Scientific Research Institute for Labour and Social Protection
Bucharest University of Economic Studies
amalia.cristescu@incsmmps.ro
amalia.cristescu@economie.ase.ro

Silvana BOBÂRNAT

National Scientific Research Institute for Labour and Social Protection
University of Bucharest, Faculty of Sociology and Social Work
silvana.crivoi@incsmmps.ro

Abstract. *The increase in income inequalities from one period to another for certain vulnerable groups are realities faced by most countries of the world, and these aspects have been accentuated by the effects of the measures imposed as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. These situations first oblige governments to take concentrated and integrated actions in order to improve the effects of these phenomena on people's well-being and social inequalities. The main mechanism by which the state ensures a more equitable distribution of income is the system of social benefits, along with the system of direct and indirect taxation. In this study, we evaluated the capacity of the social benefits system, respectively of the direct and indirect taxation systems, to contribute to the reduction of inequalities and the increase of the population's well-being in Romania. For this purpose, income microsimulation techniques were applied on microdata from the Household Budget Survey for Romania and indicators to evaluate income redistribution and progressivity of the tax-benefit system were calculated. The results were discussed for detailed tax and benefit instruments and compared in the light of progressivity and effectiveness in inequality reduction. Following the analysis, no significant changes in the estimated redistributive effects were observed in 2020 compared to previous years, although the year 2020 was affected by the COVID-19 crisis.*

Keywords: income inequalities, social transfers, taxation, COVID-19 effects.

JEL Classification: J31, H21, H24.

1. Introduction

Income inequality is a global problem, and the COVID-19 pandemic has increased the authorities' concerns in trying to mitigate inequalities through social and fiscal policies. Income inequality affects both developed countries and those with an emerging economy, and the Global Wealth 2022 report highlighted a trend of increasing inequality among the population in 2020 compared to 2019. According to this report, in 2020, the top decile of the population (the richest 10 %) owned 55%-75% of global wealth, and the main determining factors of this situation seem to be globalization, labour market reforms, technologies, but also the COVID-19 pandemic.

Within limits that are difficult to calculate and which depend on specific social, economic and historical contexts, social inequalities are desirable because they provide motivations for development and innovation. However, if the phenomenon of social inequalities increases - as has happened in recent years in developed economies, but also in emerging ones (Dabla-Norris et al., 2015), the effects are undesirable. Socially, inequalities lead to a decrease in trust in social institutions, reduction of social cohesion and conflicts (Dabla-Norris et al., 2015). Judging from the perspective of economic development as a whole, social inequalities have a mostly negative influence (Castells-Quintana and Royuela, 2014). The increase in income inequalities, respectively the instability of income levels from one period to another for certain vulnerable groups are realities faced by most countries of the world. This obliges governments first to take concentrated and integrated actions in order to ameliorate the effects of these phenomena on people's well-being, children's development and social inequalities. Thus, even if the level of inequality is not a problem in itself, the causes and consequences of income inequality and its growth must be taken into account. And here we mean a variety of phenomena, from poverty to poorer health and lower life expectancy, crime, breakdown of communities, intergenerational immobility and the propagation of poverty from one generation to another, all of which are of utmost importance to any society (Salverda and Nolan et al., 2009).

In 2020, Covid-19 narrowed the prosperity gap between rich and emerging countries, as countries with strong economies were hit hard at the start of the pandemic. However, in the medium and long term, its consequences could affect emerging markets to a greater extent. The pandemic generated an increase in income inequalities between rich and poor countries because the latter had fewer resources and policies to mitigate the impact of the crisis. In addition, the pandemic has accelerated long-term structural trends that will not be favourable to many emerging economies. In addition, the crisis continues to have an impact on employees and businesses, and the most disadvantaged are those that were struggling even before the crisis. In fact, the crisis has only exacerbated existing social and economic inequalities, undoing the little progress previously achieved and making it considerably harder to implement for sustainable development. These social and economic inequalities, labour shortages and inflation will lead to the creation of medium and long-term "scars" on economies and societies, unless well-targeted efforts are made by policymakers to make the recovery as wide and sustainable as possible.

An analysis of studies on how the COVID-19 pandemic affected income inequality in the US in 2020-2021 found that employment, earnings, and education were affected differently

by demographic groups and occupations. The pandemic has disrupted low-paid service jobs the most, disadvantaging women and lower-income groups at least temporarily, and this may have long-lasting effects. Government policies implemented in response to the pandemic offset much of the effect on revenues. Higher paid workers have been able to earn more from the opportunities created to work online. Income-disadvantaged students experienced greater educational failure due to school closures. The shutting down of schools and kindergartens disrupted the work of many parents, especially mothers. In conclusion, the pandemic may have increased income inequality in the long run, as lasting changes in work, consumer demand, and production will likely benefit higher-income groups and erode opportunities for some less-advantaged groups. Telework has been constantly increasing. High-touch jobs and services may continue to face reduced demand and increased automation. School disruptions were worse for lower-income students and are likely to have persistent negative effects that may increase future inequality within more recent birth cohorts. At the same time, the history of the 1918 flu shows that the effect of a pandemic on income inequality, education, health and wealth depends on the nature of the pandemic and on the behavioural and political responses (Piacentini et al., 2022)

The impact and effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on income inequality have only just begun to be seen globally due to the lack of data on individual and household incomes. The most recent studies in this direction used simulated data or data collected from household surveys (O'Donoghue et al. 2020, Almeida et al. 2021, Clark et al. 2021). Their results suggested that income inequality fell after the outbreak of the pandemic, primarily because of massive government transfers without which inequality would likely have increased as a result of job losses among lower-income and vulnerable workers. However, the history of studies in this area has shown that income inequality tends to increase during pandemics (Furceri et al. 2020, Galletta and Giommoni 2020).

Analysis of data from administrative tax registers shows that the Covid-19 pandemic has increased income inequality in Sweden. Supportive government policies moderated growth, and simulations showed that without these interventions, inequality would have increased two to three times more. There was also evidence that if the Swedish government had distributed the amount of support differently, inequality might have even fallen during the pandemic, as observed in other Western economies (Waldenström, 2021). Some research has also shown that income inequality has increased during the pandemic, mainly due to layoffs and fewer hours among low-income, part-time workers. Supportive government policies significantly mitigated the rise in inequality, but did not reverse it (Angelov and Waldenström, 2021).

The main mechanism by which the state ensures a more equitable distribution of income is the system of social benefits, along with the system of direct and indirect taxation. We can talk about two approaches in this context: the vertical redistribution of income (from the rich to the poor) which is responsible for reducing inequalities in the distribution of income, respectively the horizontal redistribution, which refers to the fluctuations of income for a single person throughout his/her life. The progressivity of taxes and social benefits, but also the focus and generosity of the latter affect the distribution of income not only in terms of disposable income (after transfers and taxes), but also the initial one, the so-called

original (market) income distribution. This is because social benefits and taxes can affect individuals' motivation to work. Considering these aspects, in this paper we have carried out a study based on the evaluation of the effects of social benefits and taxation of personal incomes on the reduction of income inequalities.

2. Methodology

The analysis is based on the methodology for assessing the effects of social benefits and taxes developed by the World Bank through the Commitment to Equity (CEQ) approach (Lustig and Higgins, 2017). This considers the following aspects:

- Assessing the degree of income redistribution through fiscal and social benefits policies.
- Individual assessment of the redistributive character of each social benefit and each tax (or group).
- Individual assessment of the progressivity of each social benefit and each tax (or group).

For this, first, some income concepts – the basis of the approach – are defined as follows. *Market income* consists of wages, income from self-employment, income from property, transfers from other households, etc. A related concept is *Market income plus pensions*, which adds pensions to market income but subtracts social security contributions for pensions (since the pension is treated as future income for those paying pension contributions). *Gross income* is obtained by adding social security contributions for pensions to market income plus pensions. *Net income* is obtained by subtracting all direct taxes and social contributions from the Gross Income. Furthermore, *Disposable Income* is calculated by adding social benefits/transfers to Net Income. Finally, *Consumable Income* is obtained by subtracting indirect taxes (VAT, excises) from Disposable Income.

By using these income concepts, the contribution of social benefits and taxes to reducing/increasing inequalities can be determined through the following indicators:

- *The Kakwani index* indicates the progressiveness/regressiveness of a tax or social transfer. In the case of taxes, it is calculated as the difference between the concentration coefficient of the tax and the Gini coefficient of market income. For transfers, it is calculated inversely as the difference between the market income Gini coefficient and the transfer concentration coefficient. The concentration coefficient is calculated based on the cumulative distribution of taxes paid/transfers received and population.
- *Marginal contribution to reducing inequality*, shows how many Gini points an element of tax or social transfer contributes to reducing the Gini index of income inequality. It is calculated as the difference between the Gini index with and without the respective transfer or tax.

This approach was applied to microdata from the Romanian Household Budget Survey (HBS), for the period 2019-2020, provided by the Romanian National Institute of Statistics. In the survey, detailed information is collected on all components of household income and consumption, so that all the income concepts presented above could be determined. It was also necessary to carry out microsimulations to obtain indirect taxes paid by households in the form of value added tax, excise duties on fuels, energy, tobacco, and alcohol. These are

not recorded as such in the database, but could be determined with certain limitations based on detailed household consumption information and fiscal legislation.

Preparing the databases was a complex process that consisted in aggregating data at the household level with those at the individual level, recoding the variables, constructing new variables by processing the existing ones or imputations. This ultimately resulted in a new microdatabase on which the simulations were performed. The simulations were based on the 2018 simulation model built for Romania (Badiani-Magnusson, Militaru, 2022), while the parameters for social benefits and taxes have been updated to 2020.

Hypotheses. We assume that direct taxes and social contributions are borne entirely by the earner, while indirect taxes are borne by the final consumer. Information on direct taxation, such as personal income tax and social security contributions can be identified as such in the household survey. As for indirect taxes, its burden has been imputed based on detailed consumption data which is available in HBS and the legal framework in the area of indirect taxation. We have calculated the value added tax (VAT) and the excises applied on alcohol, tobacco, fuel, and energy. In the validation process of imputed data, the comparison with macro aggregates showed a gap between the VAT calculated on survey data and the VAT from national accounts, which can be explained by unregistered consumption. In order to account for this, the VAT rate was adjusted so that the ratio of total tax collections observed in the survey to private consumption is equal to the effective rate observed in the macro data.

Social transfers were directly identified in the survey data which provides detailed information on contributory and non-contributory social benefits beneficiaries and the net amounts received. From the contributory benefits, we mention pensions, temporary work incapacity allowances, maternity allowances, child care allowances, unemployment benefit. The non-contributory benefits are very numerous and include the state allowance for children and other benefits granted to families with children, the minimum guaranteed income, heating aid, minimum pension, disability benefits, and so on. The main transfers, as well as personal income tax and social contributions were also simulated based on policy rules, being then validated with survey data.

Limits. There are some limitations of the analysis that should be mentioned. The analysis does not consider behavioural, life cycle, or general equilibrium effects, estimating the static first order effects. It is assumed that consumer demand and labour supply are perfectly inelastic. We treat overall consumption at household level, while the distribution of consumption within households is not considered due to the lack of data in this respect. Informal incomes are not taken into account; therefore, the real income distribution could be different.

3. Results

First, as a starting point for our discussion concerning the general degree of income redistribution through social benefits policy, we must note that the effectiveness of social transfers in reducing inequalities is low in Romania, compared to other EU countries. The

graph below shows the simple differences between the Gini indices before and after transfers in Romania and in the European Union, average for the 27 countries. There are two ideas that emerge. First, social transfers in Romania contribute less to inequality reduction than social transfers in the “average” EU. And second, this gap between Romania and EU average seems to have widened in recent years, after a rather favourable period between 2016 and 2019.

Figure 1. Effectiveness of social transfers for inequality reduction, Romania vs. EU27

Source: own estimations based on Eurostat data.

If we follow the Gini index calculated on the basis of the income concepts described in the methodology, we can see how, as a whole, the transfer and taxation elements contribute to the reduction of inequalities. Thus, the high level of inequality calculated based on market income plus pensions is reduced towards the disposable income. Interestingly, at the level of consumable income, the degree of inequality increases slightly, which shows that taxation of consumption contributes to increasing inequality.

Figure 2. Gini coefficient, based on income concepts

Source: own estimations based on HBS data for Romania (2020, 2019)

Furthermore, if we look at both the redistribution through social transfers and the one achieved through taxation, we can illustrate the distributional impact of social benefits and taxes by means of a graph broken down by income deciles in which the contribution of social benefits and taxes in the income for each group of households can be observed. Also, the net position of households in relation to the state budget can be determined. From this point of view, we have two types of households: net contributors (if the amounts paid to the state budget in the form of taxes exceed the amounts received in the form of social transfers and pensions) or net beneficiaries (the reverse situation). In the graph below, these contributions are related to market income plus pensions and refer to the year 2020. First, it can be seen that households in the first decile rely to a very large extent on transfers from the state. Then, starting from the fourth decile, households contribute to the state budget more and more in the form of direct taxation, and from the second decile onwards they pay more as social contributions. It is worth noting how indirect taxation affects household incomes, with very poor households bearing the burden to a much greater extent than average or rich households.

Figure 3. Net cash position of households, Romania 2020

Source: own estimations based on HBS data for Romania (2020)

Overall, the assessment of the net position of households in relation to the state budget shows that starting with decile three, households pay more to the budget than they receive. So, basically, only deciles one and two are net beneficiaries, in other words, the poorest 20% of households, the remaining 80% of households are net contributors to the state budget.

It is useful to investigate the elements of taxation and social transfers in more detail because their effects are not necessarily homogeneous, even if they belong to the same category.

Thus, although, overall, all social benefits are progressive and contribute to the reduction of income inequality, there are very important differences between them regarding the size of the effects. The graph below shows the two indicators described in the methodology (Kakwani coefficient and Marginal contribution to the reduction of inequalities) for the main social transfers. We find that the *State Allowance for Children* has the greatest redistributive effect, due to the large amounts allocated to children from poor families, but its progressivity is lower, as poor families are not effectively targeted, even if there is a higher likelihood in their case to have more children. The most progressive transfers are those that are granted with income testing (*Family Support Allowance* and *Minimum guaranteed income*), but these contribute very little to reducing inequalities due to their very small amounts. *Home heating aid* and the *Minimum Pension* are two instruments with a fairly high degree of progressivity (targeting the poor), but their contribution to reducing inequalities is almost null. We note the contribution to the reduction of inequalities of the benefits granted to disabled people due to their significant amounts.

Figure 4. *The redistributive effect and progressivity of the social benefit system*

Source: own estimations based on HBS data for Romania (2020)

Direct taxation is progressive and helps to reduce inequalities. The personal income tax is more progressive than the social security contribution, but has a smaller inequality-reducing effect compared to the social security contribution which collects more (25% of market income vs. 10% of taxable income). The progressivity of the income tax is mainly the result of the personal deductions it incorporates. The social health insurance contribution and the labour insurance contribution (paid by the employer) are equally progressive, the former contributing more to the reduction of inequalities due to the higher percentage (10% vs. 2.25%).

Figure 5. *The redistributive effect and progressivity of taxes*

Source: own estimations based on HBS data for Romania (2020)

Regarding indirect taxation, we note that it is regressive overall and contributes to the increase of inequalities. Excise taxes on tobacco and alcohol are regressive and contribute to deepening inequalities, as poorer households are more affected in terms of the share of expenditure on the consumption of these products (tobacco, alcohol) in total income.

Figure 6. *The redistributive effect and progressivity of taxes, detailed components*

Source: own estimations based on HBS data for Romania (2020)

The value added tax (VAT) is the biggest contributor to rising inequality due to the higher share of consumption expenditure in total income for poor households. On the other hand, excise duties on fuels and energy are progressive, being borne more by households with higher incomes, as expected. But even so, excise taxes on energy and fuels contribute to increasing income inequality.

It should be noted that the analysis was carried out for both 2019 and 2020, but no significant differences were observed between the two years in terms of the effects of the social benefits system and taxation on the reduction of income inequalities.

Conclusions

Inequalities in the labour market consist mainly in wage income inequalities, but they can also be related to other aspects such as employment and underemployment in the labour market, the quality of professional life, job and income security. Factors that contribute to the unequal distribution of labour income are: the unequal distribution of skills and abilities in the employed population, inequalities in access to education, differences in health status, technology and globalization, labour market institutions, including wage unions and agreements between employers, financial deepening or the growth of financial markets (financial deepening), attitudes and beliefs of employees and employers, redistributive policies (Doan, Strazdins and Leach, 2020). Government redistributive policies aim to reduce social inequalities and poverty and can be effective if applied correctly, and these policies have played an important role during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Our research contributes to the development of knowledge regarding the analysis of the effects of social and fiscal policy on income redistribution and the reduction of income inequalities in Romania. Using an approach based on the definition of different income concepts and the evaluation of some indicators that quantify the progressivity and the marginal contribution to the reduction of inequalities, the redistributive effect, and the reduction of inequalities in the case of the different components of the system of social transfers and taxes was determined. The data that formed the basis of the analysis came from the HBS survey of the National Institute of Statistics (NIS). The analysis shows that social benefits are progressive and redistributive, so they contribute to a certain extent to the reduction of inequalities, and so does direct taxation. The most redistributive social benefit is the state allowance for children. Income-tested benefits make a minimal contribution to reducing inequality, although they are progressive, with amounts being very small to produce an effect. Indirect taxes are overall regressive and accentuate inequalities, being a burden especially for poor households. At the same time, we note that no significant changes were observed in the redistributive effect in 2020 compared to previous years, although the year 2020 was strongly affected by the COVID-19 crisis.

Acknowledgment

Part of this work was supported by the NUCLEU Program funded by the Romanian Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization (Project PN 22_10_0104).

References

- Angelov, N. and Waldenström, D., 2021. *COVID-19 and income inequality: Evidence from monthly population registers*, CEPR Discussion Paper 16333, <<https://www.iza.org/de/publications/pp/178/covid-19-and-income-inequality-evidence-from-monthly-population-registers>>
- Badiani-Magnusson, R. and Militaru, E., 2022. *The Distributional Impacts of Taxes and Social Spending in Romania – 2018 Model and Selected Simulations*, World Bank Group. United States of America. Retrieved from <<https://policycommons.net/artifacts/2680987/the-distributional-impacts-of-taxes-and-social-spending-in-romania/3704468/>> on 20 Mar 2023. CID: 20.500.12592/m19049>
- Castells-Quintana, D. and Royuela, V., 2014. Tracking positive and negative effects of inequality on long-run growth, *Empirical Economics*, 53(4), pp. 1349-1378. <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00181-016-1197-y>>
- Dabla-Norris, E., Kochhar, L., Suphaphiphat, N., Ricka, F. and Tsounta, E., 2015, *Causes and Consequences of Income Inequality: A Global Perspective*, International Monetary Fund. <<https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/sdn/2015/sdn1513.pdf>>
- Doan, T., Strazdins, L. and Leach, L., 2020. Cost of poor health to the labour market returns to education in Australia: another pathway for socio-economic inequality, *European Journal of Health Economics*, 21(4), pp. 635-648. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10198-020-01163-2>.
- Furceri, D., Loungani, P., Ostry, J.D. and Pizzuto, P., 2020. *COVID-19 will raise inequality if past pandemics are a guide*, VoxEU.org, <<https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/covid-19-will-raise-inequality-if-past-pandemics-are-guide>>
- Galletta, S. and Giommoni, T., 2020. *Pandemics and inequality*, VoxEU.org, <<https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/pandemics-and-inequality>>
- Higgins, S. and Lustig, N., 2017. *Allocating Taxes and Transfers and Constructing Income Concepts*. In *Commitment to Equity Handbook. A Guide to Estimating the Impact of Fiscal Policy on Inequality and Poverty*, edited by Nora Lustig. Washington DC: Brookings Institution Press.
- Inchauste Comboni, M.G. and Militaru, E., The Distributional Impact of Taxes and Social Spending in Romania (August 23, 2018). *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, No. 8565, Available at SSRN: <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=3238408>>
- Kakwani, N., 1993. Statistical inference in the measurement of poverty, *Review of Economics and Statistics* 75 (4), pp. 632-639.
- Lustig, N., editor, 2018. *Commitment to Equity Handbook: Estimating the Impact of Fiscal Policy on Inequality and Poverty*. Washington, DC: Brookings Institution Press and CEQ Institute, Tulane University. Advance online version available at: <<http://www.commitmenttoequity.org/publications/handbook.php>>
- Militaru, E., Popescu, M., Vasilescu, D. and Cristescu, A., 2022. “Romania 2019-2022” Euromod Country Report. Available at: <<https://euromod-web.jrc.ec.europa.eu/resources/country-reports/latest>>
- Piacentini, J., Frazis, H., Meyer, P.B, Schultz, M. and Sveikauskas, L., 2022. The Impact of COVID-19 on Labor Markets and Inequality, *Economic Working Paper*, WP-551, <<https://www.bls.gov/osmr/research-papers/2022/ec220060.htm>>

- Salverda, W., Nolan, B. and Smeeding, T.M., 2009. *The Oxford Handbook of Economic Inequality*, Oxford Handbooks in Economics, <<https://academic.oup.com/edited-volume/34553>>
- The Credit Suisse Research Institute (CSRI) (2022) – Global Wealth Report 2022, <<https://www.credit-suisse.com/media/assets/corporate/docs/about-us/research/publications/global-wealth-report-2022-en.pdf>>
- Waldenström, D., 2021. *Income inequality during the Covid-19 pandemic*, CEPR Discussion Paper 13.08.2021, <<https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/income-inequality-during-covid-19-pandemic>>